

**International Conference on New Research in
Agri-food and Tourism
BIOATLAS 2012
www.rosita.ro/bioatlas**

1. Biodiversity capitalization and Tourism application

*Biodiversity and Agriculture Technologies Environment
Biodiversity and Fores ResourcesLandscape Management and
Development of Tourism Industry
Rural Tourism, Agri-tourism*

**2. Bio-food and Public Health and Culinary
Production**

*Eco-biotechnologies and Minimal Processing in Food Industry
Minimal Gastronomic Engeneering
Sanogeneous Food and Preventive Therapies
Traditional Food and Ethno-Pharmacology*

**3. Management and IT&C in Agri-Food, Tourism and
Hospitality Industry**

*Telecommunications, GIS, GPS in Agriculture and Forestry
Information Technology in Tourism- Software Applications
Travel and Tourism Industries and Hotels and Restaurant
Management
Communication and Entertainment in Tourism*

4. Agri-food and Tourism Equipment

*Agricultural and Biotechnologies Installations and Equipment
Hotel and Restaurant Equipment
Agricultural and Tourism Transports
Installations and Equipment in Tourism Buildings*

5. Young Researchers Contributions

*Food
Travel and Tourism Industry
Hospitality Industry*

Journal of EcoAgriTourism

ISSN: 1844-8577

*

Journal of EcoAgriTourism is a follow up,
by translation in English of
"Revista de EcoAgroTurism"
ISSN 1841-642X, first issued in 2005

Vol. 8 (2012), Nr. 2 (25)

Journal of EcoAgriTourism

Bulletin of Agri-ecology, Agri-food, Bioengineering and Agritourism

SELECTED PAPERS FROM THE PROCEEDING OF BIOATLAS 2012 CONFERENCE-vol. 2

Biodiversity

CalitaTerra

Sanogeneous Food

Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality

Ideas and Concepts

News

24-26 May 2012
BIOATLAS 2012 CONFERENCE
International Conference on New Research in
Food and Tourism
www.rosita.ro/bioatlas

Editors: Gaceu L., Gruia R.

EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

Journal published by the Faculty of Food and Tourism, "Transilvania" University of Brasov.

Journal's Director:
Prof. Romulus GRUIA Ph. D.

Editor-in-Chief:
Assoc. Prof. Liviu GACEU Ph. D.

Scientific Board:
Dr. Gilles Bedoux, France
Prof. Dr. eng. Werner Hofacker, Germany
Prof. Dr. Ray F. Iunius, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. eng. Petru Alexe, Romania
Prof. Dr. Eng. Miklos Herdon, Hungary
Prof. Dr. Sukmanov A. Valerij, Ukraine
Prof. Dr. Maria Isabel Bernuga, Spain
Prof. Dr. eng. Stefan Stefanov
Prof. Dr. Simionescu Dumitru, Romania

Editorial Board:
Translator: Simona BUCSA
Asist. dr. Eng. Marius HODARNAU
Seidecaru Corina
Tohaneanu Ana Maria
Oprea Oana Bianca
Campean Radu

Main research direction: "Agriculture, Biotechnologies, Food and Tourism Development"

Romanian Society for Information Technology in Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism (ROSITA)

Research Centre for Engineering and Management in Agriculture, Food and Tourism (IMAAT)

ROSITA

EXACTLY GREEN THINKING

ISSN: 1844-8577

Published by: Transilvania University Press
Publisher Address:
500091 Brasov, B-dul Iuliu Maniu 41 A
Tel: 0268-476050
Fax: 0268-476051
E-mail: editura@unitbv.ro
Co-editor: Romanian Society for Information Technology in Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism
Str. Castelului nr. 148, 500014, Braşov, ROMANIA
Tel.&Fax.: +40-268-472222
www.rosita.ro

RESEARCH CENTRE FOR ENGINEERING AND MANAGEMENT
IN AGRICULTURE, FOOD AND TOURISM,
Transilvania University of Braşov
Bd. Eroilor nr. 29, 500036, Braşov,
Tel & Fax: 0268-415326, Tel: 0268-413000/161
e-mail: ecotec@unitbv.ro, <http://www.unitbv.ro/at>

***Journal of EcoAgriTourism, dissemination path for Bioatlas
International Conference 2012***

The Research Center Eco-biotechnology and Equipment for Food and Agriculture (EBIOTEFA) from the Institute of Research Development of Transylvania University, but also of Food and Tourism Faculty – the IMAT Department, represents the top structure for our research activity. The new research on programs and projects specific to the field are the object for certain technologies, to make ecologic and biologic food products, to optimize the respective equipment, brevets and, of course, certain scientific papers. These research results, for which we have important contributions from researchers from different institutions from Romania and many other countries are disseminated through two very important for us activities: *The BIOATLAS International Conference* and the *Journal of EcoAgriTourism*.

Within this context, the information dissemination, trough its variuos forms, should be homogeneous and harmonious. In the light of this particularly expressed desire, we conceived a correspondece between the structure of the Journal and the International Conference we organize every two years. Therefore, we present below the links between the headings of Journal of EcoAgriTourism (J of EAT) and communication session of the International Conference on New Research in Food and Tourism – BIOATLAS.

J of EAT	BIOATLAS Conference
Biodiversity	Biodiversity Capitalization and Tourism Applications
CalitaTerra	Agri-food and Tourism Equipment
Sanogeneous Food	Bio-food, Public Health and Culinary Production (i.s.ecological and biological technologies)
Sustainable Tourism and Hospitalty Ideas and Concepts	Management, IT and Law in Agri-Food, Tourism and Hospitality Industry

Papers with high degree of originality and scientific contribution as well as with important conclusions for the practice in food and tourism have been selected to be published in Journal of EcoAgriTourism.

Romulus GRUIA
Director of the Journal of EcoAgriTourism

BIOATLAS 2012 CONFERENCE**ORGANIZERS**

TRANSILVANIA UNIVERSITY of BRAȘOV
FACULTY OF FOOD AND TOURISM – IMAT Dept.
RESEARCH CENTER OF ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGIES
AND EQUIPMENT IN AGRICULTURE AND FOOD

In collaboration with:

- **ROPAM – ROMANIAN ASSOCIATION OF HERB GROWERS**
- **ROMANIAN SOCIETY FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN AGRICULTURE, FOOD, ENVIRONMENT AND TOURISM**
- **ROMANIAN ASSOCIATION OF ETHNO-PHARMACOLOGY – AFFILIATED TO EUROPEAN SOCIETY OF ETHNO-PHARMACOLOGY**
- **ROMANIAN ASSOCIATION OF ECOSANOGENESIS**

PARTNERS

- **Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Agency of Brașov**
- **National Institute of Research-Development INCD for Potato and Sugar Beet Brașov**
- **Research and Development Center for Fodder Crops and Pasture Brașov**
- **ARO-PALACE S.A. BRAȘOV**
- **ANTREC – Filiala Brasov**
- **Center for Engineering and Management in Agriculture, Food and Tourism**
- **Central Library of Transilvania University of Brasov**

HONORIFIC PRESIDENT

Prof. dr. ing. Ioan Vasile ABRUDAN
 Rector of Transilvania University of Brașov

EXECUTIV COMMITTEE

PRESIDENT OF THE CONFERENCE
Prof. Romulus GRUIA, PhD

CONFERENCE SECRETARY:
Assoc. Prof Liviu GACEU, PhD

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Honorific President: *Acad. Prof. H.C. Alexandru T. Bogdan Ph. D., M..C. al Academiei Romane*

Members:

Prof. Werner Hofacker Ph. D., University of Applied Science, Konstanz, Germany

Prof. Thomas Hoffman Ph. D., ATB, Germany

Prof. Stergios Tzortzios, Ph. D., University of Thessaly, Volos, Greece

Prof. Miklos Herdon Ph. D., University of Debrecen Centre of Agricultural Sciences, Hungary

Prof. Zeynel Cebeci Ph. D., Çukurova University Adana, Turkey

Acad. Prof. Valerii Sukmanov Ph. D. Hab., University of Economy and Commerce Donetsk, Ukraine

Acad. Prof. Valeriu Rudic, Ph.D., Institute of Microbiology and Biotechnology, Moldavia

Prof. Skubala Piotr Ph. D., University of Silesia, Poland

Prof. Monica Tereza Buscaiu Neagu Ph. D., Polytechnic University of Valencia, Spain

Prof. Dogan Yunus Ph.D., Dokuz Eylul University, Izmir, Turkey

Prof. Gilles Bedoux Ph. D University Bretagne Sud Vannes, France

*Prof. Maria Isabel Berruga Fernandez, University
Castilla La Mancha, Spain*

*Prof. Mark Shamtsyan Ph. D. St. Petersburg, State
Institute of Technology, Russia*

*Prof. Stefan Stefanov, University of Food
Technology, Plovdiv, Bulgaria*

*Assoc. Prof. Stanka Damianova, University "Angel
Kanchev" Russe, Razgrad Subsidiary, Bulgaria*

*Prof. Gianluca Schillaci Ph. D., University of
Catania, Italy*

*Prof. Patrizia Restani, Ph D., Milano University,
Italy*

*Prof. Usanee Suthammaporn, Ph. D., International
School of Tourism, Thailand*

*Prof. Petru Alexe Ph. D., University "Dunarea de
Jos" Galati, Romania*

*Prof. Ion Pirna Ph. D., Managing Director INMA
Bucharest, Romania*

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

President: Prof. dr. eng. Romulus GRUIA

Secretary: Assoc. dr. eng. Liviu GACEU

Members:

*Prof. Vasile Padureanu, Ph. D., Transilvania
University of Brasov, Romania*

*Prof. Nicolae Tane, Ph. D., Transilvania University
of Brasov, Romania*

*Prof. Carol Csatlos, Ph. D., Transilvania University
of Brasov, Romania*

*Prof. Angela Marculescu, Ph. D., Transilvania
University of Brasov, Romania*

*Assoc. Prof. Thierheimer Walter Ph. D.,
Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania*

*Prof. Gheorghe Bratucu Ph. D., Transilvania
University of Brasov, Romania*

*Prof. Florean Rus Ph. D., Transilvania University of
Brasov, Romania*

*Lecturer Cristina Canja Ph. D., Transilvania
University of Brasov, Romania*

*Lecturer Dorin Valter Enache Ph. D., Transilvania
University of Brasov, Director DSVSA Brasov,
Romania*

*Lecturer Valentin Necula Ph. D., Transilvania
University of Brasov, Romania*

*Pop Oliviu Ph. D. Transilvania University of
Brasov, Romania*

*Prof. dr. Bircu Adriana, George Baritiu University,
Brasov, Romania*

*Sorin Claudian CHIRU, Ph. D., Director INCDCSZ,
Brasov, Romania.*

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT MEMBERS

PhD stud. Simona BUCSA – simultaneous traductions

PhD Oliviu POP

PhD stud. Georgiana GADEI

Ms. Mirela MUNTEANU

Ms. Ioana POPA

Ms. Harieta BUJOREANU

Ms. Gina TOMA

Mr. Alexandru WELTER

Mr. Adrian TUDUCE

STUDENTS:

Oana Bianca OPREA

Alexandra KURTISOVICI

Anca Mariana ION

Corina SEIDECARU

Ana Maria TOHANEANU

SPONSORS:

**Craiasa Muntillor – Moeciu de Sus
Nutraceutical S.R.L. Brasov
ARO-PALACE S.A. BRASOV**

SUMMARY

Editorial	
1	<i>Journal of EcoAgriTourism, dissemination path for Bioatlas International Conference 2012</i>
Biodiversity	
	3 <i>BUTTERFLIES DIVERSITY AS FUNDAMENT FOR AN INCREASED ECOTOURISTIC POTENTIAL IN BUILA –VĂNTURARITA NATIONAL PARK</i> M. MANU F. BODESCU
	8 <i>ASPECT REGARDING OF CUMIN USES IN BAKERY RECIPES</i> O. B. OPREA, L. GACEU, A. BIRCA
	13 <i>THE ROSE (ROSA DAMASCENA) – A RESOURCE FOR DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN BULGARIA</i> I. OBRESHKOV, T. IVANOV
	18 <i>HPAEC-PAD CARBOHYDRATE ANALYSES OF BULGARIAN BLOSSOM HONEYS</i> I. OBRESHKOV, D. FRANZ, I. SCHELLENBERG
	22 <i>ECOLOGICAL USE OF INDUSTRIAL FIBER PLANTS AS RENEWABLE RAW MATERIALS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS IN ECO-TOURISM AND FOOD SUPPLEMENTS</i> D.C. OLA, D. DANILA, L. GACEU, C. SPIRCHEZ
	25 <i>PLANT SPECIES DIVERSITY IN SINCA NOUA AREA (BRASOV COUNTY) AND SOME ISSUES REGARDING THE CONSERVATION OF PROTECTED SPECIES</i> O.G. POP, R. GRUIA, A. MARCULESCU, C.L. BADARAU
	30 <i>DENSITY AND RELATIVE FREQUENCY OF SPECIES, RESOURCES OF BIODIVERSITY STUDY CONCERNING</i> A. SAVA, C. BADARAU, A. MARCULESCU
	34 <i>CHARACTERISTICS OF VERTICAL STRUCTURE IN PURE AND MIXED BEECH WITH RESINS, FROM CIUCAS MASSIF</i> A. SAVA, C. BADARAU, A. MARCULESCU
	41 <i>REUSE SCRAP WOOD TO PRODUCE ACTIVATED CARBON WITH THE REDUCING THE DESTRUCTIVE EFFECTS OVER FOREST ROADS</i> C. SLINCU, P. VICA
	45 <i>QUICK METHOD FOR THE WOOD EXPLOITATION SITES DESIGNING, AND TECHNOLOGY AND TRANSPORT ON FOREST ROADS</i> C. SLINCU, P. VICA
	49 <i>COMPARATIVE TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TWO PRIMITIVE WHEATS OF TYPE TRITICUM TURGIDUM L. SUBSP. TURANICUM " KAMUT " AND " EGYPTIAN WHEAT "</i> TZV. GOGOVA
	53 <i>TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRIMITIVE CEREAL OF TYPE TRITICUM TURGIDUM L. SUBSP. TURANICUM : "KAMUT"</i> TZV. GOGOVA, B. BOZADJIEV, D. HRUSAVOV

	57	<i>Development of forage production in farmers of Kazakhstan</i> B. YESPEROVA, I. ALIMAEV
	CalitaTerra	
	61	<i>RESEARCH ON SOIL COMPACTION CAUSED BY POTATOES HARVESTERS COMBINES</i> FL. LOGHIN, FL. RUS, I. CAPATINA
	67	<i>NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF ENERGY DISSIPATION IN MIXING PROCESS OF BREAD DOUGH</i> M.I. LUCHIAN, I. LITOVCHENKO, S. STEFANOV, C. CSATLOS
	71	<i>CYCLONE GEOMETRY INFLUENCE ON THE NUMBER OF REVOLUTIONS IN THE OUTER VORTEX</i> M. MARINUC
	77	<i>EFFECT OF INPUT VELOCITY OVER THE CYCLONE SEPARATION PROCESS</i> M. MARINUC
	83	<i>DETERMINING THE TEMPERATURE AND MOISTURE DISTRIBUTION IN APPLE SLICES DURING THE DRYING PROCESS</i> A.-M.NUÑEZ VEGA, W. C. HOFACKER
	95	<i>RESEARCHES REGARDING TEMPERATURE EVOLUTION IN TWO WAREHOUSES WITH DIFFERENT CONTROL SYSTEMS OF THE CLIMATIC FACTORS</i> C.G. PAUNESCU
	101	<i>IS POTATO STORING IN WAREHOUSES WITH TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEMS ECONOMICAL EFFICIENT?</i> C.G. PAUNESCU, GH. BRATUCU
	106	<i>ADIABATIC COOLING OF SOLUTIONS OF FOOD PRODUCTS: EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH</i> A. SOKOLENKO O. BOYKO
	110	<i>TECHNOLOGY TO BUILD A WOODEN COTTAGE THAT COMBINES TRADITIONAL STYLE WITH TECHNICAL ASPECTS MODERNIST</i> C. SPIRCHEZ, L. BADESCU, L. GACEU, D. OLA, A. GOREA, V. DEAC
114	<i>CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE ANALISYS OF HARVESTING COMBINES SYSTEMS TO IMPROVE THE COMBINES CROP PROCESSING CAPACITY WHILE MAINTAINING HIGH STANDARDS OF GRAIN LOSES AND SEED QUALITY</i> O. STAN, S. POPESCU	
123	<i>THEORETICAL STUDY ON FEEDING THE TANGENTIAL THRESHING SYSTEM OF A CONVENTIONAL HARVESTING COMBINE</i> O. STAN, G. IVAN	
131	<i>EFFECT OF MODIFIED ATMOSPHERE ON THE SHELF LIFE OF PASTEURIZED MILK</i> ST. STEFANOV, H. HRISTOV, D. STOEVA	
137	<i>STRUCTURE FORMATION AND DISPERSION ANALYSIS OF BUTTER, PROCESSED UNDER HIGH CYCLICAL PRESSURE</i> V. SUKMANOV, I. LEVIT, S. GROMOV	
144	<i>EXPERIMENTAL ESTIMATE OF POSSIBILITY TO APPLY HIGH PRESSURE FOR THE PRODUCTION OF RESTRUCTURED PRODUCTS OF CHICKEN MEAT</i> V.O. SUKMANOV, S.A.SOKOLOV, M.M. SEVATOROV, O.O. DEKAN	

	150	<i>CONTRIBUTIONS TO THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE DYNAMIC STABILITY OF THE FORKLIFT TRUCKS</i> N. SUTRU, G. BOIANGIU, S. POPESCU
	157	<i>INFLUENCE OF THE GEOMETRIC AND FUNCTIONAL PARAMETERS OF THE REAR THREE-POINT LINKAGE ON THE DYNAMICS OF TRACTOR – IMPLEMENT SYSTEMS</i> L. VASILACHE, S. POPESCU, N. ORMENISAN
	165	<i>TO THE QUESTION OF VOLUMETRIC DIVIDER DEVELOPMENT FOR FROZEN MEAT DUMPLING</i> V. VLADIMIROV, Y. PETROVA, S. VLADIMIROV
	168	<i>WOOD ONE OF THE OLDEST CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS IN HISTORICAL BUILDINGS</i> O. ZELENIIUC, B. LEPADATESCU
Sanogeous Food		
	174	<i>GROUND OF THE USE OF INTERMEDIATE PRODUCT ON BASIS OF FAT FREE MILK WITH THE USE OF EXTRACT OF ROOT OF GLYCYRRHIZA IN PRODUCTION OF CREAM CREAMY</i> V. GNITSEVYCH, N. KRAVCHENKO
	180	<i>POLYPHENOLIC CONTENT AND ANTIOXIDANT POTENTIAL OF SOME SPECIES EXTRACTS FROM PIATRA CRAIULUI MOUNTAINS</i> D. HANGANU, A.M. ANTON, O. G. POP, A. MARCULESCU
	185	<i>MICROBIOLOGICAL STUDY OF FLOURY MIXES WITH ADDITION OF TOPINAMBUR FLOUR</i> A. KOLEVA, A. YOVCHEV, D. HRUSAVOV, A. KRASTEVA, Z. DENKOVA
	188	<i>BIOREACTORS WITH LIGHT-BEADS FLUIDIZED BED: MODELING OF THE VOIDAGE FUNCTION</i> G. KOSTOV ¹ , I. MIHAYLOV ² , D. BLAZHEVA ³ , D. STOEVA ⁴ , M. ANGELOV
	194	<i>INVESTIGATION AND MODELING OF JET COLUMN BIOREACTOR: MIXING TIME IN THE APPARATUS</i> G. KOSTOV, I. MIHAYLOV, D. BLAZHEVA, M. ANGELOV
	200	<i>PHYTOTHERAPY AS A SUPPORT FOR TRAVELERS AND TOURISTS HEALTH</i> S. MANEA, V. TAMAS, G. RIZEA, D. IONESCU, A. COZEA, I. FLORIAN, A. MARCULESCU
	204	<i>QUESTS CONCERNING THE CORRELATIONS BETWEEN FOOD QUALITY AND THAT OF THE FARM TROUT MEAT</i> V. NECULA, M. BABII, M. POTROVITA, D. ENACHE, G. PUCHIANU, B. DUMITRU
	209	<i>VISCOELASTICAL BAHEVIOUR OF HONEYS</i> M. A. OROIAN, GHE. GUTT
212	<i>PRIMARY OXIDATION PRODUCTS ACCUMULATION IN WALNUT OIL DURING HEAT TREATMENT</i> C. POPOVICI, P. ALEXE, O. DESEATNICOVA	

	217	<p><i>INFLUENCE RESEARCH OF THE VEGETATIVE ADDITIVE OF PICKLED VEGETABLES ON QUALITY INDICATORS OF MEAT PRODUCTS</i> O. SABIROV</p>
	223	<p><i>IMMUNOMODULATING AND ANTITUMOUR EFFECT OF EXTRACTS OF BASIDIOMYCETES</i> M. SHAMTSYAN, V. SPIRIDONOVA, V. KONUSOVA, N. PETRISCHEV, A. SYMBIRTSEV</p>
	231	<p><i>ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY OF FROZEN STRAWBERRIES AS AFFECTED BY THE VACUUM IMPREGNATION IN POLYPHENOLRICH EXTRACT</i> V. SHIKOV, K. MIHALEV, N. YONCHEVA, V. KARAGYOZOV, P. MOLLOV</p>
	238	<p><i>INFLUENCE OF SEA KALE ON QUALITY OF DOUGH</i> O. SIMAKOVA, A. KORSHUNOVA, L. SEMENOVA</p>
	244	<p><i>RHEOLOGICAL PARAMETRES OF A CREAM FILLING USED FOR THE PRODUCTION OF CO-EXTRUDATES</i> A. SIMITCHIEV, V. NENOV, M. DUSHKOVA, N. TOSHKOV</p>
	250	<p><i>DYNAMIC VISCOSITY OF A CREAM FILLING</i> A. SIMITCHIEV</p>
	255	<p><i>COEFFICIENT OF DIFFUSION OF AROMATIC EXTRACTION PRODUCTS FROM HAWTHORN (Crataegus monogyna Jaqc.)</i> S. TASHEVA, S. DAMIANOVA, M. ERGEZEN, P. MERDZHANOV, A. STOYANOVA</p>
	259	<p><i>VARIATION OF ESSENTIAL OIL CONTENT FROM HERBS USED IN DIET AND PHYTOTHERAPY, FROM SPONTANEOUS FLORA -ALBANIA AND CULTURE FLORA – ROMANIA</i> V.TAMAS, N. BORDEI , G. A. TRAISTARU, G. IVOPOL, A. COZEA, L. SHUKA, M MERSINLLARI</p>
	263	<p><i>PROTEIN CHANGES OF CHICKEN LIGHT AND DARK MUSCLES DURING CHILLED STORAGE</i> K. VASSILEV, G. IVANOV, D. BALEV , G. DOBREV</p>
	269	<p><i>QUALITY CONTROL AND FOOD SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN THE BLUEBERRY JUICE PRODUCTION</i> Z. VELCHEV, R. DINKOVA, H. DINKOV</p>
	275	<p><i>STUDY THE STABILITY OF EMULSIONS PRODUCED BY COMPLETE REPLACEMENT OF MILK FAT WITH SOYBEAN OIL</i> R. VLASEVA, M. IVANOVA</p>
	280	<p><i>IMAGE DATA OF CRUMB STRUCTURE OF BREAD WITH TOPINAMBUR FLOUR</i> A. YOVCHEV, A. LE-BAIL, A. KOLEVA, A. KRASTEVA</p>
Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality		
	283	<p><i>CONTRIBUTIONS ON SEGMENTING CUSTOMERS WHO RENT CARS THROUGH ONLINE SYSTEMS AND ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF SERVICES RECEIVED</i> A. I. NECHITA D. M. DANILA</p>
	287	<p><i>COGNITIVE AND MANAGEMENT DIMENSIONS OF SUSTAINABLE TOURISM</i> V. GHERASIM</p>

	Ideas and Concepts	
	296	<i>DESIGNING TIMBER HARVESTING SITE MAPS WITH LOW INVESTMENT TOOLS</i> S. A. BORZ
	302	<i>USAGE OF INTERNET SERVICES BY FARMERS IN HUNGARY</i> A. CSEH
	308	<i>ASPECT RELATED TO THE COLOUR ANALYSES OF VEGETABLE PRODUCTS DURING CONVECTIVE DRYING PROCESS</i> L. GACEU, E. TECUCEANU, I.M. BYELYAYEVA, O.B. OPREA
	313	<i>THE EFFECT OF THE USE OF DIFFERENT CATERING PRODUCTION SYSTEMS UPON THE CONTENT IN SOLUBLE VITAMINS OF FISH AND MEAT MEALS</i> G. PLOSCUTANU (LENCO), A. MAZAREL
	320	<i>A SURVEY ON IDENTIFICATION OF USER NEEDS REGARDING LINGUISTIC SUPPORT FOR ORGANIC.EDUNET PORTAL</i> M. UMIT UNAL, ZEYNEL CEBECI, M. ALI GOKCE
326	<i>THE PERCEPTIONS OF AGRICULTURAL GRADUATES ON THE CORRELATION OF THEIR LABOUR MARKET SITUATION AND QUALIFICATION IN HUNGARY</i> M. HERDON, Z. ZÖRÖG	
	News	
	332	<i>TOURISM EVENTS</i>

BUTTERFLIES DIVERSITY AS FUNDAMENT FOR AN INCREASED ECOTOURISTIC POTENTIAL IN BUILA – VÂNTURARIȚA NATIONAL PARK

M. MANU F. BODESCU

Abstract: *In 2011, the author undertook lepidopterological research at several locations in Buila – Vânturarița National Park (Romania), an area which was unknown from this point of view. The identified material comprises 33 species. According to European law (Directive Habitats no. 92/43, 1992) two species are protected: *Leptidea morsei major* (Grund, 1907) and *Everes alcetas alcetas* (Hoffmannseng, 1804). There are reported as species which bear a great faunistic and zoogeographical value, as well as ecotouristic ones. The butterflies' diversity from this protected area could be a proper factor for an increased ecotouristic potential.*

Keywords: *butterflies, protected area, diversity, ecotourism.*

1. Introduction

With Romania's accession to the European space, in 2007, our country adopted a national strategy for biodiversity conservation, which is directly correlated with the actual European legislation, concerning conservation of natural habitats and of wide fauna and flora (Directive Habitats 92/43/CEE). The aim of this legal frame is to ensure the maintenance or restoration of a favorable conservation status of European biodiversity, by establishing specific measures for natural habitats as well as for wild flora and fauna, taking account of economic, social and cultural needs of member states. A European ecological network of special areas of conservation has been established, called Natura 2000, which includes sites that host natural protected habitats or wild species, which requires measures to ensure a state of favorable conservation.

One of these protected areas is Buila-Vânturarița National Park. Due to its isolated nature and difficult access, there are many entirely preserved elements of the natural patrimony: natural habitats, virgin forests, numerous protected species of flora and fauna, mineralogical and paleontological sites and caves. Fauna, as well as flora, is extremely varied. Many of the species in the Buila-Vânturarița Massif are protected by international conventions that Romania has also ratified (conventions from Berna, Bonn, CITES, the Directives on Habitats and Birds). All these biological treasure are important ecotouristic

objectives, which increase the ecological and touristic value of the park. But, some of the fauna groups have not been identified, as butterflies (Lepidoptera: Rhopalocera). In Romania, 202 butterflies were identified [7]. Lepidopterological studies in this protected area have not been realized till now. Some biological collectings were made nearby to Buila – Vânturarița National Park, in Râmnicu Vâlcea by Popescu – Gorj A., in 1960 [4].

The present paper brings new informations concerning butterflies (Lepidoptera: Rhopalocera) from an important protected area from Romania. In the same time this material wants to be an argument for ecotouristic value for the investigated area.

2. Material and methods

The faunistic material (presented further on) was collected in three field trips from nine sites from Buila – Vânturarița National Park, carried out in the spring, summer and in the autumn, 2012..

Four types of habitats were investigated: riparian area, forest edge, high altitude meadow (1000- 1600 m altitude) and low altitude meadow (under 1000 m altitude) (Fig.1).

The butterflies have been collected with the entomological net. Another nondestructive used method (from the conservation point of view) was photos. This method provides protection for butterflies' species and for their habitats. The taxonomical identification was made after

Lafranchais, 2004 and Tolman & Lewington, 2009 [3, 8].

Buila-Vânturarița is the smallest national park in Romania, with a total area 4186 ha, located in the Vâlcea County (south-western part of Romania), in the southern corner of Căpățâni Mountains (the Meridional Carpathians), lying on the territory of the Costești and Bărbățești villages and of the Băile Olănești city. The Park comprises the linear limestone ridge of the Buila-Vânturarița Massive, 14 km long. It lies from the

western corner of the Bistrița Gorges to the eastern side of the Olănești Gorges (Folea), and it is dominated by the two peaks from whom the massive took its name: The Buila Peak (1849 m) and the Vânturarița Mare Peak (1885 m). The Massive has the specific characteristics of the karstic relief, with many exokarstic shapes (gorges, limestone slopes, dolines, lapiez fields, swallets, needles, detritus fields, straits) and endokarstic (caves and pitches) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Investigated habitats from Buila-Vânturarița National Park.

Fig. 2. Geographical position of Buila-Vânturarița National Park.

3. Results and discussions

33 species were identified, belonging to the following families: Papilionidae (3%), Pieridae (21%), Lycaenidae (52%) and Nymphalidae (24%). These represent 14% from all identified species from Romania (Lepidoptera: Rophalocera). According to Romanian law no. O.U.G. 57/20.06.2007, Directive Habitats no. 92/43, 1992 and Red Data Book of European Butterflies (RDBEB), which mentions the

conservation status of plant and animal species, two butterflies, were identified as species with special protection status: *Leptidea morsei* and *Everes alcetas* [1, 2, 9]. It must be highlighted that one species is endemic for Europe (*Erebia euryale syrmi*) [7]. Another important criteria for butterflies conservation is the national status established by Rakosy in 2003, 2005 (VU – vulnerable, EN – endangered, NT – potential threatened) [5, 6] (Table no.1).

Table 1

Identified species of butterflies (Lepidoptera: Rophalocera) from Buila – Vânturarița National Park

Habitats	Identified species	Species with conservative value
High altitude meadows	<i>Erebia ligea nikostrate</i> (Fruhstorfer, 1909) <i>Issoria lathonia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Araschnia levana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Erebia euryale syrmi</i> (Fruhstorfer, 1909) – endemic species for Europe-
Low altitude meadows	<i>Leptidea sinapis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Pieris napi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Erebia ligea nikostrate</i> (Fruhstorfer, 1909) <i>Melanargia galathea satmia</i> (Fruhstorfer, 1917) <i>Argynnis paphia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Araschnia levana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Vanessa atalanta atalanta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Lassiommata megera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Hipparchia fagi fagi</i> (Scopoli, 1763) <i>Maniola jurtina jurtina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Aphantopus hyperantus hyperantus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Lycaena phlaeas phlaeas</i> (Linnaeus, 1761) <i>Polyommatus icarus icarus</i> (Rottemburg, 1775) <i>Aricia agestis agestis</i> (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775) <i>Apatura iris iris</i> (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)	<i>Leptidea morsei major</i> (Grund, 1907) - species protected by HD 92/43 EEC, O.U.G. 57/2007 and RDBEB- - National status = EN- <i>Everes alcetas alcetas</i> (Hoffmannseg, 1804) - species protected by HD 92/43 EEC and O.U.G. 57/2007- - National status = EN- <i>Iphiclides podalirius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) -National status = NT- <i>Pieris manni manni</i> (Mayer, 1851) - National status = EN-
Riparian areas	<i>Leptidea sinapis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Anthocaris cardamines</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Pieris napi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Lassiommata maera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Erebia ligea nikostrate</i> (Fruhstorfer, 1909) <i>Melanargia galathea satmia</i> (Fruhstorfer, 1917) <i>Pararge aegeria tircis</i> (Butler, 1867) <i>Issoria lathonia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Argynnis paphia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Polyommatus therites</i> (Cantener, 1835) <i>Inachis io</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Polygonia c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Araschnia levana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Vanessa cardui cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Vanessa atalanta atalanta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Limenitis camilla camilla</i> (Denis & Schiffermuller, 1775)	<i>Leptidea morsei major</i> (Grund, 1907) - species protected by - species protected by HD 92/43 EEC, O.U.G. 57/2007 and RDBEB- - National status = EN- <i>Erebia euryale syrmi</i> (Fruhstorfer, 1909) – endemic species for Europe-
Forest edges	<i>Leptidea sinapis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Gonepteryx rhamni</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Anthocaris cardamines</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Pieris napi</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Lassiommata maera</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Issoria lathonia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Argynnis paphia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Polyommatus therites</i> (Cantener, 1835) <i>Inachis io</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Polygonia c-album</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Aglais urticae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) <i>Araschnia levana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Iphiclides podalirius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) -National status = NT-

Taking account of the species distribution, the most favorable habitats (even from the conservative point of view) were riparian areas and low altitude meadows. Some environmental conditions influence the butterflies distribution, as abiotic ones: temperature (over 17⁰), the quantity of solar energy (over 60%) or the clouds coverage (less than 40%), the speed and wind direction and the biotic ones: the level of flowering plant's coverage. The rougher

environmental condition from forests edges and high altitude meadows, due to the longer and offset winter, with low temperatures and high snow layers, which persists till the end of the may, could be a possible explanation of these differences in species distribution. If we take into discussion the characteristically species for each habitat, the most increased number were recorded in low altitude meadows and the lowest in high altitude meadows (Fig. 3).

Fig.3. Distribution of the identified butterflies species in habitats from Buila - Vânturarița National Park (Total sp. = total number of species; Sp.c.v. = species with conservative value; Ch. sp. = characteristically species)

4. Conclusions

Lepidoptera (Rhopalocera) is very important invertebrate group from ecological point of view, being one of the most important pollinators. In Europe, the ecological education programmes are one of the main tools for butterflies' conservation. Taking account of the biodiversity, Romania is one of the richest countries, which could represent a huge ecotouristic potential. Although, the Romania's butterflies fauna was studied, there still are protected areas where have not a complete inventory of these invertebrates, as Buila – Vânturarița National Park. In 2011, lepidopterological research in this area provided identification of 33 species, from which four are protected on national and European level.

Besides their ecological role, these protected species could have ecotouristic value. In order to materialize this ecotouristic value, some activities could be realized: transect or arranged platforms for butterflies watching; special places for their breedings, conservation and ecological education workshops, outdoor activities for children, photo or video exposition with thematic, etc. All these actions will contribute to the increasing of ecotouristic potential in Buila – Vânturarița National Park.

This study was funded by project no. SMIS-CSNR 1337/2011-2013: "Mapping of the principal groups of arthropods from the main park's habitats"- from POS MEDIU program: "Revision of Buila – Vânturarița National Park management plan and the monitoring strategy for

protected habitats and species” and by project no. RO1567-IBB01/2012 “Researches concern relation between biodiversity and functions from some ecosystems from Romanian Carpathians” from the Institute of Biology-Bucharest, of the Romanian Academy.

References

- ***http://www.mmediu.ro/protectia_naturii/biodiversitate/Strategie_Biodiversitate_2000_Ro.pdf
- *** <http://www.buila.ro>
- *** Monitorul Oficial nr. 442 din 29 iunie 2007. Ordonanța de urgență nr. 57 din 20 iunie 2007 privind regimul ariilor naturale protejate, conservarea habitatelor naturale, a florei și faunei sălbatice.
- *** Monitorul Oficial 262 din 13 aprilie 2011. Legea 49 din 7 aprilie 2011. pentru aprobarea Ordonanței de urgență a Guvernului nr. 57/2007 privind regimul ariilor naturale protejate, conservarea habitatelor naturale, a florei și faunei sălbatice.
- *** Directiva Habitare 92/43 EEC, din 21 mai 1992, privind conservarea habitatelor naturale și a speciilor de plante și animale sălbatice.
<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:31992L0043:EN:NOT>
1. IUCN 1994. IUCN Red List Categories. Prepared by the IUCN Species Survival Commission. IUCN Gland Switzerland.
 2. IUCN 2001. IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria Version 3. IUCN Species Survival Commission IUCN Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK. 1-30.
 3. Lafranchis, T.: *Butterflies of Europe. New field guide and key*. Diatheo, 35 rue Broca F-Paris, France, 2004.
 4. Popescu- Gorj, A.: *Lepidopteres nouveaux ou rares pour la faune de la Republique Populaire Roumaine*. In: Trav. Mus. Mist. Nat „Gr. Antipa” , vol. 2, 1960, p.267-278.
 5. Rákosy, L.: *Lista roșie pentru fluturii diurni din România*. In: Bul. Inf. Soc. lepid. Rom., vol. 13 (1-4), 2003, p.71-78.
 6. Rákosy, L.: *U.E și legislația pentru protecția lepidopterelor din România*. In: Bul. Inf. Soc. lepid. Rom., vol. 16(3-4), 2005, p.71-78.
 7. Székely, L.: *The Butterflies of Romania – Fluturii de zi din România*. Brastar Print-Brașov, 2008.
 8. Tolman, T, Lewington, R.: *Collins Butterfly Guide: The Most Complete Field Guide to the Butterflies of Britain and Europe*. Harper Collins Publisher, 77-85 Fulham Palace Road, London W68JB., 2009.
 9. Van Sway, C.A.M., Warren, M.S.: *Red data book of European butterflies, Nature and Environment, no. 99*, Council of Europe Publishing, Strasbourg, 1999.

ASPECT REGARDING OF CUMIN USES IN BAKERY RECIPES

Oana Bianca OPREA, Liviu GACEU, Adriana BIRCA

Abstract: *The purpose of this paper is to emphasize the cumin influence in bakery products (eg. bread) regarding the main organoleptic characteristics. Also, some approaches were started from medical features to culinary uses of cumin. Moreover, there are some observations regarding the preservation period increasing with about 50% relative to the classical bakery products.*

Key words: *bread, cumin, spices.*

1. Introduction

Cumin (Cuminum cyminum) – is most commonly used to flavor foods and is widely available in both seed and powder form. While cumin is a favorite on the spice rack, it has a number of curative properties which make it a versatile natural medicine. The uses of cumin are practically endless.

It has immediate results in treating diseases like calming a number of digestive disorders including morning sickness, indigestion, heartburn, ulcers, diarrhea and flatulence.

It is usually used in tea form, treating also sore throat and coughs. In table 1 are presented some bioactive substances that show the importance of this spice in medical and culinary area.

Energy	1,567 kJ (375 kcal)	Cumin
Carbohydrates	44.24 g	
- Sugars	2.25 g	
- Dietary fiber	10.5 g	
Fat	22.27 g	
- saturated	1.535 g	
Protein	17.81 g	
Water	8.06 g	
Vitamin A equiv.	64 µg (8%)	
Riboflavin (vit. B2)	0.327 mg (27%)	
Niacin (vit. B3)	4.579 mg (31%)	
Vitamin B6	0.435 mg (33%)	
Folate (vit. B9)	10 µg (3%)	
Vitamin B12	0 µg (0%)	
Vitamin C	7.7 mg (9%)	
Vitamin E	3.33 mg (22%)	
Vitamin K	5.4 µg (5%)	
Calcium	931 mg (93%)	
Iron	66.36 mg (510%)	
Magnesium	366 mg (103%)	
Phosphorus	499 mg (71%)	
Potassium	1788 mg (38%)	
Sodium	168 mg (11%)	
Zinc	4.8 mg (51%)	

2. Material and method

Using the bread machine Moulinex 573 804, there were prepared several products to show in which ways can a specific spice, change several organoleptic properties.

The following materials are used to prepare different types of bread [4]:

- 190 ml of water;
- 3,5 little spoons of oil;
- 1 spoon salt;
- 350 g flour;
- 2,5 little spoons of sugar;
- 1 little spoon of yeast;
- + 4 g of cumin.

As working method, was chosen direct method, and cumin was inserted as 4 g seeds, spread in flour volume. Cumin, such as other spices, was used in bread dough, to see if it can increase the product preservation. The expectation was that organoleptic properties, color, taste and consistency were preserved better than with other spices.

If in preliminary researches it has been shown that cumin influence the organoleptic properties of a bakery product, it has been decided to show the benefits of using spices instead of other additives that are used nowadays in preparing different bakery products.

a.

b.

*Fig. 1 Dough with cumin using direct method workflow
a. Dough forming phase b. Dough kneading phase*

According to the technical notes from the bread machine Moulinex, the program is divided into the following operations:

- 30 minutes preheating;
- 5 minutes first kneading;
- 5 minutes rest;
- 15 minutes second kneading;
- 49 minutes rest;

- 10 second third kneading;
- 25 minutes rest;
- 10 seconds fourth kneading;
- 45 minutes rest;
- 46 minutes cooking.

Total time: 3 hours and 41 minutes.

3. Results and discussions

In figure 2 it is presented a 500 g bread in which dough has added cumin. It can be observed the normal aspect of crust and the volume increasing of the product.

Fig. 2 Final product with cumin after baking process

In figure 3 it can be observed the porosity of the bread and the other organoleptic properties such: color, plasticity and elasticity of crumb, state of baked etc. In table 2 it is presented the main characteristics of the product, and can be emphasized the extension of preserving period from 4 to 7-8 days.

Fig. 3 Section of baked products with cumin, after 1, 4, 8 days

Table 2

Spice	Taste	Confusion with other spices	Nutritional value	Organoleptic properties preservation
Cumin	Distinctive flavor and strong, warm aroma are due to its essential oil content.	Caraway	1tbsp of cumin spices contains: - Calories: 22 - Fat(g): 1.34 - Carbohydrates(g): 2.63 - Fibers(g): 0.6 - Protein: 0.25	9 days

Other uses of such products with cumin are presented in table 3.

This spice has a lot of interesting uses in medical and culinary area.

Medical uses of cumin	Culinary uses of cumin
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Cumin is a very good source of iron, which is needed to transport oxygen to all the cells within the body. * Cumin helps the body to absorb nutrients efficiently. * It is said to be a good general tonic and stimulant for the body. * It has been used to treat chest and lung disorders such as pneumonia and coughs. * Researchers are studying the anti-carcinogenic properties of cumin. It is found to prevent liver and stomach tumors forming in animals. * A paste made from cumin seeds and peppermint oil placed on the abdomen is said to relieve abdominal pains and liver disorders. * Cumin relieves flatulence, bloating, gas and other related stomach ailments. * Cumin is a diuretic. * It can relax muscles and prevent muscle cramps. * Cumin is said to help mothers produce more milk to feed their newborn babies. * Cumin is sometimes used as an antiseptic and also has antibacterial properties. * Cumin can reduce nausea and sickness, even during pregnancy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Add to citrus-flavored meat or poultry marinades. * Use as a rub for lamb or pork. * Cumin partners chilli very well. * Use cumin for barbeque sauces and marinades. * Add cumin seeds to bread or muffin dough or batters. * Sprinkle ground cumin into a cheese omelette mixture. * Fry with onions and use to flavour lentils. * Mix with olive oil and pour over stir-fried vegetables. * Add cumin to rice or couscous for an exotic flavour. * Add cumin to hot and spicy soups or sauces. * Use in curries and chillies. * Use in lamb or pork casseroles and stews. * Cumin is used in pickles and chutneys. * Cumin goes well with vegetables such as courgettes and aubergines. * Cumin is used in Falafel, deep-fried chickpea and spice balls. * Cumin also goes well with fried or roast potatoes. * Use cumin in spicy salads.

4. Conclusions

The adding of cumin in bakery products is a proper method for improving the quality and some organoleptic features of the bakery

products. Direct method for bread making is assuring a normal crust, a good porosity and a proper baking of the product. Moreover, the final product preserves the organoleptic

features for 7-8 days, almost 50% more than the classic bakery product.

References

1. K.C. Srivastava, Extracts from two frequently consumed spices — Cumin (*Cuminum cyminum*) and turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) — Inhibit platelet aggregation and alter eicosanoid biosynthesis in human blood platelets, Department of Environmental Medicine, Institute of Community Health, Odense University, J. B. Winsløws Vej 19, DK-5000 Odense, C, Denmark.

2. O. B. OPREA, L. GACEU, PRELIMINARY RESEARCHES ON USING SPICES IN TRADITIONAL BAKERY PRODUCT RECIPES, Journal of EcoAgri Tourism, Vol. 7, nr. 2, 2011, pg.15-18, ISSN: 1844-8577 Brasov, Romania
3. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cumin>
4. www.moulinex.com

THE ROSE (*ROSA DAMASCENA*) – A RESOURCE FOR DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN BULGARIA

I. OBRESHKOV* T. IVANOV**

Abstract: *Since its introduction to Bulgaria, the rose has found its second home. For centuries it has influenced the local culture and lifestyle of people. Nowadays, being one of the high-quality rose oil producing countries, Bulgaria should benefit by the promotion of a unique cultural tourism product that includes the rose. In the present article a short history of Rosa Damascena in Bulgaria is traced and few of the Rose festivals and culinary applications are marked.*

Keywords: *Rosa Damascena, rose, cultural tourism, culinary tourism.*

1. Introduction

A contemporary definition for tourism is given by Petrov [1] who defines the tourism as a set of activities, including roundtrip to, within and from selected target areas and regions, cultural, informational and emotional enrichment, health promotion, as well as the relevant service. The cultural tourism as a subdivision of the tourism provides an opportunity to get acquainted with the history, local people's lifestyle, their traditions and customs as well as their cuisine [2].

Bulgaria is a country with rich historical heritage due to its strategic location on the road from East to West. Starting with the civilization of Thracian people, remarks on the lifestyle have been left also by the Slavs, Romans, Byzantines, Bulgarians, and Ottomans.

Introduced to Bulgaria in the medieval ages, the rose (*Rosa Damascena*) has found favorable climatic conditions such as temperature and air humidity in the Sub-Balkan region. Its main application is usually linked to the world-famous essential rose oil. The rose is in the heart of every Bulgarian – usually the typical tourist souvenir brought from Bulgaria is the so called “muskal” – a small wooden bottle with a glass vial full of rose extract. The rose is widely spread in the food industry – enriching the traditional hard alcoholic drink rakiya with the tender rose aroma or within some recipes for jams and desserts. Annually there are special celebrations dedicated to the rose, attracting domestic and international tourists from all over the world. The rose is presented on various post-stamps issued in Bulgaria. Undoubtedly, the rose is the flowers'

queen and is a famous symbol of the Bulgarian tourism.

2. History of the oil bearing rose in Bulgaria

One of the most important oil-bearing rose species is *Rosa damascena* Mill. which is known as “Gol-e-Mohammadi” in Persian [3]. Iran has been mentioned as one of its origins [4]. From Syria, *Damascena* mill. was brought to Bulgarian lands in 1644 by a Turkish merchant [5]. Thus the plant is called damask rose [6]. At this time Bulgaria was part of the Ottoman Empire. In the Sub-Balkan mountain range the climatic conditions favored the rose growth, thus finding a second home in Bulgaria. The rose gave its name to a whole region – the Rose valley of Bulgaria – a centre of rose oil production and export for centuries. During the 19th century the industrial cultivation took place and the rose was spread throughout the whole Sub-Balkan valley.

On May 21, 1837 Helmuth Karl Bernhard Graf von Moltke wrote: “Kazanlak is the Turkish gulestan, that is, country of roses. There the roses grow in furrows, like potatoes”. In the 1850's the rose was planted mainly in four geographic areas of Bulgaria – Kazanlak, Karlovo, Tchirpan, Stara Zagora and Nova Zagora. Twenty years later, it was spread also in the surroundings of Elena, Triavna and Sevlievo, as well as in the region of Pazardjik.

In 1878 cuttings from the improved stock were returned to Anatolia and planted in Isparta and Burdur [7]. The founder of the Bulgarian tourism, Aleko Konstantinov, described the essential rose oil as a traditional Bulgarian symbol [8,9]. In 1903

* Dept. of Catering and Tourism, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria, e-mail: obreshkov_ivan@yahoo.com

** Dept. of Catering and Tourism, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

the first Rose festival was organized in the town of Kazanlak.

The white oil-bearing rose *Rosa alba* is the second most important plant for Bulgarian rose production.

3. Rose and cultural tourism

The rose has been part of legends, celebrations, festivals and commemorations for centuries. In ancient Greek mythology the color of red rose is associated with the beauty Rosalia's blood. The emperor Cleopatra organized events of beauty and the rose fragrance was in the air. The Roman Empire turned the rose festivities into celebrations of the free human being and liberty. In the Middle Ages rose participated in Arabian rituals. Built in 1835-40 in Plovdiv, the Hindliyan's house hosted a fountain with running rose water for aroma purposes.

Fig. 1. Bulgarian logo for tourism

The cultural heritage is the foundation of the cultural tourism activities that could comprise participation of the tourists in events and tasting the local cuisine. A variety of products from *Rosa Damascena* (rose water, rose oil, rose dried buds, rose dried petals) finds broad application in culture, cuisine, aromatherapy, landscape design [10], and medicine [11].

The first Festival of Roses in Bulgaria was organized in 1903 in the capital of roses Kazanlak, followed by Karlovo in 1906. After 1944 the tradition in Karlovo declined but people from the neighboring village of Rozino started celebrating on May 3, 1957. The Rose Festival continued 10 years. In 1967 with a Ministerial decree the Rose Festival was declared as a national holiday. The first celebration at a national level took place in Pavel Banya on June 4, 1967. Both manufacturers and masked dancers, called "koukeri" were singing and dancing during

the whole fest. Nowadays the Rose festival is supported by the mineral water festival. Both are celebrated in the end of second week of June. Sixteen years ago, since 1996, a rose festival has been organized in Strelcha [12].

Being a form of cultural tourism, festivals are defined by Ilieva [13] as an opportunity for presentation of a tourist destination. Moreover, the tourism festival contributes to the economic and cultural development of the destination. Thus the role of the local tourism information office is to promote the activities and facilitate the connection between the tourists and the destination. The unique tourism product that differs from its competitors could be assumed as the main driver [14].

As a result of our study, we conclude there are rose tourism development strengths and among these are:

- Rose is the Bulgarian Tourism Symbol;
- Reducing the local people unemployment during the harvest period and the tourist attraction activities;
- Providing important opportunity for increase of the incomes of low qualified local people;
- Promotion of cultural activities such as rose festivals and beauty contests;
- Rural areas development.

The weaknesses of the rose tourism are:

- Early get up in order to participate in the pick-up activities;
- The traditional rose-picking ritual is in the open air and depends on the weather;
- High weather risk;

There are different opportunities ahead:

- European programs for development;
- Growth interest in cultural tourism including the culinary tourism.
- Participation in the 7th framework programme of EU.

In Fig. 2 a flow chart for rose jam is presented.

The specific tourist product demand, motivated by consumer interest in local food and culinary culture will increasingly grow [15].

Rosa Damascena is used in various culinary receipts such as teas, desserts, soups, rose vinegar, rose honey, rose water, rose yoghurt, rose milk. The rose petals are used for the production of ice-cream, rose petal tea, rose jam; the rose water – in rose water syrup fruit and rosewater lemonade.

Fig. 2 Rose jam flow chart

The traditional *gyulovitsa* (rose rakiya) is a 40-degree alcoholic drink with a rose aroma achieved by addition either of rose petals or rose water to the original national distilled fruit alcoholic drink. Cases of mixing rose essence, water and ethyl alcohol are also noted. The beverage is served cooled.

Along with traditions, the scientific approach of Mollov *et al.* [16] broaden the application of rose to fortify the color stability of strawberry juices.

The annual export of rose products is about 60 tones per year but this figure doesn't include the products sold in Bulgarian hotels as souvenirs. Thus the real export is much greater.

Kazanlak is known as the capital of roses. A tourist itinerary for the festival programme in Kazanlak could include but is not restricted to:

- A beauty contest with coronation of the Queen of Roses;
- Morning departure to the rose fields and traditional rose-picking ritual;
- Visit to a rose-distillery;
- Visit to the Museum of Roses

- Participation in the street procession in Kazanlak - introduces scenes from the Bulgarian literature; presenting the entourage of the Thracian King Seuthes III;
- Attend folklore group performances from Bulgaria and abroad;
- Shopping at the traditional art crafts exhibition-bazaar;
- Rose aromatherapy procedures at the accommodation venues in the town;
- Visit to the Thracian Kazanlak Tomb (UNESCO).

4. Rose and the post ambassadors

There are several series of philatelic stamps issued in Bulgaria. Being used by tourists (as seen by the large number of copies), they are often called the post ambassadors.

A series of eight stamps named "Roses" (Fig. 3) Bulgaria, 5th of June 1970, ## 2065 -

2072. Without overprint. Artists: V. Tomov and Zh. Tishev. Printed in Leipzig. The bear yielding rose is numbered #2065 (1st) and is issued in 4 million copies.

Fig. 3. Roses issued in 1970

A series of six stamps named "Bulgarian roses" (Fig. 4). Bulgaria, 20th of July 1985, ## 3414 - 3419. Without overprint. Artists: Iv. Bogdanov. Issued in 6 million copies as singles and 300,000 as blocks.

Fig. 4. Bulgarian roses issued in 1985

A series of six stamps named "Roses" (Fig. 5). Bulgaria, 12th of December 1994, ## 4150 - 4155. Without overprint. Artists: A. Yaneva. Issued in 150,000 copies.

Fig. 5. Roses issued in 1994

5. Conclusion

The rose has influenced the lifestyle of the local people for centuries becoming part of the sustainable culture of destination. Today Bulgaria is a famous high quality rose-oil producer. The rose impacts the annually held cultural events and local cuisine. The promotion of Bulgaria as a rose destination should be enhanced on the international market.

References

- ¹ Petrov, P.S.: *Edno po-razlichno definirane na nyakoi osnovni ponyatiya v turizma (In Bulgarian)*. In: Geografiya '21 ISSN - 1312-6628, vol. 2, 2010, p.3-8.
- ² Ilieva, K.: *Rolya na natsionalnata kuhnya v kulturniya turizam (In Bulgarian)*. In: Proceedings of International Scientific Conference – "Cultural Corridor Sofia-Ohrid-Cultural Tourism Without Boundaries", Geya Libris, Sofiya, 2011, p. 112-115.
- ³ Moein, M., Karami, F., Tavallali, H., Ghasemi, Y.: Composition of the Essential Oil of *Rosa damascena* Mill. from South of Iran. In: Iranian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences, vol. 6(1), 2010, p. 59-62.
- ⁴ Chevallier A. *The encyclopedia of medicinal plants*. London: Dorling Kindersely, 1996.
- ⁵ Orozov, P.: *The Rose, its history*. Messers. Kazanlak. 1864.

- ⁶ Pal, B.P.: *The Rose in India*. In: Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Delhi, India, 1991.
- ⁷ Orozov, P.: *The Rose, its history*. Messers. Kazanlak. 1864.
- ⁸ Konstantinov, A. *Bay Ganyo* (In Bulgarian). Trud, Sofia, 2010.
- ⁹ Konstantinov, A. *Do Chikago i nazad* (In Bulgarian), Trud, Sofia, 2010.
- ¹⁰ Horn, W.: *Micropropagation of roses*. Biotechnology in Agriculture and Forestry. Springer-Verlag, Germany. 1992.
- ¹¹ Staikov, V., I. Kalajiev. *Study of oil roses (Rosa damascena Mill.) originated from India, Morocco, Iran and Bulgaria* (in Bulgarian). In: Plant Science, vol. 17(4), 1980, p.58–68.
- ¹² <http://strelchacalimanestitourism.eu> (accessed on March 11, 2012)
- ¹³ Ilieva, K.: *Festivalniyat turizam v Burgas - sastoyanie i perspektivi*. In: "Predizvikatelstva pred turizma prez XX vek", Sbornik s nauchni dokladi, UNSS, Katedra "Ikonomika na turizma", Yubileyna nauchna konferentsiya s mezhdunarodno uchastie, Sofiya, Avangard Prima, vol. 1, 2011, p. 214-224.
- ¹⁴ Ilieva, K.: *The Role of the Tourist Information Center – Burgas, Bulgaria, in Promoting Regional Tourism Product* (In Bulgarian: Rolya na turisticheskiya informatsionen tsentar – Burgas, Balgariya, za promotsiya na regionalniya turisticheski product). In: Horizonti, University of St. Kliment Ohridski, Bitola, Macedonia, vol. 7(7), 2011, p. 543-553.
- ¹⁵ Ilieva, K.: *Rolya na natsionalnata kuhnya v kulturniya turizam* (In Bulgarian). In: Proceedings of International Scientific Conference – “Cultural Corridor Sofia-Ohrid-Cultural Tourism Without Boundaries”, Geya Libris, Sofiya, 2011, p. 112-115.
- ¹⁶ Mollov, P., Mihalev, K., Shikov, V., Yoncheva, N., Karagyozov, V.: *Colour stability improvement of strawberry beverage by fortification with polyphenolic copigments naturally occurring in rose petals*. In Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies, vol. 8(3), 2007, p. 318-321

HPAEC-PAD CARBOHYDRATE ANALYSES OF BULGARIAN BLOSSOM HONEYS

I. OBRESHKOV* D. FRANZ** I. SCHELLENBERG**

Abstract: Five Bulgarian honeys produced at different regions of the country have been studied with respect to their carbohydrate composition. The composition of honey depends on its geographical and botanical origin. The purpose of this study was to determine the carbohydrate composition of Bulgarian honeys by means of HPAEC-PAD. The results showed that predominating sugars were glucose and fructose, followed by saccharose. In small amounts, other sugars (maltose, melezitose and trehalose) were also presented. Arabinose, raffinose and rhamnose were not detected.

Keywords: honey, carbohydrates, HPAEC-PAD.

1. Introduction

Among the traditional natural foodstuff in Bulgaria, honey has been known, produced and consumed by people for centuries.

Due to its composition, honey is recognized for its nourishing, antioxidant [1] and antibacterial [2] properties. Recently, Lazarova and Yurukova have studied the pollen and inorganic compositions of Bulgarian honeys [3,4]. The chemical composition of honey has been linked to its botanical and geographical origin. Moreover, the carbohydrate determination is a valuable source for information in detection of fraudulent impact on the natural product.

In addition to glucose, fructose and saccharose, Cotte *et al.* [5] determine the presence of the disaccharides maltose and trehalose, and the non-reducing trisaccharides raffinose and melezitose in French honeys, where as Rodriguez *et al.* [6] identified arabinose.

There are different methods for carbohydrate determination – Dubois colourimetric method [7], gas [8-10], planar [11] and high-performance liquid chromatography. HPAEC-PAD is the contemporary method-of-choice for carbohydrate analyses [12] due to their weakly acidic nature.

Thus, the purpose of this study was to determine the carbohydrate composition of Bulgarian honeys by means of high-performance anion-exchange chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection (HPAEC-PAD).

2. Material and methods

Five blossom honey samples (F1, F2, F3, F4 and F5) were bought directly from various local bee-keepers located in different North and South regions of the country. The type of honeys was defined by the producers themselves. The honeys were stored at room temperature in glass jars until analyses.

An aliquot of 2 g of honey was diluted with double-distilled water (TOC = 4 ppb; 18.2 MΩ 10⁻² m) and the dilution was analyzed by means of HPAEC-PAD after filtration.

The samples were analyzed on a Dionex IC system, model DX-500 (Sunnyvale, CA, USA), equipped with a GP-40 gradient pump, AS40 autosampler, LC20 chromatography enclosure and ED40 pulsed amperometric detector with a gold working electrode was used. The pulse potentials on the ED40 detector were: $t = 0$, $E = 0.05$ V; $t = 0.20$ s, $E = 0.05$ V (start); $t = 0.40$ s, $E = 0.05$ (end); $t = 0.41$ s, $E = 0.75$ V; $t = 0.60$ s, $E = 0.75$; $t = 0.61$ s, $E = -0.15$ V; $t = 1.00$ s, $E = -0.15$ V [13]. After injection of a filtered sample (25 μL) into a CarboPac PA-100 column (4 × 250 mm) (Dionex Corp., USA), the carbohydrates were isocratically eluted with mobile phase consisted of 100 mM NaOH at a flow-rate 0.5 mL.min⁻¹ for 33 minutes run time. The eluted carbohydrates were plotted with Chromeleon Client 6.60 SP1a Build 1449 (Dionex). The carbohydrates were identified by comparing the retention times of external standards.

* Dept. of Catering and Tourism, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria, e-mail: obreshkov_ivan@yahoo.com

** Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Center of Life Sciences, Institute of Bioanalytical Sciences, Bernburg, Germany

** Anhalt University of Applied Sciences, Center of Life Sciences, Institute of Bioanalytical Sciences, Bernburg, Germany

The following analytical sugar standards were used: D(+)-glucose, D(-)-fructose and D(+)-maltose monohydrate (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany); D(+)-trehalose dehydrate, L(+)-rhamnose monohydrate, D(+)-melezitose monohydrate and D(+)-raffinose pentahydrate (Carl Roth GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany); L(+)-arabinose (Fritz Leidholdt-Biochemie, Germany); D(+)-sucrose (Fluka, Ronkonkoma, USA). Fifty percent (w/w) sodium hydroxide solution was obtained from J.T. Baker (Deventer, Netherlands).

Statistical analyses were performed as the obtained data were processed using STATISTICA statistical software package (version 7.0) and Origin 8.0. All honey samples were analyzed in triplicates.

3. Results and discussion

The carbohydrate profile of honey was evaluated by means of HPAEC-PAD. The elution took place in the following order: trehalose (4.4 min), glucose (6.8 min), fructose (7.6 min), saccharose (11.5 min), melezitose (16.4 min), maltose (24.2 min). Three carbohydrates were not detected by the system, namely arabinose, raffinose and rhamnose. Both fructose and glucose (Table 1) comprised more than 90 % of the carbohydrate content. In Table 1 data about the relative carbohydrate composition in Bulgarian honeys are presented.

Saccharose is the third most abundant carbohydrate in the samples, followed by maltose, melezitose and trehalose.

Table 1. Relative carbohydrate content

Carbohydrate	Fru	Glu	Mal	Mel	Sac	Tre
Sample						
F1	51.4	38.5	1.9	1.5	5.7	1.0
F2	50.8	41.8	1.6	1.7	3.2	0.9
F3	52.1	40.4	2.6	1.5	3.0	0.5
F4	50.3	39.8	2.2	1.9	5.1	0.7
F5	54.2	36.6	2.5	1.9	3.4	1.5

The good baseline separation ($R_s > 1.5$) allowed quantifying the carbohydrates. The quantitative data are presented in Table 2. In addition to the average values, the relevant standard deviations are shown. The

predominating carbohydrate was fructose with average content in the samples $33.7 \text{ g } 100\text{g}^{-1}$. Being the second, glucose varied between 23.24 and $27.06 \text{ g } 100\text{g}^{-1}$.

Table 2. Carbohydrate composition of Bulgarian honeys [$\text{g } 100\text{g}^{-1}$]

	Fru	Glu	Mal	Mel	Sac	Tre	Fru/Glu
F1	31.07 (0.11)	23.24 (0.12)	1.14 (0.05)	0.92 (0.01)	3.43 (0.02)	0.63 (0.01)	1.34
F2	32.92 (0.19)	27.06 (0.05)	1.05 (0.04)	1.11 (0.01)	2.06 (0.01)	0.58 (0.00)	1.22
F3	34.83 (0.10)	27.01 (0.15)	1.72 (0.08)	1.01 (0.01)	1.98 (0.08)	0.31 (0.01)	1.29
F4	31.37 (0.06)	24.82 (0.02)	1.36 (0.04)	1.21 (0.03)	3.16 (0.05)	0.44 (0.01)	1.26
F5	38.66 (0.10)	26.12 (0.08)	1.75 (0.07)	1.38 (0.02)	2.39 (0.01)	1.06 (0.03)	1.48

Descriptive Statistics

Mean	33.77	25.65	1.40	1.13	2.60	0.60	1.32
Min	31.07	23.24	1.05	0.92	1.98	0.31	1.22
Max	38.66	27.06	1.75	1.38	3.43	1.06	1.48
St Dev	3.12	1.62	0.32	0.18	0.66	0.28	0.10

The ratio between fructose and glucose is always above one. Ultimately, the fructose is almost 50% as much as the glucose (1.48). Rodriguez *et al.* [6] found similar the ratios between fructose and glucose (F/G) content ranging between 1.19 and 1.39.

Melezitose usually is found in higher quantities in honeydew honeys. All samples (F1, F2, F3, F4 and F5) showed the presence of melezitose in their composition. According to Bogdanov [14] honeys with less than 0.6 g.100g⁻¹ were classified as blossom honeys using the melezitose as a

discriminant value. At the same time, Bogdanov assumed exceptions from this rule.

Both the Bulgarian and EU legislation state that the blossom honey must have minimum content of the sum of fructose and glucose of 60 g 100g⁻¹. This criterion defines samples F2, F3 and F5 as blossom honeys, whereas samples F1 and F4 cover the criterion for honeydew honeys for a minimum of 45 g 100g⁻¹. All samples were within the limit of the Bulgarian legislation concerning the contents of sucrose (less 10 g 100g⁻¹).

Table 3. Pearson correlation coefficients

	Fru	Glu	Mal	Mel	Sac	Tre	Fru + Glu
Fru	1.00						
Glu	0.55	1.00					
Mal	0.78	0.36	1.00				
Mel	0.67	0.32	0.48	1.00			
Sac	-0.58	-0.98*	-0.37	-0.21	1.00		
Tre	0.65	-0.08	0.21	0.64	0.04	1.00	
Fru + Glu	0.95**	0.79	0.72	0.62	-0.81	0.45	1.00

*statistically significant at p<0.01

**statistically significant at p<0.05

The total carbohydrate content was within the range of 60-71 g 100g⁻¹ honey.

In Table 3 the correlation matrix for the single carbohydrates is shown. Glucose and saccharose were strictly correlated. It was found that there is a statistically significant negative correlation at the level of significance p < 0.01 between the absolute quantities of glucose and saccharose (R² > 0.95). No significant correlation was found at p < 0.01 among the other carbohydrates. In addition analyses was performed at the level of significance p < 0.05 and was found a positive correlation that is statistically significant between

the sum of fructose and glucose, and the fructose itself.

4. Conclusions

Five Bulgarian honeys produced at different regions of the country have been studied with respect to their carbohydrate composition. Six carbohydrates (fructose, glucose, maltose, melezitose, sucrose and trehalose) were identified and the relevant relative ratios were calculated. Moreover, the absolute quantities of the carbohydrates were determined. Rhamnose, arabinose and raffinose were not detected.

References

- Vela, L., Lorenzo, C. de, Perez, R.A.: *Antioxidant capacity of Spanish honeys and its correlation with polyphenol content and other physicochemical properties*. In: Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture, vol. 87(6), 2007, p. 1069-1075.
- Bogdanov, S.: *Characterisation of antibacterial substances in honey*. In: Lebensmittel-Wissenschaft und-Technologie, vol. 17(2), 1984, p. 74-76.
- Lazarova, M., Yurukova, L.: *Pollen and Inorganic Analyses of Bee Honey from Shumen District (North-Eastern Bulgaria*). In: Comptes Rendus de l'Académie Bulgare des Sciences, vol. 60(11), 2007, p. 1187-1192.
- Yurukova, L., Atanassova, J., Lazarova, M.: *Preliminary study on honeydew honey from Bulgarian market*. In: Comptes Rendus de l'Académie Bulgare des Sciences, vol. 61(11), 2008, p. 1433-1440.
- Cotte, J.F., Casabianca, H., Chardon, S., Lheritier, J., Grenier-Loustalot, M.F.: *Application of carbohydrate analysis to verify honey authenticity*. In: Journal of Chromatography A, vol. 1021(1-2), 2003, p. 145-155.

6. Rodriguez, O.G., de Ferrer, B.S., Ferrer, A., Rodriguez, B.: *Characterization of honey produced in Venezuela*. In: Food Chemistry, vol. 84(4), 2004, p. 499-502.
7. Dubois, M., Gilles, D.A., Hamilton, J.K., Rebers, P.A., Smith, F.: *Colorimetric method for the determination of sugars and related substances*. In: Analytical Chemistry 28(3), 1956, p. 350-356.
8. Kurz, C., Carle, R., Schieber, A.: *Characterisation of cell wall polysaccharide profiles of apricots (*Prunus armeniaca L.*), peaches (*Prunus persica L.*), and pumpkins (*Cucurbita sp.*) for the evaluation of fruit product authenticity*. In: Food Chemistry 106(1), 2008, p. 421-430.
9. Kurz, C., Leitenberger, M., Carle, R., Schieber, A.: *Evaluation of fruit authenticity and determination of the fruit content of fruit products using FT-NIR spectroscopy of cell wall components*. In: Food Chemistry 119(2), 2010, p. 806-812.
10. Ramirez-Truque, C., Esquivel, P., Carle, R.: *Neutral sugar profile of cell wall polysaccharides of pitaya (*Hylocereus sp.*) fruits*. In: Carbohydrate Polymers 83(3), 2011, p. 1134-1138.
11. Vaccari, G., Lodi, G., Tamburini, E., Bernardi T., Tosi, S.: *Detection of oligosaccharides in sugar products using planar chromatography*. In: Food Chemistry 74(1), 2001, p. 99-110.
12. Davis, M. W.: *A rapid modified method for compositional carbohydrate analysis of lignocellulosics by high pH anion exchange chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection (HPAEC/PAD)*. In: Journal of Wood Chemistry and Technology 18(2), 1998, p. 235-252.
13. Bansleben, D., Schellenberg, I., Wolff, A.-C.: *Highly automated and fast determination of raffinose family oligosaccharides in Lupinus seeds using pressurized liquid extraction and high-performance anion-exchange chromatography with pulsed amperometric detection*. In: Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture 88(11), 2008, p. 1949-1953.
14. Bogdanov, S., Gfeller, M.: *Classification of honeydew and blossom honeys by discriminant analysis*. In: ALP Science, vol. 500, 2006.

ECOLOGICAL USE OF INDUSTRIAL FIBER PLANTS AS RENEWABLE RAW MATERIALS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS IN ECO-TOURISM AND FOOD SUPPLEMENTS

D.C. OLA* D. DANILA* L. GACEU* C. SPIRCHEZ**

Abstract: *The paper presents the versatile applications of fiber plants in various applications with a positive impact upon achieving a higher efficiency of the use of agricultural land. The development of the new ecological techniques involves the sequestration of CO₂ emissions and in the same time provide a positive ecological impact upon biodiversity of the rural space. This paper presents the multiple applications of the fiber plants crops such as hemp and flax.*

Keywords: *renewable materials, fiber plants, hemp, flax, food supplements.*

1. Introduction

Fiber plants such as hemp and flax are considered valuable crops for both fibers and food supplements for human and animal nutrition.

Hemp crops are known to have a long tradition in the history of mankind this crop being the support of the clothing and sailing industry. Earliest findings of hemp products in Europe date back to 800-400 B.C.

They are often used in rotation cultures, since these crops have a high growth density with deep rooting system, as is the case of hemp, that has a positive impact on weed control and soil loosening. Since hemp has a powerful weed suppression it can be used also to clear arable land from weed without the use of herbicides. The cultivation tradition before the synthetic fiber era showed that higher yields were recorded on food crops that were used in rotation with the cultivation of fiber plants such as hemp and flax.

Another positive aspect of these plants is the fact that they require very little maintenance and they can be used entirely on various fields of the industry and agriculture.

Hemp is also crop that supports agrobiodiversity as many insects, birds and wildlife seek shelter and nourishment in these crops with

a minimal impact upon the production output. Biodiversity studies carried by Morntfod and Small (1999) presented the biodiversity friendliness of 23 crops based on a set of biodiversity parameters. The crops studied included industrial fiber crops and finally a scale was developed according to the biodiversity impact of each culture. The hemp crops were placed in a favorable top position as it can be seen in figure 1.

The use of fiber plants in Europe has been greatly affected by the development of the synthetic fibers and low production price. Even more the technologies used in the production of fine natural fibers are still behind the actual technological potential and therefore as far as the fibers demand for top applications, the synthetics fibers remain an overwhelming competitor.

New markets have been formed in the favor of natural fibers that require a not so pretentious quality and offer a weather friendly solution to insulation materials, landscape mats, agrotexiles, building materials and food supplements [2].

Based on the cultivation of flax and hemp a specific tourism niche was developed based on products manufactured entirely the fiber plants, in countries such as France and Austria. The applications range from accommodation facilities that use as construction material from natural

* Dept. of Engineering and Management of Food and Tourism, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: danielola@unitbv.ro

* Dept. of Engineering and Management of Food and Tourism, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: daniladan@unitbv.ro

* Dept. of Engineering and Management of Food and Tourism, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: gaceul@unitbv.ro

** Dept. of Wood Processing and Wood Products Design, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: cosmin.spirchez@yahoo.com

fibers to specialties of foods and drinks approved by the national regulations, such as: hemp oil, hemp butter, hemp chocolate, hemp sauce, hemp pasta, hemp bars and patisserie that use hemp seeds and oils.

Worldwide there are many manufacturing companies that offer a large variety of products that have as raw materials industrial fiber plants.

Fig. 1. Biodiversity evaluation impact of various agro-forests crops [1].

2. Applications of fiber materials in eco-tourism

Hemp fibers can be used in many various ways and the latest application is focused in the production of insulation mats. This product has a growing market especially in projects that target the building of the “zero emissions house”. Some European countries encourage this kind of projects and also projects that try to make tourism facilities based on eco-friendly materials. The natural fibers offer a very nice living environment and are most desired especially for their capability to regulate humidity.

Since 2008, the construction industry has been reduced greatly by the recent financial crisis and this has been seen also in the sector of natural insulation products.

Another large pool of applications in the rural tourism are products used for the landscape such as agro textiles, geotextiles or products used for the animal husbandry such as mattresses, shoe lifts, fibers for animal nesting. Many garden applications represent other products that complete the support that comes in agro-tourism. Traditional products of hemp twine, textile yarns and fabrics can become a support for specific in the rural and cultural attractions of agro-tourism.

Hemp seeds can be used in traditional bakery and in culinary products with great added value in the human health. The hemp seeds can be collected as part of the fiber crop or can be produced in crops destined especially for the seeds production. The main use of hemp seeds in the eco-tourism can be divided in two main directions: for human nourishment and for animal feeding.

Hemp seeds presented as whole grains or hulled hemp seeds are a great source of oil and protein rich food supplement. Many of the healthy food consumers appreciate greatly natural sources of proteins and can be used to supplement the low animal protein diets.

Hemp oil is regarded as being one of the main quality vegetable oil that provides an ideal proportion of omega 6 to omega 3 fats. In figure 2 can be seen a comparison of the different fats content on oils that are rich in omega 3 fats and omega 6 fats. It can be seen that hemp oil offers a valuable balanced vegetable oil that can supplement the human nourishment and provides a healthy diet.

Fig. 2. Fats content comparison of various vegetal oils [3].

The healthy food market represents an ever growing sector where hemp seeds can have a greater role.

Today the largest amounts of hemp seeds are sold for animal feed, as bird seed or as bait for fishers.

3. Overview of hemp byproducts

In the processing of the hemp plants, new technologies have been developed that offer a more sustainable fiber production. The fiber separation produces also significant amounts of hurds and rich fertilizing dust. The residual hurd content in the fibres is generally according to the hemp specie in a ration that can be from 1.5 to 2 parts of hurds to fibers.

Hemp hurds are used in the animal bedding especially because their absorbance properties that makes them a good absorbent, very easy to handle and are rapid to decay after use adding also valuable nutrients in the ground used.

Many agro touristic facilities are based on the exploitation of animal farms and of animal entertaining activities. In the caring and keeping

of animals hemp hurds play a special market as animal bedding. The main sector is represented by the horse husbandry especially in the equestrian facilities. Most of the hemp hurds used as animal bedding are destined for the horse bedding as this sector was more opened to the advantages offered by the hemp hurds.

A small part of the hemp hurds are also used and suitable for other animals and is often used for pets and poultry. The market of home pets is growing more and more and the hemp hurds represents a product with an expected increase on the market share in the next years.

A new sector of use for the hemp hurds are the construction sector where hurds are used insulation. The Insulation with hemp hurds can be realized by pouring the bulk hurds and compacting them by different means. Another way of producing hurds insulation is to compact them into density boards or bricks or loam construction. These products are a new direction that can be used in the building of the green houses that use environmentally friendly building materials.

4. Conclusions

It can be seen that natural fiber plants offer a very large applications pool and if used extensively can support many tourism units and activities.

The natural fiber production and technology proves that it can still be a long sustainable base for various applications. The agro-tourism can greatly benefit by integrating the hemp products in its facilities and in its offers.

References

1. Montford, S., Small, E.: *Measuring harm and benefit: The biodiversity friendliness of Cannabis sativa*. In: Global biodiversity, 1999, 8(4): 2–13.
2. Piotrowski, S., Carus M.: *Ecological benefits of hemp and flax cultivation and products*. nova institute 2011, no.5.
3. Strunz, U., Jopp, A.: *Fit mit Fett – Gute Fette von Killerfetten unterscheiden*. Wilhelm Heyne Verlag, München 2002.

PLANT SPECIES DIVERSITY IN SINCA NOUA AREA (BRAȘOV COUNTY) AND SOME ISSUES REGARDING THE CONSERVATION OF PROTECTED SPECIES

O.G. POP* R. GRUIA* A. MARCULESCU* C.L. BADARAU*

Abstract: *The flora of Sinca Noua area (Brașov County) is very rich - 545 taxa, with several rare species and subspecies. Regarding species' richness, the Asteraceae family was most numerous, represented by 63 taxa, followed by the Poaceae with 51 species. Applying the IUCN criteria on a regional level upon the 545 taxa found, we found following distribution of categories: EN – 2 taxa, NT – 10 taxa, LC – 502 taxa, NA – 6 taxa, DD – 25 taxa.*

Keywords: *plant species diversity, Șinca Nouă*

1. Introduction

Sinca Noua, a village at the foot of the Fagarash Mountains, located in Brașov County, can be characterised by a broad variety of habitats and an astonishing natural beauty and richness. The economics of the region are based on small subsistence farms, with the traditional extensive and little mechanised way of land-use still in place. This system is seriously endangered by several factors, but most importantly by the socio-economic upheavals due to the accession to the European Union and the predicted climate change. By knowing the current situation we will be able to detect and monitor changes in biodiversity.

2. Study area

The richness of the flora and the diversity of the habitats in the area of Sinca Noua are closely related to the complex geological substrate and the particularities of the relief. Hence, in the lower parts of the region we find Holocene (sand, gravel, loess deposits) and Pleistocene sediments, just a little higher, schist and sandstone from the Palaeogene. Further, on the surface, appear marls and conglomerates from the Upper Cretaceous and, as some small islands, limestone and older, Aptian conglomerates (from the Lower Cretaceous) and Triassic dolomite.

The highest peaks (belonging to the Taga Mountain), that form the Southern limits of the small Sinca Depression, are formed by metamorphic rocks, in some parts dominated by the green schist's facies, and in others by amphibolites' facies. In the close neighbourhood of the investigated territory, around Taga

Mountains, we registered small islands of Mesozoic magmata.

Most of the land belonging to the community of Sinca Noua is circumscribed to the Sinca Depression, which is a small compartment (maximum width a bit more than 8 km) in the South East corner of the Fagaras Depression. In the Quaternary Era, a lake filled the Sinca Depression, in which alluviums brought by the mountain streams were deposited. Nowadays, several creeks and streams, tributary to the Sinca stream, which had fragmented the hollow bed into a few almost flat segments, some of them narrower, some wider, traverse this depression. These fragments – by the locals called “poduri”(=plateau) – are used now as hay meadows, pasture land, or arable land. Only two hills appear above these “plateaus” with glacial appearance: Maguricea Hill (647 m) and Poiana Lunga Hill (approx. 800 m). Between those two hills and the foot of the Taga Mountains (with much higher peaks) the Wolf Valley (Valea Lupului) widens into an interesting wet area, called by the locals “Mlaca” – a regionalism for “mlastina” (marsh, swamp) originating from the Bulgarian/Serbian word “mlaka”.

2. Material and methods

In order to gain a good insight into the flora of the 5,500 ha big study area, the research team spent altogether around two months between May and November in the field.

Where possible we identified the specimens in the field, otherwise some samples were taken for further examination in the laboratory. One part of the collection was further on given to the

* “Transylvania” University from Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism, Brasov, Romania. e-mail: oliviupop@yahoo.com

Herbarium of the Forestry Faculty in Brasov and the Faculty of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine in Bucharest.

To evaluate in which way these species are endangered we used the criteria of the Red List of Higher Plants of Romania (Olteanu et al., 1994): E – endangered, V – vulnerable, R – rare, NT – not threatened. In addition we used the IUCN criteria (version 3.1, 2001) to classify species identified in the region for their risk of extinction. Therefore the IUCN criteria were adapted to a regional level – Strâmba valley, Magurica Hill, Poiana Lunga (~ 6,000 ha) – according to the recommendations given by the IUCN (“Guidelines for the Application of IUCN Red List Criteria at Regional Levels: version 3.0”): CR – critically endangered; EN – endangered; VU – vulnerable; NT – near threatened; LC – least concern; DD – data deficient; NA – not applicable.

3. Results and discussions

Plant species diversity

The flora is very rich with several rare species and subspecies: *Lycopodium complanatum*, *Botrychium multifidum*, *Eleocharis carniolica*, *Lysimachia nemorum*, *Hypericum humifusum*, *Rumex thyrsiflorus*, *Carex hartmanii*, *Dryopteris affinis*, *Melampyrum pratense*, ssp. *purpureum*. Especially remarkable is the presence of some orchids (*Orchis laxiflora* ssp. *elegans*, *Spiranthes spiralis*, species of *Epipactis*, *Cephalanthera* etc.) as well as the species diversity in the *Rubus* genus and the sedges (*Carex* sp.).

Even though the list of species – a total of 545 taxa, is already very impressive for such a small area, this number will still increase with further investigation, especially with a deeper look into plant communities that were of lower interest for this first evaluation (for example weeds on fields). Some more species are most likely to be discovered by a more detailed investigation in the areas at higher altitudes. We did, for example, find in an earlier survey in close vicinity of the study area, a lot of typical mountain meadow species (*Arnica montana*, *Trollius europaeus*, *Phleum alpinum*, *Gentiana kochiana*, *G. utriculosa*, *G. praecox*, *Knautia longifolia*, *Leucorchis albida*, *Bupleurum diversifolium*, *Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Traunsteinera globosa*, *Botrychium lunaria*, *Avenula praeusta* ssp. *adsurgens*, *A. planiculmis*), plants that might occur also in the Sinca Noua area. Looking at specie’s richness, the Asteraceae family was most

numerous, represented by 63 taxa, followed by the Poaceae with 51 species (Tab. 1).

Tab. 1: Species distribution on the most common plant families.

Family	No. of species
Asteraceae	63
Poaceae	51
Cyperaceae	31
Fabaceae	29
Rosaceae	28
Lamiaceae	26
Orchidaceae	22
Caryophyllaceae	22
Apiaceae	21
Ranunculaceae	19
Srophulariaceae	19
Polypodiaceae	14
Brasicaceae	13
Polygonaceae	12
Rubiaceae	12
Juncaceae	11

Applying the IUCN criteria on a regional level upon the 545 taxa found, we found following distribution of categories: EN – 2 taxa, NT – 10 taxa, LC – 502 taxa, NA – 6 taxa, DD – 25 taxa.

Plant Species with special protection status

I. Annex II of the EU Habitat Directive (animal and plant species of community interest whose conservation requires the designation of special areas of conservation)

Eleocharis carniolica

Fam. Cyperaceae

Habitat: on damp places in oak forests up to the fir zones, along rivers, or on temporary flooded meadows.

Distribution: This species is distributed mainly in central and eastern Europe; in Romania it is wide spread (Braşov, Cluj, Constanţa, Covasna, Maramureş, Mehedinţi, Mureş, etc.); in the study area we found it on Podul Strâmbei, the plateau between Lupului valley and Strâmba valley.

Abundance: rare (locally abundant) – swamps and humid meadows on the plateau.

Major risks: At the time being the species is in a good conservation state. The species would be severely endangered by draining the humid areas

and meadows, and abandoning mowing would lead to an advance of bushes and later on forests into the open areas inhabited by *E. carniolica*.

Proposed management measures: preserving the traditional land use and prohibiting eventual initiatives of draining wetlands where the species occurs.

Monitoring: 1. Permanent supervision of the conservation state of the humid habitats that shelter this species and maintaining the traditional way of land use; 2. Counting and mapping of individuals on sample surfaces.

II. Species Of National (Included In The Red List Of Higher Plants In Romania) and Local Interest

Spiranthes spiralis (Autumn Lady's-Tresses)

Fam. Orchidaceae

Habitat: dry meadows, margin of the forests, on moderately acid soils.

Distribution: In the study area, we found this species on the communal pasture land between V. lui Gheabata and P. Sarat, and in V. Hontului.

Abundance: rare; we found it in three locations on the pasture, with a maximum of 20 individuals in each. Our estimate for the total population size does not exceed 200 individuals.

Major risks: At the moment the species is in a precarious conservation state due to permanent threats, represented by overgrazing and initiatives to improve the pasture land without taking into consideration the ecological needs of this species.

Proposed management measures: preserving the traditional land use including walking on with livestock. In case improvement measurements for the pasture are taken, different treatment has to be considered on the sites where this orchid occurs. We recommend an additional survey to identify the precise number of individuals.

Monitoring: 1. Permanent supervision of the conservation state of the species' habitat; 2. Maintaining the traditional way of land use (as a pasture), with a certain number of livestock grazing on it according to the pasture's capacity; 3. Evaluating population size by direct count of all individuals or by counting individuals on fixed and marked sample plots. A monitoring example is given below.

Botrichium multifidum

Fam. Ophioglossaceae

Habitat: margin of the forests and bushes.

Distribution: In the study area, we found this species in the beech and hazelnut bushes at the margin of the pasture on Poiana Lunga.

Abundance: very rare, we found only one single individual.

Major risks: At the moment the conservation state can not be evaluated; in general, main threats are grazing in the forests and clearing of bushes where the species has been identified.

Proposed management measures: preserving the traditional land use including walking on with livestock and avoiding to clear woodlands in areas where the species occurs.

Monitoring: 1. Permanent supervision of the conservation stage of the species' habitat; 2. Supervising and maintaining the traditional way of land use (as hay meadows).

Achillea ptarmica (Sneezewort)

Fam. Asteraceae

Habitat: Damp grassy places, meadows, pastures, marshes.

Distribution: In the study area, we found this species in the upper Valea Lupului ("Mlaca") and in the Strâmba valley.

Abundance: sporadically.

Major risks: At the time being the species is in a good conservation state. Abandoning mowing is the main threat, since bushes and thereafter forests will take over, leading to vanishing of the species.

Proposed management measures: preserving the traditional land use and keeping the customary periods of hay cutting.

Monitoring: 1. Permanent supervision of the conservation stage of the species' habitat; 2. Counting and mapping of all individuals identified.

Gladiolus imbricatus (Wiesen-Siegwurz)

Fam. Iridaceae

Habitat: Meadows and damp meadows.

Distribution: We found this species in the Strâmba valley and on the plateau between V. Lupului and V. Strâmbei.

Abundance: sporadically to rare on the sites mentioned above.

Major risks: At the time being the species is in a good conservation state. Abandoning mowing is the main threat, since bushes and thereafter forests will take over, leading to vanishing of the species.

Proposed management measures: preserving the traditional land use and keeping the customary periods of hay cutting.

Monitoring: 1. Permanent supervision of the conservation stage of the species' habitat; 2.

Supervising and keeping of the traditional land use regime in that area (as hay meadows).

Epipactis palustris (Marsh Helleborine)

Fam. Orchidaceae

Habitat: Wet or damp places (marshes).

Distribution: We found this species in following areas: Piriul lui Gheabata, Mlaca, Valea Lupului, Strâmba.

Abundance: locally abundant.

Major risks: At the time being the species is in a good conservation state. Main threats are represented by long droughts, draining of the wet areas on meadows, and abandoning mowing, which would lead to bushes and forests coming back.

Proposed management measures: preserving the traditional land use and prohibiting eventual initiatives of draining wetlands where the species occurs.

Monitoring: Permanent supervision of the conservation stage of the species' habitat.

Orchis laxiflora

Fam. Orchidaceae

Habitat: Wet marshy meadows.

Distribution: In the study area we found this species in Mlaca and the Strâmba valley (Map 5).

Abundance: a maximum of 30 individuals at each location.

Major risks: At the time being the species is in a good conservation state. Main threats are represented by long droughts, draining of the wet areas on meadows, and abandoning mowing, which would lead to bushes and forests coming back.

Proposed management measures: preserving the traditional land use and prohibiting eventual initiatives of draining wetlands where the species occurs.

Monitoring: 1. Permanent supervision of the conservation stage of the species' habitat; 2. Counting of individuals on sample plots.

Lysimachia nemorum (Yellow Pimpernell)

Fam. Primulaceae

Habitat: Damp, shaded places in woodlands and copses, occasionally along riverbanks.

Distribution: In the study area we found this species on Poiana Lunga (a ridge between V. Gheabata and Pârâul Sarata), and in Valea Hontului.

Abundance: The species is abundant in the two sites where it was located.

Major risks: At the moment the species is in a rather precarious state due to permanent threats represented by overgrazing and possible measurements taken to improve the pasture land without taking the ecological needs of this species into consideration.

Proposed management measures: Preserving the traditional land use, including walking on with livestock. In case improvement measurements for the pasture are taken, different treatment has to be considered on the sites where this orchid occurs. We recommend an additional survey to identify the precise number of individuals.

Monitoring: 1. Permanent supervision of the conservation state of the species' habitat; 2. Maintaining the traditional way of land use (as a pasture), with a certain number of livestock grazing on it according to the pasture's capacity; 3. Evaluating population size by counting individuals on fixed and marked sample plots.

3. Conclusions

The flora of Sinca Noua area is very rich - 545 taxa, with several rare species and subspecies: *Lycopodium complanatum*, *Botrychium multifidum*, *Eleocharis carniolica*, *Lysimachia nemorum*, *Hypericum humifusum*, *Rumex thyrsiflorus*, *Carex hartmanii*, *Dryopteris affinis*, *Melampyrum pratense*, ssp. *purpureum*. Especially remarkable is the presence of some orchids (*Orchis laxiflora* ssp. *elegans*, *Spiranthes spiralis*, species of *Epipactis*, *Cephalanthera* etc.) as well as the species diversity in the *Rubus* genus and the sedges (*Carex* sp.).

Regarding species' richness, the Asteraceae family was most numerous, represented by 63 taxa, followed by the Poaceae with 51 species.

Applying the IUCN criteria on a regional level upon the 545 taxa found, we found following distribution of categories: EN – 2 taxa, NT – 10 taxa, LC – 502 taxa, NA – 6 taxa, DD – 25 taxa.

Acknowledgement: this paper is supported by the Sectoral Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the contract number POSDRU/89/1.5/S/59323.

References

1. Ciocârlan, V.: *Flora ilustrată a României, Ed. II*, Ed. Ceres, București, 2000.
2. IUCN: *IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria: Version 3.1. IUCN Species Survival Commission. IUCN*, Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK., 2001, ii + 30 pp.
3. IUCN: *Guidelines for Application of IUCN Red List Criteria at Regional Levels: Version 3.0. IUCN Species Survival Commission. IUCN*, Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK, 2003. ii + 26 pp.
4. Oltean, M., et al.: *Lista roșie a plantelor superioare din România*, Inst. de Biologie. Studii sinteze, documentații de ecologie, 1:1-52, București, 1994.
5. Pop, I., Tretiu, T.: *Contribuții la cunoașterea vegetației de la Șinca Nouă*, 209-235, Studii și Cercetări de Biologie, Cluj-Napoca 1958.
6. Pop, O.G. (ed.): *Flora și habitatele de la Șinca Nouă*, Ed. Univ. Transilvania, Brașov, 2008.

DENSITY AND RELATIVE FREQUENCY OF SPECIES, RESOURCES OF BIODIVERSITY STUDY CONCERNING

A. SAVA* C. BADARAU** A. MARCULESCU**

Abstract: *To measure biodiversity, within a species number of community, most often used is Simpson index, with which it is used and the extent of information – Shannon index. After Patil, G.P, Taille, C., (1982), diversity indices are mathematical functions of relative abundance. The biodiversity analysis, based on relative abundance, instead of using absolute abundance, has limits, when the processes who change total abundance, do not affect, apparently, the relative abundance. Also, the biodiversity can be analyzed through relative frequency and density of species, as is reflected in this study.*

Keywords: *biodiversity, relative frequency, herbaceous and shrubs species.*

1. Introduction

Density is the number of individuals per unit area and frequency is the number of sample areas containing copies of a given species the total number of sample surfaces (Târziu, 2003).

If density were considered all species identified in sample surfaces, for frequency calculation was considered only herbaceous and shrub layers

2. Place of research, analysis and calculation of density and relative frequency of species

The research regarding the study of abundance were made in pure beech forest ecosystems, as well as mixtures of beech and pine, located in Ciucas massif. We had to pass four production sites (marked UP), in the massif, namely Dălghiu (UP I) Zizinului Valley (UP II), Village Valley (UP III) and Buzău Springs (UP IV).

To made the research, were studied two types of stands, namely pure beech stands (young and old with both a witness and with works) and mixed stands of beech and pine (young and old, with both witness and with works).

3. Methodology and calculation of density and relative frequency

To achieve the research, were studied two types of stands: pure stands of beech and beech mixed with resins (fir tree, spruce, pine, larch). In

the pure beech forests and in those in mixture with coniferous trees were analyzed young (aged 40 years and 70ani) and older stands (aged 95 years and 150 years).

Was made 24 experimental couples (marked "C"), each couple comprising two experimental variants: a witness variant (noted "m"), who has not been interfered with any type of silvicultural work, or at most have been completed a hygiene work, and a variant with works (noted "p") such as the progressive cuts.

Density was calculated by extrapolating the number of individuals identified in the area of reports per hectare and for frequency, was used the coefficient of variation and the values are presented in the table no.1.

4. Results and discussion

The table no.1, shows the number of individuals per hectare for herbaceous and shrub layers. For characterization of specific diversity, we used the coefficient of variation of frequency, whose values are presented in the same chart.

In the figures A,B,C,D,E,F,G and H are, by comparison, values of coefficient of variation of the relative frequency and the number of species for trees analyzed as a whole, considered herbaceous layers and shrub. It may be noted that in all cases, the coefficient of variation of relative frequency increase with the number of species, herbaceous species were significantly higher

* Dept. of Food Industry and Tourism, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: aliona_sava@yahoo.fr

** Dept. of Food Industry and Tourism, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: carmen_badarau@yahoo.com

** Dept. of Food Industry and Tourism, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail:angela_marculescu@yahoo.com

Table 1

Values of species densities identified and the frequency variation coefficients for the analysed areas

Experimental couple	Variant	Total number of identified species	Number of individuals of each layer to ha		Coefficient of frequency variation s% f	
			herbaceous	shrubs	herbaceous	shrubs
Young pure beech						
C1	77A m	35	135500	2900	85,400	42,200
	120 p	46	336500	3450	67,250	57,044
C2	29A m	35	112250	1375	64,506	51,320
	33D p	48	211000	2875	48,340	35,996
C3	22C m	21	120000	1535	27,567	27,700
	15F p	28	138250	1264	90,444	74,300
C4	65A m	33	95231	1125	84,450	59,254
	126E p	44	139200	4172	76,305	57,230
C5	102Am	26	86250	1823	73,900	49,300
	102Dp	38	137500	2315	59,600	45,655
C6	43Fm	24	151250	2110	40,847	34,042
	43Gp	36	192000	3570	82,005	51,172
Old pure beech						
C7	23A m	19	136500	2450	51,280	24,655
	1A p	29	311000	5250	83,200	65,900
C8	19B m	24	191000	3100	67,784	23,370
	27A p	33	311000	5250	91,270	55,370
C9	21A m	30	181000	2900	98,200	42,271
	21L p	37	271270	3350	69,466	40,203
C10	21J m	24	183270	-	71,501	-
	7F p	34	251250	-	88,918	-
C11	22A m	28	135500	2900	88,564	34,282
	49A p	36	336500	3450	82,443	37,140
C12	m	33	112250	1375	78,620	50,520
	p	40	390000	2275	73,625	34,390
Young beech trees mixed with resin						
C13	22D m	28	181000	1467	61,400	43,621
	23B p	39	339500	2752	78,120	50,506
C14	33F m	29	195321	2275	51,551	48,288
	38C p	50	271250	2850	81,617	30,403
C15	131B m	48	149250	1462	89,582	48,900
	126B p	56	154260	4875	98,151	47,023
C16	19 m	22	96500	2162	38,500	24,180
	28A p	10	110231	875	33,151	62,700
C17	109A m	38	206000	2485	62,062	45,755
	15D p	51	331200	1157	70,156	46,750
C18	27A m	43	68000	1700	60,200	50,211
	33A p	59	167500	1575	92,400	31,300
Old beech trees mixed with resin						
C19	37Bm	40	321000	2370	49,125	39,217
	91Dp	48	339250	3560	75,320	52,420
C20	26 m	26	282500	5500	36,312	25,312
	24B p	68	321000	7250	93,825	49,300
C21	12C m	36	381000	3100	62,064	46,450
	2B p	41	559500	4125	51,051	57,321
C22	29A m	33	135500	2900	62,900	37,200
	146 p	55	336250	3400	89,120	59,080
C23	44Am	57	280200	1325	95,300	52,100
	45Cp	61	459250	1475	82,581	43,590
C24	43Am	48	237400	3200	68,567	40,324
	42Ap	57	239250	1365	80,637	53,619

A. Correlation between relative frequency s%f and the herbaceous and shrub layers, for pure beech, young witness stand

B. Correlation between relative frequency s%f and the herbaceous and shrub layers for pure beech, young with works stand

C. Correlation between relative frequency s%f and the herbaceous and shrub layers for older pure beech, witness stand

D. Correlation between relative frequency s%f and the herbaceous and shrub layers, for older pure beech, with works stand

E. Correlation between relative frequency s%f and the herbaceous and shrub layers, for beech mixed with pine, young witness stand

F. Correlation between relative frequency s%f and the herbaceous and shrub layers, for beech mixed with pine, young, with works stand

G. Correlation between relative frequency s%f and the herbaceous and shrub layers, for older beech mixed with pine, witness stand

H. Correlation between relative frequency s%f and the herbaceous and shrub layers, for older beech mixed with pine, with works stand

Fig.1. The correlation of frequency s%f with the number of species of herbaceous layers and shrubs for all types of trees, pure and mixed variants witness and with cuts

number of shrubs. Also, we found that the variants covered with cuts, the number of species is higher compared to control variants. If the couple C10, 21 J witness stand, 7F with works stand, the shrub species number is very small, less than two, which is why the coefficient of variation of relative frequency can not be calculated, and is zero. In the control variants, the correlation coefficient R is larger for herbaceous than for the shrub layer. Values are close and highly significant in beech stands mixed with resin (0.751, 0.699, for old stands, and 0.71, 0.615, for young stands). A correlation coefficient values are lower for pure stands and significant (0.6993, 0.443, for old stands, and 0.700, 0.566, for younger stands). In the stands with works, herbaceous and shrub variants, the correlation is significant in that the correlation coefficient R values are lower, the lowest values being 0.358, 0.196 respectively for pure stands, old. The reason for the overlap decreases in this case is given by cutting the trees that intervention by specific technical operations herbaceous and shrub layers affect the purpose of destruction, and therefore the distribution of individuals on the surface. To mention that, in the gradual cuts, by affecting larger or smaller areas, in the same place, the distribution of species is unevenly affected.

5. Conclusions

Both, the table 1, and the figures A,B,C,D,E,F,G, and H, we can make the following conclusions:

- the species diversity is greater in the stand with works, compared to the witness stand;
- the relative frequency values decrease from the herbaceous layer to the tree layer;
- regarding the two types of trees (pure beech and beech mixed with resin), higher values we meet in mixed beech with resin, which due to the presence of several species, that's ensure a greater stability in time.

References

1. Borza AL., și Boșcaiu N.: *Introducere în studiul covorului vegetal*, Editura Academiei Republicii Populare Române, 1965;
2. Ciucă, M., și Beldie, AL.: *Flora munților Ciucaș*, Editura Academiei R.S.R, București, 1989;
3. Ciucă, M. : *Flora și vegetația pajiștilor din munții Ciucaș*, Editura Academiei R.S.R, București, 1984;
4. Parascan, D., și Danciu, M.: *Botanică forestieră*, Editura „Pentru Viață”, Brașov, p. 324, 2002;
5. Târziu, D. 2003: *Ecologie generală și forestieră*, „Vasile Goldiș”, University Press, Arad;
6. Vlonga, Șt.: *Cercetări ecologice în făgete montane și amestecuri de rășinoase cu fag din Masivul Ciucaș, în care se aplică tratamentele codru regulat*, Teză de doctorat, Brașov; 1998

CHARACTERISTICS OF VERTICAL STRUCTURE IN PURE AND MIXED BEECH WITH RESINS, FROM CIUCAȘ MASSIF

A. SAVA* C. BADARAU** A. MARCULESCU**

Abstract: *In the models based on the relationship between diversity and disturbance, the specific forest ecosystems is manifested through a high sensitivity of trees to falling down in the wind, resulting changes in specific composition, especially at late stages of succession. In this sense, the frequency of disturbance is often caused by some cyclical biological processes such as the growth period required by a tree, so as to create a through hole in canopy collapse. The timing of ecosystem disturbances with certain cycles is represented by increasing the negative effects of falling snow, if they occur in autumn, when trees are still in leaves, causing selective mortality of species and therefore unsuitable, changes in the composition. In terms of temporal variation in diversity, its changes, correlated with successional changes, may occur in the same forms of life or a series of grassy type plants, shrubs and trees. In this context, there was an increase of grassland diversity, as long as they are dominated by herbaceous species. If their progress towards typical forests, the diversity decrease. If the species richness and equitability decrease, as the successional maturation, this are signals in some oakforests of Costa Rica (Kapelle, M., 1995). In the current conditions of human intervention, high levels of diversity are found in woods in excess of mesophilic old age 50-100 years exploitability (Angelstam, P., 1998.*

Keywords: *diversity, Shannon-Wiener index, real basic area, vertical structure.*

1. Introduction

In the case of trees, specific diversity increases from boreal forests to the equatorial (Lugo, AE, 1988). In Europe, Mediterranean forests are considered as having high levels of species diversity. Also, in the tropical forest tree, the species richness increases. Globally, the highest levels of diversity are found in wet tropical forests, which concentrates more than half the species on Earth (Wilson, EO, 1988). In Romania, the biodiversity of natural ecosystems is one of the highest in Europe, our forests are identified over 60 native forest species, 70 shrub species, 500 herbaceous species, about 300 species of forest (Giurgiu, V. 1995).

The research on vertical stand structure study, were conducted in pure beech and mixed beech with coniferous (pine, spruce, larch), located in the Ciucas massif. We had to pass four production units (UP), in the massif, namely Dălghiu (UP I) Zizinului Valley (UP

linearly with the amount of precipitation (Gentry, AH, 1998). These studies show a tripling of the number of species in the xeric forests to the humid forests.

Regarding the vertical structure diversity of trees, in this study, it was expressed through a series of indicators of biodiversity, such as the Shannon-Wiener index, Pielou index of equity, maximum diversity and actual base area.

2. Place of research

II), Valley Village (UP III) and Springs lip (UP IV).

3. Research method

* Dept. of Food Industry and Tourism, Transilvania University of Brașov, Romania, e-mail: aliona_sava@yahoo.fr

** Dept. of Food Industry and Tourism, Transilvania University of Brașov, Romania, e-mail: carmen_badarau@yahoo.com

** Dept. of Food Industry and Tourism, Transilvania University of Brașov, Romania, e-mail:angela_marculescu@yahoo.com

In the beech forests, both the pure beech and mixed beech with resins, were analyzed young (aged 40 years and 70years) and older stands (aged 95 years and 150 years). Were made 24 experimental couples (marked "C"), each couple comprising two experimental

$$H' = -\sum_{i=1}^S p_i \ln p_i, \quad p_i = n_i / N$$

S – represents the number of diameter classes;

The relations for the maximum diversity (H_{max}) and for the diameter classes equity (E):

$$H_{max} = \ln S, \quad E = H' / \ln S$$

S –the number of diameter classes;

Echitatea este maximă posibilă în cazul în care toate clasele de diametre ar fi reprezentate prin același număr de arbori.

3.The number of trees – as an index of density (it was considered the number of trees identified in the test market - 500m²).

4. Results and discussions

Shannon- Wiener index values for classes of heights (H'h), coefficient of variation of height (s% h), and actual base area (Gr), are summarized in Chart no. 1. Data represent all

variants: a control variant (noted "m"), and variants with works (such progressive cuts), and covered with paper version (marked "p"). The used index for the calculation of vertical structure of trees:

p_i – the proportion representation of each diameter classes;

n_i – the number of trees of i classes;

N – the number of all trees.

H' – Shannon –Wiener index;

2.The basic area (G_r) – as an index of density;

variants analyzed, grouped by trees type. Also, are presented maximum diversity values (H_{max}), and the equity classes of diameters (E).

Table 1

Shannon-Wiener index values of height classes (H'h), maximum diversity (H_{max}), height classes of equity (E), and actual base area (Gr) in studied stands

Experimental couple	Variants	Shannon-Wiener (H'h) index	Maximum diversity (Hmax)	Height classes of equity (E)	Actual base area (Gr, m ²)	Numbers of trees
Young pure beech						
C1	77A m	2,1478	2,3026	0,9327	2.8022	63
	120 p	1,1441	1,3972	0,8189	2,1648	48
C2	29A m	1,9707	2,1026	0,9372	2,1092	58
	33D p	1,8522	2,0794	0,8907	1,9653	33
C3	22C m	2,2478	2,4549	0,9156	3,2238	52
	15F p	2,0156	2,2972	0,8774	2,6593	33
C4	65A m	2,9616	2,9979	0,9879	3,1377	58
	126E p	1,8413	1,8918	0,9733	2,8735	39
C5	102A m	1,9299	1,9794	0,9749	1,6772	43
	102D p	1,9047	1,9794	0,9623	1,7982	30
C6	43F m	1,9479	2,1026	0,9264	2,5739	55
	43G p	1,8603	2,0794	0,8946	2,3272	37

Old pure beech						
C7	23A m	2,0441	2,0794	0,9830	2,5915	14
	1A p	1,9952	2,0794	0,9595	3,2247	7
C8	19B m	1,9339	2,0972	0,9221	2,8621	19
	27A p	1,9081	2,0794	0,9176	1,6416	8
C9	21A m	2,3513	2,6391	0,8909	3,6372	27
	21L p	2,0164	2,3026	0,8757	2,4519	17
C10	21J m	2,2891	2,4391	0,9385	4,1756	36
	7F p	1,6838	2,0794	0,8097	2,2392	21
C11	22A m	1,9646	2,0694	0,9494	4,0249	27
	49A p	1,8431	1,9459	0,9471	1,9134	12
C12	44B m	2,0611	2,2459	0,9177	2,5415	29
	43G p	1,9636	2,1253	0,9039	2,3759	16
Young mixed beech with resins						
C13	22D m	1,9915	2,1026	0,9472	2,9779	61
	23B p	1,9338	2,1026	0,9197	2,2343	28
C14	33F m	2,0838	2,2794	0,9142	2,9952	68
	38C p	1,9792	2,2459	0,8813	2,5384	44
C15	131B m	1,5350	1,6325	0,9403	3,2049	64
	126B p	1,2452	1,4972	0,8317	2,8371	47
C16	19 m	2,5674	2,7794	0,9237	3,7188	51
	28A p	1,9851	2,2459	0,8838	2,0489	35
C17	109A m	2,9701	2,9926	0,9925	3,8716	51
	15D p	1,8892	1,9456	0,9710	3,2223	36
C18	27A m	2,8867	2,9926	0,9646	3,3163	50
	33A p	1,7298	2,0972	0,8248	2,3348	33
Old mixed beech with resins						
C19	37Bm	2,1066	2,1972	0,9587	3,1215	15
	91Dp	1,4751	1,6094	0,9165	3,2468	13
C20	26 m	2,2877	2,3979	0,9540	2,9944	15
	24B p	1,7329	1,7918	0,9671	2,3338	12
C21	12C m	2,2941	2,3980	0,9567	3,3755	24
	2B p	1,8090	1,9459	0,9296	2,1244	18
C22	29A m	2,4067	2,5649	0,9383	3,0993	31
	146 p	1,8226	1,9459	0,9366	2,2515	18
C23	44Am	2,1722	2,3979	0,9059	4,0208	14
	45Cp	2,0228	2,3394	0,8647	2,0856	9
C24	43Am	2,3172	2,5045	0,9252	2,4727	14
	42Ap	1,5624	1,8822	0,8301	1,6352	10

To capture the vertical structure variability, was plotted graphycs with the Shannon - Wiener classes of heights (H'h). From table. 1, we can see that with fewer trees in the stands covered with works, (comparing witness variants with works variants), falls the vertical structure diversity, expressed by Shannon-Wiener index, which is valid for all models covered by works, to the witness, in which the index has higher values.

Also, in the old trees and covered with works, the index values are lower from the young stands and with works, and this is explained by the fact that in the old trees were made progressive cuts: the implementation in the light cuts, connection or seed cuts, leading to an extraction of a greater number of trees, from young stands and covered with rarerly cuts, where the number of trees removed is less, the trees being removed uniformly. In the witness stands, the harvesting of trees is much lower ,

and the diversity of vertical structure changes little, depending on the reduction of trees in the stand, but also their height. In the graphics below (Fig. A,B,C,D,E,F,G,H), we studied the

change in vertical structure, based on the relative frequency of trees on height classes with changing the number of trees.

A. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the number of trees, in the young, pure, witness beech

B. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the number of trees, in the young, pure, with works beech

C. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the number of trees, in the old, pure, witness beech

D. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the number of trees, in the old, pure, with works beech

E. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the number of trees, in the young, witness, mixed beech with resins

F. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the number of trees, in the young, with works, mixed beech with resins

G. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the number of trees, in the old, witness, mixed beech with resins

H. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the number of trees, in the old, with works, mixed beech with resins

Fig. 1 The Shannon-Wiener index variation reporting to the number of trees, in the pure beech and mixed beech with resins, with both variants, witness and covered with works

Basically, the vertical structure diversity decrease with the decreasing number of trees in the stands with works, and that can be explained by reducing the variability of height classes. To represent Shannon-Wiener index in

relation to the base area, as shown in the graphics below, have been used logarithmic functions, aiming at, the change of the vertical structure based on its variation.

A. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the basic area, in the young, pure, witness beech

B. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the basic area, in the young, pure, with works beech

C. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the basic area, in the old, pure, witness beech

D. The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the basic area, in the old, pure, with works beech

E.The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the basic area, in the young, witness,mixed beech with resins

F.The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the basic area, in the young, with works,mixed beech with resins

G.The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the basic area, in the old, witness,mixed beech with resins

H.The Shannon-Wiener index variation, reporting to the basic area, in the old, with works,mixed beech with resins

Fig. 2 Shannon-Wiener index variation reporting to the basic area in the pure beech stands and mixed beech with resins stand, with both variants, witness and with works, individually taken

Also, it can see, the slight tendency to increase Shannon-Wiener index, to the base area, for the witness variants, and slight downward trend of this indicator for the variants covered with works. We may conclude that the vertical structure diversity decreases with increasing intensity of intervention in the stands, and the correlation coefficient is quite significant.

By applying progressive cutts treatment (connection, implementing light, sowing), all trees are harvested from an specifics area,

Analyzing the two types of forests, pure beech and mixed beech with resins, in terms of vertical structure, represented by Shannon

which reduces the variability of diameter classes, and heights classes, thus affecting the value of Shannon-Wiener index as a measure of structural diversity. So in the work stands completed with rarerly type cuts, the value of this index is lower in the witness variants, but the values are somewhat higher than those of the progressive cuts, because the trees are uniformly harvested from the stand and they are in a less number .

5. Conclusions

Wiener index, we can make the following conclusions:

-diversity of vertical structure, represented by the Shannon-Wiener index, increases with the number of trees (witness variant), and decreases with

reducing their number, which is determined by anthropic influence that exists in a lesser or greater extent.

- we may say that the vertical structure diversity index is higher in young beech stands mixed with resins, followed by pure beech; this is explained by the fact that the beech mixed with resins, present a greater variety of tree species with different heights, and thus influence the vertical structure variability.

- in the old stands, both pure and mixed with resins, diversity is lower, Shannon-Wiener index values are quite similar (only slightly higher for pure stands old), and the number of trees is reduced.

References

1. Angelstam, P.: *Maintaining and restoring biodiversity in European boreal Forests by developing natural disturbance regimes*, Journal of Vegetation Science 9, IAVS, Opulus Press, Uppsala, 1998;
2. Biriş, I.-A.: *Cercetări privind diversitatea producătorilor din ecosistemele de făgete de pe clina sudică a Carpaților Meridionali, între Valea Oltului și Valea Prahovei și influența măsurilor de gospodărire asupra acestora*, Teză de doctorat, Brașov, 2001;
3. Gentry, A.-H.: *Changes in Plant Community Diversity and Floristic Composition On Environmental and Geographical Gradients*, Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden, no. 75, 1998;
4. Giurgiu, V.: *Protejarea și dezvoltarea durabilă a pădurilor României*, Ed. Arta Grafică, București, 1995;
5. Kappelle, M., și Kenis, P.-A.: *Changes in diversity along a successional gradient In a Costa Rican upper mountain Quercus forest*, Biodiversity and Conservation, p. 10-34., 1995;
6. Lugo, A.-E.: *Estimating reductions in the diversity of tropical forests species*, Biodiversity, National Academy Press, Washington, p. 58-70, 1988;
7. Vlona, ȘT.: *Cercetări ecologice în făgete montane și amestecuri de rășinoase cu fag din Masivul Ciucaș, în care se aplică tratamentul de codru regulat*, Teză de doctorat, Brașov, 1998;
8. Wilson, E.-O.: *The diversity of life*. P. 68-81. In: de Blij, H.Y. (ed.), „Earth 88: Changing Geographic Perspectives”. National Geographic Society, Washington, DC, p. 392, 1988.

REUSE SCRAP WOOD TO PRODUCE ACTIVATED CARBON WITH THE REDUCING THE DESTRUCTIVE EFFECTS OVER FOREST ROADS

C. SLINCU P. VICA

Abstract: *Through logical thinking must accept the important role of judicious management of forest roads in forest. Well-managed forest roads have an important role in the development of human activities in forest areas and also in protecting forest ecosystems. Where forest roads are well built, according to ecological principles, there was made a major step in developing a harmonious life*

Key words: *Scrap wood, flood, charcoal;*

1. Beneficial Role of Forest Roads in Water Quality and Generally the Environment under Normal Exploitation of Forest Resources

Management under normal operation and nature of forest resources for production, forest roads have an important role in the exploitation of water quality and the environment in general. The design and construction of the forest roads made properly with the principles of good practice guidelines in the field lead to protection of ecosystems in the area, avoiding the damage caused by the logging of the forestry tractors.

Well-designed forest roads and ropeways combined with forest (usually gravity) reduce negative impacts on ecosystems at least 70%.

2. Complex Recovery of Wood Quantities. The Cleaning of the Scrap Wood and Its Valorification

After heavy rains there is'nt a forest road that does not have to suffer through clogged culverts (usually tubular undersized often because of cost) and plugging ditches materials driven by rainwater. The greatest destructive effect they have wood materials, generally of small diameter and great length (cracked thin wood carving and bulk).

Fig. 1 – *Trifle material in wood exploitation site*

Collecting the wood can be made by small teams specialized in collecting scrap wood along the streams that are crossed by forest roads. These teams must be independent mobile units, for example small family-type organization associations (FA), with minimal equipment (a small tractor, gender, U650" trailer and winch, 1-2 sawing machines - small and medium power, some ciochinare, if funds started in place are insufficient tractor trailer can initiate installation of a horse cart, not without interest to the mobile units equipped with some plastic tubing cut in long, placed end to the selected areas with high inclination, to wood waste collection permit gravity).

Fig. 2 – Pieces of wood after the floods

What will be done with this material, different sizes and different species?

This material will be stored in large areas along the road, at least 10 mst of deposit, and is next phase of transformation into **charcoal** in metal mobile flasks.

3. The Charcoal

The efficiency of the forestry and wood turning involves not only forest accessibility and cleaning operating activities, but also diversifying the ways in which wood can be added in simple, commercial value. The principle is simple: the use will be better, at lower production costs and higher selling prices, all kinds of wood, including waste, the waste will increase the value of standing timber, which allows transfer of costs by operating large works that can be executed carefully. This economic connection is very important because it can bring to light a series of little or no resources currently used, such as for example charcoal, which can be produced in the primary platform, using a technology that meets current environmental standards:

- phase exothermic decomposition of wood (wood inflammation after), when there are vapors, drying wood;
- Phase Oxidation intensive, between 150 ° C and 250 ° C, the wood decay in chemical elements (C, H, O, N). Now occurring chemicals such as acetic acid, raw acid, propyl and amyl alcohol, methyl alcohol ;
- Phase Oxidation viscous substances, between 250 ° C and 350 ° C, it achieves the flammable hydrocarbons and high viscosity substances (coal). The final phase, 350 ° C - 400 ° C, obtaining charcoal (80% carbon).

4. Rediscovering activated carbon

Using charcoal industry is relatively new, mainly in metallurgy and chemistry: first charcoal market has developed in Europe early last century. Activated carbon is charcoal that after appropriate treatment has improved the absorption properties. Activated carbon is obtained in simple installation by treatment with steam at temperatures of 500-800 °C. By enabling coal increases its absorption capacity of over one million times.

This propertz of absorption will create in future a role in activated carbon:

- ater purification
- pollution-control
- purification of gas
- regeneration of solvents
- fractional distillation
- purification of alcohol
- pharmaceutical industry
- food industry
- obtained catalysts
- manufacture of cigarettes (nicotine filter)
- purification of sugar

In conclusion the role of charcoal in the modern life, it will become increasingly difficult to avoid.

Fig. 3 – The charcoal obtaining instalation (scheme)

References

1. Andreescu, V.: Exploiting Forests - Didactic and Pedagogic Publishing House, Bucharest 1967.

2. Bereziuc, R.; Alexandru, V.; Ciobanu, V.; Ignea, Gh.; Abrudan, I.; Derczeni, R; (Consultants: F. Trifoi, N. Oprisa, P. Vica, I. Dobre, A. Pavel, I. Cazan, B. Popa) – Guideline for Designing, Building and Maintenance of Forest Roads, The

- “Transilvania” University Publishing House, Brasov 2006.
3. Bereziuc, R., Oprita, V., 1974: Design and construction of forest roads, Ceres Publishing House, Bucharest.
 4. Constantinescu, Gh.; Dănăilă, Gh.; Smadu, G. – Sorting and Primary Wood Industrialization Centres, Ceres Publishing House, București, 1981.
 5. Stinghe, VN, Sburlan, DA: Forestry Agenda, Agro Publishing House, Bucuresti 1968
 6. Ministry of Forest Economy and Building Materials – The Wood Exploitation Central - Frame of Technological Schemes (intern use), București 1977.
 7. Ministry of Wood Industrialization and Building Materials - The Wood Exploitation Central - București –Unified Labour Norms and Normatives in Forest Exploitation, 1989.

QUICK METHOD FOR THE WOOD EXPLOITATION SITES DESIGNING, AND TECHNOLOGY AND TRANSPORT ON FOREST ROADS

C. SLINCU* P. VICA**

Abstract: *One of the most important phases, in the long circuit of the wood capitalization, represents the designing and organization of the wood exploitation sites. This stage includes a great volume of knowledge, data and work, all these on the support named experience in the field. The present study is meant to contribute in finding the solution to this laborious phase by joining the works with new methods with the revaluation of the existent data.*

Key words: *design, wood exploitation, environmental funds.*

1. About the efficiency and the ecological technologies and transport on forest roads

Efficient exploitation of forests shouldn't be seen narrow, strictly in terms of profit. Paradigm evaluated only in terms of economic efficiency of the operating company recently changed, requiring the adoption of additional criteria that reflects the objective of environmental conservation. But as the environmental conservation requires additional measures to organize the operation site, another criterion that was considered was and what we generically called "feasibility" technological solution, understood as "the probability of adoption, combined with duction likely to work out the operation".

2. Generalities regarding the designing and organization wood exploitation sites

The wood exploitation technological process is very complex, starting with the operations and related phases succession, where the wood is displaced and transformed.

These operations have well defined successions and well defined places, and most probable (for our country) the structure of the technological process is:

- partial harvesting process;
- partial collection process;
- works in primary platform;
- technological transport;

The method of studying on level curves maps, with simple programmes accessory, it is considered

- works in sorting and wood transforming units or in final deposits.

The organization of a wood exploitation site is achieved through projecting (designing) and it refers to a series of methods and actions aimed at establishing the technological solutions of the wood exploitation, the technical and material preparation and the programming-management of the works related to the wood exploitation site.

The suitable works for these methods are structured in: preparing works, final office works and field works.

3. Preliminary actions in the designing and organizing of the wood exploitation sites through proposed methods the material preparation (map-drawing, wood structure, access, i.e.)

3.1. Studying on the Level Curves Maps (accessory with simple programmes like Nego, Mapper) of the Geographic Elements with Orography and Accessibility Information

These level curves maps must be obtained from the forest administrator (who owns them since the forest management). These maps (after they are updated regarding the parcelling and modified in a decade) they should be scanned and stored on magnetic support. At the demand (after payment), these maps can be committed to all the interested persons through the licensed specialists.

to be the ideal solution in this moment, when the national programme for forest cadastre (in modern

*Paying Agency for Rural Development and Fisheries, e-mail: cristian.slincu@gmail.com

**National Forest Administration – ROMSILVA, e-mail: petrisor.vica@gmail.com

GIS data) is being delayed.

This method represents an intermediate way between the method of study on draft maps (usually squared) and the method of study on digital maps.

3.2. Field Actual Studying of the Elements Regarding Orography, Accessibility, Coppice Structure, etc.

The technological process establishment, including collecting distances, phases and operations percentage, placement of primary platform(s), possible assortments of wood, organization elements.

Fig.1 Operational variants based on expanding forest road network, under the protection of forest ecosystems

3.3. Study about the Necessary Auxiliary Works

These are:

- Necessary works related to production process (tractor roads, assembly-disassembly funicular

- lines, harness ways, skidding lines, primary platform, moist zones cross over works, etc.);
- Works related to labour security (protection, against the fire);
- Organization-house holding works (for accommodation in optimum conditions, places for animals rest and food, etc.)
- Ecological Works

The next possible negative effects on the environment must be estimated such as: affected forest trees, small plants (from seed), the soil, waters, etc. and anticipated the necessary works for diminishing these effects too.

These works (of a great proportions) must be well dimensioned and, logically it is, to be supported by „environmental funds”, especially coming from the wood exploitation sector.

3.4. The estimative calculation of costs in the wood exploitation process development

In this stage all the phases of the production process, for each section will be taken in the analysis, with a great attention on the **costs of ecological works.**

For a close estimation of the production process (with all its annexes) there are need specialists with a good orientation over forest field and a good experience in this domain.

4. The wood exploitation technological process analysis

4.1. The analysis on different variants of the wood exploitation technological process

The criteria had in view, at the variants exploitation analysis of the site, the following:

- The conditions imposed by the terrain configuration;
- The endowment (with work equipment, machines) existing in the country and in the zone; this can impart a certain trend in the exploitation process at macro level;
- The endowment possibility of the economic unit, on the chapters:

- Equipment endowment possibility imposed by the terrain configuration, with the great productivities, for trade imposed assortments;
 - Institutional credit-acquisition equipment and machine frame;
 - Adequate labour from specific forest zones, with connected qualifications and specializations;
- The economic unit capacity of knowledge and integration in the actual economic-trade frame;
 - The organic structure (state, banking, diverse NGOs, central and local authorities) capacity of the understanding forest exploitation phenomenon.

4.2. The choice of the most advantageous variant

The most advantageous variant (from different points of view, all with convergence to the economy) analyses aspects such as:

- Economic aspects;
- Ecological aspects;
- Social aspects;
- The global context of the branch and sector.

4.3. The economic efficiency resulted in the study of the variants

In the actual context when we are facing a great power crisis (in intensity and time), the wood (inclusively the neglected assortments) will have a more accentuated role. Therefore the concept of “strengthened forest development on continuity principle” is even more imposed than the “biodiversity conservation” concept.

The economic efficiency of the analysed variants results from the comparison of the costs with the estimated revenues evolution.

Hence it is opened another chapter for the process efficiency or for the increasing of the existent efficiency.

This new and incited action of efficiency, based on the provided elements of the **specialist-consultant in designing and organization in wood exploitation sites** is taken over by the other specialists (economic-commercial and of other nature) through the actual profound studies taking

into analysis another technological processes, in the existent context.

5. Conclusions regarding the organization and development of the forest exploitation process

This study, in the long way of the forest exploitation, wants to explain the important role of the **consultant in designing and organizing forest exploitationsites**. (Thisspecialization must be reinserted in the field and developed in the new terms too).

How must be viewed this consultant and how is viewed his new job?

- To be included in a corpse in the consultants system from forest domain;
- To be authorized by o diverse commission accepted at national level;
- To have work notions (without need to go to the extreme) with the computer and to have large experience in the terrain work.

What prerogatives are due to the consultant in designing and organization of the forest exploitation sites?

- The gathering data from authorized administrator of the forest and at local level too;
- The analysis at the office and in the terrain of all aspects regarding the forest exploitation site;
- The determining of exploitation optimal frame (technologies, economical-social context);
- The harmonious link with all involved and adjacent organisms of the exploitation process;
- The documentation (final product) drawing up and its inclusion in the long process of the forest valuation.

References

1. Bereziuc, R.; Alexandru, V.; Ciobanu, V.; Ignea, Gh.; Abrudan, I.; Derczeni, R; (Consultants: F. Trifoi, N. Oprisa, P. Vica, I. Dobre, A. Pavel, I. Cazan, B. Popa) – *Guideline for Designing, Building and Maintenance of Forest Roads*, The “Transilvania” University Publishing House, Brasov 2006.
2. Constantinescu, Gh.; Dănăilă, Gh.; Smadu, G. – *Sorting and Primary Wood Industrialization Centres*, Ceres Publishing House, București, 1981.
3. Oprea, I., Borz, S. A., *The Wood Exploitation Site Organization*, The Transilvania University Publishing House, Braşov, 2007.
4. Oprea, I., Sbera, I., *The Technology of Wood Exploitation*, TRIDONA Publishing House, 2004.
5. Ministry of Forest Economy and Building Materials – *The Wood Exploitation Central - Frame of Technological Schemes (intern use)*, Bucureşti 1977.
6. Ministry of Wood Industrialization and Building Materials - *The Wood Exploitation Central - Bucureşti –Unified Labour Norms and Normatives in Forest Exploitation*, 1989.

COMPARATIVE TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TWO PRIMITIVE WHEATS OF TYPE TRITICUM TURGIDUM L. SUBSP. TURANICUM " KAMUT " AND " EGYPTIAN WHEAT "

TZVETANA GOGOVA

Abstract: A comparative technological characteristics are obtained based on the basic characteristics of grain, flour and bread, resulting from two primitive wheat of type *Triticum's turgidum L.subsp. Turanicum* - " Egyptian Wheat " and "Kamut". The main goal of this study was to evaluate the possibilities for application of the "Egyptian Wheat" in the bakery industry in Bulgaria. The grain of " Egyptian Wheat " contains 4,31 % wet gluten more than the grain of wheat " Kamut ". The obtained results regarding the milling and physico-chemical characteristics were found to be identical. The yield of wet gluten in the flour of " Egyptian Wheat " is 5 % more than that of "Kamut". In addition, the gas-forming ability of " Egyptian Wheat " flour is higher than that of "Kamut". The organoleptic characteristics of bread produced by " Egyptian Wheat " were found to be very similar to those of "Kamut".

Keywords: technological characteristics, grain, flour, bread, "Kamut", " Egyptian Wheat ", bread-making

1. Introduction

"Kamut" is an alternative cereal of our traditional wheat for people suffering of intolerance towards the wheat products. In a published study by the International association of food allergies (FIAA), is concluded that 70 % of the tested people suffering from an allergy with wheat gluten did not show such a indications to the wheat "Kamut"[10].

"Kamut", the wheat of the Egyptian pyramids, is not modified, either by crossing or genetics. It has not been a subject to the modern selection. It is only cultivated in accordance with the requirements of bio-farming (an absence of pesticides, fertilizer and chemical additives) [10].

In 2004 for a first time in Bulgaria has begun an importation and researching on a cereal called "Kamut" [11]. Based on this import, in 2006 the wheat was cultivated in our country. The newborn wheat is called "Egyptian Wheat" The bibliographic survey revealed that there is no published data for the application of the "Egyptian wheat" in the food industry. In the literature, there are only few data on the chemical composition of this type of wheat but there is no data for its technological properties [11]. For a first time in Bulgaria a comparative characteristic of the basic technological properties of both "Egyptian Wheat" and "Kamut" is performed.

According to Quinn and Pfannhauser [12, 13] these types of wheat have 30- 40 % higher

protein content compared to the other types of durum wheat and they are also richer in olygo elements such as the manganese and the selenium. The protein content of a similar types of durum wheat varies from 15 to 18 %, lipids from 0,5 to 3,5 %, carbohydrates from 70 to 90 % and food fibers from 1,0 to 2,0 %, based on humidity of grain in the range 9,8 - 12 %. The protein content and total lipids of *Triticum turgidum ssp. Turanicum* is significantly higher than those of the other varieties of durum wheat - 40 % and 37 % respectively.

Considering the cited data above, it could be concluded that a comparison between the basic characteristics of both wheat and their by-products is needed in order to determine if the one cultivated in Bulgaria ("Egyptian Wheat"), can be applicable to the baking industry.

2. Purpose

The main purpose of this study is to compare the technological characteristics of two types of wheat that belong to *Triticum turgidum ssp. Turanicum* ("Egyptian wheat" - cultivated in Bulgaria from grains of "Kamut" and "Kamut") and assessment of the "Egyptian Wheat" applicability for bread-making.

3. Materials and methods

The grains of “Egyptian Wheat” used for the study were cultivated at the Institute of the phylogenetic resources – “K. Malakov”, Sadovo. The Grain of “Kamut” is an organic product produced by Neufarm International, Zarrentin and bought from Germany. The grain was subjected to a preliminary cleaning and conditioning. The total milling yield of flour was 70 %.

The grain characteristics measured were: humidity [4], hectoliter weight [5], mass of 1000 grains [6], vitreousness [3], ash content [2], total protein content [1], the yield of wet gluten [7] and softening of the wet gluten [15]. The flour is qualified by: the humidity [4], quantity and quality of wet gluten [7], α - amylase activity (falling number test) [9] and the strength of the flour which was determined by trial baking test [8], the titratable acidity, the strength of the flour by penetration evaluated by Index K_{60} [15], gas forming ability [15]. The organoleptic analysis of the final product was conducted according to the following characteristics: crumb porosity, taste, aftertaste, flavor, the color of the lower and upper crust layers, the color of the crumb and the thickness of the upper and lower crust layers. The loaves were evaluated by: mass, volume and shape retaining ability [15].

4. Results and discussion

The basic milling and physico-chemical characteristics of the grains of “Egyptian Wheat” and “Kamut” were studied and compared.

Based on the obtained data presented on Figure 1 one can see that the hectoliter weight is similar for both wheat. The mass of 1000 grains of the “Egyptian wheat” is slightly lower (3.4g) than that of “Kamut”. The same tendency is observed for the vitreousness, the ash content and the softening of wet gluten. The protein content of both wheat is equal (19 %), however it is a bit higher compared to the protein content of the other types durum wheat which typically varies from 12 to 14 % [14]. The quantity of wet gluten of ' Egyptian Wheat ' is 33,4 % and it is 4,31 % higher than that of “Kamut” (29,09 %).

A comparison of the basic characteristics of flours produced from the tested wheat is done. The results are presented on Figure 2.

Analysis of the results presented on Figure 2, shows that all tested characteristics of the flours were at the limits typical for the durum wheat.

The yield of wet gluten of flour of “Egyptian Wheat” was 5 % higher than that of “Kamut”. The yield of wet gluten for both flours was similar. The alpha – amylase activity for both flours is low and that of the “Egyptian Wheat” was slightly lower (12s) compared to the alpha-amylase activity of the “Kamut”.

The gas forming ability of the two flours is compared and the results are presented on Figure 3.

The observed tendency for the gas forming ability of “Egyptian Wheat” is fundamentally different from that of “Kamut”. It is strongly increased during the first 30 minutes of the analysis reaching 12,0 cm³ or 8,7 cm³ more than that of “Kamut”. Then the gas forming ability decreased to the 60th minute and remained constant until the 120th minute. The lowest gas forming ability was observed at the 150th minute. The gas forming ability of the flour of “Kamut” increased regularly to the 60th minute of the experiment reaching 5,2 cm³ and then remained stable. The lowest level (4,8 cm³) was observed at the 150th minute.

For each time interval of the analysis the gas forming ability of flour of “Egyptian Wheat” was higher than that of “Kamut”. The biggest difference was observed in the first 30 minutes, and the smallest at the 150th minute. The highest gas forming ability of the flour of “Egyptian Wheat” was observed during the first 60 minutes of the analysis. For the flour of “Kamut” the highest gas forming ability corresponded between 60 and 120 minutes of the analysis. A trial baking tests were conducted for the two flours and the organoleptic characteristics of the loaves were determined.

The organoleptic characteristics of baked breads made of “Egyptian wheat” and “Kamut” were very similar: a typical exterior of wheat bread with a good forming abilities and irregular crust coloration with a dark spots without cracks; the color of the crumb is dark yellow; gas pores are small and uniformly distributed; a taste and smell non-typical for a wheat bread with nuances of butter and an aftertaste of hazelnut which are long-lasting.

5. Conclusions:

- It was determined that the yield of wet gluten of grain of “Egyptian Wheat” is 4,31 % higher

than that of “Kamut”. The other characteristics are very similar. The yield of the wet gluten in the flour of “Egyptian Wheat” is 5 % higher than that of “Kamut”. The flour of “Egyptian Wheat” has higher gas forming ability than that of “Kamut”. The organoleptic characteristics of

baked breads made of “Egyptian wheat” and “Kamut” are very similar.

- According to the obtained results, regarding the basic characteristics of grain, flour and bread from “Egyptian Wheat” and “Kamut” it could be concluded that the “Egyptian Wheat” is completely applicable to the production of bread in Bulgaria.

Fig. 1 Basic milling and physico-chemical characteristics of grains of “Egyptian Wheat” and “Kamut”

Fig. 2 Basic characteristics of flours from “Egyptian Wheat” and “Kamut”

Fig. 3 Gas forming ability of flours of “Egyptian Wheat” and “Kamut”

6. References

1. BS 13490 - 1976 Cereal and cereal products. Protein content
2. BS 13492 - 1976 Cereal and cereal products. Ash content
3. BS 13378 1976. Grains. Methods of determination of vitreousness.
4. BS IN ISO 712: 2009 Cereal and cereal products - Determination of the moisture content - Reference method;
5. BS IN ISO 7971 - 2009 Cereal - Determination of the hectoliter weight;
6. BS IN ISO 520 - 2010 Cereal- Determination of the mass of 1 000 grains;
7. BS IN ISO 21415 - 1: on 2007 Wheat and wheat flours - Gluten content - Left 2: Determination of the quantity of wet gluten by mechanical means
8. ICC standard 131. Trial baking test
9. ISO 3093:2009 Common wheats, ryes and their flours, durum wheats and their semolinas - Determination of the falling number according to Hagberg-Perten test
10. Krasteva A ., Tz. Gogova (2003) - " The cereal treasure of the Pharaoh ", magazine "Pain plus", p. 37;
11. Krasteva A ., B. Bozadjiev, Tz. Gogova, S Stoyanova, K. Kolev (2007) - Technological characteristics of primitive wheat type - *Triticum turgidum ssp. Turanicum*. "Egyptian wheat".Scientific works UFT, " Food science, engineering and technologies - 2007 ", Volume LIV, Issue 1, p. 148 - 153.
12. Quinn R. Mr. (1999) – “Kamut: Ancient grain, new cereal, perspectives on new crops and new uses, J. Janick (ed), ASHS Press, Alexandria, Goes
13. Pfannhauser W. (1997) – “Kamut”, Agriculture Handbook, Cereal grains and pasta, p. 20071 - 20076
14. Stallknecht G.F ., K.M. Gilbertson, J.E. Ranney (1996) - " Alternative Cereals of wheat " Progress in new crops. ASHS Press, the United States, The New Crop Resource Online
15. Vangelov A ., Gr Karadzhov (1993) - "Bread-making", Guide of TP(PRACTICAL Excercises), Zemizdat, Sofia

TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRIMITIVE CEREAL OF TYPE *TRITICUM TURGIDUM L. SUBSP. TURANICUM* : "KAMUT"

TZV. GOGOVA* B. BOZADJIEV* D. HRUSAVOV*

Abstract: "Kamut" is an alternative cereal of our traditional wheat for persons suffering of intolerance towards the wheat products. It is cultivated according to the rules of organic farming and represents a good raw material for production of bakery products. For the first time in Bulgaria we conducted a research on the grain, flour and bread of "Kamut". It is determined that the grains of "Kamut" have higher: total protein content, hectoliter weight, quantity of wet gluten and vitreousness compared to the other durum wheat of this type: 5%, 3,7 %, 14,8 % and 4,0 %, respectively. The flour is defined as a medium strong. A flow diagramme of the technological operations was designed. The organoleptic qualities of the bread "Kamut" are lowered, because of the poor porosity and irregular colored crust.

Keywords: grain, flour, bread, "Kamut", bakery products.

1. Introduction

Since 2004 for a first time in Bulgaria has begun an import and researches on a cereal called "Kamut" [11]. This wheat belongs to the *Turgidum* ssp type *T. Turanicum*. Some researchers [12, 13, 14] indicate that the grain of "Kamut" is two - three times bigger than the durum wheat, and its protein content is 20 to 40% higher. It contains more essential amino acids, more saturated fatty acids. Rich in selenium, it helps eliminating the free radicals and also prevents from cardiovascular diseases. Its content of magnesium and zinc indicates that it could be used as an excellent anti-fatigue food, its carbohydrates, lipids and potassium confirm its high nutritional value. Its chemical composition is: 359 calories per 100g; water 9,8 %; proteins 17,3 %; lipids 2,6 %; carbohydrates 68,2 %; fibers 1,8 %; potassium 446mg; phosphorus 411mg; magnesium 153mg; calcium 31mg; iron 4,2mg; sodium 3,8mg; manganese 3,2mg, copper 0,46 mg; Vit B1 0,45mg; B2 0,12mg, Niacine 5,54mg; Vit E 1,7mg.

Cultivated only in organic farming, "Kamut" has a delicious taste of walnut or hazelnut, slightly buttered [10]. Only the harvests which answer the specifications of "Kamut" are sold under the naming of seed "Kamut". The farmers try hard to avoid the contamination by modern varieties of wheat on their fields (standard: purity 99 %). A particular attention is imperative during

the harvest: grains must be delivered absolutely intact in mills (standard: max.3 % of defected grains), and so to preserve their taste and nutritional value. On the market we could find the "Kamut" in a form of grains, bulgur, semolina, flakes, either in grains blown in some muesli. It enters in the composition of a certain pastries and bakery products. The brand "Kamut" is a quality label, that ensures the top quality both of grain and final bakery products. So the term 'bread of "Kamut"' is reserved for a bread prepared by 100 % of cereal "Kamut" (bio-product). The sour which has not been prepared by flour of "Kamut" is rejected. This is important for those consumers who are allergic to the wheat gluten. Pastas of "Kamut" are always prepared with 100 % of flour "Kamut" [10, 11].

Until now, in Bulgaria there is no proof of the existence of any studies on the technological properties of wheat "Kamut". The purpose of this study is to investigate the technological characteristics of wheat "Kamut" for its application in the bakery industry in the country.

2. Materials and Methods

Grain "Kamut" produced by Neufarm International, Zarentin is purchased from a bioproducts store in Germany.

For the purpose of this study we used grain, flour and bread made of "Kamut". The grain was

* Dept. of Food Technology, Plovdiv University of Food Technologies, Bulgaria, e-mail: tzv_gogova@abv.bg

subjected to a preliminary cleaning and conditioning. The total milling yield of flour was 70 %. The grain characteristics measured were: humidity [4], hectoliter weight [5], mass of 1000 grains [6], vitreousness [3], ash content [2] (BS 13492 - on 1976) [2], total protein content [1], the quantity and the quality of wet gluten [7]. The flour is qualified by: the humidity [4], quantity and quality of wet gluten [7], α -amylase activity (falling number test) [9] and the strength of the flour which was determined by trial baking test [8], the titratable acidity, the strength of the flour by penetration evaluated by Index K_{60} [15], gas forming ability [15].

The organoleptic analysis of the final product was conducted according to the following characteristics: crumb porosity, taste, aftertaste, flavor, the color of the lower and upper crust layers, the color of the crumb and the thickness of the upper and lower crust layers. The loaves were evaluated by: mass, volume and shape retaining ability [15].

3. Results and Discussion

The experiments began with the determination of certain milling and physicochemical characteristics of wheat grain "Kamut". The obtained results are presented in table 1.

Milling and physicochemical characteristics of wheat grain "Kamut"

Table 1

No	Characteristics	"Kamut"
1	Moisture content, %	11,9
2	Hectoliter weight, kg/100dm ³	78,8
3	Weight of 1000 grains, g	64,7
4	Vitreousness, %	74
5	Density, g/cm ³	1,39
6	Linear sizes of grains,	
6.1	- lenght, mm	9,4±0,50
6.2	- width, mm	3,1±0,24
6.3	- thickness, mm	2,9±0,21
7	Ash content, %	1,43
8	Protein, %	19,00
9	Wet gluten, %	29,09
10	Softening of gluten, mm	10,0

The obtained results presented in Table 1, show

that the following characteristics: hectoliter weight (78,8 kg / 100dm³), vitreousness (74 %) and yield on the wet gluten (29,09 %) were higher than those of the other types of durum wheat by: 3,7 %, 14,8 % and 4,0 % respectively. In respect of the grain size, the grain of "Kamut" were bigger than those of the other types of wheat, with a larger difference in lenght of 40% [12,13, 14].

The total protein content is one of the main indicators that characterizes the technological properties of wheat. The average protein content in the durum wheat is about 14 % and 19% in "Kamut" [12,13, 14].

The studies continued with the determination of certain technological characteristics of the flour "Kamut". The results are presented in the Table 2

Basic technological characteristics of flour "Kamut"

Table 2

No	Characteristics	"Kamut"
1	Moisture content, %	14,4
2	Wet gluten, %	32,0
3	Softening of gluten, mm	7,5
4	Acidity, °H	2,0
5	Strength of the flour by penetration, index K_{60} , U.P.	0 min – 129 30 min - 148 60 min – 152
6	Falling number, s	425

From the obtained results presented in Table 2, one can see that the quantity of wet gluten of flour "Kamut" (32,0 %) is similar to that of the of durum wheat. The softening of the wet gluten by 7.5 mm, indicates that it is a strong gluten. The activity of alpha-amylase was found to be very low and the index K_{60} shows that the flour is medium strong.

The results regarding the gas forming ability of flour "Kamut" are presented on Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Gas forming ability of flour "Kamut"

The gas forming ability sharply increased in the first 60 minutes of the experiment and it is found to be 5,2 cm³. This value is retained up to 120 min followed by a slight decreasing (4.8 cm³) on the 150 min. It could be concluded that the flour “Kamut” has a high gas forming ability.

Based on the obtained results of milling and physicochemical characteristics of grain and flour “Kamut” a flow diagramme of the technological operations for production of bread was composed (Figure 2).

Fig. 2 Scheme of technological operations for bread “Kamut”

The final loaves were characterized by organoleptic characteristics: typical exterior of wheat bread with a good forming capabilities and irregular crust coloration with a dark spots without cracks; the color of the crumb is dark yellow; gas pores are small and uniformly distributed; a taste and smell non-typical for a wheat bread with nuances of butter and an aftertaste of hazelnut which are long-lasting.

4. Conclusions

1. It is determined that the grains of “Kamut” have higher: total protein content, hectoliter

weight, quantity of wet gluten and vitreousness compared to the other durum wheat of this type: 5%, 3,7 %, 14,8 % and 4,0 %, respectively. The flour is defined as a medium strong.

2. A flow diagramme of technological operations for production of bread “Kamut” is designed. The organoleptic characteristics are as follow: typical exterior of wheat bread with a good forming capabilities and irregular crust coloration with a dark spots without cracks; the color of the crumb is dark yellow; gas pores are small and non-uniformly distributed; a taste and smell non-typical for a wheat bread with nuances of butter and an aftertaste of hazelnut which are long-lasting.

5. References

1. BS 13490 - 1976 Cereal and cereal products. Protein content
2. BS 13492 - 1976 Cereal and cereal products. Ash content
3. BS 13378 1976. Grains. Methods of determination of vitreousness.
4. BS IN ISO 712: 2009 Cereal and cereal products - Determination of the moisture content - Reference method;
5. BS IN ISO 7971 - 2009 Cereal - Determination of the hectoliter weight;
6. BS IN ISO 520 - 2010 Cereal- Determination of the mass of 1 000 grains;
7. BS IN ISO 21415 - 1: on 2007 Wheat and wheat flours - Gluten content - Left 2: Determination of the quantity of wet gluten by mechanical means
8. ICC standard 131. Trial baking test
9. ISO 3093:2009 Common wheats, ryes and their flours, durum wheats and their semolinas - Determination of the falling number according to Hagberg-Perten test
10. Krasteva A ., Tz. Gogova (2003) - " The cereal treasure of the Pharaoh ", magazine "Pain plus", p. 37;
11. Krasteva A ., B. Bozadjiev, Tz. Gogova, S Stoyanova, K. Kolev (2007) - Technological characteristics of primitive wheat type - *Triticum turgidum ssp. Turanicum*. "Egyptian wheat" .Scientific works UFT, " Food science, engineering and technologies - 2007 ", Volume LIV, Issue 1, p. 148 - 153.
12. Quinn R. Mr. (1999) - " Kamut: Ancient grain, new cereal, perspectives on new crops and new uses, J. Janick (ed), ASHS Press, Alexandria, Goes
13. Pfannhauser W. (1997) – “Kamut”,

Agriculture Handbook, Cereal grains and pasta,
p. 20071 - 20076

14. *Stallknecht G.F ., K.M. Gilbertson, J.E. Ranney (1996) - " Alternative Cereals of wheat " Progress in new crops. ASHS Press, the United States, The New Crop Resource Online*

15. *Vangelov A ., Gr. Karadzhev (1993) - "Bread-making", Guide of TP(PRACTICAL Excercises), Zemizdat, Sofia*

Development of forage production in farmers of Kazakhstan

Yesperova B., Alimaev I.

Abstract: The paper presents the main layout of forage production in Kazakhstan taking in consideration differences between small household, large and medium size farmers. There are discussed the main directions for developing in different types of farming, resources and other conditions for a sustainable growing.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, farmers, forage production

1. Introduction

Everyone knows that obtaining the maximum quantity and the highest quality of the products directly depends on feeding of the livestock. This is related to the use of zonal feed rations.

Currently, we have exactly determined the level of the animal products produces. The first category thereof (up to 20% of all agricultural

entities) is represented by rather large farms holding at least 300 meat and dairy cattle heads, having the resource base (land, funds, machinery, personnel, etc.). The second category of owners (at least 80% of all agricultural entities) is represented by small and medium-sized farms and households, which have a limited number of cattle and almost no resource base. Furthermore, the second category of owners produces up to 80% or more of all meat and milk (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Tendency of the development of forage resources

Clearly, owners of farm livestock possessing resource bases in normal circumstances have real opportunities to develop further. The state has been rendering a certain support to such farms, subject to the outlook of creation of modern cattle-breeding productions based on them. The second category of owners who fail to have their own resource base, are most vulnerable and

exposed to risks (weather, price, lending, and other ones), and the development outlooks of this category are limited. At the same time, these farms have the right to life, at least because they employ over 30% of the country's population. In addition, the domestic market is mainly provided with cattle-breeding products by such farms.

Fig. 2. Development of the forage production in large and middle size farmers.

In farms lacking such preconditions, the forage base will consist of pasture forage, hay (purchased or harvested by the owner) and few concentrates purchased in the form of bold or crushed barley-corn or grain production wastes. Extensive forage production will prevail for this category of farms, where the main component will be the cheap pasture forage. To ensure higher stability of production in such farms, we believe it is required to solve a number of organizational tasks. The problem related to pasture forages becomes increasingly urgent, from year to year. Pastures of the "settlements" lands are used around auls. Pasture areas depend on this or that settlement, but the majority of such areas are not bound to the specific settlement's livestock numbers, i.e. the livestock grows but

the areas do not change. Hence, the allowable load standards are breached and pastures are normally degrading (there are 26.5 million hectares of degraded pastures in the country) (fig. 3).

The sound feeding of the livestock can be ensured by the farms having their own resource bases, which are capable of growing feed crops and produce forages of the required volume and range. In other words, the direction of forage production will depend here on economic operations of an agricultural entity (meat, milk, wool production), specific objectives (milk yield per forage-fed cow, surplus in body weight of the young stock by the date of slaughtering, wool yield per sheep, etc.), a region / natural zone of the farm.

For example, a farm located in the Northern region in engaged in youngster graziery and pursues the following goal – by the 20-month age the bullocks shall have the body weight of 420-450 kg/head. To obtain the expected yield, the regional scientifically substantiated ration has been worked out to ensure proper feeding, when livestock at 12 to 20 months are supposed to eat 2,548 fodder units, including: hay (9.9%); haylage (19.9%); concentrates (26.3%); and pasture forage (43.9%). As to cropping capacity and nutrition value, such ration can be substantially ensured in conditions of the Northern region with the haylage (a mixture of peas, oats and barleys); hay (by sowing *Bromus inermis* Leyss; concentrates (by sowing forage barley). Considering the average cropping capacity of *Bromus inermis* Leyss when used for hay – 12 centner/hectare; the mixture of peas, oats, and barleys when used as the haylage – 40 centner/hectare; forage barley when used as the fodder grains – 12 centner/hectare; pastures – 15

centner/hectare, the following volumes will be required per 100 heads of grass-fattened youngsters: a mixture of annual crops for the haylage – 44 hectares; *Bromus inermis* Leyss for the hay – 50 hectares; barleys for the fodder grains – 56 hectares, and pastures – 311 hectares. In the given instance, the forage production is dependant on the ration and is aimed to ensure proper feeding of the livestock. Thus, feed crops, their cropping capacity and area where they will be grown by the specific farm, shall be determined.

Such target use of land resources with planting the most productive and valuable in nutrition terms crops, shall be the rule of the modern forage production in farms having their resource bases. Such farms will require scientific consultations with regards to establishment of feeding rations, selection of forage crops and their production practices. In this case it is possible to discuss development of intensive forage production (fig. 2).

THE DEVELOPMENT OF FORAGE PRODUCTION IN HOUSEHOLDS

Fig. 3 The development of forage production in households

There are standby pasture lands. Most probably, each aul's livestock should be brought in line with forage capacity of the allotted pastures located in the vicinity to such aul (seasonal plots for agisted livestock may be

allotted). In parallel, it is required to solve issues related to water supply to the pastures. The second objective is to produce hay. For the cattle to be able to overwinter well, 20 centners of high quality hay should be harvested per cattle head. Today over 50% of small owners have to

purchase such hay, though in a volume that is far from the required one. Hay is quite expensive everywhere (10 to 30 tenge/kg). In regions with flood plains, there are still drowned rivers and other moisture-rich areas, where the sufficient volume of hay is harvested, and this problem is not urgent there. However what shall be done in places with few or no hayfields?

Perhaps, it is necessary to create hayfields of wheat grasses, *Bromus inermis* Leyss and other permanent forage crops in such places. Depending on a livestock, share participation and other factors, organizationally, this issue can be solved by rural population. Perhaps, an example set by some pilot projects will suffice here.

Thus, in our opinion, today the forage production sector should develop in two directions:

intensively in those farms that wish to reach the level of the advanced countries' cattle-breeding; and extensively, in farms lacking their own resource bases, but employing the majority of rural population and providing the domestic market with the agricultural products. The forage production outlooks should be planned subject to the above considerations.

References

1. Agency of statistics of the Republic Kazakhstan, 2009.
2. Kelley Cormier, Farm restructuring in Kazakhstan: An Institutional Economics Approach.

RESEARCH ON SOIL COMPACTION CAUSED BY POTATOES HARVERSTERS COMBINES

FL. LOGHIN* FL. RUS** I. CAPATINA***

Abstract: *The paper presents results of experimental researches carried out in order to assess the state of soil compaction caused by the pressure exerted by the tires of the potato harvesters. During the experimental researches it was used a self-propelled equipment specifically designed to assess the soil compaction. Measurements were performed on the same field and same weather conditions, with different technical equipment for harvesting potato tubers. The measuring points were lined up by the motion direction of agricultural aggregate, and also on tires trace left on the ground, in the mark left by the spur wheels and between those, to depths of 0 cm and of 80 cm. The measuring results were synthesized in graphics which allow the evaluation of compaction state of soil. The conclusions allow the elaboration of an appropriate management for agricultural workings of harvesting potato tubers.*

Keywords: *soil, compaction way, penetration resistance, harvesting agricultural aggregate.*

1. Introduction

In the last two decades there has been a steady increase of tractors weight and of agricultural machines, as a consequence of the increasing trend of their capacity of work in order to reduce the time required for carrying out specific tasks, and in this way it was increased the loads to their decks. For this reason, the greatest pressure that is exerted on the soil surface is from the tires of agricultural machines variable mass, such as: self-propelled harvesting machine (cereals, potatoes, beet etc.), towed or semi combine of harvesting (potatoes, beet). To this category of agricultural machines, the pressure exerted on the soil surface is variable, being determined by two components: a relative constant component due to its own machine mass and a variable component depending on the material quantity found out in the hopper.

Soil compaction is defined as an increase of apparent density of soil with simultaneous reduction of porosity. This phenomenon manifests itself by reducing the volume of capillary spaces and thus of soil air volume, having as consequence:

- reduction of gas diffusion in soil, fact which leads to a low level of development of roots and in extreme cases can cause asphyxiation of plant roots;
- reduction of microbial activity, with direct effects upon the rate of decomposition of organic matter, incorporated into soil;
- reduction of water movement in soil mass, which may lead to a longer stagnation of water on the soil surface;
- a difficult supply of plant nutrients, due to the low level of development of their roots [4, 5].

To develop a proper management of specific farming operation, the general objective of experimental researches is to highlight the way of changing of soil physical and mechanical properties as a result of pressure exerted by the tires of agricultural aggregates with variable mass, by continuous assessing of the state of soil compaction [3, 6].

2. Material and methods

The determination of resistance to penetration is a simple method of assessing the state of compaction of the soil, used in researches on the

* Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania*, e-mail: loghinflorin@unitbv.ro

** Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania*, e-mail: florus@unitbv.ro

*** Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania*, e-mail: ionutcapatana@yahoo.com

influence of soil works because it highlight the seasonal dynamics of soil physical condition [2]. The method of determining the resistance to penetration is based on simultaneous measurement of force P which must be applied to a standard cone-shaped body forced to penetrate the soil subjected to analyze (fig. 1, a) and of

penetration depth (fig. 1, b) maintaining constant the penetration velocity. To remove the influence of friction forces between the cone rod and the ground, the rod diameter is smaller than the diameter of the conical body base (fig. 1, b) [1, 2].

Fig. 1. The operation principle of cone penetrometer [1]

Introducing the gauge body in the soil under the action of crush force created by a human operator has the following major drawbacks:

- Variable speed with which the conic body is introduced in the soil, which is dependent on the anatomical characteristics of the operator (weight, height, muscle force);
- Special exercise, maximum resistance at entering reaching values up to 1000 N.

For the same soil and penetrometer used by two operators with distinct anatomical features, leads to obtaining different values of entering resistance.

Accuracy of measurements is closely related to the pushing ability of penetrometer' drill in the soil coating tested at a constant speed. Data collection for the entire area required to achieve geo-referenced maps of soil tamping, is time consuming, costly and often inconvenient.

For measurements we used a device designed by Transilvania University of Braşov in collaboration with National Research Institute - for Machines and Installations Development designed to Agriculture and Food Industry - Bucharest. This equipment, was made in order to eliminate disadvantages of the measurements by a human operator, and consists of following main parts (Fig. 2): Energetic crawler system, which provides independent transport of the entire

- equipment on the surface of the studied lands 1;
- Electronic penetrometer with Eijkelkamp Penetrologger digital display 3 (s. fig. 4);
- Device for operation with constant speed of the penetrometer 2;
- GPS Global positioning system;
- Portable electronic computer;
- Hydrostatic and electric energy source 5, 6.

To introduce the rod and cone of penetrometer with a constant speed in the soil, this was mounted on a hydraulic cylinder rod, which in turn was placed on a special built metallic frame, which can be attached through a suspension mechanism on the small crawler conveyer transport system. Adjusting the vertical position of the metallic frame is done through a detached hydraulic cylinder, thus the force applied by the penetrometer on the soil and the entering course should be correctly established. This system only demands one operator.

The experimental determinations were made on a farmland located in Covasna / Romania, an area that is favourable for potato cultivation. For each mechanized harvester was chosen a monitored area. The monitored areas were divided into ten measurement areas, for each area of measurement it is performed a total of five sets of measurements.

Fig. 2. The equipment used for determinations

In figure 3 are presented aspects from the harvesting potato tubers with combines used in experimental researches. Table 1 shows the main characteristics of those.

a.

b.

c.

Fig. 3. Harvesting combines: a. GRIMME SE 75-30 Combine - tractor CASE III JV 70; b. GRIMME SE 150-60 Harvesting machine – tractor John Deere 6930; c. GRIMME SF 150-60 Harvesting machine (self propelled).

Table 1

Name of the harvesting machine	Type of the harvesting machine	Nb. of harvested lines	Mass machine	Hopper capacity	Energy source
GRIMME SE 75-30	trailed	1 line	4300 kg	3000 kg	Tractor CASE III JV-70
GRIMME SE 150-60	trailed	2 lines	9350 kg	6000 kg	Tractor John DEERE 6930
GRIMME SF 150-60	Self Propelled	2 lines	12,900 kg	6000 kg	Engine-Mrcedes-Benz OM 906 LA, power 205 kW

Fig. 4. Penetrometrul digital Eijkelkamp Penetrologger

Fig. 5. Capacitive humidometer KKT, PT-1

3. Results and discussion

Using specific operations of Excel application, the data obtained as a result of

experimental results are presented as graphics which show best the effect produced by the combine passing upon the estate of soil compaction.

Fig. 6. The variation of average resistance of depth penetration, for SE 170 – 50 self-propelled combine: a. – the average value of the resistance of soil penetration before the combine passing; b. - the average value of the resistance of soil penetration after the combine passing.

In figure 6 is graphically presented the average resistance to penetration on depth before and after the passing of Grimme SE 170-50 selfpropelled combine.

Analysing the two graphics we find the following: - the effect of the pressure exerted by the combine tires SE 170-50 on soil is felt to a depth of 30...35 cm; - to depths between 5 and 15 cm, the average value of the penetration resistance increases with

about 0,7 MPa, after this depth the average value is growing increasingly smaller.

In figure 7 are graphically presented the variation of average penetration on depth, before and after the passing of agricultural aggregate made of John Deere 6930 Premium tractor and the combine GRIMME SE 150 – 60 trailed on two lines.

Fig. 7. The variation of average penetration on depth, before (a) and after (b) the passing of agricultural aggregate John Deere 6930 Premium tractor and the combine GRIMME SE 150 – 60

The analysis of the two graphs shows the following:

- the pressure effect exerted by the tires of John Deere 6930 Premium tractor unit - combines GRIMME SE trailed 150-60 on soil are felt to a depth of 20...25 cm;

- to depths between 5 and 15 cm the average penetration resistance increases about 0.3 MPa.

Figure 8 presents the average variation resistance to penetration for the measurements made on the access road of heavy trucks carrying potatoes to the storage place.

Fig. 8. The average variation of resistance to penetration on depth, the agricultural unit consisting of JV70 CASE III tractor and Grimme SE 75-40 combine trailed in one row

Analysing the two graphs we observe the following:

- the pressure effect exerted by the tractor unit tires CASE III JV 70 - GRIMME SE 75 – 30 combine hauled on one row felt on soil to a depth of 25...30 cm;
- the average penetration resistance registers a much smaller increase than from the other two combines.

4. Conclusions

Regarding the influence of agricultural machinery traffic with variable mass upon the penetration resistance, we observe that this increases significantly, especially at the soil surface. Also the penetration resistance values increase at the same time with the increasing mass of the material from the hopper.

The results of the experimental researches for all the types of combines used at harvesting works, revealed the fact that at a depth of 35...40 cm the average values of the penetration resistance are approximately the same for all measuring points. This aspect indicates that the aggregate does not cause soil compaction at this depth, the effect of compaction on the soil surface produced by the combine harvester can be averted by implementing some basic works of soil quality.

The biggest penetration resistance values were obtained in the measurement points located on the technological paths (both surface and deep), which indicates the fact that the farm machinery traffic effect is felt in time and that the resistance to penetration depends on the agricultural works applied to the land.

The compaction of agricultural land is a form of soil degradation, being an unwanted consequent phenomenon that occurs during the execution of agricultural works. The phenomenon is impossible to be avoided, but it can be kept under control through proper management, for this it is necessary to perform the monitoring of the causes which lead to land compaction.

The fastest way to monitor the state of compaction can be achieved by measuring the

penetration resistance points located in space. The space location of measurement points and measured values allows the elaboration of maps through which it can be achieved proper management of agricultural technologies.

The determination of the penetration resistance is a simple and effective method of assessing the state of soil compaction, it reveals the seasonal dynamics of the soil physical condition.

References

1. Loghin, Fl. and I. Căpățină 2010. *Aspects Regarding the Reduction of Penetration Resistance of Soil as a Consequence Soil Working*. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal. pp. 1619-1622.
2. Molnar, I. 2008. *Research on the Influence of Agricultural Machines and Tractors of Soil Compaction*. PhD Thesis, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca/Romania.
3. Rudiger, A., Werner, D. and Steinert, P. 1991. *Einfluss von Reifeninnendruck, Radlast und Überrollhäufigkeit auf die Verformung des Bodens*. Agrartechnik, no.1, pp. 19 - 21.
4. Rus, Fl., and C. Csátlos 2009. *Complex Systems and Methodologies for Determining the Mechanical and Physical Characteristics of Soil*. Transilvania University Press of Basov.
5. Rus, Fl. and Fl. Loghin 2010. *The Management of Soils Compaction*. Proceedings of the International Research & Innovation in Engineering, COMAT 2010 no. 3. p. 314-319.
6. Soane, B. D., van Ouwerk, C. 1994. *Soil Compaction in Crop Production*. Elsevier, Amsterdam.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: This paper is supported by the Sectoral Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the project number ID59323.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF ENERGY DISSIPATION IN MIXING PROCESS OF BREAD DOUGH

M.I. LUCHIAN* I. LITOVCHENKO** S. STEFANOV** C. CSATLOS*

Abstract: *Mixing theory is important for its relevance in understanding some of the most fundamental problems involving bread dough flows, and for its practical impact in connection with bakery industry and other food industries. The aim of this article is to develop advanced technology for numerical simulation of bread dough mixing process, in order to provide a predictive capability of optimum design parameters of dough mixers using Computational Fluid Dynamics code named Flow Vision.*

Keywords: *mixing, bread dough, numerical simulation, CFD, Flow Vision.*

1. Introduction

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is the division of Fluid Mechanics focused on numerical simulation of the heat and mass transfer in different technical industry, including bread making process. The main problem of CFD is numerical integration of the Navier-Stokes equations describing the fluid dynamics. Additional equations are needed to describe turbulence, porosity and other physical and chemical phenomena and processes. [2]; [6]

Commercial code Flow Vision is intended for modeling of three-dimensional fluid (bread dough) flow in technical object with subsequent visualization of the results using different methods of computer graphics.

The modeled flows may be steady or unsteady, laminar or turbulent, compressible, weakly compressible, or incompressible.

Flow Vision is based on the finite-volume approach to the integration of the fluid dynamics equations. It uses a hexahedral adaptive grid with local refinement. Sub-grid resolution technology is implemented for accurate approximation of curvilinear geometry. The technology enables to import geometries from CAD systems and to interact with finite-element systems. The technology implies automatic grid generation, only several parameters are to be specified in order to build the grid for a computational domain of arbitrary complexity. [7]

Access to the model parameters and possibility to local adapt computational grid allow simulation of bread dough flow with strong swirl, free surfaces, etc.

2. Working steps

Calculation of a bread dough mixing flow implies the following steps: [5]

- creation of the mixer geometry of computational domain in a CAD system and import of the geometry to Flow Vision from the VRML;
- specifying mathematical model;
- setting boundary conditions;
- specifying primary grid and criteria for its adaptation to the solution and boundaries;
- specifying parameters of the numerical methods used for integration of different equation;
- calculation, which are carried out without user interference;
- visualization of the obtained results, saving the needed characteristics in files;
- repetition of calculations on a finer grid in order to estimate the accuracy of the results.

The goal of the flow of bread dough mixing simulation is to obtain the fields of energy, pressure, and other quantities in the computational domain. The calculations require specifying the laws governing the flow. The set

* Dept. of Food Industry, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: m_luchian@yahoo.com

** National University of Food Technology, Kyiv, Ukraine, e-mail: igor.lytovchenko@yahdex.ua

** University of Food Technology, Plovdiv, Bulgaria, e-mail: stvstefanov@yahoo.com

* Dept. of Food Industry, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: csk@unitbv.ro

of the laws constitute the mathematical model of the flow. [1]; [4]

In general, the mathematical model is a set of partial differential equations describing conservation of mass, momentum, and energy; corresponding boundary conditions, and appropriate state equations.

3. Computer numerical simulation

Mixing parameters are external factors for mixing operation that may adapt to the requirements of mixing in correlation with physical and chemical composition of wheat flour dough.

The dimensions of the mixing space and the amounts of mixed materials play important role in dough formation and influence its properties. Many researches have been done and studied the flow of material by numerical simulation and mixing mechanism in conventional mixers or extruders. [5]

This study approach three-dimensional numerical simulation of dough mixing that occurs very often in the bread processing industry. The motivation of this study is to

Fig. 1. Spiral Mixer SL 50

The results of the simulation flow in the mixer using Flow Vision, e.g. dissipation of pressure and kinetic energy, are presented in next figures.

For study of the processes passing in the mixer at the time of its work, there are made computer simulations in medium of the program system Flow Vision. For the purposes of the simulations it is used the method of the finite volume. [4]

The given model describes the flowing of viscose fluid on small numbers of Max ($M < 0.3$), small and big (turbulent) numbers of

develop advanced technology for modeling dough mixing, in order to provide a predictive capability of optimum design parameters of dough mixers. [3]

It was investigated a dough mixer with rotating mixing spiral arm Model SL 50 (Figure 1), placed eccentric from batter bowl.

The spiral mixing arm is rotating around a vertical axis in the batter bowl, considered in a vertical orientation (x, y, z), as can be seen in Figure 2.

In this study, a CFD package (Computational Fluid Dynamics) called Flow Vision was applied to build the model calculation and the calculation results. First was designed a parameterized three-dimensional geometric model of the mixer with spiral arm. For this purpose was applied a CAD software (called Solid Works), used in the design of objects with very complex geometry. Geometry from Solid Works transferred to CFD Flow Vision preprocessor package is more flexible and precise than in the case that be realized with the preprocessor itself.

Fig. 2. 3D - model of mixer

1- opposite spiral; 2- spiral mixing; 3- lid; 4- batter bowl

Reynolds. In this model are included the equations of Navier-Stokes and the energy equations.

The model of turbulent incompressible fluid is based on the using turbulent viscosity μ_t . The determination of μ_t depends on the chosen model of turbulence.

In the model are used the Navier-Stokes equations:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \nabla(V \otimes V) = -\frac{\nabla P}{\rho} + \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \left((\mu + \mu_t) (\nabla V + (\nabla V)^T) \right) + S \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla V = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } S = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{hyd}}{\rho} \right) g + B + \frac{R}{\rho} \quad (3)$$

At rotating coordinate system, the force of rotating looks like in equation (4):

$$B = -2\omega V - \omega^2 r \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \nabla(vh) = \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \left(\left(\frac{\lambda}{C_p} + \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \right) \nabla h \right) + \frac{Q}{p} \quad (5)$$

The equation used for energy calculation is (5):

4. Results and discussion

The object of the investigation is mixing bread dough (Mixer SL 50) with the geometric and force characteristics. There have been carried out simulation studies of the processes in the mixer during its work with bread dough.

The conditions of the simulated experiment are: density of the bread dough: $\rho_1=1100 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $\rho_2=1200 \text{ kg/m}^3$; viscosity: $\mu=2,61 \text{ Pa.s}$; frequency of rotation of the spiral mixing: $n_1=180 \text{ rev/min}$ and frequency of rotation of the batter bowl: $n_2=30 \text{ rev/min}$.

There are investigated the following indexes of the regime of the mixer:

- Figures 3 and 4 - change of the pressure of bread dough into 3D horizontal sections of the

mixer at a density of the product $\rho_1=1100 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $\rho_2=1200 \text{ kg/m}^3$; at maximum value of the scale of the pressure – 400Pa;

- Figures 5 and 6 present the dissipation of the kinetic energy in the mixer at a density of the bread dough $\rho_1=1100 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $\rho_2=1200 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

High pressure values of the bread dough (Figures 3 and 4) are observed in two areas: in areas between the mixing spiral and the batter bowl walls (360÷400 Pa) as a result of volume reduction between the working organ and the walls of the batter bowl in the process of work, and in a layer near the walls of the batter bowl (200 ÷ 280 Pa), which is explained by the centrifugal forces and the hydrostatic pressure.

Fig. 3 Pressure of the bread dough in horizontal sections of the mixer at a density 1100 kg/m^3

Fig. 4 Pressure of the bread dough in horizontal sections of the mixer at a density 1200 kg/m^3

Fig. 5 Dissipation of the kinetic energy in the mixer at a density of bread dough 1100 kg/m^3

Fig. 6 Dissipation of the kinetic energy in the mixer at a density of bread dough 1200 kg/m^3

The dissipation of the kinetic energy (Figures 5 and 6) is proportional to the gradient of the velocity. The highest values are observed in areas adjacent to the surface of the spiral, the opposite spiral and the walls of the batter bowl.

In the carried out simulation experiments with bread dough with different density (1100 kg/m^3 and 1200 kg/m^3) results are not significantly different, since the change in viscosity is not significant (important) like we can see from results of simulation.

The obtained results provide a possibility for optimization of this type dough mixing machines in reference to the size and proportions of the batter bowl and the working organs.

Acknowledgements

This paper is supported by the Sectorial Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the contract number POSDRU /88/1.5/S/59321: *Investment in sustainable development through doctoral scholarships INDED*.

Thanks for help to PhD Prof. Eng. Lytovchenko Igor from National University of Food Technology, Kyiv, Ukraine and also I want to thank you to Assoc. PhD Prof. Eng. Stefanov Stefan from University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

References

1. Bakker A., Cathie N., LaRoche R.: *Modeling of the Flow and Mixing in HEV Static Mixers*, 8th European Conference on Mixing, Cambridge, U.K. IChemE Symposium Series No. 136, 1994, p. 533-540.
2. Oshinowo L., Bakker A., Marshall E. M.: *Mixing Time - A CFD Approach*, Canada, 1999.
3. Read, N. K., Zhang S. X., Ray W. H.: *Simulations of a LDPE Reactor Using Computational Fluid Dynamics*, AIChE Journal 43(1), 1997, p. 104-117.
4. Versteeg, H. K., Malalasekera W.: *An Introduction to Computational Fluid Dynamics: The Finite Volume Method*, Longman Scientific & Technical, Essex, UK, 1995.
5. Yi P., Hu Y., Liu S.: *Numerical Investigation of Effect of Stirring Blades on Mixing Efficiency of a Planetary Kneading Mixer with Non-Newtonian and Viscoplastic Materials*, TheXVth International Congress on Rheology, 2008, p. 442-444.
6. Wyman, N.: *CFD Review*, available at <http://www.cfdreview.com>.
7. <http://www.fv-tech.com/>

CYCLONE GEOMETRY INFLUENCE ON THE NUMBER OF REVOLUTIONS IN THE OUTER VORTEX

M. MARINUC*

Abstract: Cyclones models have been used without relevant modifications for more than a century. Most of the attention has been focused on finding new methods to improve performance parameters. This paper presents the influence of cyclone geometry with tangential entry over the number of rotations that perform heterogeneous solid-gas mixture in the outer vortex. Also, it is presented the variation of sedimentation time with the input velocity depending on the length of the cyclone.

Keywords: cyclone geometry, number of revolutions, sedimentation time, velocity.

1. Introduction

Cyclone separators are widely used in many industrial and research areas where it is necessary to achieve separation from the mass of the gases. The advantages afforded by cyclones, refer to: no moving parts, compactness of construction, simple operation, low cost manufacturing, service and repair, operate in a wide field variance suspension and adaptability to a wide range of grain solid particles in suspension. In terms of construction, the cyclones are simple devices, but the mathematical model equations that describe the flow and separation processes that occur within them are highly complex. Researchers, who have studied the work of these devices, have developed a series of theories and empirical models that can be used for designing. [1]

The separation processes are ubiquitous in various technological processes of various industries, belonging to the chemical, petrochemical, mining, pharmaceutical and agro-food processes. In general, this process is a physical separation of two phases (Gas/Liquid, Gas/Solid, Liquid/Solid), formed from a continuous phase (carrying particles), and a dispersed phase (particles). Cyclones are the most widely used separator devices which are based on the action of particle centrifugal force in suspension, being created by the vortex of fluid in the cyclone. [2]

Inside the cyclone, due the inlet geometry and the cyclone housing, elements mass of the fluid are moving simultaneously in three directions: after a direction parallel to the vertical axis of the cyclone, with speed v_z ; a rotating movement around a vertical axis, with the peripheral speed u

and on radial direction, perpendicular to the axis of rotation, with speed v_r . (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1 The directions of motion for a fluid mass element

In different parts of the cyclone, the value of these rates is not constant, changing according to local conditions of flow. Movements in the vertical direction and rotation cause the spiral motion of fluid.

Depending on the values of the three speeds: v_z , u , v_r , inside the cyclone is three main streams:

I - central area, called the secondary vortex, which is an ascending stream formed in the center of the cyclone around the vertical axis, representing the spiral movement of the fluid phase which separated from the solid phase. The limit on the radial direction of this vortex is in the area of radius R_1 , where the upward velocity v_z and peripheral velocity u have the maximum values (Fig. 2). The radial velocity of the fluid at level and within the secondary vortex, is zero ($v_r=0$). Characteristic for this stream of fluid is that the axis of symmetry of the cyclone may present local eccentricities (undulations in the axis of symmetry of the truncated part of the cyclone) or general (on the entire height of the cyclone).

* Dept. of Food Engineering, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: mimy_85@yahoo.com

II - the primary vortex that is a fluid stream forming in the area between the radii R_1 and R_2 of the cyclone representing the spiral motion of heterogeneous mixture that is placed inside the cyclone tangentially through the supply pipe. From Figure 2, it can be observed that near the critical radius R_0 , the velocity v_z changes its sign, so that between the range R_1 - R_0 , located closer to the cyclone axis, the velocity v_z is oriented upward (the current is upward), and in the range R_0 - R_2 , located closer to the cyclone wall, velocity v_z is facing down (the current is downwards).

III - the flow in the boundary layer, (Fig. 3) containing a thin layer δ , which is the whole inner surface of the cyclone. Inside the cyclone two regions differ, in each of this, the fluid flow in the boundary layer is presented different characteristics.

Fig. 2 Diagram of fluid circulation within the cyclone

The first region comprises the top cover of the cylindrical sector of the cyclone and the outer surface of the central exhaust tube, in which fluid motion is stable, without fluid trends mixing from the boundary layer with the fluid from the other areas.

Fig.3 The fluid flow from the boundary layer inside the cyclone

The second region is the conical part of the cyclone in which the fluid motion from the

boundary layer is unstable, with fluid elements and solid particles which are tend to move toward the center of the cyclone, and on radial direction with entrance tended in the central vortex. (Fig. 3)

The geometry inlet influences the nature of the primary vortex and has a key role in the general eccentricity of the secondary vortex. The slit shaped tangential has a rectangular section and created within the cyclone a general eccentricity of the secondary vortex with the axis of symmetry of the cyclone. [3]

2. Cyclone Theory. Collection Efficiency

A very simple model can be used to determine the effects of both cyclone design and operation on collection efficiency.

In this model, gas spins through a number N of revolutions in the outer vortex. The value of N can be approximated as the sum of revolutions inside the body and inside the cone:

$$N = \frac{1}{a} \left(h + \frac{H-h}{2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of turns inside the device (no units); a - height of inlet duct (m); h - length of cyclone body (m); $H-h$ - length (vertical) of cyclone cone (m).

To be collected, particles must strike the wall within the amount of time that the gas travels in the outer vortex. The gas residence time in the outer vortex is:

$$\Delta_i = \frac{\pi \cdot D \cdot N}{V_i} \quad (2)$$

where Δ_i is the time spent by gas during spiraling descent (sec); D - cyclone body diameter (m); V_i - gas inlet velocity (m/s), $V_i = Q/b \cdot a$; Q - volumetric inflow (m³/s); b - width of inlet (m).

The maximum radial distance traveled by any particle is the width of the inlet duct b . The centrifugal force quickly accelerates the particle to its terminal velocity in the outward (radial) direction, with the opposing drag force equaling the centrifugal force. The terminal velocity that will just allow a particle initially at distance W away from the wall to be collected in time is:

$$V_i = \frac{b}{\Delta_i} \quad (3)$$

where V_i is the particle drift velocity in the radial direction (m/s).

The particle drift velocity is a function of particle size.

Assuming Stokes regime flow (drag force = $3\pi \mu p V_i$) and spherical particles subjected to a centrifugal force mv^2/r , with m - mass of particle in excess of mass of air displaced, $v = V_i$ of inlet flow, and $r = D/2$, we obtain:

$$V_i = \frac{(\rho_p - \rho_a) \cdot d_p^2 \cdot V_i^2}{9 \cdot \mu \cdot D} \quad (4)$$

where V_i is the terminal velocity (m/s); d_p - diameter of the particle (m); ρ_p - density of the particle (kg/m^3); ρ_a - air density (kg/m^3); μ - air viscosity ($\text{kg/m}\cdot\text{s}$).

Substitution of the 2nd equation into the 3rd eliminates Δ_i . Then, setting the two expressions for V_i equal to each other and rearranging to solve for particle diameter, we obtain:

$$d_p = \left[\frac{9 \cdot \mu \cdot b}{\pi \cdot N \cdot V_i \cdot (\rho_p - \rho_a)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

It is worth noting that in this expression, d_p is the size of the smallest particle that will be collected if it starts at the inside edge of the inlet duct. Thus, in theory, all particles of size d_p or larger should be collected with 100% efficiency.

The preceding equation shows that, in theory, the smallest diameter of particles collected with 100% efficiency is directly related to gas viscosity and inlet duct width, and inversely related to the number of effective turns, inlet gas velocity, and density difference between the particles and the gas.

In practice, collection efficiency does, in fact, depend on these parameters. However, the model has a major flaw: It predicts that **all** particles larger than d_p will be collected with 100% efficiency, which is incorrect. This discrepancy is the result of all our approximations.

Lapple (1951) developed a semi-empirical relationship to calculate a "50% cut diameter" d_{pc} , which is the diameter of particles collected with 50% efficiency. The expression is:

$$d_p = \left[\frac{9 \cdot \mu \cdot b}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot N \cdot V_i \cdot (\rho_p - \rho_a)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

where d_{pc} = diameter of particle collected with 50% efficiency.

Note the similarity between the last two equations. The only difference is a factor 2 in the denominator. [4]

3. Work steps

For theoretical research regarding the influence of cyclone geometry with tangential inlet over the number of rotations that perform the heterogeneous mixture solid-gas in the outer vortex were used the cyclone dimensions resulting from the calculation and using AutoCAD.

Fig. 4 Notation for the physical construction of the cyclone

For dimensional calculating it was chosen an input speed of impure gas in the inlet pipe 15 m/s and a volume flow 0,111 m³/s. With this data we determined the size of the cyclones parts according to geometric similarity reports of a cyclone type chosen. Thus, parts of the cyclones size used in theoretical research are shown in table 1 and 2.

In calculations, for the dimensions of cyclones studied in theoretical research it was used the notation from Figure 4 and for calculating the number of revolutions and sedimentation time were used the relations (1) and (2).

It has used the following dimensions of the intermediate products resulting from the grist: big semolina= 1200 [mm]; middle semolina= 630 [mm]; small semolina= 400 [mm]; harsh dunst= 66 [mm]; soft dunst= 56 [mm]. [5]

Known parameters and formulas were introduced in Microsoft Office Excel 2003 and were calculated the numbers of revolutions that perform the heterogeneous mixture solid-gas in the outer vortex and the sedimentation time and the values obtained were recorded in table 1 and table 2.

Values obtained with varying the cylindrical part length

Table 1

<i>a [m]</i>	<i>H-h[m]</i>	<i>h[m]</i>	<i>N[rotations]</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>v_i</i>	<i>Δt[sec]</i>
0,122	0,488	0,244	4	0,244	20	0,153232
0,122	0,488	0,3	4,459	0,244	20	0,170816
0,122	0,488	0,35	4,8689	0,244	20	0,186516
0,122	0,488	0,4	5,2787	0,244	20	0,202216
0,122	0,488	0,488	6	0,244	20	0,229848

Values obtained with varying the conical part length

Table 2

<i>a [m]</i>	<i>H-h[m]</i>	<i>h[m]</i>	<i>N[rotations]</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>v_i</i>	<i>Δt[sec]</i>
0,122	0,488	0,244	4	0,244	20	0,153232
0,122	0,5	0,244	4,04918	0,244	20	0,155116
0,122	0,65	0,244	4,663934	0,244	20	0,178666
0,122	0,7	0,244	4,868852	0,244	20	0,186516
0,122	0,732	0,244	5	0,244	20	0,19154

4. Results and discussions

In calculations it was used an input velocity of 20 m/s. With data obtained it were drawn the charts of variation of the number of revolutions. In the first case, the length of the conical part of the cyclone it was keeping constant and it was

drawn the chart of variation of the number of revolutions with the cylindrical length of the cyclone, (Fig. 5). In the second case, the length of the cylindrical part of the cyclone it was keeping constant and it was drawn the chart of variation of the number of revolutions with the conical length of cyclone, (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5 Variation of the number of revolutions of the particles with the cylindrical part length of the cyclone

Fig. 6 Variation of the number of revolutions of the particles with the conical part length of the cyclone

For the theoretical research regarding the influence of cyclone dimensions over the sedimentation time depending on the velocity input in the cyclone, it was considering 5 values of the velocity input: $v_1=15$ m/s; $v_2=17$ m/s; $v_3=19$ m/s; $v_4=20$ and $v_5=22$ m/s. Also, it was

drawn the corresponding graphs for the first case of variation of the cylindrical cyclone length with the time sedimentation, seen in figure 7, and for the second case of variation of the conical cyclone length with the sedimentation time, seen in figure 8.

Fig. 7 Variation of sedimentation time with the input velocity depending on the length of the cylindrical part of cyclone

Fig.8 Variation of sedimentation time with the input velocity depending on the length of the conical part of cyclone

5. Conclusions

The literature in the field revealed that the number of parameters to be taken into account in designing a cyclone is numerous, including the type and geometry of the cyclone, the flow and geometry inlet.

According to the theoretical research, the number of revolutions of the particles is increases with the cylindrical and conical part length of the cyclone; this is resulting from the charts from figure 5 and 6.

From the chart of variation of time sedimentation with the input velocity it can be observed that sedimentation time is increased with the decreased of the velocity input in the cyclone. Also, it can be seen that the sedimentation time is decreased with the length of the conical or cylindrical part of the cyclone.

It was demonstrated theoretical that the smallest time sedimentation for the solid particles in the cyclone, it was obtained for a velocity input of 22 m/s for a cyclone with the length of conical and cylindrical part of 0,244 m.

References

1. Kegg, S.: *A numerical investigation of gas cyclone separation efficiency with comparison to experimental data and presentation of a computer-based cyclone design methodology*, Thesis, 2008.
2. Mokni, I., Dhaouadi, H. et al.: *CFD Simulation of the Flow Field in a Uniflow Cyclone Separator*, Engineering Letters, 2009.
3. Rus, Fl.: *Operații de separare în industria alimentară*, Editura Universității Transilvania, Brașov, 2001.
4. <http://engineering.dartmouth.edu/~cushman>.
5. Lupea, A. :*Tehnologii în industria alimentară*, Universitatea Tehnică, Timișoara, 1995.

Acknowledgement: This paper is supported by the Sectoral Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the contract number POS-DRU: *ID 59321*.

EFFECT OF INPUT VELOCITY OVER THE CYCLONE SEPARATION PROCESS

M. MARINUC*

Abstract: *Transport in air currents is a process that produces large amounts of dust. For this reasons, the research of separation process in the cyclones has become a necessity and a concern regarding the optimization of manufacturing process of various powdered food products. The input air velocity affects both the fan energy consumption and the dust collection efficiency. The objective of this paper is to demonstrate theoretically the influence of the input velocity into the cyclone over the collection efficiency. Also, the specific parameters of the installation transport in air currents are presented in this paper.*

Keywords: *input velocity, transport, cyclone separator, efficiency.*

1. Introduction

Given the need to further increase product quality resulting from industry and the tightening legislative activity, importance of studies and research on the separation of heterogeneous solid-gas mixtures in order to modernize the equipment of installations of the air becomes evident [1].

Initially, environmental pollution was only a natural process. As human activity has grown and diversified, the relationship between artificial and natural pollution has changed continuously. Currently, industrial pollution, urban and agricultural has become a serious problem that threatens not only the further development of the industry but threatening itself flora and fauna of the planet [2].

Cyclone is a component of dedusting installations, the most widely used in practice, mainly with the role to retain large industrial dust with very good efficiency and low cost and for very fine particles, can be a very beneficial first step of separation. Their simple design, low capital cost and nearly maintenance-free operation make them ideal for use as pre-cleaners for more expensive final control devices such as bag houses or electrostatic precipitators.

There are three primary reasons for separating gases from solids in solids processing: to minimize emissions for environmental purposes, to protect other processing equipment (turbines, etc.) from particle-laden streams, and to stop unwanted gas solids reactions from occurring. The efficiency of separation achieved by the

cyclone depends upon the nature of the process. If the process stream is dry and the particles are relatively large and free flowing, collection is relatively easy. If is not, or there is special chemistry or extreme temperature involved, particulate collection can be challenging [3].

The basis for many of the empirical separation efficiency models is the condition in which a particle of a particular size and density would orbit indefinitely around the axis of the cyclone [4].

The principle of separation in a cyclone is to increase the effect of sedimentation by centrifugal force, which is made by introducing tangential suspension in a device. The efficiency of separation cyclones is much higher than dusting rooms because in a centrifugal force field, the effect of separation is maximized.

In the case of cyclones, the effect of centrifugal force manifests itself differently from particles and gas. Due to centrifugal force the solid particles are thrown to the wall where they lose energy and fall moving under the action of gravity at the bottom of the device where it is discharged (particle mass > gas mass). So, gas is moving downward spiral, solid particles being driven to the top of the gas and then gas (air) is discharged through the central tube of the cyclone due to the circulation effect [5].

2. Specific parameters of the installation transport in air currents

2.1. Parameters of air carrier and material transported

In the transport technique in the air currents, air is considered as a blend of clean

* Dept. of Food Engineering, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: mimy_85@yahoo.com

air, water vapor and impurity components and in state sleep is characterized by the following physical parameters: pressure (static), temperature, humidity and heat content.

In technical calculations is neglecting the influence of humidity and the validity of the gas law is allowed to determine the density depending on the temperature and pressure. When comparing the results of calculations with measurements for various steady states are chosen so - called normal state, which is defined by the transport technique of: temperature $T_N = 293,16^\circ K$; pressure $P_N = 101325 Pa(N/m^2) = 1,01325 bar = 760mm col Hg$; relative humidity $\varphi = 50 \%$; density $\rho_N = 1,2 kg/m^3$.

The flow in pneumatic transport in food industry and agriculture is practically turbulent in all cases, velocity distribution in the cross section of pipeline being considered:

$$\frac{V_{med}}{V_{max}} = 0,84 \pm 0,04, \quad (1)$$

where: V_{med} și V_{max} are average and maximum velocity of current air.

Materials transported can be homogeneous (sugar, flour, cereals) or less homogeneous (sawdust, wood chips, mixed materials).

At the construction and calculation of extraction installations and pneumatic conveying will take into account the shape of the particles, their density, their size and destination of material to be transported [6].

2.2. Concentration of air-particle mixture

Mixture concentration is the weight of mass or volume of the particle in the mixture air-particle and is defined by:

- mass concentration: $c_m = \frac{m_p}{m}$, în kg/kg ;
- volumetric concentration: $c_v = \frac{V_p}{V}$, în m^3/m^3 ;
- dispersed solid density: $c_{mv} = \frac{m_p}{V}$, în kg/m^3 ,

where: c_m is the mass concentration; c_v - volumetric concentration; m_p , V_p - mass, respectively the volume of material in the mixture; m , V - mass, respectively the volume mixture of air-particle.

Depending on the material flow, velocity and density of the material, the section of the pipe, concentrations c_v and c_{mv} may be expressed by relations:

$$c_v = \frac{Q_{mp}}{S \cdot \rho_p \cdot V_p} [m^3/m^3], \quad (2)$$

$$c_{mv} = \frac{Q_{mp}}{S \cdot V_p} [kg/m^3], \quad (3)$$

where Q_{mp} is the mass flow of particles, and S - section of the pipeline.

Material laden air is:

$$\mu = \frac{Q_{mp}}{Q_{ma}}, \quad (4)$$

where Q_{ma} is the mass flow of air carrier.

2.3. Velocity of free fall

Velocity of free fall and floating rate of particles are parameters that define the aerodynamic characteristics to particle transport in air currents [6].

The two terms are defined as follows:

- **velocity of free fall** is the velocity of the particles become stationary (uniform) after the acceleration in a space where the air is at rest;
- **floating rate of particles** is air current speed rising, able to keep particles in suspension status.

For the calculation, is considering a particle of any kind placed in infinite space, where the air is at rest. It is assumed that the particle has traveled the acceleration space and makes a smooth motion. Direction of the particle will correspond with that one where the particle encounters the least resistance.

As figure 1, the equation of balance of forces acting on the particle is:

$$\overline{G} + \overline{F}_{as} + \overline{F}_p = 0, \quad (5)$$

where: \overline{G} is gravity force; \overline{F}_{as} - static buoyancy force; \overline{F}_p - pressure force is exerted on the particle surface.

Relation (5) can be written on components:

$$G = mg = \rho_p \cdot V_p \cdot g; \quad (6)$$

$$F_{as} = m' \cdot g = \rho_a \cdot V_p \cdot g; \quad (7)$$

$$F_p = F_\omega + F_{ac}, \quad (8)$$

where: m is the particle mass; m' - mass of air displaced by the particle; ρ_p și ρ_a - particle density, i.e. air density, in kg/m^3 ; V_p - particle

volume, in m^3 ; F_{ω} - resistance force acting on the direction of particle; F_{ac} - cinematic buoyancy force who acting perpendicular to the direction of the particle.

Fig. 1 Free fall of particles

For F_{ω} și F_{ac} can be written the following relations:

$$F_{\omega} = c_{\omega} \cdot A \cdot \frac{\rho_a \cdot v_d^2}{2} [N] \quad (9)$$

and

$$F_{ac} = c_a \cdot A \cdot \frac{\rho_a \cdot v_d^2}{2} [N], \quad (10)$$

where: c_{ω} is the coefficient of resistance force, which depends on $Re = \frac{v_d}{\nu}$ and particles form; c_a - cinematic buoyancy force coefficient; A - particle projection area in a plane perpendicular to the direction of travel; v_d - speed of the particle, in m/s ; ν - dynamic viscosity of air, $\nu = 1,85 \cdot 10^{-6} m^2/s$.

2.4. The general equation of motion of the particles

Particles transported in a straight airflow tended to orient so that the resistance to current is minimal.

The air swirls causes an oscillatory movement, favoring an alternative game between the force of air and inertia that gives bodies a pendulum movement or rotation.

The general equation of motion of particles driven by a current of air (figure 2) is:

$$\vec{G} + \vec{F}_{as} + \vec{F}_r + \vec{F}_{\omega} + \vec{F}_{ac} = 0, \quad (11)$$

where:

$$F_{\omega} = c_{\omega} \cdot A \cdot \frac{\rho_a}{2} |\bar{v}_a - \bar{v}_p|^2; \quad (12)$$

$$F_{ac} = c_a \cdot A \cdot \frac{\rho_a}{2} |\bar{v}_a - \bar{v}_p|^2,$$

where: G is gravity force; F_{as} - static buoyancy force; F_r - resistance force due to collisions between particles and pipe wall friction; F_{ω} - driving force equal to the resistance that opposes the air flow; v_a - average velocity of turbulent air flow at the point where the particle is; v_p - velocity of the particle; F_{ac} - cinematic buoyancy

Fig. 2 Motion of particles of any form

In most cases it is considered that the pressure force F_p acting on the center of gravity of the particle.

In the case of particles of any form, from the forces specified is get an oscillatory motion which forming a boundary layer which increases the mass amount of rotation, close to the spherical [6].

3. Collection efficiency

The principle of separation in a cyclone is to increase the effect of sedimentation by centrifugal force, which is made by introducing tangential suspension in a device. The efficiency of separation cyclones is much higher than dusting rooms because in a centrifugal force field, the effect of separation is maximized.

In the case of cyclones, the effect of centrifugal force manifests itself differently from particles and gas. Due to centrifugal force the solid particles are thrown to the wall where they lose energy and fall moving under the action of gravity at the bottom of the device where it is discharged (particle mass > gas mass). So, gas is moving downward spiral, solid particles being driven to the top of the gas and then gas (air) is discharged through the central tube of the cyclone due to the circulation effect [5].

Cyclone efficiency characterizes its ability to retain from fluid environment the solid particles

of a certain minimum size required. At the same cyclone, changing the particle density and fluid viscosity, changes its efficiency. To retain the minimum of particles diameter required is necessary to align the input speed of the fluid in the cyclone with product characteristics (density of the medium, particle density, and viscosity) and constructive parameters of the cyclone.

Efficiency of solids separation in a cyclone has typical value of 70-80%, but if the fluid is loaded with large amounts of solids, separation efficiency exceeds 99%.

Stairmand (1951) described the collection efficiency curve which indicates the efficiency of the cyclone for separating particles of given density over a range of sizes. This curve is also known as the grade efficiency curve.

Researchers over the years have produced a number of predictive models that use empirical information related to the geometry and operating conditions of specific cyclone designs and are intended to estimate cyclone collection efficiency. Leith (1984) summarized a number of these models. His list included models by Stairmand (1951), Barth (1956), Lapple (1951) and Leith and Licht (1972). Ogawa (1984) also

reviewed a number of predictive models including Lapple and Shepherd (1940), Barth (1956) and Stairmand (1951) [7].

4. Material and Method

The cyclone dimensions used in theoretical research were derived from dimensional calculation and design using AutoCAD. For dimensional calculating it was chosen an input speed of impure gas in the inlet pipe 15 m/s and a volume flow 400 m³/s. With this data was determined the size of the cyclone parts according to geometric similarity reports of a cyclone type chosen. In figure 3 it can be observed the geometry of the cyclone with tangential entry.

To calculate cyclone efficiency have used the relationship given by Leith and Litch (1972). The Leith and Licht(1972) model predicts the grade efficiencies based on the concept of continual radial back mixing of the uncollected particles, and on the calculation of an average residence time for the gas in the cyclone [8]. The Leith and Licht equation proposed and used in this theoretical research is:

$$\eta = 1 - \exp \left\{ -2 \left[\frac{\left(\frac{\pi \cdot D^2}{4} \cdot h \cdot \frac{\frac{\pi \cdot D^2}{4} \cdot (h-s) + \frac{\pi \cdot D^2}{4} \cdot \left(\frac{\ln+s-h}{3} \right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{d}{D} + \frac{d^2}{D^2} \right) - \frac{\pi \cdot D e^2 \cdot \ln}{4}}{8 \cdot \frac{D^3}{a \cdot b}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \cdot \left(\frac{\rho \cdot d_p^2 \cdot v}{18 \cdot \mu \cdot D} \right) \cdot 1,5 \right] \right\} \cdot 100 \quad (13)$$

Fig. 3 Cyclone with tangential entry:
 1 - cylindrical body; 2 - cone-shaped body; 3 - outlet of solids particle; 4 - outlet of gas; 5 - gas supply hole doped.

In relation (13), η is the efficiency of the cyclone; D – diameter cylindrical body, $D = 0,250$ m; h – upper height of the cyclone, $h = 0,56$ m; s – depth of penetration of purified gas hose, $s = 0,28$ m; ln - natural length of cyclone, m; De - outer diameter of central tube exhaust gas purified, $De = 0,122$ m; ρ - solid particle density, a – height of the cyclone inlet, $a = 0,122$ m; b- width of the cyclone inlet, $b = 0,061$ m; $\rho = 1110$ kg/m³; μ - gas mixture viscosity; $\mu = (37.4 + 0.506 \cdot T) \cdot 10^{-5}$, $T = 293$ [K]; d_p - dimensions of particles, m; v - the average inlet velocity, m/s.

For theoretical investigation regarding the influence of the input velocity in the cyclone

over the separation process efficiency were used six input velocity values: $v_1=13$ m/s; $v_1=15$ m/s; $v_1=17$ m/s; $v_1=20$ m/s; $v_1=22$ m/s; $v_1=25$ m/s and a constant particle size of 0.000056 m.

Known parameters and formulas were introduced in Microsoft Office Excel 2003.

In table 1 are recorded the values obtained by calculating the separation efficiency with the relationship given by Leith and Licht (1972) for the six input velocity values listed above according to the five values of the cyclone inlet section: $S_1 = 0,001575$ m²; $S_2 = 0,002912$ m²; $S_3 = 0,004928$ m²; $S_4 = 0,006608$ m² and $S_5 = 0,007440$ m².

Table 1

Separation efficiency values depending on the input velocity in cyclone

v [m/s]	dp [m]	η_1 [%] ($S_1=0,001575$)	η_2 [%] ($S_2=0,002912$)	η_3 [%] ($S_3=0,004928$)	η_4 [%] ($S_4=0,006608$)	η_5 [%] ($S_5=0,00744$)
13	0,000056	74,917	78,561	71,635	66,796	64,755
15	0,000056	76,556	80,115	73,329	68,537	66,506
17	0,000056	77,961	81,437	74,789	70,049	68,031
20	0,000056	79,740	83,098	76,650	71,993	69,997
22	0,000056	80,758	84,041	77,721	73,121	71,141
25	0,000056	82,090	85,266	79,131	74,615	72,660

5. Results and discussions

The graph from figure 4 shows that the lowest efficiency was obtained to velocity input of 13 m / s and section area inlet $S_5 = 0.0074$ m², while for a velocity input of 25 m / s and a section area inlet $S_2 = 0.002912$ m² cyclone has reached a separation efficiency of 85,266 %. Also, it can be observed that the degree of separation in

centrifugal field is increased with the increases of input velocity in the cyclone.

The chart showed the effect of input velocity in cyclone over the separation efficiency. It can be noting that for the cyclone with the inlet section $S_2 = 0.002912$ m², the degree of separation is higher for any value of the input velocity unlike other sections of inlets cyclone.

Fig.4 Variation of separation efficiency with input velocity in cyclone

6. Conclusions

According to the theoretical research, the separation efficiency is better with as the input velocity in cyclone is higher and the cyclone inlet section is smaller.

To retain the minimum of particles diameter required is necessary to align the input speed of the fluid in the cyclone with product characteristics (density of the medium, particle density, and viscosity) and constructive parameters of the cyclone.

References

1. Vișan, S., Angelescu, A., Alpopi, C., *Mediul înconjurător – poluare și protecție*, Ed. Economică, București, 2000.
2. Julieta Florea, Dan Robescu, *Hidrodinamica instalațiilor de transport hidropneumatic și de depoluare a apei și a aerului*, București.
3. T. M. Knowlton: *Handbook of Fluidization and Fluid-Particle Systems*, Edited by Wen-Ching Yang, ISBN: 978-0-8247-0259-5, 2003.
4. Leith, D. Cyclones. In M. E. Fayed, L. Otten (Eds.): *Handbook of Powder Science and Technology*. (pp.730-745). City: Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, 1984.
5. Ivan, E., Craiu, I., Onița, N.: *Operații și aparate în industria alimentară*, Editura Mirton, Timișoara, 2003.
6. Brătucu, Ghe., *Mașini de ridicat și transportat în industria alimentară și agricultură*, Editura Universității Transilvania, Brașov, 2011.
7. Kegg, S.: *A numerical investigation of gas cyclone separation efficiency with comparison to experimental data and presentation of a computer-based cyclone design methodology*, Thesis, 2008.
8. Kuo and Tsai *On the theory of particle cutoff diameter and collection efficiency of cyclone*, Aerosol and air quality research, vol. 1, no.1, 2001.

Acknowledgement: This paper is supported by the Sectoral Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the contract number POS-DRU: ID 59321

DETERMINING THE TEMPERATURE AND MOISTURE DISTRIBUTION IN APPLE SLICES DURING THE DRYING PROCESS

A.-M. NUÑEZ VEGA*

W. C. HOFACKER*

Abstract: *The quality of dried products mainly depends on temperature and moisture content changes during the drying process, as they govern the quality determining reactions that take place during dehydration. The temperature and moisture fields developing in the drying material during drying can be determined by solving the governing differential equations. They describe the heat and mass transport in the material and on its surface. For the determination of the temperature and moisture distribution, a lumped parameter model of the drying material was established, using discretization and calculation methods known from aerospace engineering. These methods are originally used for simulation and design of thermal control systems of space- and aircraft. The paper describes these methods as well as the simulation results for the drying process. It provides information on the dependency of heat and mass transport coefficients on local temperature and moisture content. Finally, the results are compared to experimental results obtained in a previous study.*

Keywords: *convective drying, heat and mass transfer, mathematical modeling, lumped parameters.*

1. Introduction

Most biological products are dried using hot air forced convection - a very energy intensive process that is responsible for up to 25% of national industrial energy consumption in the developed countries.¹ Due to economic and environmental reasons it is aimed to minimize energy demand. Furthermore there is a increasing demand for high quality dried products that retain their natural appearance.²⁻⁵ As the quality of the drying process is a function of drying time, product quality and energy consumption, for process optimization all three aspects have to be accounted for.⁶ An instrument for design can be computational fluid dynamics and numerical simulations of coupled heat and mass transfer within the product. They facilitate the prediction of the most convenient drying conditions if the dependency of the product's drying behavior on process conditions is known. Convective drying of fruits and vegetables is a complex process involving simultaneous coupled heat and mass transfer within the drying material and at the boundary to the drying air. Extensive research has been directed towards mathematical prediction of the drying process of biological materials. Barati and Esfahani⁷ stated that over 200 drying models for various foods had been offered in literature until 2009. The status of food

process modeling and models for safety, quality, and competitiveness of the food processing sector was the topic of a workshop held in 2006 and summarized and edited by Datta in 2008.⁸⁻¹⁶ Puri and Anantheswaran¹⁷ as well as Wang and Sun¹⁸ give a comprehensive overview of the use of the Finite-Element Method in food processing and developments in numerical modeling of heating and cooling processes in the food industry. There are also numerous more recent papers on simulation and modeling in the food industry, for fruits and vegetables,¹⁹⁻²⁶ meat,²⁷ bread,^{28,29} and coffee³⁰ to mention a few. However, the coupled heat and mass transfer is so complicated, that no universally applicable model has been formulated to describe the drying process for all biological materials. Most of the approaches presented in literature provide simplifying assumptions. Shrinkage is often neglected and/or thermo-physical properties are assumed to be constant.^{7,21,25,26,31-34} In addition most published work in literature about mathematical modeling of the drying process of foodstuffs does not differentiate between mass transfer in liquid and gaseous state.^{22-26,31,35} The present work deals with the simulation of apple drying, as apples are the most consumed fruit in several western countries³⁶ and their consumption is on the rise in many other countries, too. An example for this is China, with a per capita consumption of 19 kg

* Department of Thermal Process Engineering, HTWG Konstanz, Germany, e-mail: Anna.NunezVega@htwg-konstanz.de

in 2004 and an upward trend.³⁷ A multitude of publications on simulation of apple drying can be found,^{31,33,35,38-47} although only Lin et al.⁴⁶ proposed an approach similar to the model presented in this paper, but for the simulation of a novel simultaneous infrared dry blanching and dehydration (SIRDBD) process. In the work presented, a lumped parameter model of the drying material was established, using

discretization and calculation methods known from aerospace engineering. The aim of this study was to develop a model that takes into account temperature and moisture dependent material and transport properties, shrinkage and mass transfer occurring in liquid and gaseous states respectively.

2. Mathematic model

In order to solve the coupled partial differential equations describing simultaneous heat and mass transport within the drying material, apple slices are discretized in nodes, representing the finite elements of the problem area. The apple slice

geometry as shown in figure 1 therefore was segmented into 31 nodes, of which for clarity reasons only 9 are depicted. Figure 2 shows a schematic sectional view through the drying material.

Fig. 1. Segmentation of an apple slice into nodes

Fig. 2. Schematic sectional view through the drying material

The nodes are treated as isothermal, and also as of uniform moisture content. By this means, the governing partial differential equations can be transformed into a system of non-linear equations, which is solved by using an implicit forward backward differencing method (Crank-Nicholson method).

In this work, the following assumptions are made:

- one-dimensional heat and mass transfer within the drying material
- transport of water vapor within the drying food is not negligible
- heat, liquid and vapor fluxes can be described with identical mathematical approaches
- shrinkage is not negligible
- material properties are assumed to be functions of local moisture content and temperature
- sample consists of nodes that are treated as isothermal and as of uniform moisture

With respect to heat transfer, three different nodes can be distinguished:

i. Diffusion nodes D have a thermal capacity C that is calculated from the specific heat c and the mass of the node consisting of the mass of the dry matter M_{dm} and the moisture in liquid and gaseous state M_w :

$$C = c \cdot (M_{dm} + M_w) \quad (1)$$

ii. Arithmetic nodes D° differ from diffusion nodes, as they do not have a thermal capacity.

iii. Boundary nodes B are characterized by having a constant temperature

Each node can interchange heat, water and vapor with the adjacent nodes, except the arithmetic nodes at the edges, because no liquid water but vapor passes to the drying air. An internal source of heat HI can be allocated to every node allowing for taking into account loss of heat caused by phase transition.

Heat transfer

The nodes are coupled through conductors describing heat conduction as well as heat transfer through convection. Their conductance values are calculated in different ways:

$$G_{cond} = \lambda \cdot \frac{A}{h} \quad (2)$$

$$G_{conv} = \alpha \cdot A \quad (3)$$

In these equations, h is the distance between coupled nodes and A the heat exchange area. As heat transfer is assumed to occur only perpendicularly to the direction of airstream

conductive heat flow between nodes \dot{H}_j and convective heat transfer at the lower and upper surface \dot{H}_s can be described as follows:

$$\dot{H}_j = \lambda_j \cdot \frac{A}{h} \cdot (\theta_j - \theta_{j+1}) = G_j \cdot (\theta_j - \theta_{j+1}) \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{H}_{sl} = k_H \cdot \alpha \cdot A \cdot (\theta_a - \theta_{sl}) = G_{sl} \cdot (\theta_a - \theta_{sl}) \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{H}_{su} = \alpha \cdot A \cdot (\theta_{su} - \theta_a) = G_{su} \cdot (\theta_{su} - \theta_a) \quad (6)$$

In Equation (4) λ_j means a mean thermal conductivity calculated with the average temperature and moisture content of the involved nodes. The convective boundary conditions at the upper surface are different from those on the lower surface. The apple slices lay on a grid reducing heat and mass transfer at the lower surface. This is accounted for by the parameter k_H , which has to be < 1 . The drying surface is represented by an arithmetic node and the drying air by a boundary node.

Mass transfer

Analogue to heat conduction, liquid moisture fluxes \dot{M}_w are assumed to be proportional to a constant of proportionality, namely the liquid diffusivity κ_j , that determination is explained in equation (16). The driving force is the difference in moisture content between adjacent nodes. With respect to particle density ρ_{pj} liquid moisture streams going from node j to j+1 are calculated:

$$\dot{M}_{wj} = \kappa_j \cdot \rho_{pj} \cdot \frac{A}{h} \cdot (X_j - X_{j+1}) \quad (7)$$

At the drying surface water stream (liquid state) is zero.

Water vapor transport is described by Fick's law of diffusion. This is a valid assumption, as water vapor pressure within hygroscopic materials is low compared to ambient pressure. Therefore, the unidirectional diffusion can be approximated to

the stationary equimolar case with a water vapor pressure difference ($P_{vj} - P_{vj+1}$) as the driving force:

$$\dot{M}_{vj} = \mu_j \cdot \delta_{va} \cdot \frac{A}{h} \cdot \left(\frac{P_{vj} - P_{vj+1}}{R_v \cdot T_j} \right) \quad (8)$$

In this approach, R_v is the individual gas constant for water vapor, T_j is the mean absolute temperature, and δ_{va} is the mean diffusion coefficient for water vapor in air (diffusion is not hindered) of involved nodes. The internal resistances abating vapor diffusion are summarized in the resistant coefficient μ_j ⁴⁸.

The convective boundary conditions for heat transfer and vapor streams leaving the drying material at the lower and upper surface are given by:

$$\dot{M}_{vsl} = k_M \cdot \beta \cdot \frac{P^\circ}{P_{vsl} - P_{va}} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{P^\circ - P_{va}}{P^\circ - P_{vsl}} \right) \cdot \frac{A}{R_v \cdot T_{sl}} \cdot (P_{va} - P_{vsl}) \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{M}_{vsu} = \beta \cdot \frac{P^\circ}{P_{vsu} - P_{va}} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{P^\circ - P_{va}}{P^\circ - P_{vsu}} \right) \cdot \frac{A}{R_v \cdot T_{su}} \cdot (P_{vsu} - P_{va}) \quad (10)$$

The parameter k_M is introduced considering lower mass transfer at the lower surface. As no mass transfer but heat exchange can take part where the apple lies on the grid, k_M has to be < 1 , and also smaller than k_H . T_{sl} and T_{su} are mean values between surface and air temperature, P_{vsl} and P_{vsu} are water vapor partial pressures at the lower and upper surface and P_{va} is the water vapor pressure of the drying air.

The water vapor partial pressures within the drying material are determined by means of moisture sorption isotherms. This is valid if two conditions are complied:

- i. water activity within the drying material is identical to relative humidity
- ii. relationship for sorption isotherm can be applied for parts of the drying material

In this case water vapor pressure partial pressure in node j is calculated from water activity a_{wj} and saturation pressure:

$$P_{vj} = a_{wj} \cdot P_v^\circ \quad (11)$$

Heat transfer through phase transition

During convective drying, water vapor diffuses into regions of higher temperatures. Therefore recondensation can be excluded. Due to heat of vaporization of water h_{evap} and heat of sorption h_{sorp} the difference of vapor streams entering and

leaving the node ($\Delta \dot{M}_j = \dot{M}_j - \dot{M}_{j-1}$) leads to a loss of heat HI_j within a node:

$$HI_j = \Delta \dot{M}_j \cdot (h_{evap} + h_{sorp}) = \Delta \dot{M}_j \cdot h_{tot} \quad (12)$$

3. Numerical techniques

The lumped parameter model provides algorithms to solve the heat transfer problem numerically. The thermal system is brought into a stable state with respect to the energy balance for every iteration loop. The new temperatures of diffusion nodes $\theta_{j,new}$ (and arithmetic nodes, considering $C = 0$) are calculated using the following equation:

$$\sum_j^n G_j \cdot \left(\frac{\theta_{j,new} - \theta_{j,old}}{2} - \frac{\theta_{j+1,new} - \theta_{j+1,old}}{2} \right) + HI_j = C_j \cdot \frac{\theta_{j,new} - \theta_{j,old}}{2} \quad (13)$$

The software allows implementing individual FORTRAN code. It is executed either before, or after every iteration step. This is the key to integration of mass transfer into the model. It also allows determining material and transport properties with temperatures and moisture content calculated in the last iteration loop. While new nodal temperatures are determined by the thermal software, new moisture masses are calculated by producing a mass balance for every node:

$$M_{wj} = M_{wj}^{old} + (\dot{M}_{wj} + \dot{M}_{vj}) \cdot dt - (\dot{M}_{wj+1} + \dot{M}_{vj+1}) \cdot dt \quad (14)$$

4. Parameters used in the model

In this work relationships found in literature as well as empirically determined ones were applied (Table 1).

Thermal conductivity

There is a wide variation of reported experimental data of thermal conductivity of foodstuffs. Saravacos and Maroulis⁴⁹ evaluated

information given in literature statistically, and suggested an empirical mathematical model for calculating thermal conductivity in foods as a function of moisture content X and absolute temperature of the drying material T:

$$\lambda(X, T) = \frac{1}{1+X} \cdot 0.287 \cdot e^{\left(-1390 \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{333}\right)\right)} + \frac{X}{1+X} \cdot 0.589 \cdot e^{\left(-285 \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{333}\right)\right)} \quad (15)$$

Heat and Mass Transfer coefficients

A common approach in practical engineering is applied, expressing the heat transfer coefficients without dimension via Nusselt-number (as a function of Reynolds- and Prandtl-number) and the mass transfer coefficient via Sherwood-number (as a function of Reynolds- and Schmidt-number). Depending on the flow condition, they are calculated by different empirical equations.

Mass transport coefficients

As the approaches in literature do not differentiate between mass transfer in liquid and gaseous state, an empirical equation for liquid

diffusivity was established. It takes into account its temperature as well as moisture dependency and comprises three parameters:

$$\kappa(\theta, X) = a_1 \cdot \theta \cdot \left[1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{X}{a_2} \right)^{a_3} \right] \right] \quad (16)$$

The resistance coefficient is assumed to be moisture dependent and the diffusion coefficient for water vapor in air reflects temperature dependency. For the resistance coefficient a similar approach to liquid diffusivity was developed, whereas an empirical equation for the diffusion coefficient was given by Schirmer.⁵⁰

$$\mu(X) = b_1 \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{X}{b_2} \right)^{b_3} \right] \quad (17)$$

$$\delta_{va}(\theta) = \frac{2.26}{P^\circ} \cdot \left(\frac{\theta + 273.15}{273.15} \right)^{1.81} \quad (18)$$

Table 1. Variables used in the model

variable	equation	
Particle density ⁴⁰	$\rho_p = \frac{1+X}{\frac{1}{1690} + \frac{X}{999}}$	$\left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \right]$
Saturation pressure ⁵¹	$P_v'' = 133.289474 \cdot 10^{\left(\frac{7.5 \cdot \theta}{\theta + 237.3} + 0.6609 \right)}$	[Pa]
Specific heat ⁵²	$c = 1750 + 2500 \cdot \frac{X}{1+X}$	$\left[\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{K}} \right]$
Water activity ⁵²	$a_w = 1 - \exp \left[- 0.0002926 \cdot (\theta + 288.4) \cdot \left(\frac{\ln \left(\frac{X - 0.08502}{0.001347} \right)}{0.4861} \right) \right]$	[-]
Heat of sorption ⁵²	$h_{\text{sorp}} = 1.2 \cdot 10^6 \cdot e^{\left(-\frac{X}{10} \right)}$	$\left[\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}} \right]$

Shrinkage

Assuming that the decrease of drying material volume is equal to the volume of water removed, a linear approach describing shrinkage can be applied. Experimental results⁶ showed that the average ratios of shrinkage were 0.34 for thickness (h_x/h_0) and 0.84 for diameter (d_x/d_0), leading to different equations:

$$h(X) = h_0 \cdot \left(0.66 \cdot \frac{X}{X_0} + 0.34 \right) \quad (19)$$

$$d(X) = d_0 \cdot \left(0.16 \cdot \frac{X}{X_0} + 0.84 \right) \quad (20)$$

5. Results and discussion

In order to determine the empirical constants used in the equations for transport coefficients, the drying curves simulated were adjusted to experimental data provided by Sturm⁶ who examined the drying behavior of apples, variety Jonagold in a wide parameter range. An experiment with drying parameters in the middle

of the parameter space was chosen to fit calculated data. Once the empirical parameters were determined, the model was verified by comparing predicted drying curves with experimental ones using different process parameters. The parameters found are listed in the Notations. It was also examined if the influence of temperature, velocity and relative humidity of drying air are all reproduced correctly by the model.

Transport properties

As shown in Figure 3, liquid diffusivity has got a maximum at high moisture content. Inside the apple slices there is a continuous liquid film preventing vapor diffusion completely. As drying proceeds moisture content decreases leading to a microstructural change that is responsible for increasing transport resistance. At very low moisture content mass transport in liquid state is negligible as equalizing between the cells stops. In this range of moisture content vapor diffusion becomes the crucial transport mechanism. Pores become empty, allowing vapor to move through the emerging hollows. Both transport phenomena are enforced by temperature.

Fig. 3. Mass transport coefficients as function of moisture content for different temperatures

Drying curves

Figures 4 and 5 represent the drying behavior as a function of temperature θ_a and velocity w_a respectively, the parameters which have the greatest influence on the drying process. Those parameters have been varied according to the

available experimental data. Dew point temperature or humidity of air respectively has little effect on drying characteristics in the range investigated.⁶ Figure 4 shows the predicted and experimentally determined drying curves for different air temperatures (35°C, 60°C and 85°C), whereas velocity and dew point temperature were held constant ($w_a = 3.4 \text{ m/s}$,

$\theta_{dp} = 17.5^\circ\text{C}$). As reported by Sturm⁶ air temperature has the most significant influence on drying time. Drying time can be shortened considerably by increasing air temperature due to the higher temperature difference between the drying surface, and air leading to a higher amount

of heat being transferred to the drying material. Increasing product temperature also leads to higher water vapor pressures within the product, and consequently convective mass transfer increases.

Fig. 4. Predicted and experimental determined drying curves for different air temperatures θ_a

Fig. 5. Predicted and experimental determined drying curves for different air velocities w_a

The effect of air temperature on reduction of drying time is higher at low temperatures than at high temperatures, if changing temperature for the same amount. Additionally, product quality can deteriorate significantly if exceeding product specific temperature limits. The model shows high accuracy over the whole range of moisture content and temperature. Figure 5 depicts predicted and experimental drying curves at different air velocities (2.0 m/s, 3.4 m/s and 4.8

m/s) but constant temperature ($\theta_a = 60^\circ\text{C}$) and dew point temperature ($\theta_{dp} = 17.5^\circ\text{C}$). Qualitatively the influence of air velocity on drying behavior is similar to that of temperature. Increasing air velocity reduces drying time significantly. This effect decreases with higher velocities. Air velocity influences transfer coefficients at the drying surface. For calculating Nusselt- and Sherwood-number (Nu, Sh) Reynolds-number (Re) is used being proportional

to velocity. Again predicted data shows a high degree of accuracy. Therefore it can be assumed, that the model reproduces the physical effects correctly.

Temperature

Figure 6 shows the predicted and experimental measured upper surface temperature of food as a function of relative moisture content X/X_0 . Air properties were constant and equal to 60°C, 3.4

m/s and 17.5°C for temperature, velocity and dew point temperature. At the beginning of the drying process surface temperature rapidly increases to wet bulb temperature ($\approx 30^\circ\text{C}$). After this warm-up stage temperature increase is significantly reduced due to the cooling effect caused by evaporation at the surface. When moisture content falls below approximately 10% of the initial content, temperature rises again and approaches that of air temperature.

Fig. 6. Predicted and experimental measured upper surface temperature θ_{su}

According to Pavón-Melendez et al.⁵³, predicted temperature differences between the drying surface and interior are marginal as Biot-number is < 1 during the whole drying process. The heat is transferred rapidly into the interior, as the apple slices are quite thin. Because of shrinkage,

the initial thickness of only 3.8 mm is even reduced to nearly one third during the drying process. Figure 7 shows the predicted moisture content for different times as function of dimensionless height, which takes into account shrinkage.

Fig. 7. Predicted moisture distribution for different times of drying

The upper surface of the apple slices dries much faster than the lower one. Especially at the beginning of the drying process moisture is unequally distributed and after about 40 minutes the upper surface layer tends to equilibrium moisture content, whereas the lower one still contains 70% of the initial moisture content. In the final stages of drying moisture distribution gets more and more symmetric. After about 120 minutes, the lower surface layer reaches equilibrium moisture content, and the drying process is increasingly controlled by internal resistances.

6. Conclusions

The present work introduces a lumped parameter model describing coupled heat and mass transfer phenomena. With respect to most work published in literature, the main innovation introduced by this study was to differentiate between mass transfer in liquid and gaseous state. Shrinkage and dependency of thermo physical properties on

temperature and moisture content was also taken into account. The mathematical model enables the prediction of moisture content as a function of time within the examined range of process parameters with high accuracy. It was shown that the influences of external drying parameters are predicted correctly. At the same time, it enables the prediction of moisture content as well as temperature at different depths in the slab of apple slices at different drying times. Further investigation is necessary, as the present model neglects three dimensional transport phenomena, local heat and also mass transfer coefficients, and traces back shrinkage only to moisture content, but not to geometry. Due to ambiguous heat and mass transfer conditions at the lower surface of the apple slices, further experimental data excluding these uncertainties should be generated. Then a second verification of the model with this data can be executed. Later on, quality aspects might be simulated and integrated into the model as well, as they mostly depend on temperature and moisture content.

7. Notation

A	exchange area	m^2
a_w	water activity in food	-
c	specific heat of food	$J/(kg \cdot K)$
C	thermal capacity of food	J/K
d	diameter of apple slices	m
G	conductance value	W/K
h	height of a node	m
h_{evap}	heat of evaporation	J/kg
h_{sorp}	heat of sorption	J/kg
h_{tot}	total heat of evaporation	J/kg
M	mass	kg
\dot{M}_i	mass flow	kg/s
P_v	water vapor partial pressure	Pa
P°	system pressure	Pa
\dot{H}_i	heat flow	W
HI	loss of heat (evaporation)	W
X	moisture content (dry basis)	kg_w/kg_{dm}

Greek Symbols

α	heat transfer coefficient	$W/(m^2 \cdot K)$
β	mass transfer coefficient	m/s
δ_{va}	diffusion coefficient (vapor in air)	m^2/s
θ	food temperature	$^\circ C$
κ	liquid diffusivity	m^2/s

λ	thermal conductivity of food	$W/(m \cdot K)$
μ	diffusion resistance coefficient	-
ρ_p	particle density of food	kg/m^3
φ	relative humidity of air	-

Subscripts

0	initial
a	air
dm	dry matter
l	lower side
s	surface
u	upper side
v	vapor
w	water (liquid state)

Empirical Constants

$k_H = 0.10$	heat transfer
$k_M = 0.35$	mass transfer
$a_1 = 6.5e-12$	liquid diffusivity (magnitude)
$a_2 = 2.0$	liquid diffusivity (location)
$a_3 = 1.1$	liquid diffusivity (slope)
$b_1 = 0.008$	diff. resistance coeff. (magnitude)
$b_2 = 2.0$	diff. resistance coeff. (location)
$b_3 = 2.0$	diff. resistance coeff. (slope)

References

1. Mujumdar, A. S.: *Drying Symposium Series (IDS): A personal perspective*. Drying Technology 17 (1-2), xi–xx (1999).
2. Fernandes, F. A. N., Rodrigues, S., Law, C. L., Mujumdar, A. S.: *Drying of Exotic Tropical Fruits: A Comprehensive Review*. Food Bioprocess Technol 4 (2), 163–185 (2011).
3. Krokida, M., Tsami, E., Maroulis, Z.: *Kinetics on color changes during drying of some fruits and vegetables*. Drying Technology 16 (3-5), 667–685 (1998).
4. Kiranoudis, C. and Markatos, N.: *Pareto design of conveyor-belt dryers*. Journal of Food Engineering 46 (3), 145–155 (2000).
5. Nijhuis, H., Topping, H., Muresan, S., Yuksel, D., Leguijt, C., Kloek, W.: *Approaches to improving the quality of dried fruit and vegetables*. Trends in Food Science & Technology 9 (1998).
6. Sturm, B., *Einfluss der Führung des Trocknungsprozesses auf den Trocknungsverlauf und die Produkteigenschaften empfindlicher Biologischer Güter*. Forschungsbericht Agrartechnik 491 des Arbeitskreises Forschung und Lehre der Max-Eyth Gesellschaft Agrartechnik. VDI (VDI-MEG) (2010).
7. Barati E. and Esfahani J., *Analytical Modelling of The Transport Phenomena on Temperature and Moisture History of Food During Drying Process*. Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems. Croatia (2009).
8. Banga, J. R., Balsa-Canto, E., Alonso, A. A.: *Quality and Safety Models and Optimization as Part of Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*. Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safety 7 (1), 168–174 (2008).
9. Black, D. G. and Davidson, P. M.: *Use of Modeling to Enhance the Microbiological Safety of the Food System*. Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safety 7 (1), 159–167 (2008).
10. Datta, A.: *Status of Physics-Based Models in the Design of Food Products, Processes, and Equipment*. Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety 7 (1) (2008).
11. Datta, A. K. and Halder, A.: *Status of food process modeling and where do we go from here (Synthesis of the outcome from brainstorming)*. Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safety 7 (1), 117–120 (2008).
12. Ivester, R. W.: *Productivity Improvement through Modeling: An Overview of Manufacturing Experience for the Food Industry*. Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safety 7 (1), 182–191 (2008).
13. Jousse, F.: *Modeling to Improve the Efficiency of Product and Process Development*. Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safety 7 (1), 175–181 (2008).
14. Marks, B. P.: *Status of Microbial Modeling in Food Process Models*. Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safety 7 (1), 137–143 (2008).
15. Sablani, S. S.: *Status of Observational Models Used in Design and Control of Products and Processes*. Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safety 7 (1), 130–136 (2008).
16. van Boekel, M. A. J. S.: *Kinetic Modeling of Food Quality: A Critical Review*. Comp Rev Food Sci Food Safety 7 (1), 140–158 (2008).
17. Puri, V. and Anantheswaran, R.: *The finite-element method in food processing: A review*. Journal of Food Engineering 19 (3), 247–274 (1993).
18. Wang, L. and Sun, D. W.: *Recent developments in numerical modelling of heating and cooling processes in the food industry - a review*. Trends in Food Science & Technology 14, 311–323 (2003).
19. Toğrul, H.: *Simple modeling of infrared drying of fresh apple slices*. Journal of Food Engineering 71 (3), 311–323 (2005).
20. Lagunez-Rivera, L., Ruiz-López, I. I., García-Alvarado, M. A., Salgado-Cervantes, M. A.: *Mathematical Simulation of the Effective Diffusivity of Water during Drying of Papaya*. Drying Technology 25 (10), 1633–1638 (2007).
21. Bonis, M. V. de and Ruocco, G.: *A generalized conjugate model for forced convection drying based on an evaporative kinetics*. Journal of Food Engineering 89 (2), 232–240 (2008).
22. Janjai, S., Lamlert, N., Intawee, P., Mahayothee, B., Haewsungcharern, M., Bala, B. K., Nagle, M., Leis, H., Müller, J.: *Finite Element Simulation of Drying of Longan Fruit*. Drying Technology 26 (6), 666–674 (2008).
23. Janjai, S., Lamlert, N., Intawee, P., Mahayothee, B., Haewsungcharern, M., Bala, B., Müller, J.: *Finite element simulation of drying of mango*. Biosystems Engineering 99 (4), 523–531 (2008).

24. Janjai, S., Mahayothee, B., Lamlert, N., Bala, B., Precoppe, M., Nagle, M., Müller, J.: *Diffusivity, shrinkage and simulated drying of litchi fruit (Litchi Chinensis Sonn.)*. Journal of Food Engineering 96 (2), 214–221 (2010).
25. Oztop, H. F. and Akpinar, E. K.: *Numerical and experimental analysis of moisture transfer for convective drying of some products*. International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer 35 (2), 169–177 (2008).
26. Kaya, A., Aydın, O., Demirtaş, C.: *Experimental and theoretical analysis of drying carrots*. Desalination 237 (1-3), 285–295 (2009).
27. Diéguez, P. M., Beriain, M. J., Insausti, K., Arrizubieta, M. J.: *Thermal Analysis of Meat Emulsion Cooking Process by Computer Simulation and Experimental Measurement*. International Journal of Food Engineering 6 (1) (2010).
28. Purlis, E. and Salvadori, V. O.: *Bread baking as a moving boundary problem. Part 2: Model validation and numerical simulation*. Journal of Food Engineering 91 (3), 434–442 (2009).
29. Purlis, E.: *Bread baking: Technological considerations based on process modelling and simulation*. Journal of Food Engineering 103 (1), 92–102 (2011).
30. Nilnont, W., Thepa, S., Janjai, S., Kasayapanand, N., Thamrongmas, C., Bala, B.: *Finite element simulation for coffee (Coffea arabica) drying*. Food and Bioproducts Processing (2011).
31. Jun, W., Jing-ping, Z., Jian-ping, W., Nai-zhang, X.: *Modeling Simultaneous Heat And Mass Transfer For Microwave Drying On Apple*. Drying Technology 17 (9), 1927–1934 (1998).
32. Queiroz, M. and Nebra, S.: *Theoretical and experimental analysis of the drying kinetics of bananas*. Journal of Food Engineering 47 (2), 127–132 (2001).
33. Bravo, J., Sanjuán, N., Ruales, J., Mulet, A.: *Modeling the Dehydration of Apple Slices by Deep Fat Frying*. Drying Technology 27 (6), 782–786 (2009).
34. Barati, E. and Esfahani, J.: *Mathematical modeling of convective drying: Lumped temperature and spatially distributed moisture in slab*. Energy 36 (4), 2294–2301 (2011).
35. Białobrzewski, I.: *Simultaneous Heat and Mass Transfer in Shrinkable Apple Slab During Drying*. Drying Technology 24 (5), 551–559 (2006).
36. Aprikian, O., Levrat-Verny, M.-A., Besson, C., Busserolles, J., Rémésy, C., Demigné, C.: *Apple favourably affects parameters of cholesterol metabolism and of anti-oxidative protection in cholesterol-fed rats*. Food Chemistry 75 (4), 445–452 (2001).
37. Blanke, M. M.: *Obstbau in China*, UWSF - Z Umweltchem Ökotox 17 (2), 64–65 (2005).
38. Chiang, W.-C. and Petersen, J. N.: *Experimental Measurement Of Temperature And Moisture Profiles During Apple Drying*. Drying Technology 5 (1), 25–49 (1987).
39. Vergara, F., Amézaga, E., Bárcenas, M. E., Welti, J.: *Analysis of the Drying Processes of Osmotically Dehydrated Apple Using the Characteristic Curve Model*. Drying Tech. 15 (3), 949–963 (1997).
40. Krokida, M. K., Kiranoudis, C. T., Maroulis, Z. B., Marinos-Kouris, D.: *Drying Related Properties Of Apple*. Drying Technology 18 (6), 1251–1267 (2000).
41. Lewicki, P. P. and ŁUKASZUK, A.: *Changes Of Rheological Properties Of Apple Tissue Undergoing Convective Drying*. Drying Technology 18 (3), 707–722 (2000).
42. Moreira, R., Figueiredo, A., Sereno, A.: *Shrinkage Of Apple Disks During Drying By Warm Air Convection And Freeze Drying*. Drying Technology 18 (1-2), 279–294 (2000).
43. Doymaz, İ.: *An Experimental Study on Drying of Green Apples*. Drying Technology 27 (3), 478–485 (2009).
44. Wang, Z., Sun, J., Liao, X., Chen, F., Zhao, G., Wu, J., Hu, X.: *Mathematical modeling on hot air drying of thin layer apple pomace*. Food Research International 40 (1), 39–46 (2007).
45. Verma, L. R., Bucklin, R. A., Endan, J. B., Wratten, F. T.: *Effects of drying air parameters on rice drying models*. Transactions of the ASABE 1985 28, 296–301 (1985).
46. Lin, Y. L., Li, S. J., Zhu, Y., Bingol, G., Pan, Z., McHugh, T. H.: *Heat and Mass Transfer Modeling of Apple Slices Under Simultaneous Infrared Dry Blanching and Dehydration Process*. Drying Technology 27 (10), 1051–1059 (2009).
47. Putranto, A., Chen, X. D., Webley, P. A.: *Modeling of Drying of Food Materials with Thickness of Several Centimeters by the*

- Reaction Engineering Approach (REA)*.
Drying Technology 29 (8), 961–973 (2011).
48. Krischer, O. and Kast, W.: *Die wissenschaftlichen Grundlagen der Trocknungstechnik*. 3rd ed. (Springer Verlag, Berlin, 1978).
49. Saravacos, G. D. and Maroulis, Z. B.: *Transport properties of foods*. (Marcel Dekker, New York, 2001).
50. Schirmer, R.: *Diffusionszahl von Wasserdampf-Luftgemischen und die Verdampfungsgeschwindigkeit*. VDI Beiheft Verfahrenstechnik 6, 176–177 (1938).
51. Tetens, O.: *Über einige meteorologische Begriffe*. Geophysik 6, 297–309 (1939).
52. Hugenschmidt, S., *Simulation des Transportes von Wärme und Feuchte in einer trocknenden einseitig überströmten kapillarporösen Platte*. Bachelor Thesis. University of Applied Science Konstanz (2010).
53. Pavón-Melendez, G. H. J. A., Salgado M. A., García, M. A.: *Dimensionless analysis of the simultaneous heat and mass transfer in food drying*. Journal of Food Engineering 51 (4), 347–353 (2002).

RESEARCHES REGARDING TEMPERATURE EVOLUTION IN TWO WAREHOUSES WITH DIFFERENT CONTROL SYSTEMS OF THE CLIMATIC FACTORS

C.G. PAUNESCU*

Abstract: *In this paper is presented the temperature variation in two potato warehouses, which uses two different systems for controlling and monitoring the climatic factors, respectively, in one warehouse is used an automatic system for controlling and monitoring the temperature, produced by the Dutch company OmniVent, and in the other one a mechanical system for air ventilation. In both warehouses the potatoes are stored in boxes on a height on maximum 4 meters and the conditioned air flow is introduced through the perforated floor. The researches were done during the months of December 2010 – April 2011.*

Keywords: *potato, temperature adjustment, warehouse.*

1. Introduction

Warehouses for fruits and vegetables that exists worldwide are very different from a country to another depending on the climatic conditions, the economic possibilities, the production organization etc. The main classification criteria for warehouses are:

- after the storing conditions in the depositing space: without automatic adjustment systems for climatic parameters and with automatic adjustment system for climatic parameters;
- after the nature of the stored merchandise and the specific activities inside the warehouse during a year: specialized for different fruits or vegetables and universal(in which are stored many products);
- after the constructive type: mono-pavilions and multi-pavilions;
- after the dotage degree with machinery and technical equipments for climatic control, conditioning etc.: simple and improvised, which are not having any equipments and also, are not representing constructions adequate for storing technological request; specialized warehouses without equipments; modern warehouses which have an adequate construction and all the installations and equipments necessary;
- after the thermal solution used for the warehouse cells climatic control: with centralized installation; with individual installation for each cell;

- after the automating degree: without automatic installation; with installation which assures the determination of the parameters which are involved in the storing process; with installations which assures the monitor, the control and the automatic adjustment of the storing parameters.

The functional scheme of a warehouse provided with mechanical ventilation without climatic installations is presented in Figure 1. From de storing cells 1, the vicious air is aspired through the canal 2 and the pipe 3, by the ventilator 8. The fresh air is repressed by the ventilator 7, after was prior passed through the heat exchanger 6 and the humidifier 5. The ventilation and the recirculation regime is realized through the valves 4, which are manipulated by the command device 9 [1,3].

The advantages of the mechanic ventilation warehouses refers to: in the autumn months the warehouses can be used to potatoes pre-silage, which can be subdue to some drying through introducing an air flow of 15...18 °C, which contribute to wound healing and permits storing heights which can reach up to 4 m, permitting in this way a better space use; during summer the warehouse can be used to drying other agricultural products, especially the grains; is realized a judicious uniformity of temperature and humidity; the water condensation is avoided [2].

*Dept. of Eng and Manag. in Food and Tourism, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: catalin.paunescu85@yahoo.com

Fig 1 Warehouse with mechanical ventilation system[1]

The disadvantages of the mechanic ventilation warehouses consists, on one hand in the fact that the storing parameters (temperature and humidity) can't be controlled, and on the other hand the air flow mix can't be adjusted properly.

For eliminating the heat, the carbon dioxide and the water emitted by the products which are stored in bulk is necessary that through the entire product mass to permanently pass a cold airflow. This supposes an air circulation system from floor to ceiling, uniform distributed in the products mass [1, 2].

The mixing is realized in different proportions regarding the products temperature and humidity, so the airflow temperature which is introduced in the ventilation canals to be with maximum -0.5 °C smaller. In specialized literature is recommended that the airflow temperature in the ventilation canals to be smaller that the products mass temperature with $3..6$ °C. Is important to determine the temperature inside the ventilation canals and regarding this data to operate the airflow admission flaps.

2. Material and Method

The measurements were held in the period December 2010 – April 2011, covering in this way the entire period of potatoes existence in the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet- Brasov warehouse, in which the measurements were done.

To offer confidence to the measurements, these were done in every week at the same hour, each parameter being determined ten times and eliminating in this way the possible measurements errors.

The most important parameters in the case of this type of warehouse (temperature and humidity) were measured using a portable thermo-anemometer type VT 300 (fig. 2) manufactured by the French company KIMO. To this device were attached the following instruments: the anemometer with chatterbox which uses a Hall effect sensor (fig. 3); the hot wire anemometer which uses a thermo resistance with negative temperature factor; the hygrometer with capacitive element; the thermocouple penetration probe type SFP-K (fig. 4).

Fig.2 - VT 300 Portable Thermo-Anemometer[4]

Fig.3 - Anemometer type LV 107[4]

Fig.4 - Thermocouple Penetration Probe Type SFP-K[4]

The temperature of the airflow which is introduced by the ventilators through the perforated floor was measured with the anemometer type LV 107. Temperature and humidity are of great importance because they can compromise the potatoes situated near the ventilation holes. That is way it is recommended that before starting the ventilation system to measure the outside air temperature.

Fig.5 -Fluke 568 Infrared Termometer[5]

This device is having a spectral response between 8...14 μm and it can measure temperatures between $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$... $+850\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a accuracy of: $\pm 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ from the displayed value in -

50 °C ...-20 °C interval; $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.5\%$ from the displayed value in -20 °C ...+200 °C interval; $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2\%$ from the displayed value in 200 °C ...+538 °C interval; $\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3.5\%$ from the displayed value in 538 °C ...850 °C interval. The display resolution is of 0.1 °C [5].

To eliminate the measurement errors of these parameters it was waited three minutes before the

first determination. This time was considered sufficient so: the ventilation cycle was covered completely at least one time; the electric engine of the ventilator to reach the nominal power; the temperature of the air introduced through the perforated floor to be the real one and not the temperature of the existing air before the ventilator start.

Fig. 6. Automatic adjustment system

Also, there were measured the temperatures of the walls, the floor and the warehouse ceiling with a infrared thermometer type Fluke 568 (fig. 5).

In the modern warehouse, with automatic systems for controlling and monitoring the temperature were acquired 1530 values, distributed through 130 days. These data were measured by Ni-Cr Type K sensors placed inside the storage cells and recorded in a database as Excel files by the OptiLink application, which is a component part of the automatic temperature adjustment system produced by OmniVent. (fig.6).

This application permits to monitor the climatic factors and to change the parameters of the controllers which are connected to Opticon, its interface realizing a serial communication between the computer and the controllers. Sent and received data can be printed, used to make graphs and stored in a database. An interesting feature of this application is the fact that the user can create its own interface with settings, measurements and calculations considered important to him.

3. Results and Discussions

The temperature values for each week were systemised and for each month was done their average. In table 1 are written the temperature values recorded in the warehouse with mechanical ventilation system, in the warehouse with automatic control systems for the climatic factors and the exterior temperature which was measured by a sensor connected to the automatic control system of the second warehouse

In the case of the warehouse without automatic control systems, the temperature was measure every 1 meter and in table 1 is written the average of these values. Because the values recorded by the Dutch system were numerous (1530 values for the interior temperature, respectively 1600 for the exterior temperature), they were first processed statistical with the Dataplot software and afterwards written in table 1.

Table 1

Average temperatures for the measured period

	Months in which measurements took place				
	December	January	February	March	April
Temp.In. Mechanical Ventilation System, °C	4	4,7	4,1	3,8	11,2
Temp. In. Automatic Control System, °C	2,54	2,13	2,05	4,54	6,75
Exterior Temp., °C	-6,98	-4,4	-3,53	2,18	8,6

Data from table 1 were represented graphic in figure 5. In can be observed that during the months of December 2010 – March 2011 in the both warehouses is maintained a temperature situated in the optimal storage interval for potato, with the specification that in the modern warehouse the temperature is kept at the lower limit of the interval, while in the other warehouse the temperature is kept at the upper limit of the interval.

This situation is modified beginning with April, when the exterior temperature is rising and the warehouse with mechanical ventilation system can't assure anymore a constant optimal temperature. As it can be seen there exists a proportional factor between the slopes of these two temperatures. Also, in the modern warehouse the temperature is rising, but with a slower rate and the reason for this increase is the fact that the seeding seasons approaches and the temperature of the tubers which are incorporated in ground must be at least of 7...9 °C

Fig. 7. Temperature variation on a 5 month period

In figure 7 with the blue line is represented the temperature inside the mechanical ventilation

warehouse, with red line the temperature inside the modern warehouse and with green line the exterior temperature.

4. Conclusions

In a climate resemble to the one in Brasov area, in the cold winter-spring months, the potato storage can be done successfully in warehouses without automatic control systems for monitoring and controlling the climatic factors. It is recommended for the producer economic efficiency, that in the cold periods to store potatoes in warehouses which have only mechanical ventilation, or if they are stored in modern warehouses to close the temperature control systems and use only natural or mechanical ventilation.

A modern warehouse with automatic adjustment systems is justified in the harvest moment when the outside temperature is high and it is recommended to decrease the temperature of the potato mass, but also in warm spring months when the potato seed must be kept at a specific temperature.

Acknowledgements:

This paper is supported by the Sectorial Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the contract number POSDRU/6/1.5/S/ ID 59321

References

1. Bratucu, Gh., s.a.: *Transportul intern, manipularea și depozitarea produselor agroalimentare*, Editura Universității Transilvania din Brașov, 2010.
2. Paunescu C.G., Bratucu, Gh.: *Climatic factors measurement in a warehouse without automatic control systems*, Bulletin of the Transilvania University, Series II, Vol.4, No.1/2011, Brasov, Romania.
3. Brătucu, Gh., Păunescu C. : *Contribution to perfecting temperature automatic adjustment systems in vegetables and fruits warehouses*, Research Journal of Agricultural Science, Vol.42, p 570-576, Timisoara, 2010.
4. <http://www.kimo.fr/> Accessed: 5.03.2011
5. <http://www.fluke.com/> Accessed: 20.03.2011

IS POTATO STORING IN WAREHOUSES WITH TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEMS ECONOMICAL EFFICIENT?

C.G. PAUNESCU* **GH. BRATUCU****

Abstract: Nowadays due to the global energy crisis the price of electricity is increasing year after year. Because potato are resistant vegetables and their selling price is low, in this paper it will be discussed if storing potato in modern warehouses, with automatic climatic installation is more efficient from an financial point of view comparing to storing potato in warehouses without climatic factors adjustment installations.

Keywords: heat, potato, storage.

1. Introduction

The big variance of temperature, light, oxygen, moisture or the lack of water vapours but also the natural enzyme of potatoes, after a certain period of time, tends to deteriorate the products. Potatoes, which are perishable products, need certain storage conditions, which will be taken into account when the quality politics is elaborated. It is recommended to avoid: to heavy and voluminous stacks; natural light impact over stored potatoes; high temperatures.

The expiration dates of stored products will be permanently monitored by updating the products inputs and outputs database. Periodically inspections are made for evaluating the potatoes health. If the products had suffered quality deterioration, they must be isolated immediately from the other products.

It must be taken into account that these products are having a high water content, which can lead to big losses during their storage. In Table 1 are specified the medium losses at potatoes storage during October-March in different types of warehouses.

Table 1

Warehouse type	Weight medium losses, [%]	Weight losses limits, [%]
Ditches in the ground	25.0	8,8...30.3
Huts	17.8	15.0...18.0
Cellars	17.0	12.0...21.3
Modern warehouses	13.8	13.4...14.2

The functional scheme of a warehouse with mechanical ventilation and without automatic control system for the climatic factors as the one in which the measurements were made is presented in Figure 1. The vertical canals 8 permits directing the atmospheric air flow. The air control system is made through its introduction from the warehouse exterior by the ventilator 1.

The air enters the warehouse through the opening placed in the leading canals 10 or through the variable dimension canals existing in the perforated floor 6. Because cold air is introduced inside the warehouse a part of the hotter existing air is cooled and

another part is evacuated through the warehouse ceiling. The other notations in Figure 1 are having the following signification: 2- routing air flow flap; 3 - excess air evacuation orifice; 4 – air recirculation flap; 5 – ventilation hole; 6 – perforated floor (with variable openings); 7 – ventilation hole to exterior; 8 – air vertical directing canal; 9 – air horizontal directing canal, under the floor; 10 – air flow directing canals; 11 – ventilation hole. In figure 2 is presented the scheme of a warehouse with a temperature adjustment system, which receives cold air from a cooling unit, air which is ventilated trough the perforated

*Dept. of Eng and Manag. in Food and Tourism, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: catalin.paunescu85@yahoo.com

**Dept. of Eng.and Manag. in Food and Tourism, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: gh.bratucu@unitbv.ro

floor and then eliminated through the upper side of a lateral wall [1,2].

Fig. 1. Warehouse with mechanical ventilation system[1]

Fig. 2. Warehouse with temperature control system [5]

The advantages of warehouses with mechanical ventilation are: in the autumn months the warehouses can be used to pre storing potatoes, which can be subdue to drying by introducing an air flow of 15...18 °C, which contributes to wound healing and permits storage heights that can reach 4 m so, in this way, the warehouse space is optimal used; during summer the warehouse can be used to drying other agricultural products; a uniform temperature and humidity is realized; water condensation is avoided.

The disadvantages of warehouses with mechanical ventilation consist, on the one hand, in the fact that the storing climatic parameters (temperature, humidity, air composition) can't be controlled and, on the other hand, the air mixture can't be adjusted proper [1],[4].

For eliminating heat, carbon dioxide and water emitted by the potatoes stored bulk is

necessary that through the stored products mass to pass permanently a cold air flow. This supposes an air circulation system from the perforated floor to the ceiling, uniform distributed in the products mass.

Factors which determine potatoes storage necessity are:

- the technical factor which imposes the important deliveries and making some operations which require a certain time and a special technical endowment: conditioning, packaging, labelling, marking, loading, sending, receiving;
- the economic factor- synchronizes the agricultural products input with the consume rhythm, maintains products stocks into an optimal volume for using space and assures the necessary structure for market supplying continuity with necessary products.

The potatoes nutritive value and their characteristics during the storing period must be

maintained, their decrease under certain limits meaning that their introduction into the food chain is impossible [3].

2. Material and Method

To make the calculations was considered a medium store cell with a capacity of 930 tones. This is a 24 m long by 18 m wide building with 6.5 mm eaves height and 15° pitch roofs. The U-values for the roof, walls and floor are 0.25, 0.32 and 0.36 W/m²°C. Was assumed an air leakage of 0.5 air changes per hour, two air distributions fans of 2.0kW each running continuously to circulate the store air. From specialized literature was considered that the potato respiration heat is of 10W/t at a storage temperature of 3.5°C [3].

The total consumed energy for maintaining a constant storage temperature is a sum of 5 factors which will be explained in detail.

The first factor is heat gain by conducting through the building fabric. The higher the outside temperature, the larger the plant cooling capacity will be needed. For the considered U – values and the storage cell dimensions at a

temperature difference of 13 °C, it will be used equation (1) to calculate the total heat gained.

The title must be as short possible. If necessary, a subtitle is provided.

$$H_{bf} = U \cdot A \cdot \Delta T. \quad (1)$$

Applying equation (1) to the buildings walls, floor and ceiling it will be obtained the heat flow for each element:

- for the walls representing the wide
 $H_{bfw} = 0.32 \cdot 139 \cdot 13 = 578.2 W;$

- for the walls representing the length:
 $H_{bfl} = 0.32 \cdot 156 \cdot 13 = 648.9 W;$

- for the floor:
 $H_{bff} = 0.36 \cdot 432 \cdot 13 = 2021.7 W;$

- for the ceiling:
 $H_{bfc} = 0.25 \cdot 447 \cdot 13 = 1452.7 W.$

By adding these values it is obtained the heat gain through building fabric:

$$H_{bfTOT} = 578.2 \cdot 2 + 648.9 \cdot 2 + 2021.7 + 1452.7 = 5928.2 W.$$

The second parameter is the heat gained due to air leakage and is calculated using equation (2):

$$H_{al} = \rho \cdot C_p \cdot q \cdot \Delta T, \quad (2)$$

where: ρ is the density of air, $\rho = 1.23 \text{ kg/m}^3$; C_p – the specific heat of air, $C_p = 1.005 \text{ kJ/kg}$; q – the air flow, $q = 0.5 \text{ air changes/h}$; ΔT – the temperature difference, $\Delta T = 13 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

For the considered storage cell with a volume of 3336 m³ it will be obtained:

$$H_{al} = 1.23 \cdot 1.005 \cdot \frac{3336 \cdot 0.5}{3600} \cdot 13 = 7.44 \text{ kW}$$

The third parameter is the heat gained due to electrical equipment operating in the warehouse (for 4 fans of 2 kW power each, with a 70 % efficiency):

$$H_f = 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 0.5 = 4 \text{ kW}$$

The fourth parameter is the heat produced by potato respiration and is calculated considering the respiration rate found in specialized literature for a 3.5 °C storage temperature with equation (3):

$$H_{pot} = \frac{\text{Mass of potato} \cdot \text{Respiration rate} \left(\frac{W}{t}\right)}{1000}. \quad (3)$$

Considering the storage is at full capacity (930 t) and the respiration rate is 10 W/t, the heat produced by potato is:

$$H_{pot} = \frac{930 \cdot 10}{1000} = 9.3 \text{ kW}$$

The final parameter refers to removing the heat from the crop after harvest with a rate of 0.5 °C per day to avoid any risk of subsurface condensation. This can be used for calculating the necessary energy during the first month of storage and through a period of 6 months storage time to consider that the installation had malfunctions which will add another 20 days of heat removing from the stored mass with the same rate of 0.5 °C per day. This parameter is calculated with equation (4):

$$H_{rhc} = \frac{m \cdot 1000 \cdot c \cdot \delta T}{t}, \quad (4)$$

where: m is the mass of stored potato (t); c – the specific heat of potato, $c = 3.80$ kJ/kg; δT – the temperature reduction over cooling period, $\delta T = 0.5$ °C; t – time of cooling period, $t = 24$ h.

The heat which must be removed to cool the crop is :

$$H_{rhc} = \frac{930 \cdot 1000 \cdot 3.8 \cdot 0.5}{24 \cdot 3600} = 20.45 \text{ kW}.$$

By adding these parameters the total heat which must be removed is:

$$H_{total} = H_{bfTOT} + H_{al} + H_f + H_{pot} + H_{rhc} = 5.93 + 7.44 + 4 + 9.3 + 20.45 = 47.12 \text{ kW}$$

In Brasov area for a storage period of 6 months (October 2011...March 2012) with a total of 183 days the parameters will be divided as follow due to regional climate and the medium length of removing heat from potato. In these conditions for 51 days all the parameters exists, in 91 days the fifth and second parameters misses (during

the moths of December, January and February the average outside temperature is close or a little bit lower than the storage temperature) and in the remaining 41 days only the fifth parameter misses, the total heat which must be is calculated with relation (5):

$$H_{total} = 24(91 \cdot (H_{bfTOT} + H_f + H_{pot})) + 51 \cdot (H_{bfTOT} + H_{al} + H_f + H_{pot} + H_{rhc}) + 41 \cdot (H_{bfTOT} + H_{al} + H_f + H_{pot}) \quad (5)$$

Introducing the calculated values for the considered case, the total cooling load which must be removed is:

$$H_{total} = 24(91 \cdot (5.93 + 4 + 9.3)) + 51 \cdot (5.93 + 7.44 + 4 + 9.3 + 20.45) + 41 \cdot (5.93 + 7.44 + 4 + 9.3) = 125303 \text{ [kW]}.$$

Considering that the cooling system is modern and has a high efficiency it will be needed a total electrical energy of 34800 kWh.

an average value of 0.4 RON/kWh is 13920 RON without VAT [6].

3. Results and Discussions

From table 1 it can be seen that a in modern warehouse with systems for controlling only the temperature the medium weight losses are of 13% while in old warehouses the losses are of 18%. So there exists a difference of 5 %.

As it can be seen the difference is not big and can vary from case to case event to the point of making the storage of potato in modern warehouses less profitable than in warehouses with mechanical ventilation systems.

This difference means 46.5 t of potato which is loss in an old warehouse comparing to a modern one. In March, the price of potato in Romania for large quantities varied between 0.3 RON and 0.5 RON per kg. For an average of 0.4 RON per kg that means that the losses costs are of 18600 RON [7].

Use clear ideas, short sentences, and standard terminology. Special characters, symbols, and measure units must comply with the standards in use.

For an industrial consumer according to the official price list [5] the cost varies due to several parameters between 0.3...0.6 RON/kWh. So, the electrical energy consumed for maintain a constant temperature (only for cooling) costs, for

Also it must be noted that 2011 was a very good year for potato crop in Romania, fact which lowered the potato price very much comparing to year 2010 when the potato prices reached at the end of March 2011 between 1...1,5 RON per kg. So for a year like 2010 the advantage of using a modern warehouse is obvious, the profit being 2...3 times bigger in the case of modern warehouse.

4. Conclusions

1. Storing fruits or vegetables in modern warehouses has its advantages in terms of crop

losses due to storage, but also due to the supplementary energy consumption in years with large quantities of products in the market the use of cooling installations for maintaining a constant temperature can reduce the producer profits.

2. In years with large quantities of potato in the market is recommended for the producers to use the cooling installation only for lowering the potato mass temperature and afterwards to use only the ventilation system.

3. For fruits or vegetables with a bigger perishable degree than potato, the use of modern warehouses is obvious and it has good results, but in the case of potato, due to his natural resistance to storage a modern warehouse with complete automatic systems for controlling the climatic factors in the actual context of Romania is open for discussion and influenced very much of the potato production in the respective year.

Acknowledgements:

This paper is supported by the Sectorial Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the contract number

POSDRU/6/1.5/S/ ID 59321

References

1. Brătucu, Gh., s.a.: *Internal Transport, Manipulation and Storage of the Agroalimentary Products*, Transilvania University Publishing House, 2010.
2. Păunescu C.G., Brătucu Gh.: *Research Regarding Temperature Determination in Different Zones of Warehouses for Fruits and Vegetables*, In 3rd International Conference "Advanced Composite Materials Engineering", p 188-191, 2010.
3. Pringle, B., Bishop, C., Clayton, R.: *Potatoes Postharvest*, CABI Publishing House, 2009
4. Rastovski, A., van Es, A., et.al.: *Storage of potatoes*, Centre for Agricultural Publishing and Documentation, Wageningen, 1981.
5. <http://www.aardappelpagina.nl>
Accessed on 15.03.2012
6. <http://www.eon-energie.ro/ro/eon-moldova-furnizare/agenti-economici/tarife-energie/>
Accessed on 10.04.2012
7. [www.piata-agricola.ro/Piata cartofului](http://www.piata-agricola.ro/Piata_cartofului)
Accessed on 10.04.2012

ADIABATIC COOLING OF SOLUTIONS OF FOOD PRODUCTS: EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

A. SOKOLENKO O. BOYKO *

Abstract: *Research of the adiabatic cooling of solutions with the different concentration of dry matters was conducted. The curves of cooling of solutions are got. Influence of content of dry matters on finish temperature and speed of the adiabatic cooling was investigation. On the basis of experimental data analytical dependence is certain which describe this process.*

Keywords: *adiabatic cooling, speed of cooling, vacuum, solution.*

1. Introduction

Cooling substance without change of enthalpy all system has names adiabatic cooling. Fall in temperature liquid or sold as a result of evaporation from phase separation surface without heat application from external influence most famous example of this process. Type of adiabatic cooling what caused by boiling stream of materials has called adiabatic boiling. This thing originates after making underpressure above surface of the liquid.

At achievement of such value of absolute pressure, at what value of temperature of boiling of liquid it will be below than temperature of solution, there is his "effervescence".

Evaporation part of water what contains in stream of materials has result lessening of energy liquid or sold what remain. It has result in a fall in temperature liquid or sold.

We can find enough information about dynamics fall in temperature food products under the terms of adiabatic cooling in literary source. It does disallow full value measure of use and rationales parameters of process what contains adiabatic boiling.

2. Experimental stand

Experimental stand what represent on figure 1 was develop for realization this research.

At first part of experiment sample 2 put within vacuum-chamber 1. Next step is potting of vacuum-chamber 1 and turning on vacuum pump 6. Value of vacuum in vacuum-chamber is keeping within limits 0.94-0.96 atm. (residual

Fig. 1. An experimental stand is for determination of intensity of the adiabatic cooling

- 1 – vacuum-chamber,
- 2 – sample what must be investigating,
- 3 – module for summation and convert type of signal,
- 4 – module for converts type of digital signal,
- 5 – PC, 6 – rotary vacuum pump,
- 7 – manometer, 8 – adapter.

pressure 0.06 – 0.04 atm.). Value of pressure was checking according to manometer 7 on-scale indication.

Thermocouples were distributed in volume of experiment sample 2. Vacuum-chamber 1 has especial hole for thermocouples. Hole obturated hermetically.

We using eight thermocouple simultaneously for taking temperature of solution in research to

* Dept. of Technical mechanics and packing engineering, *National University of Food Technologies*, Kyiev, Ukraine, e-mail: mif63@i.ua

the effect that reduce uncertainty of measurement temperature such as systematical data precision takes from thermocouples. Data that taking from thermocouples are average when measuring result was taking during of experiment purposely find average temperature in reservoir.

For making experiment we use copper-constantan thermocouples. They have working interval of temperature between -185°C and $+300^{\circ}\text{C}$. They are better for interval of temperature that has liquid that be research. Relative error measurement about 0.5 – 1.0 % for interval of temperature between 0°C and $+125^{\circ}\text{C}$ what means that absolute error not more that 1 Celsius degree.

Electromotive force (voltage) that emergent in place of contact (solder) thermocouple transferred across the module 3 and 4 to PC. Module # 3 converts analog signal to digital signal and summation signals from eight thermocouples to one signal. Module # 4 converts digital signal from thermocouples to type understandable to PC. Values of temperature that take during research save into file on PC. This file have format «*.txt» and we can processing this values by means of program for mathematical analysis such as MathLab, MathCAD etc. Results of processing are graph «time – temperature», «time – speed of cooling» etc.

Experiment has some repeat (five – seven time) with intention reduction influence accidental error on results of a experiment. We took value of temperature in reservoir with solution for every repeat. Value of temperature took from thermocouple average separately for every repeat.

We used special development program which average value of temperature. Necessity development and write this program is determine specific character of working module # 3, that we use in experiment. This module took signals from thermocouples not at the same time. We have delay 0.1 s between two adjacent thermocouples.

When we making average we using assumption that temperature change like linear chart between two adjacent points.

3. Results and Discussion

At first part of experiment we determined distilled water rate of cooling by adiabatic boiling. We are compared received results with well-known given from literary source. On the

basis of this comparison drawn conclusion about adequacy (rightness) of results which turn out at the conducted researches

Fig. 2. Dependence of change temperature of the distilled water to pressure above the surface of division of phases
1 - Experimental data 2 -Theoretical data

Theoretical curve 1 resulted on figure 2 it is built on the basis of data found in literary sources [17, 49]. Horizontal fragment of curve 1 on figure 2 responds to the condition when a temperature of solution is less than than temperature of boiling of solution at present in a vacuum chamber pressure. Sloping fragment of curve 1 answers the process of the adiabatic boiling of solution. Vertical it's cooling due to a heat exchange with an environment. From figure 2 clearly evidently, that experimental and theoretical curve (line 1 and 2 accordingly) on the fragment of flowing of the adiabatic boiling coincide fully. It allows drawing conclusion about adequacy of results which were got on the basis of this method of realization of experiment.

On the next stage of research influence of permeates, their molar mass was analysed, and accordingly and osmolality in solution, on the change of temperature of the adiabatic boiling of solvent, speed of the adiabatic cooling and eventual temperature of solution after completion the process of the adiabatic boiling.

For realization of these researches undertook 20 % solutions of salt, fructose, sucrose and control one. In quality control to the standard was taken the distilled water.

Curves which represent time-history temperature of solutions at the adiabatic boiling brought around to figure 3 (continuous lines) are got.

On the initial stage of experience the

temperature of solution does not almost change. The gradual cooling of solution takes place in the consequence of heat exchange with an environment. In this time absolute pressure goes down in a chamber. A value of pressure is

anymore from that which is answered by beginning of the adiabatic boiling of solution at a current temperature. This stage of research answers the horizontal fragment of chart 1 that represented on figure. 2.

Fig. 2 A change of temperature of solutions is at the adiabatic boiling

1 - Distilled water 2 - 20-ty % solution of fructose 3 - 20-ty % solution of sucrose 4 - 20-ty % solution of salt

The second stage begins from the moment of when pressure in the chamber of dilution will ripen that size at which, the process of the adiabatic boiling of solution begins. Beginning of boiling process is accompanied by beginning of evaporation of liquid phase which in turn causes the active decline of temperature of solution. It is caused by that the warmth of vaporization on a few orders anymore at heat capacity solution.

From a chart brought around to figure 4.4 evidently, that the third phase of process begins at achievement of temperature which answers an adiabatic boiling point at remaining pressure in a vacuum chamber solution. The temperature of solution goes down farther, as well as in the first phase of process, due to a heat exchange with an environment and thermal radiation.

The diagram of change of speed of cooling of solution at the adiabatic boiling is made inquiries to figure 4

Cooling of solutions is caused by two processes which take place simultaneously. For the first cooling predetermined by the process of heat exchange with an environment through the external surface of capacity, and for the second - it is arisen up at evaporation of solvent during the adiabatic boiling.

Analyzing the got chart it is necessary to mark that cooling speed, as a result of heat exchange with an environment, not considerable. On the average solution cools down less than on 0,1 °C. In the same time, beginning of process of the adiabatic boiling of solution instantly increases this speed to 2,7 - 3,6 °C. Cooling intensity is most in a few first seconds. Intensity diminishes farther. It the caused diminishing of motive force of process, namely differences are between the temperature of solution and temperature of beginning of the adiabatic boiling which answers absolute pressure present in a chamber in this moment of time.

At implementation of previous researches an analysis was conducted with the use of array of data of got from thermocouples. It costs to mark that the value of temperature turns out every tenth of second. It creates the considerable array of data on working of which the far of time and (or) resources of the computing engineering is spent. By an alternative there is the use of graphic methods of analysis or being of analytical dependences which can adequately describe this process it.

Using of graphic methods of determination of

speed of cooling of solutions for the adiabatic boiling has specific defects. A main defect is not high exactness of the got results and presence of human factor. The last shows up in exactness of realization of lines at implementation of calculations. In addition, for realization of graphic analysis it is needed to have exact graphic arts of curves of change of temperature of solution in time which needs realization of far of experimental experiments.

The attempt of receipt of analytical dependence which adequately would describe a change temperature of solution at the adiabatic boiling for the decision of this problem was executed.

The analysis of the got charts of change of temperature of solution in time was executed by means of mathematical program "Origin". This program gives possibility to the search of equalization of dependence which passes through the set points. There is plenty of heterogeneous dependences (polynomial, exponential, logarithmic, statistical and others like that) in the base of this program. At set to the array of values two variables it is possible the method of linear search to define dependence which describes an initial chart most exactly. The selection of coefficients is executed by means of least-squares method.

In our research, for a starts given results were taken got at conducted previous research for twenty percent solutions of salt, sugar, fructose and distilled water.

It was set that most exactly the results of experimental researches are described by means of equalization of kind:

$$T = A2 + \frac{A1 - A2}{1 + \left(\frac{-t}{x0}\right)^P} \quad (1)$$

For each of solutions the table of values of coefficients which are included in equalization 1 was got. Value of coefficients of equalization 1, that answer curves got during realization of researches with solutions of sugar, fructose, salt and distilled water it is given in a table 1.

Coming from the phenomenological reasoning and conducting numerical experiments it is possible to define that in equalization 1 variable accordingly answer such parameters of process of the adiabatic boiling.

The found coefficients with coincide with the values of corresponding parameters of flowing of process sufficient for technical calculations exactness.

Coming from higher resulted will put corresponding values in a formula 1.

$$T = T_{ад.кун} + \frac{T_{ноч} - T_{ад.кун}}{1 + \left(\frac{-t}{t_{\Delta T/2}}\right)^P} \quad (2)$$

For verification of adequacy of results, which turn out after a formula 2 build curves which describe time-histories of temperature of solutions.

The graphic methods of dependences of temperature in time are expected after a formula represented on figure 2 by the dotted line.

From figure 2 evidently, that the most error of determination of temperature after a formula folds 1,5 0C and has character of spades. For majority of cooling time the error of determination of temperature does not exceed 1 0C, that fully sufficiently for realization of practical application.

4. Conclusion.

Experimental researches of the adiabatic cooling of solutions of food foods are conducted. Experimental dependences which describe this process are got.

Analytical dependence which adequately describes cooling of solutions at the adiabatic boiling is found.

References

1. Бойко О.О., Соколенко А.І *Дослідження зміни температури продукту при адиабатному кипінні* In: 76-а наукова конференція молодих вчених аспірантів і студентів, 2010 – р. 337.
2. Соколенко А.І., Шевченко О.Ю., Піддубний В.А., Васильковський К.В. *Вакуум-ефекти при упаковуванні пищевої продукції* In: Мир упаковки, vol. 6 (58), 2008. p. 30-32.
3. Стефанов Ст., Ч. Саздов, Н. Арабаджиева и Й. Стефанова. *Съвременни технологии за опаковане на храни и напитки*. In: Сп. Пропак, vol. 1, 2010. p. 26-28.
4. Криворотько В.М., Йовбак В.Д., Піддубний В.А. *Вакуумне охолодження рідин і рідиновмістких середовищ* In: Харчова промисловість, vol 10-11, 2010. p. 246–248.

TECHNOLOGY TO BUILD A WOODEN COTTAGE THAT COMBINES TRADITIONAL STYLE WITH TECHNICAL ASPECTS MODERNIST

C. SPIRCHEZ, L. BADESCU, L. GACEU, D. OLA, A. GOREA, V. DEAC

Abstract: In the paper the authors present a research on the construction of a wooden cottage, designed in traditional style combined with modernism. This concept is to offer a relaxing space for vocations, parties for groups large or small, and of general interest such as business meetings. Cottage itself is built of softwood, and oak for girders and the terrace.

Keywords: wooden cottage, softwood, oak, traditional style

1. Introduction

The wood has been used since ancient times, from birth of the first tools to the most extraordinary works of art that standeth to this day.

Fig.1 Used wood in past

Wood, natural material has always had a leading role in man's daily existence.

In terms of technology, wood can be transported and installed relatively easily with minimal costs.

Assembly is quick and can be processed at low temperatures.

Wood is very sensitive, and therefore must be taken into account certain issues when you wish to use.

Harvesting should be done in winter (september-february), the period when the wood is poor sap.

Fig.2 Used wood in construction

After cutting the wood must be stacked in the natural environment required (stacks), placed at a distance of 40 cm of soil.

Storage period in the stack must be minimum 21 days.

Meanwhile, wood fiber is prepared, then you can jump in technological processes.

2. Description of technological process for preparing wood

After harvesting and exploitation of forest areas, timber is transported to the sawmill, where selected, cut and shaped by different dimensions.

Cutting is done with horizontal and vertical saws.

Final dimensions of the wood worker bookmark.

After this operation is stacked timber as mentioned above, then proceed to the drying process.

Depending on size, destination and species material will establish drying parameters.

It is natural drying, will establish the technical parameters as standard.

If using artificial drying, drying parameters are set according to the type of dryer, species and sizes.

With this construction, wood beams final humidity is less than 20%.

Fig.3 *The roof the construction*

Dry interior materials (paneling, floors, interior doors) must reach the final moisture content of 9%, external doors and windows should have the final moisture content of 9%, external doors and windows should have the final moisture content of 13%.

After the drying, proceed directly to the protection against the action of various agents destructive of plant and animal by specific means.

Oak and whitetimmer (pine and spruce) before processing has been treated against fungi and insects xylophagous.

On the outside of a treatment is applied against weather, UV rays.

Aesthetic reasons apply a layer of colorless laquer from Kober company, IG 5100 series F, then apply two coats yet final.

Inside was applied a second coat of protection from Kober company, IG series 5100 F, then to apply another two coats in shades of medium walnut, IG 5179 series.

Fig.4 *The view of construction*

The roof framing type, consisting of two waters, is equipped with a console cover balcony.

We designed it to be wrapped construction of pine wood shingles on traditional motifs.

If you follow the technological process of fabrication and installation of shingles of the roof framing then, he would vouch for 20-30 years.

Fig. 5 *The roof the construction*

3. Elements used in the construction

Exterior and interior walls are made of beams with different lengths depending on site location.

Lower beams are made of oak, because it has a high resistance to weathering.

Voids are filled with polystyrene 12 cm thick, it has the role of thermal insulation.

Fig.6 Exterior and interior walls

Semicircular shaped exterior paneling, placed horizontally on the skeleton. Interior paneling is mounted vertically on the frame in lambda and tongue.

Staircase that connects the floors are made of softwood.

Doors and windows can be of wood with double glazing.

Fig.7 Staircase the wooden cottage

4.Simulation with program Heco

With help the program Heco realised simulation for timber construction design, soon as fig.8 In figure 8 observed tensile screw.

Fig.8 Timber construction design-plan view

Fig.9 Timber construction design

In fig.9 is presented timber construction design-load.

In fig.10 is presented reinforcement type,

Fig.10 Reinforcement type

In fig.11 is observed deformation (value), bending tension.

Fig.11 Reinforcement type-load

In figure 12 is presented a beam with single load.

Fig.12 The beam with single load

In figure 13 is presented beam with support pressing without reinforcement.

Fig.13 The beam with support pressing without reinforcement (front view)

In figure 14 is presented beam with support pressing without reinforcement (perspective view).

Fig.14 The beam with support pressing without reinforcement (perspective view)

5.Conclusions

The construction itself isn't a bulky building.

The location of such buildings, as recommended in forest areas, where winter sports can take place.

The program Heco is very well in domain the wood construction.

References

1. Badescu L.: Optimizarea ferastriurii lemnului, Brasov, Editura Universitatii Transilvania, 2002.
2. Dogaru V.: Taierea lemnului cu panze circulare, Brasov, Editura Universitatii Transilvania, 2002.
3. Lazareascu C. Constructii din lemn, Editura Universitatii Transilvania, 2008
4. Taran N.: Exploatarea masinilor-unelte si a utilajelor din industria lemnului, Brasov, Editura Universitatii Transilvania, 2005.
5. Taran N.: Ferastriae circulare pentru prelucrarea mecanica a lemnului, Brasov, Editura Universitatii Transilvania, 2007.
6. Tutorial program Heco Schrauben

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE ANALYSIS OF HARVESTING COMBINES SYSTEMS TO IMPROVE THE COMBINES CROP PROCESSING CAPACITY WHILE MAINTAINING HIGH STANDARDS OF GRAIN LOSSES AND SEED QUALITY

O. STAN* S. POPESCU**

Abstract: *The paper presents the results of the analysis done on various combine harvesters that adopted specific technical solutions to process the crop and a specific technological flow inside the combine from cutting the crop to collecting the grains and discharging the MOG (material other than grain). Bloc diagrams had been used as the preferred method to present and compare the combines technological flow as well as the main harvesting combine systems or components that play a significant role in the harvesting process. The analysis was limited to components and systems that have direct contact with the crop flow performing or contributing to the threshing, separating and cleaning functions.*

Keywords: *combine harvester, block diagram, threshing, separating, cleaning.*

1. Introduction

Even though the pull type combines are still being used in certain areas, the self-propelled combine harvesters have been nowadays widely accepted as the main harvesting equipment to achieve high productivity. It is a fact that, due to continuous increase of grain production per hectare, the necessity of reducing the harvesting time, as well as continuous pressure to reduce cost and increase productivity, the combines followed the general technical and technological industry progress trend. Therefore, the main structure of grain harvesters has suffered many modifications continuously increasing their harvesting performance, from 1...2 kg/s - forty years ago, to more than 23 Kg/s (3667 bu/hr. spot work rate or about 27 Kg/s and 20263 bu harvested in an 8-hour period -CR9090 Guinness World Record, Sept 2008 in UK for the most grain harvested in an 8 hour period -[5]). On September 1st, 2011, another Guinness World Record was achieved by CLASS with a LEXION 770 TERRA TRAC hybrid combine, "The most wheat harvested in eight hours..."; the harvested crop yield per hour was 84.48 t/h (23.466 Kg/s). This rapid increase in productivity is an expected response to the ever increasing world food demand given by the

growing population, expected to change from an estimated 7 billion in 2011 to exceeding 9 billion by 2050 (World Population Prospects, United Nations).

As a result of the intense researches performed in the latest decades, there had been found ways of increasing not only the harvesters working capacity, but in the same time minimizing the seed losses, as well as increasing their quality by reducing the seed damage and foreign content in the harvested seeds. Significant progress has been made in reducing the cost of the harvesting operations while improving the operators working conditions. Thus, the performance of the combine harvesters manufactured by well-known companies like *John Deere, Case IH, AGCO, New Holland, Claas*, etc. are alike, although from a configuration and/or construction point of view there are also major differences.

The simplest way to increase the working capacity of self-propelled combine harvesters was to enlarge the working parameters of the major machine components, like the cutting width, by using larger headers (18.6 m or 61 ft is believed to be one of the biggest, if not the biggest grain harvesting header in the world [6]), the threshing system width (the beater with), the shaking surface area (by increasing the length

* Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov*, Romania, e-mail: octavian.stan@cnh.com

**Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov*, Romania, e-mail: simipop38@yahoo.com

and width of the straw walkers), or cleaning surface area and accordingly, increasing of the engine power not only to be able to respond to the new power consumption requirements, but also to increase the combines ground speed.

Starting mid-seventies, in Romania, at SC "Semănătoarea" SA –Bucharest, it was introduced in production the self-propelled grain harvester C12 under "Laverda" Italian license, with two cleaning systems and a medium working capacity. Its construction has been improved over time, thus, other versions derived from the first model had been put in production, C12 M, C12 P (with side slope correction), C14 and C14 M (a higher capacity harvester with a single cleaning system, one fan and a simplified crop flow) alongside with other smaller models, C 70, C 80, produced in a reduced series.

Another step in the development of the self-propelled harvesters manufactured in Romania was the introduction of higher working capacity

with enhanced performance harvesting combines models C 110, C 140, concept of INMA Bucharest which, within their class, were comparable to those produced abroad. From a constructive point of view they had a simplified flow chart with a single cleaning system and one radial cleaning fan.

2. Analysis of the flow chart used for grain harvesters

The flow chart of the conventional (classical) type of combine harvesters is made up of the following working processes: - reaping (harvesting), threshing, separation, cleaning, transporting and loading into the tank. The block diagram of the flow chart for the harvesters of this type using two cleaning systems is being presented in figure 1, where there are also indicated the main working parts (bodies) performing the above mentioned processes [1; 4].

Fig. 1. The bloc diagram of the conventional combine harvester technological flow with two cleaning systems

The significance of the notations in figure 1 are: q -feeding flow with crop material harvested from the field; q_{cb} -flow of material exiting the counterbeater; q_{sc} -crop flow to straw walkers; q_{ssc} -uncleaned seeds material flow separated by the straw walkers; q_{pl} -long straw material flow from the straw walkers exiting the machine; q_v -crop flow mixture from an oscillating table or transport system entering the cleaning system; q_{pl} - long straw flow eliminated from straw walkers; q_{ps} - short straw flow eliminated from cleaning; q_{plv} - chaff flow eliminated by the cleaning system; q_s - clean seed material flow separated by the cleaning system; q_i -impurities material flow eliminated from the second cleaning; q_{sn} -flow of unthreshed crop material recovered from the main cleaning system.

In certain cases, the cereal grain is directed to a huller, the additional process being used to remove the chaff and the outer husks of the harvested grain.

The combine harvester model C12 M manufactured in Romania, as well as similar foreign brands conventional combines with two cleaning systems, perform per this type of flow chart, in which it can be noticed a material flow from an apparatus positioned in series with another, as well as a closed loop material flow for the unthreshed crop escaping the first cleaning system.

In the case of the combine harvesters with only one cleaning system, such as in Romanian combines C110, C140, and currently used by all major combine manufacturers (e.g. *Class, New*

Holland, John Deere, Case-IH), the block diagram presented in figure 1 will be slightly different in that the second cleaning is being removed. The unthreshed crop is being re-introduced into the flow either returning to the threshing apparatus or to the post-beater. In the case of high crop yields, high moisture, using big headers, and/or high harvesting speeds, the high crop feeding rates can exceed the combine working capacity resulting in unbalanced crop flow and increase in unthreshed material. This aspect is more obvious when the unthreshed crop flow is designed to re-enter the post-beater, which usually has less peripheral speed than the beater, and consequently, reduced threshing capacity. This creates the opportunity for

the unthreshed crop material to re-enter the re-threshing cycle, unnecessary combine power usage, and eventually leading to increase in crop flow, system overload and even clogging.

This effect has more evidently appeared when the grain harvesters with high working capacities were starting to be manufactured, where the resulted unthreshed ear quantity was considerable, resulting in the above mentioned effects. The above situation is being modeled using a similar version of the flow chart figure 1. As such, figure 2 presents a flow chart where a dedicated special re-threshing system had been introduced for processing of the remaining unthreshed crop collected from the cleaning system.

Fig. 2. The bloc diagram of a combine technological flow including a dedicated re-threshing system

In this type of configuration crop flow, if the re-threshing system is properly calculated and sized accordingly, the possibility of crop recirculation can be eliminated and the increase in crop flow, as well as the system overloading conditions can be avoided. The threshing apparatus in this case, would have a single crop flow input from the feeder and two output flows from the counter beater to the cleaning system and to the post-beater prior to reaching the straw walkers.

The crop flow is being modified by introducing an inclined oscillating table under the straw walkers which collects the material and transfers it to the oscillating intermediary conveyor. Also the inclined table under the straw walkers serves to redirect the working flow from the re-threshing apparatus. In the case where a high flow of unthreshed crop material exceeds the working possibility of the re-threshing apparatus, the material is being circulated directly back to the cleaning system, avoiding a longer circuit back to the straw walkers.

Another remarkable solution adopted by the major combine harvester manufacturers is the huller and the second cleaning system elimination from the original technological flow that placed them before the clean grain elevator or the clean grain loading into the tank. In order to improve the cleaning system, other companies such as *Massey Ferguson*, have adopted the solution of a cleaning system with three cleaning sieves in a cascade and a double centrifugal fan or a diametral fan (*Case IH, John Deere*).

As a general tendency in the construction of modern combine harvesters is to keep a simple technological process or even simplify it, like removing the huller, or eliminating other combine components while increasing the working capacity of the combine and the working systems efficiency (e.g. the threshing apparatus).

Most of the conventional combine harvester manufactures maintained in production this type of combine and upgraded the constructive parameters of the working parts such as

increasing the beater length and the number of rails, its diameter and the counterbeater wrapping angle. Consequently, the size of the whole harvester increased including its subsystems (header, conveyors, straw walkers, fan sieves), resulting in impressive overall dimensions and masses that requires stronger, more powerful hydraulic pumps, actuators, or engines. In order to improve the combine efficiency, achieve higher harvesting speeds with bigger headers while meeting the combine systems power requirements, it became necessary to introduce more electrical and hydraulic actuators, closed loop systems, sophisticated automatic controls

and adjusting mechanisms that limit the operator intervention.

Another method to increase the combine capacity is to use two threshing apparatus in series (a double threshing apparatus) with different constructive and functional parameters in order to ensure a complete threshing process even in high crop flows. This resulted in breaking the straw material in smaller pieces and the corresponding increase in the power consumption. This harvester is mostly designed for harvesting in high moisture conditions. The bloc diagram and the material flow of this type of harvester system are being presented in figure 3.

Fig. 3. The bloc diagram of a combine system technological flow with a double threshing apparatus in series

In order to further improve the above system capacity, more, bigger cylinders had been added in the front of the combine before the crop would be separated in the straw walkers area. This would also result in breaking the straw material in smaller pieces and further increase in the power consumption. Additional cylinders above the straw walkers to help separation added more complexity to the already complex crop processing system. The bloc diagram and the material flow of this type of harvester system is similar with the one

presented in figure 3 except the added separation complexity in the straw walkers area due to the added above mentioned cylinder.

The use of dual outlet fans becomes more and more a common method to increase the capacity of the combines, a second outlet directing a separate the straw air blast to a pre-cleaning sieve independently of the main sieve air flow. This would immediately separate a quantity of grain and direct it to the bottom sieve as shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4. Conventional combine with multiple cylinders, pre-cleaning system and cleaning fan (from NH model CX8000)

1-Feeder house; 2- Threshing cylinder; 3- Concave; 4-Beater; 5-Rotary Separator; 6-Straw flow beater; 7- Straw walkers; 8-Grain Pan; 9- Dual outlet cleaning fan; 10 - Pre-cleaning Sieve; 11- Top and bottom sieves

A block diagram for the system presented in figure 4 is being presented in figure 5. The system would be similar with the one in figure 3 with the

addition of the pre-cleaning function and the associated input/output parameters.

Fig. 5. The bloc diagram of a combine system technological flow with a double threshing apparatus in series and pre-cleaning system

The short straw q_{ps} and the chaff q_{plv} is eliminated from pre-cleaning; the seeds q_s that get separated by the pre-cleaning system go to the bottom of the cleaning system. The advantage of using a pre-cleaning process to increase the combine capacity is obvious. A dedicated pre-cleaner ensures a high velocity air moving through the pre-cleaner to help blowing out a high percentage of the original chaff; the grain falls from the grain pan

to the wind-controlled pre-sieve and then onto the top sieve (NH CR9000 Elevation model).

The system presented in figure 5 has been further improved to avoid top sieve overloading as shown in figure 6 and 7; the material that falls through the pre-cleaner goes now directly to the clean grain auger. The system can be further improved to provide a clean grain from the pre-sieve in all crop and conditions as well as in high material flow.

Fig.6. Air flow in a conventional combine with added pre-cleaning system and dual flow fan (JD model T670)

1-Conveyor Augers; 2-Dedicated Pre-Cleaner; 3-Dual Flow Multiple Fans; 4- Chaffer; 5- Sieve

Fig. 7. The bloc diagram of a combine system technological flow with a double threshing apparatus in series and pre-cleaning system delivering clean grain to the clean grain auger

The greatest revolution in the field of grain harvesters construction was the development of the axial flow combine harvesters using one or two axial rotors for threshing and separation [2; 3]. The rotary technology is currently being used in addition to or in place of the cylinders-concaves

threshing system used on conventional combines. Conventional combines are still being used, however, all major combine manufacturers Class, AGCO, Case IH, Caterpillar, Deere, New Holland would now have a rotary-based combine in their production offering.

Fig. 8. The axial flow rotor (CIH)

The technological process flow of this type of harvester is presented in figure 9. If can be noticed, as mentioned above, that the number of main

working sub-assemblies has been reduced and the process flow has been simplified while increasing the harvesting combine working capacity.

Fig. 9. The block diagram of the axial flow harvesting combines technological flow

As the transversal threshing apparatus with beaters and counterbeaters grew in width, as the wrapping angle of $120...140^\circ$ became insufficient for the increased demand in combine working capacity, it has been introduced in production the axial threshing apparatus, with single and double longitudinal rotors in parallel. Because of its multiple pass threshing the axial flow combines can operate the concaves in a more relaxed position and allow grain-on-grain threshing. This gentle and thorough threshing produces a grain sample that has more whole kernels, fewer cracks and substantially less foreign material in the sample. The breeders confirmed that the

germination percentage of grain harvested is exceptionally high [7]. The axial flow system allows the combine to better match the harvesting needs of various crops types and crop conditions.

The working capacity of the axial apparatus is relatively greater than its conventional counterpart, the performance is higher, being recommended especially in harvesting with high ratios seeds versus straw material.

The concaves and grates contact surface (counterbeaters corresponding components) is much greater (correlated to the diameter and the length of the threshing apparatus), so there takes place an almost total separation of seeds from

straw due to the fact that most of the seeds are detached from the ears. This leads to the removal of the straw walkers. The un-trashed crop collected from the cleaning system is being introduced again into the rotor area, which in normal circumstances it can be processed without affecting much the material flow coming from the feeder.

3. Conclusions

After completing the analysis of the most representative types of technological solutions used on self-propelled combine harvesters it can be concluded that:

- the classical processing crop system presented in figure 1 with two cleaning systems in series is faced with the real possibility of recirculating an important quantity of material back to the threshing system and straw walkers, especially when working with relatively high material flows, leading to waste of machine energy and efficiency; increasing the first cleaning system surface area to reduce the amount of material that is being recirculated would create challenges with the air flow distribution across a large surface area;
- the threshing apparatus can become overloaded in the case of high material flows with un-trashed crop material overlapping the incoming flow material from the field limiting the machine crop processing capacity;
- between the main cleaning system and the hopper there are introduced two sub-assemblies, the huller and the additional cleaning which generally consume a lot of energy for a low return value; in most of the harvested crops those systems are not justified or even necessary;
- the system modeled with the flow chart presented in figure 2 experience also some of the above mentioned shortcomings; however, introducing the re-threshing apparatus, eliminates part of the material recirculation; this is an improved system over the one presented in figure 1, in which the overloading conditions can be avoided in many crops and conditions; the system can become limited by the cleaning system capacity;
- the modified system represented in figure 3 flow chart is successfully increasing the threshing and separating capacity by increasing the number of cylinders and the crop contact surface; further increase in the number of cylinders used for threshing and separation the

front of the straw walkers and sometimes above the straw walkers to help the separation process, would benefit the crop processing in high material flows; however, more and more cylinders would add weight and complexity, at one point becoming detrimental to the overall combine system; designing bigger cylinders as well as increasing the wrapping angle would also help the combine to process more crop; however, there are physical and legal constraints to increase the combine components as well as additional costs and power consumption that limit the combine efficiency and crop processing capacity;

- adding a dedicated pre-cleaner, system represented in figure 5, was another positive step in being able to cope with combine increased material flow; an ideal design would be able to direct the material that falls through the pre-cleaner directly to the clean grain auger in all crops and conditions as well as in high material flow without directing it to a secondary cleaning operation; dual flow fans addressed the cleaning systems air flow requirements ensuring efficiency even under heavy load conditions;
- a system with an axial flow threshing apparatus (figure 9) brings back the simplicity of combine harvester systems while creating the potential for increasing the combine working capacity; two axial rotors would further increase the combine capacity putting pressure on upsizing the cleaning system and improving the air flow;
- in certain conditions the added cylinders in the front of the rotors are justified; they create a hybrid system with high crop threshing and separation capacity;

The crop flow analysis and the bloc diagram representation method can be used to visualize and better understand the various existing combine systems. The above analysis provides the evidence that the axial flow systems are simple, with fewer elements and, due to a gentle threshing and separation process, have the potential to deliver quality grains in all crop types and conditions as well as high material flow situations. Multiple rotors create additional threshing and separation capacity. A high processing capacity combine is also recommended to use the pre-cleaning sieve that delivers clean grain directly to the clean grain auger/elevator as well as high efficiency fans with dedicated air flow to all cleaning systems.

References

1. Diaconu, G.: *Contributions on Improving Performances of the Separating-cleaning System of the Harvester Combine*. PhD – Thesis, Transilvania University of Brasov, 2001.
2. Kutzbach, H., Schneider, H.: *Scientific Challenges of grain harvesting*. ASAE - Paper , Nr. 97-1080.
3. Kutzbach, H., Waker, P., Reitz, P.: *Developments in European Combine Harvesters*. In: Proceedings of AgEng Conference, Madrid, 1996.
4. Segarceanu, M. and others.: *Researches regarding the Improvement of the Flow Sheet and the Working Parts in order to Increase the Harvester Processing Capacity*. In: Journal of University Politechnical of Bucharest, 1986.
5. http://agriculture.newholland.com/uk/en/WNH/Magazines/Documents/PARTNERS_1.pdf
6. http://www.weeklytimesnow.com.au/article/2008/10/06/11345_grain-and-hay.html
7. <http://www.farminguk.com/admin/knowledge/CR9000.pdf>

THEORETICAL STUDY ON FEEDING THE TANGENTIAL THRESHING SYSTEM OF A CONVENTIONAL HARVESTING COMBINE

O. STAN* G. IVAN**

Abstract: *Tangential threshing system is the most important element of the conventional combines cereal harvesting both in terms of workflow and energy consumption. The threshing system capacity is a function of crop feeding speed and uniformity, the technical and functional characteristics of the feeder itself, as well as the type and characteristics of the harvested crop. The objective of the study is to increase the capacity of combines by determining the optimal values of technical and functional characteristics of the feeder and of the tangential threshing system with bars, based on a mathematical model of the feeding process. Theoretical research in this area did not fully complete the mathematical model. This article presents the first part of the report.*

Keywords: *grain harvester, threshing system.*

1. Introduction

Tangential threshing apparatus is the most important system of the cereal harvesting conventional combines, both in terms of workflow and energy consumption. The

threshing system can be equipped with one or multiple cylinders. It is positioned in the harvesting combine technological flow between the feeder houses, straw walkers, and cleaning system (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. *The main components of a cereal harvesting combine with multiple cylinders tangential threshing system*

The separation of seeds from the crop material in tangential threshing system with one cylinder is up to 85% completed, falling

below 60% if improper crop and adjustments are being used or in harvesting high moisture crop conditions.

* Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania*, e-mail: octavian.stan@cnh.com

** National Institute of Research - Development for Machines and Installations designed to Agriculture and Food Industry - INMA Bucharest, e-mail: geoivan2006@yahoo.com

Fig. 2. The main components of the tangential threshing system

The single drum tangential threshing system can be a threshing cylinder with bars, threshing cylinder with studs or spike-tooth type, or wire-loop type cylinder (Fig. 3). Tangential threshing cylinders with bars perform well in most crops and can be used for different harvesting

conditions. They have a higher usage than threshing cylinders with studs or spike-tooth type, or wire-loop type threshing cylinders, which are mainly used on harvesters manufactured in Japan in difficult threshing conditions like threshing rice.

Fig. 3. Single drum tangential threshing systems [2]

The multiple cylinder tangential threshing systems (Fig. 4) are made of three rotors (APS-CLAAS, Rotary separator-New Holland, Massey Ferguson MF7200 BETA, MCS-Laverda), 4

rotors (Multi threshing system-New Holland), or 5 rotors (John Deere T-Series). The percentage of grain separation during the threshing process is 90 ... 95%.

Fig. 4. Tangential threshing system with multiple cylinders APS-System Lexion series combines (CLAAS)

The combines capacity using tangential threshing system with multiple rotors is 14...20 % higher than if using a single cylinder threshing system with the same width [1].

2. Materials and method

The tangential threshing system capacity is affected by system parameters like uniform feeding, even distribution, speed of the crop material transported by the feeder to the threshing

cylinders, clearance between the drums and the concaves, technical and functional characteristics of the threshing system itself, and the type and characteristics of the harvested crop.

The harvested crop from the header is taken by a conveyor chain with slats inside the elevator housing, and, in an ideal situation, is traveling with ears facing forward. Each slat is loaded with a quantity of material based on the material flow supply, combine speed, and the distance between the conveyor chain slats (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. The simplified mechanism of the crop passing through the feeder and onto the improved tangential threshing system of the Romanian combine model C110 ATM

$$m_r = \frac{q \cdot p}{v_{r1}}, \quad (1)$$

where: m_r is the crop material mass transported by one slat;

q – the combine harvested crop material flow;

p – the distance between the slats;

v_{r1} – the feeder slat speed.

The feeder slat speed can be calculated with the formula:

$$v_{r1} = \omega \frac{D_d}{2} = \frac{\pi n D_d}{60}, \quad (2)$$

where: ω is the angular velocity of the conveyor chain sprocket;

n – conveyor drive speed in rot/min;

D_d – chain sprocket pitch diameter.

The crop material transported by a slat between the two conveyor shafts is moving with friction on the slat and elevator housing active

surface. In position A_1 of the slat, the transported crop material is in contact with the elevator housing and travels relative to the slat under the forces represented in Fig. 6.

Transported material moves along the slat active surface from the position B_1 to the position B_2 . The force acting on a material particle positioned in B, along the active part of the slat surface is:

$$F_1 = m_r g (\cos \alpha - f \sin \alpha), \quad (3)$$

where: F_1 is the force acting on a material particle driven by the elevator slat, measured in the position A_0 ;

m_r – the crop mass transported by one slat;

g – the gravitational force;

α – the feeder angle measured from the horizontal plane;

f – the coefficient of friction of the crop material in contact with the feeder surface.

Fig. 6. Diagram of forces acting on a material particle driven by elevator slat, positioned in point A_1

The material particle acceleration is:

$$a_1 = g(\cos\alpha - f\sin\alpha), \quad (4)$$

where: a_1 is the acceleration of the material particle moving along the active surface of the slat, measured in the position A_1 ;

The material particle speed along the active surface of the slat is:

$$v_{m1} = \frac{Lg}{\omega r}(\cos\alpha - f\sin\alpha) \quad (5)$$

where: v_{m1} - is the speed of the material particle moving along the active surface of the slat, measured in the position A_1 ;

L - is the distance between the two feeder conveyor shafts.

The material particle driven by the elevator slat between the two feeder conveyor shafts is:

$$\vec{V}_1 = \vec{v}_{r1} + \vec{v}_{m1}$$

where: V_1 is the velocity of the material particle driven by the conveyor slat between the two feeder conveyor shafts;

The material particle angle of the speed vector V_1 from the perpendicular to the active surface of the conveyor slat is:

$$\delta_1 = \arctg \frac{4Lg}{\omega^2 D_d^2}(\cos\alpha - f\sin\alpha) \quad (6)$$

where: δ_1 is the material particle velocity angle measured from the perpendicular to the active surface of the conveyor slat in position A_1 .

Fig. 7. The velocity of the material particle driven by the conveyor slat, on the active surface of the conveyor slat in the position A_1

When the slat is in the position A_2 , the crop material is still in contact with the feeder housing and is moving relative to the active surface of the

conveyor slat under the forces presented in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. The diagram of forces acting on a material particle on the active surface of the conveyor slat in the position A_2 .

The force acting on the material particle along the active surface of the conveyor slat in position A_2 , is:

$$F_2 = m_r [\omega^2 r_1 + g(\cos\alpha - f\sin\alpha)] \quad (7)$$

where: F_2 is the force acting on a material particle on the active surface of the conveyor slat in the position A_2 ;

r_1 – the circle radius of the material particle in the position B_1 .

Fig. 9. The diagram of forces acting on a material particle on the active surface of the conveyor slat in the position A_3 .

The force acting on the material particle along the active surface of the conveyor slat in

position A_3 , (Fig. 9) is:

$$F_3 = m \left[g \cos(\alpha + \beta) + \omega^2 r_2 - f g \sin(\alpha + \beta) \right], \quad (8)$$

where: F_3 – the force acting on a material particle on the active surface of the conveyor slat in the position A_3 ;

r_2 – the circle radius of the material particle in the position B_2 ;

β – the conveyor slat discharge angle.

The average acceleration of the moving crop material is:

$$a_m = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \omega^2 (r_2 + r_1) + g \left[\cos(\alpha + \beta) + \cos\alpha - f \sin(\alpha + \beta) - f \sin\alpha \right] \right\}, \quad (9)$$

where: a_m is the average acceleration of the moving crop material on the active surface of the conveyor slat, while in a rotation movement.

The conveyor slat discharge angle could be calculated with the formula:

$$\beta = 2\omega \sqrt{\frac{r_2 - r_1}{\omega^2 (r_2 + r_1) + g \left[\cos(\alpha + \beta) + \cos\alpha - f \sin(\alpha + \beta) - f \sin\alpha \right]}}, \quad (10)$$

where: β is the conveyor slat discharge angle when the slat is in a rotation movement.

The crop material speed along the conveyor slat active surface is:

$$v_{m2} = \sqrt{\omega^2 (r_2^2 - r_1^2) + g (r_2 - r_1) \left[\cos(\alpha + \beta) + \cos\alpha - f \sin(\alpha + \beta) - f \sin\alpha \right]}, \quad (11)$$

where: v_{m2} is the speed of the crop material on the active surface of the conveyor slat, while in a rotation movement.

$$\overline{V}_2 = \overline{v_{r2}} + \overline{v_{m2}}, \quad (12)$$

$$v_{r2} = \omega r_2$$

In the position A_3 , the feeding velocity V_2 of the crop material moving from the conveyor to the threshing system is a combination of the conveyor slat velocity v_{r1} and the crop material velocity v_{m2} given by the conveyor slat in a rotation movement, as represented in Figure 10.

where: V_2 is the velocity of the crop material feeding the threshing system;

v_{r2} – velocity of the conveyor slat in the position B_2 .

Fig.10. The crop material velocity transported by the conveyor slat in position A_3

The crop material velocity angle δ_2 measured from the perpendicular to the conveyor slat active

surface is:

$$\delta_2 = \arctg \frac{\sqrt{\omega^2 (r_2^2 - r_1^2) + g(r_2 - r_1) [\cos(\alpha + \beta) + \cos\alpha - f\sin(\alpha + \beta) - f\sin\alpha]}}{\omega r_2} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 11. The transition zone configuration and the crop material velocity profile in the moment when the crop material is being discharged by the conveyor slat

In the transition area from the feeder to the threshing cylinder, the crop material is moving along a transition plate hinged to the first concave. This adjustable transition plate is not only sealing the transition area, but also ensures a reduced feeding angle and a smooth transition of the crop material entering the first element of the threshing system. Its geometry follows the direction of which the crop material is leaving the conveyor slat. In addition, the transition plate geometry in the hinge area is one of the determining factors that influence the smooth taking over of the crop material by the threshing drum bars/elements. The transition zone configuration as well as the crop material velocity profile in the moment when the crop material is being discharged by the conveyor slat, are presented in Figure 11.

The crop mat height when feeding the threshing system could be calculated with the formula:

$$h_a = \frac{q}{l_{ev} v_a \gamma}, \quad (14)$$

where: h_a is the height of the crop mat feeding the threshing system, in m;

q – the combine crop material flow, in kg/s;

l_{ev} – the feeder opening width inside the feeder housing, in m;
 v_a – the crop material speed entering the threshing unit, in m/s;
 γ – the crop material bulk density, in kg/m^3 .

The experimental trials, conducted in 1982 by a team from the Department of Agricultural Machinery of Bucharest Polytechnic Institute, using the combines model C110, have shown in harvesting wheat that, for the $v_{r1}=6,1m/s$ slat conveyor speed, the percentage of seeds remaining in the straw after the threshing process is completed is minimal, while the percent of unthreshed crop and broken seeds stay within acceptable limits. The power consumption is about 30...40% less versus using a 2m/s slat conveyor speed. The results of the experiments also revealed that the percent of seeds that do not pass through the concave is maxim at 3,25m/s conveyor slat speed and it is getting lower as the conveyor speed goes up until it reaches 6,1m/s. The threshing system power consumption continues to lower down as the conveyor slat speed goes up, The power consumption lowering rate is higher when the conveyor slat speed is between 2...4m/s, after that, it continues to lower as the conveyor slat speed goes up but at a lower rate [3].

3. Results

For the calculation of the parameters used in this analysis, the following values are being used, values characteristic to the Romanian harvesting combine model C110ATM [4,5]: the crop material flow: $q=3,9...6,2\text{kg/s}$; - conveyor chain sprocket drive speed: $n=518\text{ rot/min}$; - the chain sprocket pitch diameter: $D_d=0.142\text{m}$; the distance between two consecutive slats: $p=0.16\text{m}$; - the slat width: $l_{slat}=1,03\text{m}$; - the radius to point B_1 : $r_1=0.096\text{m}$; - the radius to point B_2 : $r_2=0.118\text{m}$; the feeder angle measured from the horizontal plane $\alpha=32^\circ$; the distance between the two feeder conveyor shafts: $L=1.63\text{m}$.

According to the mathematical model presented, the results are: the crop material mass transported by one slat: $m_r=0,162...0,258\text{kg}$; the slat speed: $v_{r1}=3.85\text{m/s}$; the speed of the crop material along the active surface of the conveyor slat in position A_1 : $v_{m1}=2,64\text{m/s}$; the speed of the crop material driven by the conveyor slat between the two conveyor shafts: $V_1=4.67\text{m/s}$; the material particle velocity angle measured from the perpendicular to the active surface of the conveyor slat in the position A_1 : $\delta_1=34.42^\circ$; the conveyor slat discharge angle when the slat is in a rotation movement: $\beta=16^\circ$; the speed of the crop material along the active surface of the conveyor slat in a rotation movement: $v_{m2}=3.723\text{m/s}$; the conveyor slat speed in point B_2 : $v_{r2}=6.4\text{m/s}$; the speed of the crop material driven by the conveyor slat in a rotation movement: $V_2=7.4\text{m/s}$; the material particle velocity angle measured from the perpendicular to the active surface of the conveyor slat: $\delta_2=30.19^\circ$; the threshing system crop feeding speed of harvesting combine model C110 ATM is $v_a=v_{r1}=3.85\text{m/s}$; the height of the crop mat entering the threshing system $h_a=0,064...0,102\text{m}$ (for $\gamma=15\text{kg/m}^3$).

4. Conclusion

According to experimental tests in harvesting wheat, the maximum threshing process performance is being achieved when the feeder conveyor is feeding the threshing system with crop material at about 11.738 m/s speed, which represents about 40% of the beater peripheral speed.

Future analysis will demonstrate that the feeding material speed entering the threshing unit is being increased due to the air flow created by the rotating cylinders of the tangential threshing system.

References

1. Miu, P. Modelarea procesului de treier la combinele de recoltat cereale, PhD thesis, Polytechnic Institute of Bucharest, 1995, p.23...25;
2. Kutzbach, H.D. Grain Harvesting, Combine Harvesting, Hohenheim Germania, 2003, p.129-136;
3. Segărceanu, M. ș.a. – Studii și cercetări privind îmbunătățirea parametrilor calitativi și modelarea pe calculator a procesului de lucru a aparatului de treier al combinelor de cereale, Department of Agricultural Machinery, Polytechnic Institute of Bucharest, 1981;
4. Technical Book for harvester combine C110, S.C. Semănătoarea S.A., 2001;
5. Reports on “Rezultatele încercărilor în vederea omologării a combinei autopropulsate de recoltat cereale C110”, Research Institute for Science and Engineering for agricultural machinery, Bucharest, 1995.

EFFECT OF MODIFIED ATMOSPHERE ON THE SHELF LIFE OF PASTEURIZED MILK

ST. STEFANOV* H. HRISTOV* D. STOEVA*

Abstract: *The article presents results of experimental work related opportunities for increasing the shelf life of pasteurized milk. Studied the effect of modified atmosphere packaging on microbiological processes of deterioration. Known effects of certain gases on the development of microflora in the product after its packaging.*

In the experimental work used gas environments - mixtures of carbon dioxide and nitrogen in different proportions. The results show that a certain stock of the packaging environment has a positive effect on increasing shelf life.

Keywords: *milk, modified atmosphere, content oxygen, content carbon dioxide*

1. Introduction

In the variety of food products of animal and plant origin most valuable in nutritional and biological aspect are the milk and milk products. The milk contains all necessary nutritional substances in balanced proportions and easy to absorb form. It is unstable product and the shelf life prolongation is related to special treatments. By using different types of lactic acid bacteria and their vital activity the milk is amended and acquires new taste, nutritional, biological and even healing properties. Milk and milk products are the best source of easy to absorb calcium. This mineral has vital significance for developing of the human bones and teeth. Many studies prove that the lack or the insufficient milk and milk products consumption increases the risk of osteoporosis. The milk also contains great number of vitamins but in comparatively small quantity. In fact it contains all necessary vitamins for the normal growth of the young organism in the first weeks of its development. The quality of some of the vitamins is changed during storing of the milk, thermal and process treatment, transport and other activities.

There are regulative documentations, which describe the ways and rules for accepting, purifying, quality estimation, storing, transport and cooling of the milk and milk products. Fresh milk of good quality should be homogenous liquid in white color with slightly cream-colored nuance, no sediments or impurities. It has specifically pleasant smell and taste. Its important

laboratory determinate indices are: density, basis weight, acidity, non-fat solids and freezing point. The pasteurized milk for fresh consumption is obtained by thermal processing of cows milk, then cooling and packaging.

In the market, it is available in the following varieties – whole milk (natural, standardized and recovered) and skim milk.

The aim of the pasteurization is:

- To destroy the main part of the vegetative micro-flora and pathogenic bacteria, which does not form spores;
- To improve the consistency of the end product;
- To create good conditions for development of the beneficial lactic acid micro-flora in the production of fermented milk products.

If the pasteurization is performed at temperature below 60 °C, then the active lipase helps for rancidification of the milk products, which leads to worse quality and lower food value of the end product. When pasteurization is performed at temperature 93÷95°C for 10÷15 min, there is a great loss of vitamins. The most sensible are vit C, vit B1, vit B12, which are almost totally destroyed. The quantity of vit D, vit B vit E almost does not change.

There are different methods for prolongation the shelf-life of the milk and milk products, as well as packaging technologies.

The most common one during the last decades is the aseptic technology process and packaging. The milk and milk products should be stored and

* Dept. of machinery and equipment for food industry, University of food technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria, e-mail: stvstefanov:@yahoo.com

transported cooled in order to arrive to the consumer in perfect condition. The milk products which are usually put under many negative outer influences can be stored in sealed packaging at room temperature for months. The number of products in aseptic packaging constantly increases, due to their advantages:

- No refrigerator storage is needed;
- No preservatives are needed;
- The freshness and quality of the products are kept.

The principle of the aseptic processing includes friendly for the products thermal treatment together with filling the high protective characteristic packaging in sterile conditions.

The method of aseptic processing, applied to liquid foods is called UHT or HTST /high temperature-short time/. During UHT processing the product is quickly heated to temperatures /135-140°C for milk, 120°C for juices/. After short keeping /2-4 seconds for milk, 5-60 for juices/ it is quickly cooled to room temperature, at which the product is being filled in the packaging. The whole process is done in sterile conditions in closed chamber in order to prevent any unwanted outer influences.

The packaging of milk and milk products in modified atmosphere becomes more and more popular in the last years. This process gains additional prolongation of the shelf-life due to the used gas environment, which prevents the development of the micro-flora. The gas mixture is chosen on the base of the product type.

The packaging and storing conditions of foods can be divided in two major groups:

A. Changed environment: the environment is checked only once during packaging, the environment is changed, but due to the permeability of the material and the absorption of the product, it is not possible to be kept at constant composition.

B. Controlled environment: in this case the environment is preliminary set in rooms or containers with perfect hermetization and it is kept this way for the whole period of storing. In MAP – packaging there is a barrier on the way of the different influences on the packaged product. The barrier property of the packaging material and the packaging construction should prevent any product leakage as well the incoming of steam and gases, especially oxygen and water steam. In order to reserve the modified gas atmosphere inside the packaging the MAP –

packaging should be: light-, humidity-, odor-, oxygen-resistant, as well as CO₂ and N₂ resistant.

The implementation of this process is related to comparatively low investment, which has good effect on the end price of the milk products. There are data in the bibliography, which show positive effect of different gas environments on the shelf-life of milk products, like different kinds of pickled and solid cheeses, curds, dry milk etc.

2. Materials and methods

For the purpose of the following study we use pasteurized cow milk with fat content 3,4%, which had been packed in one liter packaging. The packaging material has complex structure, as the main elements are polyethylene and additives, which provide easy and fast decomposition. The packages are filled and sealed on automatic packaging machine with capacity 2000 pcs/hour. In the filling process before sealing of the package, the gas mixture is injected under pressure (1,5 - 3 Bar), so that the air goes out. The aim is to remove the oxygen, which leads to oxidation of the milk and inserting CO₂, which slows the growth of the microorganisms in the milk.

3. Modeling the change of the gas environment in the packaging

Two complete factorial designs have been performed, as the functions Y₁ and Y₂ are accordingly the quantity of the left oxygen and carbon dioxide CO₂ in the packaging.

We accept the following as independent variables:

- X₁- time** [days],
- X₂- ration C O/N₂**[%]
- X₃- pressure P** [Bar]

4. Experimental design

The influence of independent variables was determined and the process optimization achieved using response surface method [Boianov and Vuchkov 1976], [Angelov 1986], [Lambrev 1994].

A complete factorial design of the type 2ⁿ was applied with three replications at each point of the experiment, where n=3 is the number of independent variables. The polynomial describing variables y_i is of the following type:

$$y_i = B_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n B_i \cdot x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n B_{ij} \cdot x_i \cdot x_j \quad (1)$$

The regression model performance was tested by means of ANOVA.

5. Experimental matrix

The independent variables and their levels in the experiment are presented in table 1

Independent variables and their levels of variation Table 1

Independent variables, X_i	Upper level, (+) z_i^2	Lower level, (-) z_i	Centre, z_i^0	Variation range, Δz_i
Time, X_1 , day	14	1	7,5	6,5
Proportion CO ₂ / N ₂ , X_2 , %	30/70	50/50	60/40	10/10
Pressure, X_3 , bar	3,5	1	2,25	1,25

Coded design of a complete factorial experiment, type 2³

Table 2

Variant	X0	X1	X2	X3	X1 X2	X1 X3	X2 X3	X1 X2 X3
1	+1	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
2	+1	-	+	-	-	+	-	+
3	+1	+	-	-	-	-	+	+
4	+1	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
5	+1	-	-	+	+	-	-	+
6	+1	-	+	+	-	-	+	-
7	+1	+	-	+	-	+	-	-
8	+1	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

6. Results and discussion

In table 3 we can see the average values of the oxygen content O₂ (Y₁, %) and carbon dioxide CO₂(Y₂, %) for the different variations of the experiment.

After elimination of the insignificant effects (Fig.1) we achieve the following equations for the oxygen content Y₁ (O₂), % and carbon dioxide Y₂ (CO₂),% in the packaging.

Table 3

Variant	Y ₁ (O ₂), %	Y ₂ (CO ₂),%
1	2,4	34
2	0,8	23
3	6	7,8
4	11,4	6,5
5	0,2	40,5
6	0,1	25
7	7,7	9,7
8	8,4	5,8

Standardized Pareto Chart for Y1

Standardized Pareto Chart for Y2

Fig.1 Standardized effects of regression model coefficients on:

a) Y₁ (O₂), %; b) Y₂ (CO₂), %;

$$Y1 = 4,62 + 3,72 * X1 + 0,535 * X2 - 0,53 * X3 + 0,956 * X1 * X2 + 0,202 * X1 * X3 - 0,38 * X2 * X3 - 0,76 * X1 * X2 * X3 \quad (2)$$

$$Y2 = 19,04 - 11,5875 * X1 - 3,96 * X2 + 1,21 * X3 + 2,66 * X1 * X2 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2 Amendment of the oxygen content in the packaging according to the pressure (X3) and the gas environment ratio (X2)

We can see on figure 3 and figure 6 that when the time is amended (X1) and the ratio (X2) of the gas mixture, we have the smallest influence of

the pressure (X3) on the oxygen and carbon dioxide content. This can be explained by using standard packaging materials with high gas permeability.

Fig. 3 Amendment of the oxygen content in the packaging according to the time (X3) and the gas environment ratio (X2)

Fig.4 Amendment of the oxygen content in the packaging according to the pressure (X3) and the time (X1)

Fig. 5 Amendment of the carbon dioxide content in the packaging according to the pressure (X_3) and the ratio (X_2)

Fig. 6 Amendment of the carbon dioxide content in the packaging according to the time (X_1) and the ration (X_2)

Fig. 7 Amendment of the carbon dioxide content in the packaging according to the pressure (X_3) and the time (X_1)

The time (X_1) Fig. 5 and Fig. 2 is defined as most significant factor.

7. Conclusions

The best results are achieved by using modified atmosphere of CO_2 and N_2 in ratio 30/70. The increase of the CO_2 content over 30% in the gas mixture decreases the shelf-life.

The transition from normal to modified atmosphere when packaging pasteurized milk on

standard automatic packaging machine does not require high cost for modification, which makes the technology extremely effective from economical point of view.

Although the inserting of the gas mixture together with the product in the packaging, there are no disturbances in the dosing unit performance. This is proved by the achieved high sharpness of the dosing units of the packaging machine.

References

1. Angelov, A., Guidelines for engineering experimentation / in bulgarian / Ed. Sci.Tech.Union, St. Zagora, 1986, pp240
2. Bojanov, E. and I. Vuchkov., Statistical Methods for Modelling and Optimization of Multivariate objects. Ed. Technika, Sofia 1976, 515 pp / in bulgarian /
3. Lambrev, At., Foundations of engineering experiment in machines investigation. Ed. Plovdiv, HIFFI, 1994, 190pp
4. Carol A. Phillips. Modified Atmosphere Packaging and its effects on the microbiological quality and safety of produce. International Journal of Food Science & Technology. Volume 31, Issue 6, pages 463–479, December 1996.
5. Irene R. Grant¹, Margaret F. Patterson^{1,2,*}Effect of irradiation and modified atmosphere packaging on the microbiological safety of minced pork stored under temperature abuse conditions. International Journal of Food Science & Technology. Volume 26, Issue 5, pages 521–533, October 1991
6. A.A.M. Zeitoun¹, J.M. Debevere. Inhibition, survival and growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* on poultry as influenced by buffered lactic acid treatment and modified atmosphere packaging. International Journal of Food Microbiology Volume 14, Issue 2, November 1991, Pages 161-169

STRUCTURE FORMATION AND DISPERSION ANALYSIS OF BUTTER, PROCESSED UNDER HIGH CYCLICAL PRESSURE

V. Sukmanov, I. Levit, S. Gromov

Abstract: *The paper presents the results of the studies of dispersed butter. The factors affecting the performance of dispersion of the product are analyzed. The methods of microphotography and computer processing analysis of micrographs is used to study parameters of dispersion in high cyclic pressure treated butter.*

Key words: *butter, dispersion, high cyclic pressure, shelf-life.*

Butter (B) is a polydisperse, multiphase and multicomponent system of variable composition [1]. The complex structure of the dispersed oil is formed of solid and liquid phases of the milk fat triglycerides, plasma - aqueous phase with dissolved and dispersed components of milk (protein, sugars, phospholipids, and organic mineral salts, vitamins and other components), and also includes a gas phase in the form bubbles.

Multiphase butter stages explained by its components being in a solid, liquid and gaseous state. The butter phase will be defined as the set of homogeneous particles of the system, the same at all points on the composition and all chemical and physical properties, and limited by some other parts of the visible surface (the interface). The solid phase is represented by the mixed crystals of milk fat, fat globules membranes protein and milk plasma proteins. The liquid phase consists of the liquid fraction of milk, fat-free water in the form of droplets, and the bonded water in the capillaries penetrating the continuous fat phase. The gaseous phase is represented by bubbles of air and dissolved air [1,2].

Polydispersity of butter is explained by the fact that the solid phase of butterfat, water and gas phase are in the form of scattered particles, whose dimensions vary within certain limits: the crystals of milk fat are the size of 0.01-2 mm, 1-15 mm water droplets, air bubbles up 20 mm [2].

Physical properties of butter (hardness, ductility toughness, elasticity, strength and other structural and mechanical characteristics) are determined primarily by its structure and the degree of dispersion of its components. Since the last closely related texture, flavor, color, firmness of oil in storage and other consumer characteristics.

The phenomenon of butter thixotropy is the ability to soften or dissolve the structure

under the influence of mechanical stress and re-hardened after cessation of exposure.

In accordance with the classical concepts butter structure can be interpreted as a three-dimensional lattice formed by reversible (thixotropic) and irreversible (crystallization) bonds. Crystallization bonds are the contacts directly between milk fat crystals formed strong chemical bonds. Thixotropic (coagulation) bond is a link between the crystalline particles, and other structural elements of the butter through a layer of liquid fat. These bonds are formed due to weaker Van-Der-Waals forces.

The study of the mechanical properties of butter samples with different deviant consistencies showed that the brittle, layered or crumbled consistency were mainly crystalline structure as the original butter had very high strength and after its destruction the restored structure had a strength of 30 - 40% lower than the original. Ductile butter had a low strength and its structure is of predominantly coagulative nature, as after the destruction the reconstructed strength of the structure was reduced to 80 - 90%. The complete absence of crystallization explained by the elements having weaker, spotting consistency [1,2].

In the continuous fat phase droplet plasma are dispersed. Much of the droplets had network of connected plasma channels, which allows us to consider the aqueous phase as a continuous one.

The butter produced from high fat cream is characterized by high dispersion of moisture. This provides increased capacity for storage.

The average diameter of droplets in the oil from the plasma of high fat cream of 1,98-2,53 mm [4]. According to S. V. Vasilisin and F.A. Vyshmersky [3] a the majority of the oil droplets in the plasma has a diameter of 1-3 microns, and only a small number of them a

diameter of 10.9 microns. Part of the moisture is retained on the surface of fat particles and is associated with preserved shells of fat globules, a small amount of it (about 0.25%) dissolved in the fat phase.

Mass fraction of main components, including fat content and plasma varies over a wide range of fat from 52 to 82.5%, plasma - from 49 to 17.5% which contains from 1.5 to 5% of the Dry Milk Skimmed Rest. In the traditional sweet butter composition (82.5%) mass fraction of 1.3-2.2%. F.A. Vyshemirsky in [4] gives the following characteristics of the butter structure: the diameter of the plasma droplets in oil - from 0.5 to 11 microns or more, the mass fraction of moisture, % -87.8 - 90.6, Dry Milk Skimmed Rest: 9.4 - 12.2, including lactose, 4.6 - 4.9, protein 3.2 - 3.4, minerals 0.5 - 0.7, fat 0.34 - 3.95.

Many properties of butter are largely determined by its physical structure. The most important feature is the stability of oil in storage. This parameter is especially closely related to the oil with the aqueous phase, namely the degree of dispersion and the relative amount of encapsulated moisture. The presence of the close relationship between the stability of oil in storage at subzero temperatures and a higher degree of dispersion of the aqueous phase ($r = +0,75$), as well as an increase in the encapsulated moisture content ($r = +0,79$). The degree of dispersion of the aqueous phase showed strong correlation ($r = +0,72$) also with the organoleptic evaluation after two weeks of storing butter at 14°C. The appearance of rancidity in preconditioned at 21-25°C oil was accelerated by a factor of 6-7 due to a slight increase in the number of unencapsulated moisture, ie enhancement of the continuity in aqueous phase. There is a close correlation between these two indices of the aqueous phase ($r = +0,84$) [5].

The average oil droplets diameter from the plasma of high fat cream is 1,98-2,53 μm [1,2,4]. According to S. V. Vasilisin and F.A. Vyshmersky [6] the majority of the oil droplets of the plasma has a diameter of 1-3 microns, and only a small number of them a diameter of 10.9 microns.

In general, the main characteristic of disperse systems is dispersion, which is inversely proportional to the mean particle diameter and determined by specific surface area (the ratio of the total surface area of particles per unit volume or mass of the dispersed phase).

In the butter production using high-pressure cycle, the technological parameters of

the process (the number of loading cycles - n ; the maximum pressure in each cycle - P_{max} MPa, and the rate of rise of pressure relief - $v_{\text{up}}, v_{\text{down}}$ MPa / s, the temperature process - $t, ^\circ\text{C}$) largely determine the structure of the oil and the quality of the product.

Based on the foregoing, the goal of this work was to study and comparative analysis of the structure of butter, produced both by conventional technology (conversion of high fat cream), and using the high-pressure cycle.

Due to the fact that the processing of high-pressure cycle butter leads to a change in their structure (particle size, configuration and shape, relative position, etc.) there is a need of disperse systems analysis computerization, which are photomicrographs of samples of products, and that includes the detection, recognition, filtration, separation and detection of binary images containing a sufficiently large number of particles of small size, made with the use of microscopes.

Analysis of the micrographs showed that, in accordance with the accepted binary systems in the analysis of images, this system should be attributed to systems with a contour image containing the image borders silhouette image in the form of a closed non-self-dotted line the same brightness, color and intensity of staining [7]. For the processing of the images in the program used Markov discrete chains - the most convenient and efficient mathematical models of binary images [8-10].

In general, the main characteristic of disperse systems is dispersion, which is inversely proportional to the mean particle diameter and specific surface area is determined (the ratio of the total surface area of particles per unit volume or mass of the dispersed phase). A more complete picture of the dispersion curve gives the distribution of volume or mass of the dispersed phase particle size (Fig. 1).

With increasing polydispersity of the system, i.e. with increasing difference in particle size, the maximum on the distribution curve is reduced and becomes more widespread, but the area bounded by the curve and the x-axis, remains constant.

The structure, i.e. internal composition of the product and the nature of the interaction between the individual elements (particles) are determined by chemical composition, dispersion, biochemical parameters, temperature, state of aggregation, and a number of other technical factors.

Figure 1 - Distribution curves of particle size parameters:

1 - monodisperse system, 2 - polydisperse system. δ_{\min} , δ_{\max} , δ_0 - respectively the minimum, the maximum and the probability of the particle size;

$f(\delta)$ - distribution function of the volume (or mass) of the dispersion phase, which accounts for a particle with a given size range divided by the amount of the interval.

Typically, food is a multi-phase coagulation and condensation-crystallization structure. In such a dispersed system of coagulation structures formed by the interaction between particles and molecules through the layer of the dispersion medium due to the Van-der-Waals forces of adhesion. The thickness of the layer corresponds to the minimum free energy of the system. Thermodynamically stable systems in which the surface of the particles firmly bound fragments of molecules that are capable of this without losing the connection to dissolve in the dispersion medium. In turn, the dispersion medium is in a bound state. Typically, these coagulation structures are capable of spontaneous recovery from the destruction of a gradual increase in strength. The thickness of the layers to a certain extent depends on the content of the dispersion medium. By increasing the value of its content is usually reduced shear properties, and the solid state system becomes fluidlike. The degree of dispersion, i.e. the predominant particle size, even at a constant concentration of the phase affects the state of the system and its strength. Dispersity, as an independent thermodynamic parameter of the system, has a significant influence on the physico-chemical properties and parameters, among

which are reactivity, solubility, the equilibrium of chemical reactions, melting and phase transition.

To obtain a complete picture of the distribution of particles in disperse systems, the size most commonly used method of optical microscopy, which is based on direct visual study of the individual particles of the study phase - determining their number, shape and size. In general, the evaluation of particle size in a separate phase of the sample with a microscope is based on the study of particle size distribution.

In the first stage of object recognition has been used for selection of objects belonging to one of the structural elements that make up the butter: the fat balls, the particles of moisture and air bubbles [8-10]. For visual identification of the fat globules was used «Sudan 4» dye. Particles of moisture and air bubbles differed in the predominance of gray and yellowish tints on the micrographs. The use of appropriate color filters allowed to divide the analyzed butter particles with a high degree of reliability. In the second phase was carried out selection of objects in space, at which only those objects are selected that are allocated in accordance with the division of facilities and the area which ranges from S_{\min} to S_{\max} .

Spatial area was defined by the formula:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^N i, \text{ where } N \text{ is the number of unit squares;}$$

i - the current number of unit area; spatial

$$\text{perimeter defined by the formula: } P = \sum_{i=1}^N i,$$

where N - number of unit length on the perimeter,

i - the current number of units of length on the

perimeter, roundness: $\alpha = \frac{4 \cdot \pi \cdot S}{P^2}$; elongation:

$$\beta = \frac{d_{\max}}{d_{\min}}, \text{ where } d_{\max} \text{ - maximum size; } d_{\min} \text{ -}$$

the smallest size, diameter Feret, or the equivalent diameter of particles, which are the diameter of spherical particles of a conditional, which has the same volume of a particle of complex shape and

defined by the formula: $D_F = \sqrt{\frac{4 \cdot S}{\pi}}$, where S -

area projections of particles in the field of view of

the microscope; compactness: $\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{4S}{\pi}} / d_{\max}$,
 equivalent diameter: $D_{Eq} = \sqrt{d_{\max} \cdot d_{\min}}$.

As objects of investigation were taken samples of butter 72.5% fat, high-pressure cycle processed immediately after the butter is taken from butter processor. The temperature of the samples was $12 \pm 0,50$ C.

Given the results of previous studies on the influence of high-pressure cycle parameters on the microbiological sterility of butter has been studied the microstructure of butter processed in the following process parameters: sample 1 – P_{\max} 320 MPa, $n = 5$; $v_{H \uparrow} = 1$ MPa/s, $v_{H \downarrow} = 5$ MPa/s; sample 2 – P_{\max} 320 MPa, $n = 4$; $v_{H \uparrow} = 10$ MPa/s $v_{H \downarrow} = 5$ MPa/s.

The control butter sample is produced according to the existing standards at Maryinsky creamery of "Lactis". Histograms, smoothing the distribution function and the average values of the parameters studied are shown in Fig.1-6.

Figure 1 - Histograms, smoothing the distribution function and the average values of the spatial parameters a) fat globules, b) particles of water, c) air bubbles in the samples of butter: C (○) -

control sample, 1 (□) and 2 (Δ) - butter treated by high-pressure cycle.
 The area of the visual field 114355,93 mkm^2 ; interval -1 mkm^2 .

Figure 2 - Histograms of smoothing the distribution function and the mean value of the perimeter of a) the fat globules, b) particles of water, c) air bubbles in the samples of butter: C (○) - control sample, 1 (□) and 2 (Δ) - high-pressure cycle treated butter.
 The area of the visual field 114355, 93 mkm^2 ; interval - 0.5 mkm .

Analysis of the obtained results allowed to state the following changes in the dispersion characteristics of the fat globules. The number of fat globules in the high-pressure cycle treated samples of butter increased slightly (by 0.9 and 1.0%, respectively, for sample 1 and 2 compared with the control sample), indicating that dispersion (fragmentation), fat globules under the high -pressure cycle. The average area of fat globules in samples 1 and 2 decreased by 4.6 and 8.7%, which indicates a decrease in the volume of fat globules in the high-pressure cycle. However, the perimeter of the fat globules in

samples 1 and 2 decreased by 18 and 21.9%. To explain this circumstance it is advisable to use the indicator "Fere diameter" (equivalent diameter), which has also decreased by 22 and 29% in the examined samples. These figures can be explained by the fact that the high-pressure cycle leads to a change in the shape of the fat globules in which they become more regular round shape. This confirms the parameter circularity of fat globules, which in samples 1 and 2, respectively, increased by 5.3 and 9%. Compactness parameter grew by 4.7 and 7.1% and decreased elongation parameter of 13.0 and 10.1%.

Figure 3 - Histograms, smoothing the distribution function and the average value of Fere diameter of a) the fat globules, and b) particles of water, c) air bubbles in the samples of butter: C (○) - control sample, 1 (□) and 2 (Δ) - high-pressure cycle treated butter. The area of the visual field 114355,93 mkm²; interval - 0.1 mkm.

Thus, treatment of butter in high-pressure cycle leads to a fragmentation of its fat globules, increasing their compactness, they become more regular round shape.

Under the influence of the high-pressure cycle the following changes in the characteristics of dispersion of particles of moisture took place. The average number of particles of water after high-pressure cycle treatment samples 1 and 2 decreased by 1%, but their average size has decreased by 16.8 and 15% respectively.

The average value of the perimeter decreased by 14.8 and 21.5%, and the Fere diameter decreased by 21.4 and 25.7% respectively. In control samples, the average Fere diameter (equivalent diameter) of the butter is equal to 3.98 microns (for comparison, in [1,2,4],

Figure 4 - Histograms, smoothing the distribution function and the mean value and elongation of a) fat globules b) particles of water, c) air bubbles in the samples of butter: C (○) - control sample, 1 (□) and 2 (Δ) - high-pressure cycle treated butter. The area of the visual field 114355,93 mkm²; interval - 0.05 mkm.

the average particle diameter of moisture in the butter produced by churning with periodic bringing down $D_{c p} = 3,26$ mkm and with continuous bringing down $D_{c p} = 3,2$ mkm and with the way the transformation of high fat cream

$D_{c p} = 4$ mkm. Elongation parameter decreased by 10.3 and 14.1%, setting up the roundness of 28.3 and 27% respectively, and the compactness of the particles of moisture increased by 1.2 and 8.3%.

Thus, the high-pressure cycle treatment increases the dispersion of the butter, thereby increasing its consumer properties and reducing both the rate of oxidative processes and the rate of development of pathogenic organisms in the butter.

High-pressure cycle processing leads to a significant reduction in the number of air bubbles: by 36.9 and 34.5% for samples 1 and 2. However, their average size has decreased by 7.8 and 12.6%.

Figure 5 - Histograms, smoothing the distribution function and the mean value and elongation of a) fat globules b) particles of water, c) air bubbles in the samples of butter: C (○) - control sample, 1 (□) and 2 (Δ) - high-pressure cycle treated butter.

The area of the visual field 114355, 93 mkm²; interval - 0.01 mkm.

The average value of the perimeter decreased by 10.3 and 20.2% and the average Fere diameter - at 30.6 and 33.2% respectively. A comparative analysis of these values shows that

the volume of the bubbles of the gas phase decreased, and the air bubbles tend to assume the correct shape of the sphere. This is also confirmed by the increasing roundness parameter of 2.4 and 3.4% and an increase in the compactness of the bubbles of the gas phase by 12.9 and 15.3%.

High-pressure cycle butter treatment changes not only the microstructure but its nanostructure as well. Moreover, changes in micro- and nanostructures are interrelated and have mutual influence.

High-pressure cycle butter treatment leads to a thin and uniform dispersion of the plasma in the butter, increased the content of the particles d to 2 microns and increases the volume distribution in these plasmas.

Figure 6 - Histograms, smoothing the distribution function and the mean value of the compactness of a) the fat globules, and b) particles of water, c) air bubbles in the samples of B: C (○) - control sample, 1 (□) and 2 (Δ) - high-pressure cycle treated butter.

The area of the visual field 114355, 93 mkm²; interval - 0.01 mkm.

High-pressure cycle butter treatment leads to a decrease in the amount of free water and its distribution in the particles d to 5mkm and increases small particles up to d 2mkm, which plasma is not available for microbial growth, inhibition of the coalescence of the plasma particles in the micro-and nanoscale.

Thus, high-pressure cycle butter treatment inhibits the hydrolysis of fats, helping to reduce the depth of peroxide oxidation of fat and, consequently, reduces the activity of the formation of secondary oxidation products, which improves the quality and biological value for the consumer.

References

1. Production of butter: Directory / Andrianov Y.P., Vyshemirsky F.A., Kacherauskis D.V. tons, et al. Edited by Dr. of Technical Science F.A. Vyshemirsky. - M.: Agropromizdat, 1988 - 1988. - 303p. ISBN 5-10-000202-6.
2. A.P. Belousov. Physico-chemical processes in the production of butter by churning cream. - Moscow: Light and Food Industry, 1984. - 264s.
3. Vyshemirsky F.A., Topnikova E.V. The consistency of butter as an indicator of quality. "Cheese and butter manufacturing, № 1, 2008, C41-44.
4. Grishchenko A.D. Cream butter. - Moscow: Light and food industry. - 1983. - 294p.
5. Kacherauskis D. Rheological and structural properties of butter and methods of their determination. - Works of the Lithuanian branch of VNIIMS, Vilnius, 1974, v.9, p.33-39.
6. Vasilisin S.V., Vyshemirsky F.A. Effect of amount and degree of dispersion of the plasma on the intensity of the taste of the Vologda butter. Scientific and technical information. "Dairy Industry". M., 1971, vol. 9, p. 20-26.
7. Fuhrman Y.A., Yuryev A. N., Yashin V.V. Digital processing techniques and pattern recognition of binary images. - Krasnoyarsk: Krasnoyarsk Univ. Press, 1992 - 248p.
8. Butakov E.A., Ostrovsky V.I., Fadeev I.L. Image processing on a computer. - M.: Radio and Communication, 1987.
9. Fomin Y.A., Tarlovskii G.R. Statistical theory of pattern recognition. - M.: Radio and Communication, 1986.
10. Bernd Jahne. Digital image processing with CD-ROM / Bernd Jahne; Heidelberg; New York; Barcelona; Hong Kong; London; Milan; Paris; Tokio; Springer, 2002, 585p.

EXPERIMENTAL ESTIMATE OF POSSIBILITY TO APPLY HIGH PRESSURE FOR THE PRODUCTION OF RESTRUCTURED PRODUCTS OF CHICKEN MEAT

Sukmanov V.O., Sokolov S.A., Sevatorov M.M., Dekan O.O.

Abstract: *This article presents results of experimental analysis of estimating the possibility to use high pressure for making restructured products from chicken meat. Advantages of the high pressure technology in comparison with the existing technology have been considered.*

Keywords: *high pressure, restructured meat products, microbiological parameters, culinary doneness, tensile strength.*

Popularity of sausage products in Ukraine can be explained both by historically formed taste preferences of Ukrainians, and affordability of the price. Each consumer lives within the affordable price of food basket, which is also applied to meat products. In regions with a minimum standard of living, a food basket of meat products is formed either at the account of its own farm economy or low segment of the assortment. The main primary material for the sausage production is meat, fat, by-products obtained in the process of industrial processing of slaughtered animals (cattle and poultry). However, lack of primary materials of relevant quality at the affordable prices remains one of the main problems for meat processors. Thus, in recent years, a volume of meat production has increased due to poultry. Producers of sausages replenish shortage of primary material at the account of imports, which share sometimes reaches 50%. Cheap primary materials of questionable quality are mainly imported to Ukraine: trimming beef, minced chicken meat (mechanically deboned meat), American chicken, Brazilian and Polish pork. Chicken meat as the cheapest kind of meat is a leader in the volume of import, despite the fact that its volume of production in Ukraine is quite high and it fully caters for domestic demand. As a result, the meat market is unbalanced in Ukraine, it is characterized by an excess of poultry meat (67%), shortage of pork (22%), and especially beef (8%), which is due to a permanent reduction in the number of pigs and cows in Ukraine [1]. Oversupply of poultry, both of own and import production, demands new approaches to producing products capable to maintain high consumers' interest while reducing self cost of the obtained products at the account of reducing consumption of all types of energy used for their production.

Commercially available ham products are important protein food. Our preliminary analysis of

domestic and foreign scientific and technical literature showed that technology of restructured ham products based on meat primary materials is promising.

Application of restructuring allows to regulate organoleptic and structural-mechanical properties of the products, to involve primary materials, partially used in traditional technologies of natural meat products, modify functional and technological properties of primary materials, to vary chemical composition of the finished products, to expand the assortment, to increase the yield of the finished products, and production profitability.

In this regard, to increase the depth of raw meat processing and diversification of meat product it is necessary to pay attention to the chicken meat use. Restructured products are much lower in their self cost than natural ones. At present time cheaper primary materials, soya protein, complex food additives, a lot of moisture and as a consequence, a large amount of thickeners and stabilizers of different origin are used in the production. Carrageenan (E-407), enzyme transglutaminase, soya protein isolate, sodium caseinate, etc., which serve as stabilizers and thickeners as they form gel, are mostly used at the meat processing enterprises in Ukraine. These components have been researched for a long time, and in the course of studies they were allowed for application in even baby and dietetic food. However, for example, carrageenans (kappa, iota and lambda carrageenan) allowed in Ukraine, are prohibited or not recommended in Europe and America [2]. Thanks to the media, modern consumers have also elaborated persistent distrust to any additives and prefer to buy and eat food with minimal content of additives, and it is the best option to do without them.

In our opinion it is possible to find the way how to replace the potentially harmful chemical ingredients in sausage products by safer methods for

physical procession of food primary materials. The concept and technologies developed as a part of it, are based on the fact that high pressure can not only disinfect food products but also give them new properties that are more attractive to consumers. High pressure is also capable to bring the processed foods into the state of culinary doneness without thermal treatment [3].

The aim of this work is to develop technologies of restructured meat products from chicken meat with application of high-pressure that is capable to recreate a structure of unminced primary materials, which properties are similar to the structure of the whole-muscle large pieces meat without application of chemical stabilizers and thickeners.

In accordance with the aim the following tasks were resolved in the work:

- Investigate microbiological indexes of ham;
- Determine a degree of culinary doneness by experimental approach;
- Give an experimental estimate of tensile strength of the obtained ham samples.

To conduct studies, we prepared samples, which composition was determined by the ratio of muscle and adipose tissue, and was represented by three types:

- a) muscles tissue (pectoralis) - muscle tissue (shank) (M-M) ratio of 1:1;
- b) muscle tissue (pectoralis) - adipose tissue (M-F) ratio 1:1
- c) adipose tissue - muscle tissue (shank) (F-M) ratio of 1:1

Dimensions of pieces ranged from 5 mm to 30 mm.

Before packing, the samples were manually stirred; black pepper and salt were added. Then the samples were packed in the film "Poviden", marked and sent for being processed in a high-pressure chamber. Construction of the high-pressure plant allows carrying out measurements at the temperature range from 5 to 95°C. The pressure treatment was carried out from 100 to 600 MPa with exposition of pressure from 10 to 40 minutes at 23°C (these modes were previously established by means of experimental studies [4]).

One of the main indicators of quality of the restructured ham is its microbiological stability.

During the experiment, samples of three compounds were subject of microbiological analysis in the experiment process. Initially, the sample M-M appeared to have the highest bacterial load that is why we present only the results of microbiological analysis of this sample (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Microbiological parameters of the sample M-M, depending on the applied pressure

Analysis of the obtained dependency suggests that the pressure of 400 MPa provides a reduction of the samples' bacterial load to the maximum permissible values, and the pressure of 500 MPa reduces the degree of bacterial load in nearly 4 times in comparison with the maximum permissible norm. With the increase of pressure above 600 MPa it is possible to obtain samples with near-zero indexes of bacterial load.

To ensure culinary doneness of the product apart from its microbiological well-being, it is necessary to achieve microbial inactivation of the acid phosphatase enzyme. Therefore, we carried out a series of experiments to determine the degree of culinary doneness of all samples subjected to high pressure treatment instead of thermal treatment. The results of experimental studies on determining the degree of the samples' culinary doneness are given in Table 1.

Table 1 - Results of experimental studies on determining the degree of the samples' culinary doneness

Pressure Time	The mass fraction of phenol, %			
	10 min	20 min	30 min	40 min
100 MPa	0,12	0,11	0,09	0,07
200 MPa	0,077	0,071	0,063	0,054
300 MPa	0,008	0,0076	0,0071	0,0068
400 MPa	0,0075	0,0074	0,0069	0,0065
500 MPa	0,007	0,006	0,006	0,0058
600 MPa	0,006	0,005	0,005	0,005
0,1 MPa	0,14	0,14	0,14	0,14

To determine the strength of "glueing", a technique developed at St. Petersburg State University of Refrigeration and Food Technologies was used, which makes it possible to measure the strength required to tear the "glued" sample. Composite model samples obtained after cutting the processed loaves of ham, that are regularly shaped cylinders with diameter of $30 \pm 1,5$ mm and height 40 mm, were used as measuring objects. The area of

gluing was 706.5 mm². The processed samples were frozen by liquid nitrogen to dural platforms for their strong fixation, and then were torn. The limiting value of tensile strength was recorded at the time when components of the sample were completely separated from each other. Dependence of the applied tensile strength on the pressure and time of processing for all tested samples is shown in Fig. 2, 3 and 4.

Fig. 2. Dependence of the tensile strength on the pressure and time of processing for the sample M-M

Fig. 3. Dependence of the tensile strength on the pressure and time of processing for the sample M-F

Fig. 4. Dependence of the tensile strength on the pressure and time of processing for the sample F-M

Figure 5 shows the original chicken mince. Figure 6 shows a sample of M-M treated with high pressure of 200 MPa for 30 min, and Figure 7 - sample treated at 600 MPa pressure for 30 minutes. As we can see, pieces of meat in the sample, treated with a pressure of 200 MPa, didn't

stuck together with each other, whereas in the sample, treated with 600 MPa pressure, the pieces of meat are a single unit. Figure 8 shows a cross section of the sample, treated at 600 MPa for 30 minutes.

Fig. 5. *Original chicken mince*

Fig. 6. *A sample of M-M, treated with high pressure of 200 MPa for 30 min*

Fig. 7. *A sample of M-M, treated with high pressure of 600 MPa for 30 min*

Fig. 8. A cross section of the sample, treated with high pressure of 600 MPa for 30 min

Analyzing the obtained dependences it is possible to draw preliminary conclusions that with the help of high pressure treatment it is possible to recreate a structure that will be similar to the structure of whole-muscle large pieces meat without the use of chemical stabilizers and thickeners. At the same time it is possible to achieve culinary doneness without use of traditional types of thermal treatment. The most rational parameters of the process will be - 500 MPa, 30 minutes at temperature 23°C. In the future we expect to hold a series of experimental studies to determine rational parameters of the process such as temperature, pressure, time of exposure, as well as experimentally to find the optimal formulation of the restructured products and give them a rheological and organoleptic estimate.

References

1. Source: www.proinfo.com.ua
2. «Оценка некоторых пищевых добавок и контаминантов», 41 доклад объединенных

- экспертов ФАО/ВОЗ по пищевым добавкам, Женева, «Медицина», М., 1994.
3. Атермічний спосіб виготовлення печінкового паштету з використанням високого тиску: пат 37167 У Україна : МПК (2006) А 23 L 3/26 / Сукманов В.О., Соколов С.А., Севаторов М.М., Приходько І.В.; заявник і патентовласник: Донецька нац.ун-т економіки і торгівлі імені Михайла Туган-Барановського. - № 37167 ; заявл. 03.04.2008; опубл. 25.11.2008., Бюл. №22 – 4 с.
4. Коршунова Г.Ф. Использование высокого давления для производства мясной продукции / Коршунова Г.Ф., Сабіров О.В.// Збірник наукових праць Луганського національного аграрного університету. Серія: Технічні науки. – Луганськ, ЛНАУ, 2006. - №64/87 – С. 152-154.

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE DYNAMIC STABILITY OF THE FORKLIFT TRUCKS

N. SUTRU* G. BOIANGIU** S. POPESCU***

Abstract: *The first part of the paper presents the equivalent dynamical model of the forklift system in the most difficult work situations: descending on a slope braking of the vehicle in translatory motion and acceleration of the fork while lifting the load. Based on the dynamical model are elaborated the mathematical models describing the dynamical behavior of the forklift truck during moving or working. These models deliver the criteria for the overturning stability. The last section of the paper presents a measurement installation developed for experimental research on the dynamics of the fork lift truck.*

Keywords: *forklift truck, dynamical model, mathematical model, longitudinal stability, experimental research.*

1. Introduction

The complete mechanization of the manipulation of various products with the same equipment is based on applying palleting technology, which involves the placing of wrapped products on international standard size platforms, known as pallets. The manipulation of both pallets and box-pallets is mechanized and can be performed on the horizontal on relatively short distances (within a hangar or between close locations) and on the vertical up to certain heights, using the same type of equipment, as described in Figure 1, called forklift trucks.

The constructive and functional parameters are generally the following: the nominal (rated) charge to be lifted, the maximum lifting height, the constructive height, the free height, the position of the mass centre in relation to the supporting polygon and the stability characteristic.

The nominal/rated lifting charge represents the maximum charge or load that can be lifted by a motor forklift truck to the maximum height reachable by the forks, and generally varies between 500 and 5000 kg.

The maximum lifting height varies between 1600...10000 mm. Forklift trucks working in storage rooms of 8 m height, need to allow a

minimum lifting height of 5600 mm. For low height (up to 5 m) storage rooms, forklift truck lifting height needs to be of at least 3200 mm.

The constructive height of the forklift truck is conditioned by the height of the gates it has to pass, and varies between 600...1800mm for railway car forklift trucks and does not exceed 2250 mm for storage room ones. The free height represents the point to which the load can be lifted without modifying the constructive height of the truck. For storage room trucks this height needs to be of at least 3000 mm, while for railway car ones the minimum value is of at least 1250 mm.

The stability characteristic is generally presented as a diagram, where the abscissa features the values for the distance between the mass centers of the load to the fork bead (called mass centre height), while the ordinate shows the values of the load. This diagram allows the selection of the type of forklift truck depending on the mass of the manipulated load and on its plane dimensions (pallet dimensions).

2. Dynamics of longitudinal stability of the forklift truck

During travelling between the loading and the unloading place, the forklift systems are

* Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov*, Romania, PhD-Student; e-mail: sutru_nastase@yahoo.com

** Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov*, Romania, PhD-Student; e-mail: boiangiugheorghe@gmail.com

*** Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Braşov*, Romania, e-mail: simipop38@yahoo.com

frequently subjected to braking processes, which under certain circumstances may cause the loss of longitudinal stability, by overturning round the front axle. The diagram of figure 1 considers the most difficult situation in regard of stability, is when the system is braked during descending a longitudinal slope, at the same time with the braking of the charge during the lifting - lowering process (when inertia force acts upon the charge Q) [1].

The exterior forces acting upon the system during braking on a longitudinal descending

slope (tilted by angle α) with the center of gravity of the load Q lifted to height h_q are as described in figure 1: G is the own weight of the vehicle empty ; Q – load of the charged working component (fork); Z_1 and Z_2 - loads on the front and rear axle, respectively; F_f - braking force developed on the vehicle wheels; $R_{r1} = f \cdot Z_1$ and $R_{r2} = f \cdot Z_2$ – rolling resistances of the front and rear axle wheels respectively (where f is the rolling resistance coefficient of the vehicle wheels).

Fig.1. External forces acting upon the on the forklift truck during braking on a longitudinal descending slope

Due to the braking force F_f developed on the vehicle wheels, the system body is subjected to inertia forces generated by the deceleration a , forces parallel to the road surface and placed in the mass centers of the vehicle body: $G_i = a \cdot G/g$ and charge $Q_{ix} = a \cdot Q/g$, respectively. During descending the slope, the same masses are subjected also to the components parallel to the road surface of the weights of these masses: $G \cdot \sin \alpha$ and $Q \cdot \sin \alpha$, placed in the centers of gravity of these masses. During braking of charge Q while lifting or lowering, corresponding inertia forces act upon the fork, opposed to the acceleration a_q : $Q_{iz} = a_q \cdot Q/g$.

The total braking force F_f developed on the track wheels by the adherence to the road surface depends on the actuating mode of the brakes. The

maximum braking forces given by the relationship: $F_{fmax} = \varphi \cdot (Z_1 + Z_2)$, where φ is the adherence coefficient of the wheels to the road surface [3,4]. Due to the small values of the rolling resistance coefficients f compared to those of the adherence coefficient φ , the rolling resistance R_r can be neglected (i.e. $R_r = R_{r1} + R_{r2} = 0$), wherefrom follows: $F_f = (G + Q) \cdot [\sin \alpha + (a/g)]$.

The normal loads Z_1 and Z_2 on the front and rear axle of the tractor braked with deceleration a during descending a slope tilted by angle α , follow from the equilibrium equations of the simplified equivalent dynamic model of figure 1, and are given by the following expressions:

$$Z_1 = \frac{[G \cdot (L - l_1) + Q \cdot (L + l_q)] \cdot \cos \alpha}{L} + \frac{(G \cdot h + Q \cdot h_q) \cdot \sin \alpha}{L} + \frac{a \cdot (G \cdot h + Q \cdot h_q) + a_q \cdot Q \cdot l_q}{g \cdot L}. \quad (1)$$

$$Z_2 = \frac{(G \cdot l_1 - Q \cdot l_q) \cdot \cos \alpha}{L} - \frac{(G \cdot h + Q \cdot h_q) \cdot \sin \alpha}{L} - \frac{a \cdot (G \cdot h + Q \cdot h_q) + a_q \cdot Q \cdot l_q}{g \cdot L} \quad (2)$$

From the above equations follows that the inertia forces generated by the braking deceleration a and the system weight components parallel with the traveling direction cause an unloading of the vehicle rear axle Z_2 at the same time with the loading by the same value Z_1 of the front axle; this process is intensified with an increasing tilt

angle α and the braking decelerations of the truck a and of the load a_q .

The most frequent situation in practice is that of the forklift in braked downhill motion with the fork charged with the nominal load Q and fixed in transport position h_q . As $a_q = 0$, the load on the rear axle, Z_2 , is given by the following equation:

$$Z_2 = \frac{(G \cdot l_1 - Q \cdot l_q) \cdot \cos \alpha}{L} - \frac{(G \cdot h + Q \cdot h_q) \cdot \sin \alpha}{L} - \frac{a \cdot (G \cdot h + Q \cdot h_q)}{g \cdot L} \quad (3)$$

In lifting – lowering operations conducted with an acceleration a_q of the fork charged with load Q , and the forklift resting (braked) on a downhill

slope ($a = 0$), the load on the rear axle, Z_2 , is given by the equation:

$$Z_2 = \frac{(G \cdot l_1 - Q \cdot l_q) \cdot \cos \alpha}{L} - \frac{(G \cdot h + Q \cdot h_q) \cdot \sin \alpha}{L} - \frac{a_q \cdot Q \cdot l_q}{g \cdot L} \quad (4)$$

The system loses its longitudinal stability (overturns round the front axle) when the load on the rear axle Z_2 becomes zero ($Z_2 = 0$). Condition $Z_2 = 0$ in equations (3), (4) and (5) allows establishing of the maximum (critical) value of the tilt angle α_{max} , the maximum braking decelerations a_{max} of the truck or the maximum

braking deceleration a_q of the load Q which the system loses its dynamic longitudinal stability.

In braking on a downhill slope with the fork charged and fixed ($a_q = 0$) lifted into transport position, the maximum admissible acceleration a_{max} following from the condition of longitudinal overturning stability ($Z_2 = 0$ in equation (3)) of the forklift is:

$$a_{max} = g \cdot \frac{[G \cdot l_1 - Q \cdot l_q] \cdot \cos \alpha - (G \cdot h_t + Q \cdot h_q) \cdot \sin \alpha}{G \cdot h_t + Q \cdot h_q} \quad (5)$$

In braked resting on a downhill slope ($a = 0$) the maximum admissible acceleration a_{qmax} of the fork in lifting-lowering operations following

from the conditions of longitudinal overturning stability ($Z_2 = 0$ in equation (4)) of the forklift is:

$$a_{qmax} = g \cdot \frac{[G \cdot l_1 - Q \cdot l_q] \cdot \cos \alpha - (G \cdot h + Q \cdot h_q) \cdot \sin \alpha}{Q \cdot h_q} \quad (6)$$

In the same time to ensure maneuverability of the vehicle, at least 20% of the vehicle weight needs to remain on the rear axle (which is the directing axle), that is $Z_{2min} = 0,2 G$ [2,3]. By imposing this condition $Z_{2min} = 0,2 G$, the maximum values of the slope angle α_{max} and accelerations a_{max} and a_{qmax} can be computed by the equation below.

stability (manoeuvrability) of the moving system, going as far as complete loss of stability. Analysis is achievable by computer aided simulation and plotting of the corresponding graphs.

3. Experimental researches

Analysis of the analytical relationships (mathematical models) reveals that increasing the angle of the downhill slope, increasing braking intensity (increasing braking deceleration), increasing the load of the fork, increasing the transport height of the load on the fork and increasing the lifting acceleration of the charged fork cause a decrease in longitudinal overturning

The technical characteristics of the forklift deployed for experimental field tests include: deadweight/empty weight (unloaded fork) $m = 4550$ kg (with $m_1 = 2260$ kg on the front axle and $m_2 = 2290$ kg on the rear axle); wheelbase $L = 1.830$ m; coordinates of the mass centre: distance on the horizontal $x_c = 0.91$ m (in relation to the rear axle) and height $z_c = 0.65$ m (in relation

to the supporting surface). These data were determined by measurements and were used in theoretical research for the mathematical models (computer simulation). The forklift has a driving front axle and a steering rear axle (turnable wheels actuated via the steering wheel). The braking system only operates only on the front wheels.

The objectives of experimental research consisted mainly of establishing via measurements the simultaneous variation in time of the rear axle load Z_2 and the braking deceleration a of the forklift, in order to analyze the longitudinal overturning and moving stability (maneuverability) of the system under various conditions, and to verify the results of theoretical research by computer aided simulation of the devised mathematical models. Thus the accuracy of dynamic modeling developed as part of the theoretical study can be improved and eventually validated.

The experimental research was done in different displacement conditions of the forklift,

by accelerating to various speeds (3, 6, 10 km/h) and followed by braking until full stop, having the fork loaded with different weights (0, 600, 1200, 1800) placed at different lifting heights above the ground (0, 0,2 and 0,5 m). Before performing the displacement tests was determined the position of the centre of mass (height from the ground and distance to the axles) for various loads upon the fork and also different heights above the ground. In order to carry out experimental research on the longitudinal stability of the forklift truck a modern measurement installation for recording and processing of data collected by sensors was developed, which allowed the simultaneous measurement of follows parameters: the rear axle loads, the load acting upon the fork, the horizontal velocity and acceleration of the truck body and the vertical and horizontal acceleration of the charged fork. The location of measuring transducers on the machine is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Transducers and sensors mounting diagram on the fork lift truck system:
 TF_Q - transducer for the force in the fork lifting hydraulic cylinder rod (dynamic load of the fork);
 TA_{Qz} - transducer for fork acceleration on vertical direction; TA_{Qx} - transducer for fork acceleration on horizontal direction; during the forklift motion; TA_B - transducer for horizontal acceleration (implicitly the speed and displacement); TF_2 - transducer for dynamic load on the rear axle (steering axle)

Figure 3 presents the schematic of principle of the measurement, data acquisition and processing equipment. The measurement of the force acting upon the fork lifting hydraulic cylinder rod, that represents the dynamic load acting upon the fork,

was done indirectly by measuring the oil pressure in the fork lifting hydraulic cylinder. The measurement of the pressure was performed by help of a pressure transducer TF_Q (type P6A-

Hottinger with inductive half-bridge) connected to the cylinder oil pipe.

Fig. 3. Diagram of data acquisition and processing equipment

Measurement of the vertical and horizontal accelerations of the lifting fork was conducted by inductive acceleration transducers TA_{Qz} and TA_{Qx} with seismic masses (type B12/200-Hottinger, with inductive half-bridge). The dynamic load (pressure force) Z_2 on the rear (steering) axle of the forklift was measured by means electro-resistive transducers with strain gauges (of 120Ω resistance) mounted in pairs on the arms of the rear axle. The force transducer of the axle was gauged and calibrated statically on horizontal ground by loading with known weights over the static load Z_{20} that presses on the axle in the absence of a charge on the fork [3]. The measurement of the horizontal acceleration and implicitly the speed of the forklift and distance covered by the forklift during tests were achieved by an optic transducer TA_B (type S 400) mounted laterally on the truck body at 400 mm height above the ground. The transducer was calibrated on the forklift while in motion.

The data acquisition and amplifier system is of MGC plus - Hottinger type. Feeding was ensured by a 12 V cc battery by means of a 1000 W dc/ac inverter with ac 220 V output voltages. The amplifier system allows the connecting of 16 modules. The measured data, recorded on a Toshiba Satellite Laptop were transmitted to a DAS3 type data acquisition system endowed with a DAS2 control board (6 analogical input channels and 6 fast counter inputs, and dc 9...26

V feeding voltage). Data were saved on a memory card.

Figures 4 and 5 exemplify graphs of the forklift tractor's rear axle load variation versus time (fig. 4) and of its velocity (fig. 5) in the case of intensive braking on paved horizontal ground with 1800 kg fork load lifted to 0.5 m height. It has to be pointed out, that in order to prevent a possible longitudinal turn-over (towards the front) of the forklift during intensive braking, experiments did not include loads exceeding 1800 kg nor lifted higher than 0.5 m. The rear axle loads for large braking loads and great lifting heights were determined by computer simulation of the dynamic and mathematical models of the system for experimentally obtained values of deceleration. Processing of the experimental data revealed intensive braking accelerations on concrete pavement in the range of $2.2 \dots 2.75 \text{ m/s}^2$.

The experimental data confirmed from both qualitative and quantitative viewpoints the data obtained by theoretical studies, revealing that during braking the dynamic loads on the rear axle decrease, whilst increasing by the same amount on the front one. For certain values of the fork load and certain lifting heights, the load on the (steering) rear axle decreases under 20% of the forklift tractor weight. Hence, as steering is ensured by the rear axle, forklift manoeuvrability (motion stability along the set trajectory) may be

lost. The situation becomes critical only when the rear axle load becomes zero, when the forklift loses its longitudinal stability (turns over frontwise). A situation close to such a case occurs

during the motion presented in figure 4, where the rear axle unload nearly reached the static load of 10830 N corresponding to a fork load of 1830 kg.

Fig. 4. Variation versus time of the forklift rear axle load in the case of intensive braking on horizontal ground (asphalt) with 1800 kg fork load lifted to 0.5 m height (initial vehicle speed: 10 km/h)

Fig. 5. Variation versus time of the forklift velocity in the case of intensive braking on horizontal ground (asphalt) with 1800 kg fork load lifted to 0.5 m height (initial vehicle speed: 10 km/h)

4. Conclusions

The braking of the forklift trucks during descending a longitudinal slope with the filled

palettes or forklift in transport position is in relation to the longitudinal stability of the system the most difficult situation of the travelling process.

The dynamics of fork lift loader systems can be analyzed by mathematical modeling of the equivalent dynamic models of the real systems, taking into account the exterior forces to which they are subjected in various working situations. Based on the equivalent dynamical models it can be elaborated the mathematical model describing the dynamical behavior during the descending on a slope by breaking of the vehicle and acceleration of the fork while lifting the load. The mathematical models deliver the criteria for the overturning stability. By computer simulation of the mathematical models the longitudinal stability of the forklift truck can be analyzed through application in the constructive model of the fork lift truck parameters and travel and work conditions.

The experimental analysis of system behavior related to longitudinal overturning stability and maneuverability under various conditions requires the simultaneous determination of the rear axle load variation and the braking deceleration of the forklift. Further required is determining the variation of forklift acceleration/deceleration in lifting/lowering of the load.

By comparing the results of theoretical research obtained by mathematical model based simulation with the experimental, measurement-based ones, the accuracy of dynamic and mathematical modeling of the real physical models of forklifts can be verified in view of

their improvement, such as to obtain simulation-based theoretical results as close as possible to experimental ones.

Developing dynamic and mathematical models able to replace real systems and situations allows the simulation of system dynamic behavior by means on dynamic and mathematical modeling and thus partial replacement of cost and time intensive, in overturning limit situations even dangerous experimental research.

References

1. Popescu, S. *Contributions regarding the experimental research on the dynamic behavior of the tractor front loader system*. Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov, Serie A, vol 11 (46), 2004, p. 101-106.
2. Popescu, S., Sutru, N. *Contributions to the study of the dynamics of agricultural tractors equipped with front- end loader and rear fork lift loader*. Proceedings of the 8th International Scientific Conference "Engineering for Rural Development", Jeglava/Latvia, May 2009, p.165-170.
3. Sutru, N., Popescu, S. *Particularities of the Dynamic Stability of Fork Lift Trucks*. In: Anales of the University of Craiova, vol.. XXXIV/B-2005, p. 273-280.

INFLUENCE OF THE GEOMETRIC AND FUNCTIONAL PARAMETERS OF THE REAR THREE-POINT LINKAGE ON THE DYNAMICS OF TRACTOR – IMPLEMENT SYSTEMS

L. VASILACHE* S. POPESCU** N. ORMENIȘAN***

Abstract: *The paper presents the dynamic and mathematical modeling of the systems consisting of tractor and implement coupled at the rear of the tractor, based on which the dynamic loads can be determined, which act upon the tractor axle. The paper analyses the dynamic models for the systems consisting of tractor and carried implements with supporting wheels, further mathematical models which allow computer simulation of the dynamic stability of these systems are developed, aiming at the optimization of the constructive and functional parameters of the components (of tractor and implement).*

Keywords: *agricultural tractor; carried implements; three-point linkage; dynamic modeling; mathematical modeling; dynamic stability; computer simulation.*

1. Introduction

Attached implements are coupled to agricultural tractors by means of three-point linkages. While these mechanisms are typically placed at the rear of the tractor, recent

agricultural tractors are also equipped with front three-point linkages (three point-point hitch). Figure 1 shows the constructive diagram and figure 2 the classic concept of rear three-point linkage (modern version: cylinder(s) also outside) [1, 4].

Fig. 1. Constructive diagram of a rear three-point hitch of the agricultural tractor

The three-point linkage represents a 3D bar right) and an upper bar 3. The bars of the mechanisms: two lower bars (links) (1- left, 2 – mechanisms are joint-attached at one end to the

* Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Brașov, Romania*, e-mail: filianvasilache@hotmail.com

** Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Brașov, Romania*, e-mail: simipop38@yahoo.com

*** Dept. of Engineering and Management in Food and Tourism, *Transilvania University of Brașov, Romania*, e-mail: alexorme@yahoo.com

tractor body and at the other to the frame of the implement. Lifting and lowering of the implement is achieved by moving the lower bars 1 and 2 in a vertical plane, achieved by means of

the lifting rods 4 that are rotated by the lifting arms 5, actuated by means of the lifting shaft 6 (figure 2) and the hydraulic cylinder 7 of the tractor hydraulic installation.

Fig. 2. Classic concept of rear three-point hitch of the agricultural tractor:
 1- left lower bar; 2- right lower bar; 3- upper bar; 4- lifting rod; 5 - lifting arm;
 6- lift shaft; 7- hydraulic cylinder.

The geometric, constructive and dimensional parameters of the linkage elements, the positions (coordinates) of the joining points of the bars in relation to the rear axle wheels of the tractor, as well as the positions of the joining points of the bars to the implement frame are regulated by international standard. According to ISO 730-1 the three-point hitch are classified into four categories, according to the nominal tractor PTO power [3,4]: Cat. 1: under 48 kW; Cat. 2: under 92 kW;

Cat. 3: 80...185 kW; Cat. 4: 150...185 kW. Cinematically the 3D three-point linkage represents in the vertical longitudinal and the transversal horizontal plane, respectively, two four-bar mechanisms with virtual hitch point and convergence distances (fig. 3). ISO 730-1 the recommends following values for horizontal convergence distances: Cat. 1: 1700...2400 mm; Cat. 2: 1800...2400 mm; Cat. 3: 1900...2700 mm; Cat. 4: 1900...2800 mm.

Fig. 3. Horizontal (a) and vertical convergence (b) of the rear three - point linkage (ISO 730-1)

2. Mathematical modelling of the position of the vertical virtual hitch point of the three-point linkage

A rigorous modelling in the three-point linkage of the dynamics of the tractor attached implement system requires an analysis of the geometry of this mechanism. For this purpose in the longitudinal – vertical plane the 3-D three - point linkage was replaced by a four bar mechanism consisting of the upper bar and a lower bar. This mechanism is analyzed in a xOy reference frame with the origin in O_2 , the tangency (contact) point to the soil of the rear axle wheels of the tractors (fig. 4).

The lower bars BE of the linkage have standardized lengths a (established by ISO 730-1) and are attached to the tractor body in points B, placed in preset positions according to ISO 730-1, defined by the horizontal and vertical coordinates x_B and z_B in relation to contact point O_2 of the rear axle wheel. The upper bar AD is attached to the tractor body in point A, defined by the horizontal and vertical coordinates x_A and z_A .

The rear ends of the linkage bars AD and BE are attached via a joint to the bolts of the implements frame, namely to the inferior bolts E (coordinates x_E and z_E) and to the superior bolt D (coordinates x_D and z_D), the position of which on the implement framework (ISO 730-1).

Fig. 4. Computational diagram of the geometric and kinematic elements of the tractor three - point linkage

The position in the vertical plane of the vertical virtual hitch point O_v of the three - point linkage (consisting of the lower bar BE and the upper one BE, constituting a four bar mechanism) is defined by the variable coordinates x_o and z_o that represent the geometric locus defined by the intersection in the vertical longitudinal plane of the supporting lines of drawbars BE and AD of the three - point linkage. Consequently it follows that the pair of coordinates x_o, z_o of the vertical virtual hitch point O_v will be the solution of the system of the equations of the lines passing through points A and D, respectively B and E, with the final form:

$$x_{26} = \frac{m_2 \cdot x_A - m_2' \cdot x_B + z_B - z_A}{m_2 - m_2'}; \quad (1)$$

$$z_{26} = z_A + m_2 \cdot (x_o - x_A),$$

where m and m' are the slopes of the mentioned supporting lines, given by the expressions:

$$m_2 = \frac{z_D - z_A}{x_D - x_A};$$

$$m_2' = \frac{z_E - z_B}{x_E - x_B}. \quad (2)$$

The upper bar AD can be coupled to the implement frame (by joint D) in 3 positions distanced 50 mm one of another on the vertical; in some implements the inferior drawbar BE can be attached to the frame (by joint E) in two positions distanced 50 mm one of another. Consequently the position of vertical virtual hitch point O_v of the linkage unit can be modified. In order to determine the abscissa of point E (joint) of the lower bar to the implement, the angle φ had to be determined, between the axis of the inferior

drawbar and the vertical passing through the joint (B) of this bar to the tractor body. The position of point E depends on the working depth h of implement and the distance h_i on the vertical, between point E and the top of the effector elements (constructive height of the implement), from where the distance of joint E to the surface of the soil follows: $z_{E.} = h_i - h$.

The solving of the mathematical models that describe the geometric locus of the vertical virtual hitch point O_v , formed of the above systems of equations (1) and (2), allows analysis of tractor dynamics when working with attached machines with supported wheel. The vertical virtual hitch point O_v , of a working implement with supported wheel can be determined by solving the established mathematical models in MATHCAD. For this the input data fed to the mathematical models were the coordinates of the bars joints to the tractor body, as well as of the attachments points to the working implement body. For illustration purposes a system formed of an agricultural tractor type T

80 D (80 HP), equipped with a rear three—point linkage Category 2 (ISO 730-1), together with an soil loosening implement endowed with a supporting wheel (this system was used in the experimental research [5]), with working depth h . The implement working depth h was variable ranged between 0.1 to 0.5 m with a selected working depth increment of 0.05 m. Upon running of the programme the variation graphs were plotted of coordinates x_0 (upper curve) and z_0 (lower curve) of the vertical virtual hitch point versus working depth h (fig. 5).

Analysis of these graphically represented results reveals that with a increasing working depth h also the values of the vertical virtual hitch point O_v increase. The variation range of the abscissa is of $x_0 = 1.57 \dots 2.47$ m and of the ordinate $z_0 = 0.66 \dots 1.94$ m. For a working depth of 0.2...0.3 m the resulting coordinates were: $x_0 = 1.5 \dots 1.95$ m and $z_0 = 0.86 \dots 1.12$ m. The values were used as inputs for the analysis programme of the dynamics of tractor – soil loosening implement system [5].

Fig. 5. Variation of the coordinates x_0 (upper curve) and z_0 (lower curve) versus vertical virtual hitch point versus implement working depth h

3. Dynamic and mathematical modelling of the tractor – attached implement systems

The study of the influence of the tractor three—point linkage parameters on the dynamic behaviour of the system consisting of a

tractor and an attached implement with supporting wheels was conducted by dynamic and mathematical modelling of these systems. When working with a constant speed ($v = \text{const.}$) the tractor –implement system can be replaced with an equivalent dynamic model

defined by the exterior forces acting upon its components (tractor and implement), as shown in figure 6.

During motion the implement maintains a constant working depth h (established by the working technology) by means the supporting wheel attached to the implement body, that tracks the surface of the ground. In order to ensure the motion of the implement in vertical plane, in the hydraulic cylinder actuating the tractor three - point linkage the fluid is not under pressure (no pressure in the cylinders), so the piston is in floating position. Consequently, while moving on the ground the

implement oscillates around the virtual vertical point of rotation O of the four bar mechanism (resulting by the intersection of the directions of bars AD and BE of the three—point linkage). In figure 6 the position of vertical virtual hitch point O is given by the horizontal and vertical coordinates a_0 and h_0 in relation to the tangency (contact) point to the soil of the rear axle wheels of the tractors (point O_2).

The distance to joint E of the lower bars at the top of the effector element is given by height h_l and the working depth of the soil is given by distance h .

Fig. 6. Dynamic model of the tractor and attached implement with supporting wheels when working at constant speed on horizontal ground

The significance of the external forces in figure 6 is: G_t – tractor weight applied in the mass centre (of coordinates a_c and h_c); G_m – implement weight applied in the mass centre (of coordinates a_m and h_m); Z_1 and Z_2 – normal loads on the front and rear axle of the tractor; Z_m – normal load on the supporting axle (wheel) of the implement; R_{rt} – rolling resistances of the tractor wheels ($R_{rt} = f_i (Z_1 + Z_2)$, where f_i is the rolling resistance coefficient of tractor wheels); R_{rm} – rolling resistance of the implement supporting wheels ($R_{rm} = f_m Z_m$, where f_m is the coefficient of rolling resistance of the implement supporting wheels).

The resultant force F , occurring from the interaction of the implement working elements with the soil, generally forms an angle γ with the road surface and can be decomposed into: the traction resisting force $F_x = F \cos \gamma$, parallel to the soil surface, and the pressing force

$F_z = F \sin \gamma$, normal to the soil surface (the magnitudes of components F_x and F_z and angle γ depend on the type of working process and the construction of the working elements).

Traction resistance force of the implement F_x is considered to vary linearly with the working depth h , being given by the relation [5]:

$$F_x = k h, \quad (3)$$

where k represents the specific resistance of soil per unit of working depth (experimentally determined), in N/m.

The pressing force F_z depends on the angle of inclination γ of the resultant F and can be mathematically modeled by the relation:

$$F_z = F_x \operatorname{tg} \gamma = k h \operatorname{tg} \gamma. \quad (4)$$

The depth h_r at which acts the interaction force of the soil on the working elements is considered placed at a depth h_r , which for the

loosening process of implement is given by the relation [5]:

$$h_r = 0,6 h \quad (5)$$

The dynamic behaviour of the tractor – attached implement system with a supporting wheel can be analyzed as depending upon the dynamic loads on the tractor axles Z_1 and Z_2 on

the implement supporting wheel Z_m . The values of loads are obtained from the equilibrium equations of the tractor-implement system as a whole and of the implement separately (during work the implement oscillates by vertical virtual hitch point of rotation O). The final computational relationships of the dynamic loads are:

$$Z_1 = \frac{G_t \cdot a_c}{L_t} - \frac{[G_m \cdot (l_t + a_m) + F_z \cdot (l_t + l_r)]}{L_t} + \frac{F_x \cdot h_r}{L_t} + \frac{Z_m \cdot (l_t + l_s)}{L_t}; \quad (6)$$

$$Z_2 = \frac{G_t \cdot (L_t - a_c)}{L_t} + \frac{[G_m \cdot (l_t + a_m) + F_z \cdot (l_t + l_r)]}{L_t} - \frac{F_x \cdot h_r}{L_t} - \frac{Z_m \cdot (l_t + l_s)}{L_t} + (G_m + F_z - Z_m); \quad (7)$$

$$Z_m = \frac{G_m \cdot (a_0 + l_t + a_m) + F_z \cdot (a_0 + l_t + l_r) - F_x \cdot (h_r + h_0)}{(a_0 + l_t + l_m + f_m h_0)}; \quad (8)$$

The system of equations (6), (7) and (8) represents the mathematical model that describes the dynamic behaviour of the system in the vertical longitudinal plane, thus allowing analysis of the longitudinal stability in overturning and moving (manoeuvrability). During free motion of the tractor (without an attached implement) the forces acting on the implement (G_m , F_x , F_z , Z_m and R_{rm}) are zero, as the loads on the tractor axles are:

$$Z_{10} = \frac{G_t \cdot a_c}{L_t}; \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta Z_1 = Z_1 - Z_{10} = -\frac{[G_m \cdot (l_t + a_m) + F_z \cdot (l_t + l_r)]}{L_t} + \frac{F_x \cdot h_r}{L_t} + \frac{Z_m \cdot (l_t + l_s)}{L_t}; \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta Z_2 = Z_2 - Z_{20} = \frac{[G_m \cdot (l_t + a_m) + F_z \cdot (l_t + l_r)]}{L_t} - \frac{F_x \cdot h_r}{L_t} - \frac{Z_m \cdot (l_t + l_s)}{L_t} + (G_m + F_z - Z_m); \quad (12)$$

The above equations reveals that under the action of exterior forces on the implement during work (G_m , F_x , F_z , Z_m and R_{rm}) the front axle of the tractor is unloaded by ΔZ_1 that is transferred to its rear axle. The traction resisting force of the implement, F_x causes a loading of the front axle by ΔZ_1 and an unloading of the rear axle by the same quantity. The presence of the supporting wheel of the implement generates a load Z_m upon it that causes the unloading of the rear axle by ΔZ_2 and a loading by the same quantity of the front axle, simultaneously with transferring to this axle of the

$$Z_{20} = \frac{G_t \cdot (L_t - a_c)}{L_t}, \quad (10)$$

that represent the static loads on the tractor axles.

It follows that under the influence of the implements attached via the three—point linkage, the additional loads ΔZ_1 and ΔZ_2 on the tractor axles in relation to the loads during free motion (static loads) are give by the equations:

diminished load ($G_m + F_z - Z_m$). It follows that the presence of the supporting wheel on the implement causes it to take over part of the vertical forces that act upon the implement, thus diminishing the transfer to the tractor of the implement weight G_m and of the vertical component F_z of the interaction force of the implement effectors with the soil.

The transfer process of the loads from the implement to the tractor causes the load on the tractor rear axle to increase (a favourable situation for tractors with only one – rear - driving axle, that thus increase their adherent

load), but at the same time decreases longitudinal stability and manoeuvrability of the tractor. When the load on the front axle becomes zero ($Z_1 = 0$) the tractor loses its longitudinal stability and turns over by the wheels of the rear axle. When the load on the front axle Z_1 becomes smaller than 20% of the tractor weight (that is $Z_1 < 0.2 G_t$) the tractor loses its manoeuvrability; this is a critical situation that calls for ballasting (loading) the front axle with additional weights (mounted on the front wheels or on the front cross brace of the tractor) in order to regain safe control over the direction of motion of the tractor.

From the equation of load Z_m on the support wheel (5) it follows that in addition to the constructive and functional factors of the implement (forces G_m , F_x , F_z , dimensions l , l_m and L_r , as well as depth h_r of the application point of the resistance force to traction F_x), the coordinates a_o and h_o of the vertical virtual hitch point of rotation O the linkage have a

significant influence on the value of the load transmitted to the support wheel of the implement. The position of vertical virtual hitch point O can be modified by mounting the upper bar of the three - point linkage in various positions D (3 points) on the body of the implement (which constructively are distanced at 50 mm), by the position of the implement wheel in relation to the coupling elements E of the lower bar (distance l_s) and by the depth h_r at which the resistance force to traction F_x of the effector element is active. (distance h_r depends on the working depth h of the implement; for soil loosening with chisel type effector elements $h_r = 0.6 h$ [5]). Thus, by computation and simulation the optimum positions of the virtual vertical point the tractor three - point linkage and of the implement support wheel can be identified, so that the latter is subjected to a minimum load $Z_{m\ min}$, (necessary for copying the ground), while the rest of the loads on the implement are transferred to the tractor.

Fig. 7. Variation of the loads on the tractor axles (Z_1 and Z_2), of the load on the implement support wheel (Z_m) and of the additional loads of the axles in relation to the static loads (ΔZ_1 and ΔZ_2) versus working depth h

The graphs of figure 7 show, for illustration purposes, the variation of the loads on the tractor axles and on the implement (Z_1 and Z_2), as well as of the additional loads on the tractor axles

(ΔZ_1 and ΔZ_2) and on the implement versus working depth; the graphs also feature the variation of the resistance force to traction F_x and of the pressure F_z caused by the effectors.

4. Conclusions

In order to study of tractor longitudinal stability and manoeuvrability of the system formed of the tractor with attached implement with supporting wheels the tractor – implement systems can be replaced by equivalent dynamic models. Knowing the magnitude and action of the exterior forces included by the dynamic model, the mathematical models can be developed accordingly; which describes the dynamic behaviour of the system in various situations of motion and work.

The optimization of dynamics and energy consumption of tractor – soil working machine systems with supporting wheels consists of achieving a coupling (linking) of the machine to the tractor three-point linkage that satisfies a transfer to the largest possible extent onto the tractor of the vertical loads of the machine (machine weight and the vertical component of the working elements – soil interaction force).

In the case of implements with supporting wheels, only part of the forces acting upon the machine (that is machine weight and the forces normal to the soil acting upon the working elements) is transferred onto the tractor, as part of these forces are taken over by the supporting wheel of the machine. The closer the virtual hitch point to the tractor rear axle, the smaller the load on the machine supporting wheel will be, the greater the load on the rear axle and the higher the degree of unloading of the front axle.

Computer aided simulation of the mathematical models allows the study of the dynamic behaviour of the tractor-implement in

different work conditions, in view of identifying optimization solutions of its dynamics and energetic.

The developed mathematical models can utilize data obtained by experimental measurements, like magnitude and direction of the forces acting upon the working elements of the machine for various soil conditions, at different depths and velocities.

References

1. Popescu, S., Popescu, O. *Dynamic and Mathematical Model for the Study of Tractor – Implement Behaviour in Field Conditions*. In: The IIth International Conference, MOTOROL'99, Lublin /Poland, vol. I, p. 291-299.
2. Popescu, S., Ene, T.A *Analysis of the influence of constructive and work parameters of agricultural tractor wheels tires upon the agricultural soil stress*. In: Proceeding of the International Conference “Research People and Actual Tasks on Multidisciplinary Sciences” June 2007, Lozenec/Bulgaria, Vol.2, p. 178-182.
3. Renius, K. *Th. Traktoren. Technik und ihre Anwendung*. Verlagsunionn - Agrar, Muenchen, 1987.
4. Stout, B. A., CIGR. *Handbook of Agricultural Engineering, vol. III*, Edition CIGR – ASAE, 1999, p. 165...175.
5. Totolici, I. *Theoretical and experimental modelling of the soil loosening process*. PhD Thesis, Transilvania University of Brasov/Romania, 2011.

TO THE QUESTION OF VOLUMETRIC DIVIDER DEVELOPMENT FOR FROZEN MEAT DUMPLING

V. Vladimirov*, Y. Petrova**, S. Vladimirov*

Abstract: *In this study, frozen meat dumpling movement in measuring tank under vertical harmonic vibrations was considered. Recommendations for definition of vibrator rational acceleration, needed to carry out stabilization of meat dumpling bulk density were given.*

Key words: *frozen meat dumpling, vibration, volumetric divider*

1. Introduction

Production of meat dumpling - one of the most economically viable. Meat dumpling (pelmeni) and curd or fruit dumpling (vareniki) are high popular in Ukraine, and there is no subject to seasonal influences on this product demand.

Populations heighten interest to low serial production carried out development of manufacturing meat dumpling small business. However, product release is also connected with significant costs on handwork, and on prepacking which has the influence on unit value.

Specification of pelmeni prepacking in small packages lies in largeness of volume rate, occurred by the filling product unit, to the overall portion volume; high – accuracy dosing, comparable with pelmeni weight; in entangled geometric shape and negative temperature (-10°C) during pelmeni prepacking. All this factors bound early developed dividers for granular materials prepacking, that's why constructions range, based on weighted and combined methods of dose measurement was developed. However, licensed machines are expensive and are not reliable, or have mass measurement low accuracy, requiring additional costs on their updating. Enumerated disadvantages are also sharply felt on meat works of middle and low power. In result, at the present time the majority of works in our country use handwork prepacking, this has some disadvantages such as deficiency of mass measurement accuracy and deficiency of enough capacity and also creates physical burdens for prepackers. [1]

Feasible direction evaluation for pelmenis prepacking machines development, cancelling out early developed constructions disadvantages, showed us that the most effective are combined machines made up of volumetric divider and weighting and culling portions device. In addition, applied volumetric dividers have mass measurement low accuracy, which has the influence on production, overall size, value and steel intensity of the machine.

That's why workings focused on development small size volumetric dividers for pelmenis prepacking in small pack with mass measurement high accuracy are vital.

Tentative investigated experiments showed that pelmenis dosing accuracy has materially affect on bulk weight vibrations. Vertical harmonic vibrations are used for bulk weight stabilization [2].

2. Materials and methods

For detailed study of bulk weight vibrostabilization process in measurement tank aggregate was developed (Fig. 1) and high speed photography method was carried out. Aggregate consists of glassy measure tank 1 ($D = 80$ mm, $H=160$ mm) Piston 2 placed at the bottom part of aggregate rigidly bounded with strain-measuring balk 3 with the help of the stock, in the frame 4. Frame connected with plunger 5, brought in excursion by cam mechanism. During oscillation period piston position recorded by movement strain indicator. Amplitude and vibrational frequency are regulated with the help of cam

* Dept. of Equipment Food Products, Donetsk national university economics and trade after M. Tugan-Baranovsky, Ukraine, e-mail:obladn@kaf.donduet.edu.ua

** Dept. of Food Products, Donetsk national university economics and trade after M. Tugan-Baranovsky, Ukraine, e-mail:Yunic@ukr.net

mechanism eccentricity variation and eccentric rotation speed.

Fig.1. Stand for pelmenis bulk weight vibrostabilization process research with use of high-speed photography method:

1 – measuring tank; 2 – piston; 3 – strain-measuring balk;
4 – frame; 5 – plunger

For photographic film interpretation convenience reticule has been applied on container and pelmenis have been drawn down by blooming. High-speed filming was carried out by cinecamera CKC-1H. Shooting speed was defined experimentally and was composed for 2000 cadre/sec.

Aggregate functioned in following manner: measure tank 1 was bended under hopper, where was filled by imitator and then was placed under vibration piston. Plunger 5 was geared by cam mechanism while motor was turned on. Piston 2 was geared by strain-measuring balk. Strain-measuring balk was deflected during communication of product and piston. While oscillograph was turned on, motor rotation was faded in until terference between imitator and piston has appeared.

With the help of oscillogram interpretation vibration frequency was defined, whereby falling object contact with vibration piston was registered on his halfway, in other words free fall trajectory was matched by amplitude. During pressure increasing contact moment on vibration piston was registered on oscillogram.

Tentative investigated experiments showed that optimum acceleration ranges in $q_{vb} = 8 \text{ m/sec}^2$,

that's why high speed filming was carried out by next vibration accelerations: 1; 8; 15 m/sec^2 .

Measure tank was filled by test object and placed above vibrator before high-speed filming. Cinecamera and oscillograph were turned on, and upon the expiry of 0,5 sec – vibrator was turned on too.

Kinegram review highlighted that during vibration acceleration in range of $q_{vb} = 8 \text{ m/sec}^2$ intensive product orientation across measure tank volume and packing of voids were observed. Besides, these effects arise with product free fall. When test object covers the distance equal to amplitude its compatible with piston, which fades out his velocity. Pelmenis come in touch with each other almost without any stable position changes, discovered during falling process. Pelmenis orientation ends on completing 5...8 vibrations, excluding topping where pelmenis continue orientation touching measure tank brim. During upward motion they didn't move relative to each other.

Pelmenis, during vibration cycle contacted with vibrator and not oriented at low acceleration $q_{vb}=1 \text{ m/sec}^2$.

Pelmenis, during the movement under vibrator action filled free space with the acceleration $q_{vb}=15 \text{ m/sec}^2$. Product downward motion followed

by orientation of his particules, which aimed to locate bigger side along measure tank wall. In the time of piston bump, at the expense of elastic strains, there was orientation along piston platitude. It's conducted to pelmenis vibration close to center of mass. Product topping under vibration action bestirs in boiling stage. During the process pelmenis changed their position i.e. misorientation process flows.

3. Conclusion: optimum pelmenis orientation occurs with vibrator acceleration $a_{vb} = 9 \text{ m/sec}^2$. Pelmenis orientation descends across volume at the same time. Acceleration excursion to forward direction leads to misorientation pelmenis topping, to backward direction – pelmenis orientation is not observed at all. All this facts affect on volumetric dosing accuracy.

High-speed filming method also showed that effective vibrator acceleration must overpass product drop acceleration in measure tank in $1,1 \div 1,3$ times.

References

1. Владіміров В.М., Войтюшенко Н.М. До питання створення устаткування для виробництва пельменів. Обладнання та технологія харчових виробництв: Темат. зб. наук. пр./ Голов. ред. О.О. Шубін. –Донецьк: ДонДУЕТ, 2005. – Вип.12.- 218с.

2. Гончаречич И.Ф., Урьев Н.Б., Тайлесник М.А. Вибрационная техника пищевой в промышленности/под.ред. Урьева Н.Б. –М.: «Пищевая промышленность», 1977 –284с.

WOOD ONE OF THE OLDEST CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS IN HISTORICAL BUILDINGS

O. ZELENICU * B. LEPADATESCU **

Abstract: *In Romania mioritic space, nature and tradition are interconnected and are found in forms that delight us by their simplicity and longevity. They are materialized in objects, houses, wooden churches that have survived over time, and represent the Romania's cultural heritage. The paper is an overview of some ancient wooden construction aiming to bring into attention the importance of wood as renewable and sustainable raw material for buildings helping to understand the heritage we have to preserve for our identity over generations. A brief description of the oldest wooden constructions in the world and in Romania, especially churches from Maramures, is presented. This served to emphasize the role of wood as sustainable material and in the same time the importance of preserving our cultural heritage. The building system and the key factors necessary to be taken into consideration to perform durable buildings are outlined.*

Keywords: *durability, churches, old building, wooden structure.*

1. Introduction

Wood is a renewable, durable and versatile material, known as one of the most traditional building materials all over the world. In our country there is a tradition of using wood in construction represented by houses, churches, bridges, load-bearing timber structures, porches, fences, gates, really masterpieces of art.

In favor of promoting and expanding the use of wood and wood-based products in construction are the following arguments:

- high strength-to-weight ratio;
- low energy consumption in operation;
- the manufacture of wood products generates little carbon dioxide emissions;
- working with wood is relatively effortless and can be processed in any shape and size using a wide variety of jointing techniques and methods;
- long-term carbon storage (the captured carbon contained in the wood is stored in-situ in the wooden structures);
- ensure total comfort and aesthetic;
- less expensive than many alternatives.

The problems with wood are related to biodegradability and combustibility. Due to its organic composition, wood is naturally

susceptible to degradation and the propagation speed of these phenomena is directly influenced by abiotic (sun, wind, water, certain chemicals and fire) and biotic (decay and mold fungi, bacteria and insects) factors. Exposure in certain conditions of temperature and humidity affects not only the appearance of wood (grey color, splits, cracks etc), but can lead to destruction of its physical and mechanical characteristics. Even so, the balance is in favor of wood as raw material for buildings (Fig.1).

The paper aims to present the wood, from the building material perspective, which has lasted over centuries. A brief description of the oldest wooden constructions in the world and wooden churches from Maramures county is presented. This served to emphasize the role of wood as sustainable material and in the same time the importance of preserving our cultural heritage.

2. Wooden buildings lasting over centuries

Some of the oldest buildings in the world are wooden buildings. The earliest evidence of wood construction is a site near Nice, France, built 400,000 years ago using wood posts for support. The oldest wood construction found intact is located in northwest Germany, and was built about 7,300 years ago

* Dept. of Wood Processing and Wooden Products Design, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: zoctavia@unitbv.ro

** Dept. of Technological Engineering and Industrial Management, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: lepadatescu@unitbv.ro

(www.madehow.com). Hand tools and sawmill powered by the flow of water (dates from about 375), were used to process the wood. There are

different other wooden buildings attested as the oldest on the world (en.wikipedia.org), which are described in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Wood issues as building material

Table 1

No.	Wooden buildings	Year of building	Site- location	Characteristics
1.	Hōryū-ji (the Learning Temple of the Flourishing Law)	It is believed to have been completed by 607	Ikaruga, Nara Prefecture, Japan	The oldest wooden buildings still currently standing A buddhist temple; the complex serving as seminary and monastery..
2.	The Lhasa Jokhang (Alexandre, 2006)	The beginning of the 7 th century	Tibet	The oldest timber frame building in Tibet. A significant monument of surviving early Indian religious timber architecture
3.	Greensted Church	The mid-9th or mid-11th century.	Greensted village, near Chipping Ongar in Essex, England	The oldest wooden church in the world and probably the oldest wooden building in Europe. It was used large split oak tree trunks, known as traditional Saxon form of construction.
4.	Yingxian pagoda (real name Sakyamuni Pagoda) (china.org.cn)	Year 1056 during the Liao Dynasty	located in Fogong (Buddha's Palace) Temple in Yingxian China	It was built completely of timber, having 67.31 m high and it is the only extant large wooden pagoda in China and also the tallest among ancient wooden buildings of the world.
5.	Nideröst house in Schwyz. (niderost.com)	Built in 1176	In Schwyz, Switzerland	The oldest timber building of Central Europe
6.	Urnes Stave Church	Built around 1130	Luster in Sogn og Fjordane county, Norway	It is believed to be the oldest of its kind. It provides a link between Christian architecture and the architecture and artforms of the Viking Age with typical animal-ornamentation, the so called "Urnes style" of animal-art.
7.	House of Bethlehem (O'Dea, 2009)	Around 1287	Schwyz in central Switzerland	Bethlehem is one of a group of 12 ancient wooden houses in Schwyz – which happen to be the oldest surviving in Europe.
8.	The Fairbanks House	Built between 1637 and 1641	Dedham Massachusetts, North America	it the oldest surviving timber-frame house in North America. Exterior walls were covered with wide oak clapboards at the front, narrower oak on the west gable end, and narrow cedar on the rear.

9.	Kizhi churches (Intercession and Transfiguration churches) (Kelley, 2000)	Between 1694-1714	Kizhi Island in Karelia, Russia	major basic structural unit is a round log of Scotts pine (<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>) about 30 cm in diameter and 3 to 5 meters long Flat roofs were made of spruce planks and the domes are covered in aspen.
10	Europe's oldest wooden houses and churches	Between 13 th -18 th centuries	France, England, Scotland, Poland, Romania, Moldavia, Slovakia, etc.	Mostly are built using timber-frame structures

Timber has been used as a construction material in buildings in the UK since the Neolithic period. In Europe some of the oldest timber houses are found in England and Scotland and the earliest timber framed buildings existing in the UK today date back to the 13th century (Byrne, 2009).

In France in different regions like Normandy, Alsace, Brittany, Aquitaine and Paris, are often seen historical timber frame buildings and the wooden chalets in mountain regions well known, which are the prove of wood durability over time.

3. The oldest wooden churches and the Romanian cultural heritage

In all Europe, wooden churches are survived during centuries and the oldest known are: Karelia and northern Russia (1714), Petäjävesi Old Church (1763) in Finland, the Urnes Stave Church in Norway (1130), Ulucz wooden Orthodox church in Poland (1510), Hronsek church Slovakia,(1725), Broumov in Eastern Bohemia, Czech Republic (1177), the church „Saint Hierarch Nicholas” Moldavia (1757), the Church of St Mykola Chudotvoret (St Nicholas the Miracle-Worker) Ukraine (1604) and more others.

In Romania, the Wooden Churches of Maramures and gates represent a testimony of the knowledge and use of wood by local craftsmen from ancient times. Maramures is situated on the Northwest Romania, on northeastern Carpathians, along the upper Tisa River (bordering Ukraine in the north, Satu Mare county in the west). Maramures villages are distinguished by their wooden churches, unique in shape and ornamentation and eight of them in Barsana, Budesti, Desesti, Ieud, Plopis, Poienile Izei, Rogoz and Surdesti, have been recognized by UNESCO as World Heritage Sites (romaniantourism.com). Their characteristics (tall, narrow with high roofs and pointed steeples) can be described as a Gothic Style of

Maramures and they are built with the 14th century and up to the 18th century.

The oldest standing church in Maramures is considered the Church on the Hill in Ieud, namely "Birth of the Virgin" was built in 1364 and it is made of fir tree wood. The value of the church is amplified by the Codex of Ieud the oldest document written in Romanian (dated 1391, but the Romanian original dates from 792) the first document proving the existence of Romanian language (Romanian history and culture, 2009)

Among the oldest wooden churches are also considered the church from Poienile Izei, (the patron Pious Paraschiva) erected in 1604. The construction is fairly small and has a two-tier roof over the entire structure. The steeple is very short with an open balcony that expands outside of the tower. In Budesti we can found the church built in 1643, 38 m height. It has two-tier roof over the whole surface of the building with 14 pillars (7 on each side) that support the roof. The bell-steeple has an open balcony and four small towers on the spire. Barsana church having the Dedication day "The Entrance of the Virgin Mary in the Church" was built in 1720. Made of oak logs, having a double-shingled roof and the porch in two levels is considered one of the few wooden churches in Maramures with such a feature. Şurdeşti church is built on a hill in 1724 has "St. Archangels Michael and Gabriel" as patrons and is considered the highest old wooden church in Romania and in the world. (cimec.ro, 1999)

The tower measures 54 m, and the total height, measured from the bottom, being 72 m. The roof is two-tiered on its entire surface and the spire has four small turrets. The church is made completely of oak wood, without nails and the roof has performed of thousands of oak shingles.

The churches usually are built on the hills so the rain would slide off easily. The churches generally consist of a porch, a main room, and a

tower or steeple and a balcony. One of their important features is the tall tower, with spires which have a symbolic meaning that the people prayers could easily reach up into the Heavens and the massive shingled roofs (Fig. 2).

It is important to underline their common characteristic, the wooden structure which lasted over time, bringing us the ancient tradition which is transformed in a valuable heritage for the future generations.

Fig. 2. Tall towers of wooden churches: a. Ieud (tripadvisor.com); b. Budesti (flickr.com)

4. Traditional wooden building system

Looking back on the historical timber buildings and also on contemporary ones, these can be classified into two main categories (Langenbach, 2010):

- those where the entire above ground structure and enclosure system of a building consists of wood products except for plaster, nails and fasteners;
- those where the timber is used in combination with other materials such as masonry for the structure and enclosure of the buildings.

In the first category are included the oldest form of timber construction, a log cabin (Langenbach, 2010), characterized by solid wall structures, using undressed logs laid up like masonry, without nails.

The former category is referred to timber frames. Timber framing is the method of creating framed structures of heavy timber jointed together with various joints (lap jointing and mortise and tenon joint). Diagonal bracing is used to prevent "racking", or movement of structural vertical beams or posts. Timber framing techniques date back to Neolithic times, and can be seen in different parts of the world (ancient Japan, continental Europe, England Scotland, France, Germany, Denmark etc) (en.wikipedia.org) (Fig 3c)

In northern Romania, in the Maramures region, many of the houses and churches are made of wood. The churches impressed by the variety of designs and are recognized by their slender appearance slim clock towers at the western end of the building, either single or double-roofed and covered by shingles. The constructions are made generally of oak wood, in conformity with the Blockbau system (Constantinescu, 2008), or notched beam structures (the walls are made of overlapping round logs, that cross in the corners) (Fig.3a,b)

Originally founded upon huge blocks of wood rather than stone, the churches have walls built of massive baulks of oak without the help of any iron nails, reaching impressive heights (i.e. church of Surdesti, of 72 m, one of the highest wooden buildings in Europe). Walls made of spruce baulks used in the nearby Iza Valley have not survived so well (Fran, 1983).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3. (a), (b) - Blockbau system in wooden constructions (greenmountainholidays.ro), (c)- timber framing technique

There are many other wooden churches in other regions of Romania (Moldova, Muntenia, Oltenia, Banat and Crişana) which are not so well preserved and or are replaced by the local communities by the new brick churches. They don't understand the unique value of these churches which should be restored and properly

maintained and care to ensure their role in history.

6. Understanding the building's performance

It is well known that wood exposed in exterior has to stand up to climatic changes (rain, snow, wind, UV, sun rays) and subjected to prolong wet conditions, could be affected by fungal decay and wood boring insect infestation. Most of the commonly employed strategies for protecting wood today involve drying, coating and or impregnation. The old churches in Maramures represent outstanding examples of wood durability over time without protection.

Durability is defined as the ability of a building or any of its components to perform the required functions in a service environment over a period of time without unforeseen cost for maintenance or repair (CSA, 2001).

Wood is a challenging material and to work it successfully, we need to know this raw material, and the craftsmen from Maramureş seems to have

an advanced knowledge about wood and its technical performances. Using durable species well selected and harvested only in certain period of the year, applying good building practice they created functional, structurally sound and aesthetically construction for decades. They have an advanced practical knowledge and especially knowledge about raw material which was kept almost in his natural form only with slight modification before using in a construction. People took part of the entire process from designing via raw material to the completed product, taking care of every detail.

Centuries of experience of using timber in constructions coupled with extensive research over the past few decades has shown us the safe methods of construction. The key is knowledge over the entire chain from forester to the craftsmen, passing through the conception of the architect and engineer. In Fig. 4 are represented the key factors which are need to be taken into consideration to create wooden durable buildings.

Fig. 4. Key factors for wooden durable buildings

7. Conclusions

Wood is a challenging material and through knowledge about the factors that affect wood it can be created durable constructions. Whatever their location (geographical latitude), wooden buildings continue to prove their capacity to resist any weather conditions. Wood as sustainable raw material needs to be treated with consideration not only to maintain its performance in the old buildings but to perform well also into the future. The church carpenters proved over centuries their technical performances, the high quality of the wood work and the artistic refinement, thus these special

historic wooden buildings deserve to be surveyed in a manner that befits their age and historical value.

Tourism is developing fast in region like Transylvania and wooden churches represent a real attraction for tourism. In this context should make people aware of the value of wood-based heritage.

References

1. Alexander, A. The Lhasa Jokhang – is the world's oldest timber frame building in Tibet. Web Journal on Cultural Patrimony, issue 1, p.124-154, 2006. <http://www.webjournal.unior.it>

2. Byrne, Phil, T. The History of Timber Frame Houses. 2009
http://EzineArticles.com/?expert=Phil_T
3. Constantinescu, B. Romanian Architectural Wooden Cultural Heritage – The Present Status - a Survey- In Proceeding of the International Conference COST Action IE0601/ESWM, 2008 – Braga, Portugal.
4. CSA- Guideline on durability in buildings. Canadian Standard Association -CSA S478-95, rev 2001.
5. Fran, Weatherhead. Wooden churches and their paintings in the Maramures region of Romania: a preliminary study. In Antiquity issue June 1993.
<http://findarticles.com/p/articles>.
6. Kelley, Stephen J. Wood structures: a global forum on the treatment, conservation, and repair of cultural heritage. ASTM International. 2000, p. 42–47. ISBN 080312497X. <http://books.google.com/>
7. Langenbach, R. Better than Steel? The use of timber for large and tall buildings from Ancient Times until the Present. Structures & Architecture, Guimaraes, Portugal July 2010.
8. O'Dea, C. Schwyz, Swissinfo.ch. 2009. <http://www.swissinfo.ch>
9. Tampone, G., Semplici M. Danger for wooden buildings. Rescuing the hidden European wooden churches heritage Print: Free Books S.r.l. Città di Castello (PG) Italy, 2006.
10. <http://www.madehow.com/Volume-3/Lumber.html>, accessed in February 2012
11. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/>, accessed in February 2012
12. <http://www.china.org.cn/english/TR-e/43436.htm>, accessed in February 2012
13. <http://www.niderost.com/>, accessed in February 2012
14. (<http://www.romaniatourism.com/world-heritage-sites.html>- World Heritage Sites in Romania, accessed in February 2012.
15. http://romanianhistoryandculture.webs.com/t_erramaramures.htm. 2009, accessed in February 2012
16. http://cimec.ro/Monumente/surdesti/surdesti_eng.htm 1999), accessed February 2012.
17. www.tripadvisor.com/Travel-g294457-d321332/Ro
18. <http://www.flickr.com/photos/7455207@N05/4052684916/>
19. <http://www.greenmountainholidays.ro/>.

GROUND OF THE USE OF INTERMEDIATE PRODUCT ON BASIS OF FAT FREE MILK WITH THE USE OF EXTRACT OF ROOT OF GLYCYRRHIZA IN PRODUCTION OF CREAM CREAMY

V. GNITSEVYCH, N. KRAVCHENKO

Abstract: In this article the recommended parameters of process of renewal of intermediate product are reasonable on the basis of fat free milk with the usage of an extract of root of glycyrrhiza, fundamental charts over of renewal of intermediate product and making of creamy cream are brought on its basis.

Key words: intermediate product on the basis of fat free milk with the use of an extract of root of glycyrrhiza, renewal, dissolution, fundamental chart, creamy cream, duty of water.

Nowadays in the food industry the greatest interest is caused by semi-finished products in the form of dry mixes which represent the high-concentrated system with humidity 4... 5 % which also have a number of advantages. After a long time without use of the special equipment it is possible to store such semi-finished products; their use conducts to considerable simplification of technological process, expansion of the range of dessert products and finishing semi-finished products in the enterprises of a restaurant economy etc [1].

Our analysis of prescription structure and the technological process of production of finishing semi-finished products showed that the structure of many mixtures includes, for example, a sugar syrup for which preparation a long thermal processing with the subsequent cooling is necessary what leads to long process of manufacturing of a product. Also it should be mentioned that in some mixtures the preliminary condensation of a prescription mix (for example, fruit mashed potatoes) which promotes duration of technological process is necessary, and also leads

to partial destruction of nutrients under the influence of high temperatures.

In order to avoid the defects given above, we have developed a dry semi-finished product on the basis of skim milk with the usage of extract of a root of solodka which application will allow to receive products of fast quality preparation.

The developed semi-finished product [2] should be referred to a semi-finished product of high degree of readiness on the basis of which production of finished goods is carried out according to the reduced technological scheme which provides semi-finished product with restoration by various solvents (the milk, different juice, water), hashing with prescription components and furnish.

Restoration (dissolution) of a semi-finished product is a necessary operation for preparation of finishing products. Therefore, studying of processes of restoration and determination of the recommended parameters for this process was the first investigation phase.

Fig.1. Dependence of solubility of a semi-finished product on liquid temperature

It is known that speed of dissolution depends on temperature of solvent which is applied to restoration [3]. Skim milk, vegetative juice and water (control) was used as a solvent.

The data which characterize solubility of a semi-finished product in the chosen solvents in a temperature range from 10°C to 50°C, is presented in the drawing 1.

It is visible from the 1 data given in the drawing, that solubility of a semi-finished product depends on temperature of liquid and has identical regularity for all solvents - in the range of temperatures 10... 50°C solubility makes from 77 % to 98 % respectively for each type of solvent. The smallest extent of dissolution is observed at 10°C and equals 76,81 %. At increase in temperature of liquid to 40°C the extent of dissolution quickly grows, while in the range of temperatures 40... 60°C process is slowed down. Complete dissolution of a semi-finished product in all liquids is observed at temperature 50... 60°C. Therefore according to the received experimental data it is expedient to use for renewal liquid with temperature 50... 60°C.

There are two ways of restoration of dry mixes: dissolution in a small amount of liquid with the following addition of liquid which have remained, and entering of a semi-finished product into settlement amount of liquid. It is established that for our semi-finished product the most optimum way is the one where the necessary quantity of a semi-finished product joins a continuous hashing prescription amount of the liquid, then the received

mixture is left for complete dissolution of dry parts, periodically striking mechanical hashing.

The following stage is researched by the amount of the liquid, necessary for restoration of a semi-finished product. This dependence was defined experimentally, by study of foam ability and firmness of foam of the brought-down systems on the basis of the developed semi-finished product.

It is established that the brought-down systems of semi-finished product: skim milk, semi-finished product: water, semi-finished product: juice are characterized by different foam ability.

The maximum of foaming is observed in the system a semi-finished product: skim milk, entering into system of additional amount of milk proteins which as a result of superficial activity make positive impact on foam ability of system. The highest foam ability equals 410-430 %. It is a characteristic for a ratio, semi-finished product: water 1:8... 1:10 that suits the concentration of the stabilizer 1,5... 1,0 %. The increase, as well as reduction of amount of milk, leads to decrease in foam ability in the system up to 200... 150 % .

The mixture of a semi-finished product and water shows the maximum level of foam (390 %) at a ratio of components respectively 1:14... 1:16. In this case concentration of the stabilizer makes 1,0... 0,8 %.

Fig. 2. Dependence of foam ability on the hydromodule

Fig. 3. Dependence of firmness of foam on the hydromodule

From the given data it is visible on drawings 2 and 3 that the complete recovery of a semi-finished product is observed through (15... 20) x60c, thus contents of the insoluble dairy rest make 0,1... 0,13 %.

The ratio of a semi-finished product and water (hydromodule) is established experimentally by the way of research of dependence of viscosity of the system from this ratio and shown in the drawing 3. It is established that viscosity of system should be in the range of $3 < \eta < 3,6$ Pa*s for receiving

finished goods of a necessary consistence. Therefore, analyzing the obtained data it is possible to draw a conclusion that rational ratios of a semi-finished product and liquid make 1:2,0; 1:2,5 (for milk); 1:1,5; 1:2,0 (for juice) and 1:1,0; 1:1,5 (for serum).

The schematic diagram of restoration of a semi-finished product on the basis of skim milk with use of extract of a root of a solodka is provided on drawing 4.

Fig. 4. The schematic diagram of restoration of a semi-finished product on the basis of skim milk with use of extract of a root of a solodka

The received results are based on technological process of the production of finishing creams on the basis of a semi-finished product.

The technological scheme of production of cream creamy includes the following operations:

- a semi-finished product restoration;
- preparation of prescription components;
- knocked down butter;
- connection of prescription components and butter with the restored semi-finished product;
- knocked down mixture;
- furnish.

The quality of ready creamy cream is defined both by structure and a ratio of components, and a technological mode of its preparation, namely: duration of knocking down and temperature. Therefore it is necessary to define the recommended temperature of restoration of a semi-finished product and butter.

It is known that oil used with temperature below 6°C is inexpedient, as the knocking down process complicates. This results from the fact that at destruction of strong the crystal structure of butter at low temperatures form an inclusion in the form of conglomerates of dairy fat which is difficult to give in to destruction that leads to decrease in quality of cream. Therefore the recommended temperature interval of a softening of butter makes 6... 14 °C.

By the previous researches it is established that the optimum temperature of a dairy and sugar syrup should make 20... 32°C for receiving qualitative creamy cream. As syrup used with temperature above 32°C promotes melting of dairy fat of butter which reduces quality of cream.

Due to the fact set above, the temperature of the restored semi-finished product which replaces long process of preparation of a dairy and sugar syrup in production of creamy cream, should make 20... 32°C.

It is experimentally established that butter used in temperature 6... 10°C leads to receiving cream with non-uniform structure. The non-uniform structure of cream speaks that as a result of contact to butter of low temperature there is a decrease in temperature and increase of viscosity of a semi-finished product which in the course of knocking down doesn't form an emulsion with oil. Oil temperature increase to 11... 14°C allows receiving a cream with rather high organoleptic indicators. The final temperature of a semi-finished product makes 22±0,5°C [4].

The speed of knocking down also considerably influences quality of creamy cream. Therefore, the most distant researches of detection of dependence of a vzbítost of cream from speed knockings down (drawing 5) were necessary.

Fig. 5- Dependence of fluffed up of cream from the prepared semi-finished product from speed of knocking down (duration of knocking down (7... 10) *60c).

Analyzing drawing 5 data, it is possible to draw a conclusion that the cream overrun in direct ratio depends on speed of knocking down from identical regularity both for control, and for a studied sample.

The maximal value of fluffed up cream acquires at speed of thurlling - 400 turn/min and subsequent

at the increase of speed of thurlling (higher 400 turn/min) has even character.

The technological scheme of preparation of creamy cream on the basis of the developed semi-finished product is provided on drawing 6.

Fig. 6. The technological scheme of a cream of a creamy semi-finished product in use.

The characteristic organoleptic indicators of a product on the basis of skim milk with use of an extract of a root glycyrrhiza is shown in table 1.

Table 1 - the Characteristic organoleptic indicators

The name of a product	The Characteristic of indicators
The creamy Cream	Appearance: magnificent weight with a glossy surface. The Color: from cream to the straw. The Smell: butter and the raw materials entering into its structure. The taste: butter, gentle, with slightly vegetative shade. Consistence: homogeneous, keeps the form well.

The analysis of organoleptic indicators testifies to high qualitative characteristics of a creamy cream made of a semi-finished product. As a result of the spent research the recommended parameters of process of restoration of a semi-

finished product on the basis of skim milk with use of an extract of a root glycyrrhiza are defined and circuit diagrams of restoration of a semi-finished product and manufacturing of a creamy cream on its basis are resulted.

References

1. Павлюк, Р.Ю. Новые фитодобавки и их использование в продуктах питания [Текст] : Монография / Р.Ю. Павлюк, А.И. Черевко, А.И. Украинец, В.В. Погарская, В.А. Афанасьева, Т.И. Прудникова, Л.А. Чуйко, Л.В. Миркушова ; Харьк. гос. ун-т питания и торговли ; Нац. ун-т пищ. технологий. — Харьков, Киев, 2003. - 287 с. - ISBN 966-7885-40-2.
2. Гніцевич, В.А. Технологія молочно-рослинного напівфабрикату для солодких страв та його властивості [Текст] / В.А. Гніцевич, Н.В. Вольнова (ДонНУЕТ) тематичний збірник наукових праць „Обладнання та технології харчових виробництв” – 2010. –Вип. 25. – С. 64-69.
3. Радаева, И.А. Основные условия производства молочных консервов и сухого молока [Текст] / И.А. Радаева // Молочная промышленность. – 2000. – №8. – с.32-34.
4. Ратушный, А.С. Сборник рецептур мучных кондитерских и булочных изделий для предприятий общественного питания[Текст] /А.С. Ратушный, Л.А. Старостина, Т.И. Захарова ; М.: Экономика, 1985. – 295с. – ИБ № 2421.

POLYPHENOLIC CONTENT AND ANTIOXIDANT POTENTIAL OF SOME SPECIES EXTRACTS FROM PIATRA CRAIULUI MOUNTAINS

D. HANGANU¹, A.M. ANTON¹, O. G. POP², A. MARCULESCU²

Abstract: This study evaluated the total content of phenolic compounds and the free radical scavenging activity of some plants harvested from Piatra Craiului Mountains. The total phenolic content was measured by Folin –Ciocalteu reagent assay while the DPPH method was used to determine the antioxidant activity. *Rhododendron myrtifolium* extract showed the highest phenolic content (15.98 %) followed by *Alchemilla flabellata* extract with 11.68 %. The 2 most potent free radical scavenging activities were found in *Rhododendron myrtifolium* and *Alchemilla flabellata* extracts (91,4% and 91,6%). Concluding, a great amount of polyphenols compounds determines a high antioxidant capacity.

Keywords: phenolic compounds, free radical scavenging activity, Piatra Craiului Mountains

1. Introduction

Piatra Craiului mountains has a rich and widely spread spontaneous flora. There are many plants yet not identified or yet not known for their chemical composition and medical properties. It is our duty, as researchers, to discover new sources of natural treatments.

Nowadays, many disorders are the direct cause of free radicals such as nitric oxide or the alkoxy radicals. These are produced through aerobic respiration and they have a great impact on the human body cells and thus, increasing the risk of chronic diseases. To prevent this, a diet rich in edible antioxidants is recommended. Antioxidants are responsible for the neutralization of free radicals and can help the cells to reduce oxidative stress damages. Plants are a very important source of antioxidants such as several phenolic compounds and finding new species to analyzed is our goal (1,2).

In this study, we measured the total polyphenolic content from *Erigeron annuus*, *Rhododendron myrtifolium*, *Alchemilla flabellata*, *Thymus alpestris*, *Achillea schurii* and *Polygala amara* extracts. Also, to determine the total antioxidant capacity of these extracts we used DPPH assay (2,2-diphenylpicrylhydrazil radical scavenging capacity), a method based on single electron transfer (SET). One of the objectives is to correlate the antioxidant method applied with total polyphenolic content (3).

2. Materials and methods

Chemicals

The 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) 95% purity, Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). Folin-Ciocalteu's phenol reagent, methanol, ethanol and Na₂CO₃ were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

Aparatus

UV-VIS Spectrophotometer Jasco V-530

Samples extraction

The plants were harvested from Piatra Craiului mountains in the summer of 2011. After harvesting, they were cleaned in tap water and air dried at room temperature in the dark separately. After griding the herba part of the plants in a blender and turning them into powders, we took 5 g from each species and soaked them in 100 ml ethanol 50% at the temperature of 60 °C in a thermostatic bath.

Total polyphenolic content

Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent was initially intended for the analysis of proteins taking advantage of the reagent's activity toward protein tyrosine (containing a phenol group) resid. Obviously, the Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent is nonspecific to phenolic compounds as it can be

¹ Department of Pharmacognosy - Phytoterapy, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Iuliu Hațieganu", Cluj-Napoca, I.Creangă str., no. 12, Romania

² "Transylvania" University from Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism, Brasov, Romania. e-mail: oliviupop@yahoo.com

reduced by many nonphenolic compounds (vitamin C, Cu(I), etc.). Phenolic compounds react with Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent only under basic conditions (adjusted by a sodium carbonate solution to pH =10). Dissociation of a phenolic proton leads to a phenolate anion, which is capable of reducing Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent. This supports the notion that the reaction occurs through electron transfer mechanism. The blue compounds formed between phenolate and Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent are independent of the structure of phenolic compounds, therefore ruling out the possibility of coordination complexes formed between the metal center and the phenolic compounds. Despite the undefined chemical nature of Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent, the total phenols assay by Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent is convenient, simple, and reproducible (4).

Assay protocol

The standard curve was done using different concentrations of gallic acid (mg/ml). Absorption at 765 nm was measured. Total phenol contents were expressed in gallic acid equivalents (mg gallic acid/g sample).

Free radical scavenging activity determination

The DPPH \cdot radical is one of the few stable organic nitrogen radicals, which bears a deep purple color. It is commercially available and does not have to be generated before assay like ABTS. +. This assay is based on the measurement of the reducing ability of antioxidants toward DPPH \cdot .

Antioxidant assays are based on measurement of the loss of DPPH color at 517 nm after reaction with test compounds, and the reaction is monitored by a spectrophotometer.

A rapid, simple and inexpensive method to measure antioxidant capacity of food involves the use of the free radical, 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH \cdot). DPPH \cdot is widely used to test the ability of compounds to act as free radical scavengers or hydrogen donors, and to evaluate antioxidant activity of foods and not only. It has also been used to quantify antioxidants in complex biological systems in recent years. The DPPH method can be used for solid or liquid samples and is not specific to any particular antioxidant component, but applies to the overall antioxidant capacity of the sample.

Antioxidant activity has been expressed in various ways including the percentage of the reagent used, the oxidation inhibition rate and so on. An easier way to present antioxidant activity of the extracts would be a common reference

standard, that can be a synthetic antioxidant known as butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT).

Assay protocol

The DPPH \cdot solution was obtained from 10 mg of DPPH \cdot dissolved in 100 ml ethanol.

After diluting each extract, properly, we arrived at the concentration of 4×10^{-4} g FW/2ml. We took 2 ml from these dilutions and mixed them up with 2ml DPPH \cdot solution. After 30 minutes of incubation at 40 °C in a thermostatic bath, the absorbance of each sample was recorded at 517 nm.

To realize a suitable comparison, we prepared the standard antioxidant solution with the same concentration as the samples, meaning 4×10^{-4} g BHT/2ml. The measurement of the antioxidant activity was done following the same protocol as for the extracts.

The scavenging activity (antioxidant activity) was calculated with the next formula:

$$I\% = [(A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{control}}] \times 100$$

$$I\% = \text{DPPH}\cdot \text{ radical scavenging activity (\%)}$$

A_{control} = the absorbance of the DPPH solution without an antioxidant

A_{sample} = the absorbance of the sample (extract or BHT) with the DPPH \cdot solution, after incubation

3. Results and discussions

Total polyphenolic content of the extracts

Phenolic compounds are a class of antioxidant agents which act as free radical terminators (1). The Folin-Ciocalteu method is an electron transfer based assay and gives reducing capacity. It is known that total polyphenols are highly correlated with antioxidant activity and their bioavailability has been reported (5, 6, 7).

Table 1 showed the content of phenols that were found in the plants extracts measured using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and expressed in terms of gallic acid equivalent (standard curve equation: $y = 2.364X + 0.0649$, $R^2 = 0.9909$) and concentration % of gallic acid. The extract from *Rhododendron myrtifolium* contains the highest concentration of phenols from the entire series (15.98 %). The second highest concentration was that of *Alchemilla flabellata* (11.68%) and followed by *Achillea schurii*, *Erigeron annuus* and *Thymus alpestris*. The lowest concentration in phenols is 4.47% for the *Polygala amara* extract. According to our study, the phenolic compounds in *Rhododendron myrtifolium* and *Alchemilla flabellata* can be responsible for the

great antioxidant activity.

Fig. 1. DPPH• chemical structure and its reaction with a scavenger, indicated by A-H.

Tab. 1: Phenolic content in the studied plants extracts.

Sample	Absorbance	X(mg GA/sample)	C% (g GA/100g DW)
<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	0.5741	0.142	7.09
<i>Alchemilla flabellata</i>	0.9112	0.234	11.68
<i>Rhododendron myrtifolium</i>	1.2269	0.320	15.98
<i>Thymus alpestris</i>	0.5333	0.131	6.54
<i>Achillea schurii</i>	0.6761	0.170	8.48
<i>Polygala amara</i>	0.381	0.089	4.47

*GA= gallic acid, DW= herba dried

Free radical scavenging activity

Free radicals, particularly reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), are involved in the pathogenesis of several chronic and degenerative diseases such as inflammation, cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases, cancer and aging-related disorders (8, 9, 10).

The use of the DPPH• reaction (Fig. 1) has been widely diffused among food technologists and researchers, for the evaluation of free radical scavenging activity on extracts from plant, food material or on single compounds (11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16) because of its ease of use and its methodology.

Tab. 2: Comparison of DPPH• radical scavenging activity of the plant extracts with that of BHT

Sample	Conc (mg/2ml)	Absorbance	I%
<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	0.4	0.8066	40.15

<i>Alchemilla flabellata</i>	0.4	0.1120	91.69
<i>Rhododendron myrtifolium</i>	0.4	0.1159	91.4
<i>Thymus alpestris</i>	0.4	0.8345	38.83
<i>Achillea schurii</i>	0.4	0.7053	47.67
<i>Polygala amara</i>	0.4	1.3401	0.57
BHT	0.4	0.0487	94.7

For an accurate comparison, we determined the scavenging activity (I%) for the plants extracts and the BHT solution using the same concentration for all of them (0.4 mg/2 mL). From table 2 we are able to discover that the extract of *Alchemilla flabellata* has the highest antioxidant activity (the inhibition percentage is 91.69 %) and is closely followed by *Rhododendron myrtifolium* extract (91.4 %). Observing the inhibition percentage for the BHT (94.7 %), the 2 extracts can be compared in strength with this standard antioxidant. The proportionality between the concentration of phenols and the antioxidant activity it is still true, even though, *Alchemilla flabellata* extract has the highest antioxidant activity from the entire series but not the highest polyphenols content. This lack of a perfect correlation can be explained by the presence of other compounds with antioxidant activity in *Alchemilla flabellata* extract, such as organic acids widely diffused in plants or compounds based on reducing cations. These two extracts are followed in intensity of antioxidant activity by *Erigeron annuus*, *Achillea schurii* and *Thymus alpestris* extracts. The order is the same like in the case of phenolic contents scale. Therefore, in the present study we verified the direct cause between the phenolic content and the scavenging activity remembered in the scientific literature. The significantly lowest antioxidant potential was proved to be that of *Polygala amara* extract. Observing the phenolic content, this extract has, also, the lowest concentration of polyphenols. For all of this reasons, we argue that the antioxidant activity of this extract can be influenced by the small content in polyphenols or by the degradation of the compounds responsible for the free radical scavenging activity, during the preparation or conservation process.

3. Conclusions

In this work the relation between antioxidants concentration and DPPH[•] radical scavenging activity was studied. Polyphenolic compounds

have shown a different behavior towards DPPH[•] free radical, both in terms of capacity and rate of scavenging. The highest concentration of polyphenols determined the highest antioxidant activity and this method seems to be the perfect method to detect a good antioxidant. This study reveals the potency of two extracts, *Alchemilla flabellata* and *Rhododendron myrtifolium* extracts, better than that of BHT, a standard antioxidant. Thus, future studies can be oriented on less studied plants because some of them can prove to be rich in antioxidants and maybe the base of many nowadays diseases treatments. Furthermore, some this plants from the Piatra Craiului mountains spontaneous flora could represent the ground for a more controlled cultivation.

Acknowledgement: this paper is supported by the Sectoral Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the contract number POSDRU/89/1.5/S/59323.

References

1. Arash, R., Koshy, P., Sekaran, M.: *Antioxidant Potential and Phenolic Content of Ethanolic Extract of Selected Malaysian Plants*. Res. J. Biotech., 5, 16-19, 2010.
2. Pourmorad, F., Hosseinimehr, S. J., Shahabimajd N.: *Antioxidant activity, phenol and flavonoid contents of some selected Iranian medicinal plants*. African Journal of Biotechnology, 5, 1142-1145, 2006
3. Bunea, A., Rugina, O.D., Pinte, M.A., Sconta, Z., Bunea, I.C., Socaciu, C.: *Comparative Polyphenolic Content and Antioxidant Activities of some Wild and Cultivated Blueberries from Romania*. Not Bot Horti Agrobi, 39, 70-76, 2011.
4. Huang, D., B. Ou, Prior, R.L.: *The chemistry behind antioxidant capacity assays*. J Agric Food Chem, 53,1841-56, 2005.
5. Manach, C., et al.: *Bioavailability and bioefficacy of polyphenols in humans*. I. Review of 97 bioavailability studies. Am J Clin Nutr, 81, 230S-242S, 2005.
6. Prior, R.L., Wu, X., Schaich, K.:

- Standardized methods for the determination of antioxidant capacity and phenolics in foods and dietary supplements.* J Agric Food Chem, 53, 4290-302, 2005.
7. Katsube, T., et al.: *Screening for Antioxidant Activity in Edible Plant Products: Comparison of Low-Density Lipoprotein Oxidation Assay, DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay, and Folin-Ciocalteu Assay.* J Agric Food Chem., 52, 2391-2396, 2004.
 8. Locatelli, M., Gindro, R., Travaglia, F., Coisson, J.D., Rinaldi, M., Arlorio, M.: *Study of the DPPH-scavenging activity: Development of a free software for the correct interpretation of data.* Food Chem., 114, 889–897, 2009.
 9. Adiguzel, A., Ozer, H., Sokmen, M., Gulluce, M., Sokmen, A., Kilic, H., Sahin, F., Barris, O.: *Antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of the essential oil and methanol extract of Nepata cataria.* Pol. J. Microbiol., 58, 69-76, 2009.
 10. Valko, M., Leibfritz, D., Moncol, J., Cronin, M. T. D., Mazur, M., Telser, J.: *Free radicals and antioxidants in normal physiological functions and human disease.* The International Journal of Biochemistry and Cell Biology, 39, 44–84, 2007.
 11. Kondo, S., Tsuda, K., Muto, N., Nakatani, S. (2002). *Changes in antioxidant activity during fruit development in citrus fruits.* Horticultural Research (Japan), 1, 63–66.
 12. Kondo, S., Yoshikawa, H., Katayama, R.: *Antioxidant activity in astringent and non-astringent persimmons.* Journal of Horticultural Science and Biotechnology, 79, 390–394, 2004.
 13. Saint-Cricq de Gaulejac, N., Provost, C., Vivas, N.: *Comparative study of polyphenol scavenging activities assessed by different methods.* Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 47, 425–431, 2009.
 14. Sanchez-Moreno, C.: *Review: methods used to evaluate the free radical scavenging activity in foods and biological systems.* Food Science and Technology International, 8, 121–137, 2002.
 15. Skupien, K., Oszmianski, J.: *Comparison of six cultivars of strawberries (Fragaria x ananassa Duch.) grown in northwest Poland.* European Food Research and Technology, 219, 66–70, 2004.
 16. Zhang, Dong-Lin, Hamauzu, Y.: *Phenolic compounds, ascorbic acid, carotenoids and antioxidant properties of green, red and yellow bell peppers.* Journal of Food, Agriculture and Environment, 1, 22–27, 2003.

MICROBIOLOGICAL STUDY OF FLOURY MIXES WITH ADDITION OF TOPINAMBUR FLOUR

A. KOLEVA* A. YOVCHEV* D. HRUSAVOV** A. KRASTEVA*
Z. DENKOVA***

Abstract: *The microflora alteration during storage of floury mixes with topinambur flour was studied. The aerobic mesophilic and faculty anaerobic microorganisms, the moulds and yeasts, and the specific and non-specific microorganisms, were detected and enumerated. A reduction of the total microbial insemination was established (incl. coliforms), as complete reduction was reached in a 30-th day. During storage within 6 months a high concentration of viable yeast cells is being kept.*

Keywords: *topinambur, floury mixes, microflora insemination*

1. Introduction

The topinambur tubers (*Helianthus tuberosus* L.) contain a big amount of fructose polymers-inulin (80% d.b.), also cellulose and many minerals, including (mg% d.b): Fe- 10,1; Mn-44,0; Ca- 78,8; Mg- 31,7; K- 1382,5; Na- 17,2 [12, 13, 14, 15]. The content of Fe, Si and Zn is higher, if compared to that of potatoes, carrots and beet. The topinambur tubers also include in their composition proteins, pectin, amino acids and organic and fatty acids. The organic acids present within 6÷8% d.b. [9]. Citric, Malic, Succinic, Malonic and Fumaric represent the organic acids in topinambur tubers. These acids actively participate in the metabolism. Furthermore, they possess antimicrobial activity and have beneficial influence upon the acid-alkaline balance of the human's digestive tract functions. Other bioactive compounds, as 2, 5-dihydrobenzoic acid, which has antimicrobial activity, and heliangin, which has indicated significant activity in vitro against carcinoma cells, as well were extracted from the tubers [1]. The topinambur tubers are being used as preventive and curative resource in dysbiosis, diabetes type 2, etc. The addition of topinambur flour to the wheat flour (ash content 1,15%) improves the bread quality [10]. The biological and the nutritional values of these breads are increased, because of inulin, pectin and minerals [17]. The addition of inulin-containing concentrates obtained from topinambur [6] in

amounts ca. 10% flour basis enrich the whole meal breads in soluble fibres, thus the soluble/insoluble proportion.

The microbial insemination of the wheat flour is related to the cereal microflora. In cereal processing many microorganisms pass over to the flour. The difference between the amount of microorganisms in cereal and flour depends on the process of cereal cleaning before milling and on the rate of extraction. The floury mixes contain saprophytic and pathogenic microorganisms along with the added yeast, which is necessary for the process of alcohol fermentation [11, 16].

The aim of this study was to evaluate the microflora alteration of floury mixes, with addition of topinambur flour, stored in a paper-polyethylene package within 6 months.

2. Materials and methods

The experimental materials were Bulgarian commercial wheat flours type "500" and "1150", wheat bran, topinambur flour, salt and dry yeast.

"Tcharodeitsi-07" Parvomai, Bulgaria, supplies the topinambur flour, which is produced from the tubers. In appearance, it is pale beige – creamy colored powder, with specific sweet taste and odour.

All ingredients are added in relation to 100g of flour. Mix 1 and 2 are based on wheat flour type "500", whereas mix 3 is based on type "1150". The topinambur powder's amount was added at

* Dept. of Technology of Cereals, Fodder, Bread and Confectionary Products, UFT, Plovdiv, Bulgaria. Correspondent e-mail: yovchev.aleksandar@gmail.com

** Dept. of Technology of Tobacco, Sugar, Vegetable and Essential Oil, UFT, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

*** Dept. of Organic Chemistry and Microbiology, UFT, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

3% (mix 1) and 6% (mixes 2 and 3). The second floury mix also has 10% of wheat bran. All mixes have 2% dry yeast and 1,5% salt. The storage of the floury mixes was conducted within 6 months at 18±25 °C in a paper-polyethylene package.

The aerobic mesophilic and faculty anaerobic microorganisms were detected and enumerated according to standards ISO 21149 and ISO 18415.

The moulds and yeasts were detected and enumerated according to standard BDS ISO 21527.

The specific and non-specific microorganisms were enumerated according to standard ISO 16649-2.

Detection of *Salmonella spp.* was done according to standard BDS EN ISO 6579.

All experiments are conducted in a department "Organic Chemistry and Microbiology" at the University of Food Technologies (UFT), Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

3. Results and discussion

The floury mixes bear the usual cereal association of microorganisms, as the viable microorganisms count $10^3 \div 10^4$ CFU/ g. The results are presented in table 1.

During storage a reduction within 2 logarithmic units of the total microbial insemmination and of the coliforms were established. In a 30th day, no coliforms incl. *Escherichia coli* were detected. No viable cells of pathogenic microorganisms, specific for the cereal meal, were detected.

In these, ready for bread production, floury mixes, an activation of the yeast biomass (added as a lyophilized concentrate) is not established. A

high concentration of viable yeast cells is being kept.

During storage of the floury mixes, within 6 months, no moulds were detected visibly. An increase of the mould spores vitality is established into mixes 1 and 2 in a 150th day. The moulds' count (CFU/ g) detected in mix 2 is two times lower than mix 1, whereas in mix 3 there was no increase. Probably that is due to the topinambur quantity, which in mix 1 is two times lower than mix 2 and mix 3 and because of added wheat bran into mix 2.

During storage a reduction of the total microbial insemmination was established (incl. coliforms), as complete reduction was reached in 30th day. During storage within 6 months a high concentration of viable yeast cells is being kept. The floury mixes have a high degree of purity because of some active compounds in topinambur, which according to the literature have bactericidal activity. The experimental results showed that these, ready for use, floury mixes with topinambur flour could be stored within 6 months at 18±25 °C in a paper-polyethylene package.

4. Conclusion

A reduction of the total microbial insemmination was established (incl. coliforms), as complete reduction was reached in 30th day. During storage within 6 months a high concentration of viable yeast cells is being kept. The floury mixes have a high degree of purity and they could be stored within 6 months at 18±25 °C in a paper-polyethylene package.

Microbial insemmination of floury mixes with topinambur flour during storage for 6 months at 18±25 °C in a paper-polyethylene package

Table 1

Indices/ Floury mixes	Aerobic mesophilic and faculty anaerobic microorganisms, CFU/g	Coliforms, CFU/g	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , CFU/g	<i>Salmonella</i> in 25 g	Yeasts, CFU/g	Moulds, CFU/g
Mix №1						
Day 1	1,0.10 ⁵	4,0.10 ²	< 10	Not detected	1,0.10 ¹¹	< 10
Day 30	3,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		4,0.10 ¹⁰	80
Day 60	1,3.10 ³	<100	< 10		5,0.10 ¹⁰	40
Day 90	4,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		1,1.10 ¹⁰	60
Day 120	3,7.10 ³	<100	< 10		1,0.10 ¹⁰	< 100
Day 150	3,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		3,2.10 ⁹	> 400
Day 180	1,7.10 ³	<100	< 10		1,1.10 ⁹	< 100

<u>Mix №2</u>							
Day 1	1,0.10 ⁵	3,0.10 ²	< 10	Not detected	1,4.10 ¹¹	< 10	
Day 30	1,2.10 ³	<100	< 10		9,6.10 ¹⁰	50	
Day 60	2,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		2,9.10 ¹⁰	20	
Day 90	7,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		1,4.10 ¹⁰	130	
Day 120	8,5.10 ³	<100	< 10		8,0.10 ⁹	< 100	
Day 150	1,1.10 ³	<100	< 10		4,8.10 ⁹	< 200	
Day 180	6,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		5,0.10 ⁸	< 100	
<u>Mix №3</u>							
Day 1	1,2.10 ⁵	2,2.10 ²	< 10	Not detected	1,2.10 ¹¹	< 10	
Day 30	3,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		1,2.10 ¹¹	20	
Day 60	3,5.10 ³	<100	< 10		1,7.10 ¹⁰	10	
Day 90	5,3.10 ³	<100	< 10		1,2.10 ¹⁰	10	
Day 120	6,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		2,3.10 ⁹	< 100	
Day 150	2,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		1,3.10 ⁹	< 100	
Day 180	8,0.10 ³	<100	< 10		2,8.10 ⁸	< 100	

References

- Ahmed, M., El-Sakhawy, F., Soliman, S., Abou-Hussein, D.: *Phytochemical and biological study of Helianthus tuberosus L.* J. Biomed. Sci. 18, p. 134-147, 2005.
- BDS EN ISO 18415: 2011. Detection of specified and non-specified microorganisms.
- BDS EN ISO 21149: 2009. Enumeration and detection of aerobic mesophilic bacteria.
- BDS EN ISO 6579: 2009. Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs - Horizontal method for the detection of *Salmonella spp.*
- BDS ISO 21527: 2011. Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs - Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds.
- Fiber Enriched, Sugar Reduced Fermented Bakery Products.* Food Marketing and Technology, 2007, June, p. 4-6.
- ISO 16649- 2: 2011. Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs - Horizontal method for the enumeration of beta-glucuronidase-positive *Escherichia coli* - Part 2: Colony-count technique at 44 degrees C using 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl beta-D-glucuronide.
- ISO 21149: 2009. Enumeration and detection of aerobic mesophilic bacteria.
- Kays, S., Nottingham, S.: *Biology and Chemistry of Jerusalem Artichoke Helianthus tuberosus L.* CRC Press, ISBN 1420044958, 9781420044959, p. 478, 2007.
- Krasteva, A., Baeva, M., Gogova, Tzv., Durakova, A., Todorova, M.: *Investigation of the possibility of usage of flour from topinambur tubers as addition to wheat flours.* Food Processing Industry Magazine, №5, p. 46-50, 2010.
- Murgov, I., Denkova, Z.: *Microbiology.* Academic Edition of UFT, Plovdiv, Bulgaria, 2010.
- Pashtenko, L.: *Manufacture of bakery products using new types of raw materials.* M: CNIITEI, Overview series: Bakery and Pasta Industry, p. 32, 1993.
- Pashtenko, L.: *Topinambur in our life.* Voronej: VGU, p. 120, 2001.
- Pashtenko, L., Jarkova, I., Bulgakova, N., Prohorova, A., Lujblinski, S., Cherniaev, S.: *Bioactive supplements in human nutrition.* Food Industry № 7, p. 82-83, № 8, p. 72-73, 2002.
- Pashtenko, L., Rushitz, E.: *Method for bread production.* Patent of Russian Federation N94011791.
- Ray B.: *Fundamental Food Microbiology.* Fourth Edition, CRC Press, New York, 2008.
- Zelenkov V.: *Method for production of bakery and pastry products with topinambur.* Patent of Russian Federation N2128439.

BIOREACTORS WITH LIGHT-BEADS FLUIDIZED BED: MODELING OF THE VOIDAGE FUNCTION

G. KOSTOV¹, I. MIHAYLOV², D. BLAZHEVA³, D. STOEVA⁴, M. ANGELOV⁵

Abstract: *The expansion characteristics of the light-beads fluidized bed bioreactor were investigated in the present work. The voidage function of the fluidized bed was investigated and modeling in accordance with the methods of mathematical modeling and bioreactors scaling. It was developed mathematical regression relationships for the description of the voidage function. The received model will be used in the study of the column fluidized bed bioreactor and its application in anaerobic bioprocesses.*

Keywords: *fluidized bed, voidage function; mathematical modeling*

1. Introduction

The immobilized cell processes began imperceptibly to enter in the fermentation industry in the last two decades. They feature number advantages over free cell systems: a high degree of substrate conversion and high productivity of the process; an opportunity for continuous processes; reduce unproductive time to develop a new culture, prolonged use, etc. [11, 13].

An important role for the realization of the immobilized cells' advantages is the choice of the bioreactor design. In laboratory and industrial practice in a variety devices with periodic and/or continuous are used: bioreactors with mechanical stirrer, packed bed bioreactor; fluidized bed bioreactors; membrane bioreactors and others. The methods of design, modeling, optimization and scaling of these systems could be found in the literature [11, 13].

The bioreactors with different structures have different advantages and disadvantages, depending on the fermentation process. A detailed description of various aspects of the work of this type of fermentation systems can be found in the literature [2, 8].

In fluidized bed reactors exists lower mechanical loads on the particles. These systems can work with smaller-size particles without

clogging layer, high pressure losses, channeling and compression of the particles. Smaller particles lead to the minimization of internal diffusion resistance and higher heat- and mass transfer rates. On the other hand, the fluidized bed reactors have a high axial dispersion. Fluidized beds with high liquid recirculation operate under ideal mixing condition [8. Another advantage of fluidized bed reactors is the easy separation of the gas phase, which is produced at the fermentation or easy supply of immobilized system with gaseous substrate. Godia and Sola, 1995 provides detailed information about the application of the fluidized bed reactors in various areas of biotechnology.

The fluidization process of the particles begins when the interaction forces acting on the particle by the surrounding fluid are equal to the particles' weight. Therefore, the pressure losses are equal to:

$$\Delta P = L(1 - \varepsilon)(\rho_s - \rho)g \quad (1)$$

If we consider a single particle in an infinite expansion, the interaction forces can be represented as the sum of drag forces and the Archimedean force:

$$V\rho g = \text{Drag} + \text{Bioyongant} \quad (2)$$

This representation of the interaction forces has some difficulties: how to make separation of the two types of forces? The experimental

¹ Assoc. prof. Georgi Kostov, University of Food Technology, Department of wine and brewery, Blvd. Maritza№ 26,4002, Plovdiv, Bulgaria, george_kostov2@abv.bg

² Assist. prof. PhD Ivan Mihaylov, University of Food Technologies, Department of Technical mechanics and machine engineering, dkmss@abv.bg

³ Assist. Prof. PhD Denitza Blazheva, University of Food Technologies, Department of Organic chemistry and microbiology, dblazheva@gmail.com

⁴ Assist. prof. PhD Donka Stoeva, University of Food Technologies, Department of Machine and apparatus for food and flavor industry, bodurova@gmail.com

⁵ Prof. PhD Mihail Angelov, University of Food Technologies, Department of Biotechnology, mpanguelov@yahoo.com

separation is difficult, as directly can be determined only at the common interaction forces and any attempts for their interpretation is controversial. This is due to the influence of particles on the fluid flow, which is leading to an additional force acting on the particle. This additional force is a function of the pressure gradient [6].

To avoid difficulties in interpretation of the interaction forces in practical is used so-called "the voidage function" $f(\varepsilon)$. It is described by the dependence:

$$f(\varepsilon) = \frac{F_D}{F_{DS}} \quad (3)$$

where: F_D is the drag force in the system liquid-particles; F_{DS} is the drag force for the single particle.

By introducing this function we take into account the influence of the concentration of solids in the bed. In some cases the interaction forces are replaced by other proportional quantities. Depending on the problem under consideration can be examined characteristics such as: sedimentation rate in, minimal fluidization velocity or pressure loss in the bed. In these cases, $f(\varepsilon)$ is associated with characteristics examined by the expression:

$$f(\varepsilon) = \frac{4Ga\varepsilon}{\left(\frac{u}{u_t}\right)^2 3C_D \text{Re}_t^2} = \left(\frac{u}{u_t}\right)^2 \frac{C_{Dt}}{C_D} \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

which for low Re values is simplifies to:

$$f(\varepsilon) = \left(\frac{u}{u_t}\right)^{-1} \varepsilon \quad (4.1)$$

and for the high Re values is simplifies to:

$$f(\varepsilon) = \left(\frac{u}{u_t}\right)^{-2} \varepsilon \quad (4.2)$$

The voidage function is connected with the pressure losses by the expression:

$$f(\varepsilon) = \left(\frac{\Delta P}{L}\right) \frac{4d_p \varepsilon}{3C_D \rho u^2 (1-\varepsilon)} \quad (5)$$

As can be seen from equation (5) to determine the voidage function $f(\varepsilon)$ is necessary to know the drag coefficient of fluid particles in C_D . From the literature it is known that this coefficient is a function of the Re value and thus the determination of $f(\varepsilon)$ is hindered greatly.

There are different methods for determination of $f(\varepsilon)$ - solving the equations of Navier-Stokes for liquid-solids systems or for the analogy flow in tubes, taking into account the characteristics of

the suspension. From a practical standpoint, the second method is more important, since it can calculate the drag movement of the particle in the bed and to be subject to the pressure losses in the fluidized bed [6].

The purpose of this work is to study the voidage function of the light-beads fluidized bed and to develop mathematical relationships to its interpretation. For the purpose have been used experimentally obtained dates for the expansion of such fluidized bed working with polymer particles with a density in the range 1025-1250 kg/m^3 .

2. Materials and methods

The experimental set-up is shown on figure 1. It is consist from Plexiglas (1) tube with internal diameter 56 mm and height 980 mm. On its bottom is situated a distributor (2) and glass pearl bed (3) for liquid distribution. The liquid recirculated by peristaltic pump "Masterflex" (4). Flow rates were measured with a calibrated rotameter (5). A graduated ruler (6) was used for the measuring the heights of the transition interface and the total bed. On the upper side of the column is replaced cylindrical phase separator with diameter 200 mm and height 120 mm. The pressure losses is determined using differential manometer „PR-205-Evrolec,, 14, which is connect with the nipples 15.

Tap water was used as a model liquid phase with approximated density 1000 kg/m^3 .

The solid phase was 250 g alginate beads with different density. The beads were obtained by the method described by *Wijffels* [16].

The average density of the beads was determined as was described by *Zessen et al.* [17]. The beads density was increased with 2.5% and 5% sand (fraction below 0,125 mm), which was added to the alginate solution. The terminal settling velocity was determined as described by *Chhabra* [4]. Gel-beads characteristics are summarized in table 1.

The minimal fluidization velocity was determinated graphical as described by *Miura and Kawase* [12].

The porosity and solid hold-up were determined as described by *Buffiere and Moletta* [3]:

$$\varepsilon_s = \frac{M}{\rho_s SL} \quad (6)$$

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \varepsilon_s \quad (7)$$

where: M – solid phase weight (500 g); ρ_s – solid phase density, kg/m^3 ; S – column cross-section, m^2 (0,00246 m^2); L – fluidized bed height, m;

Figure 1. Light-beads column bioreactor

1-plexyglass column; 2 – distributor; 3 – drainage; 4 – peristaltic pump; 5 – rotameter; 6 – ruler; 7 phase separator; 8 – three-way valves; 9 – reservoirs; 10 – valve; 11 – conductometric cell 12 – conductometer; 14 -differential manometer; 15 – nipples; 16 – exit cell; 17 – peristaltic pump for nutrients; 18 – syringe;

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Main fluidized bed characteristics – expansion and terminal settling velocity

The bed porosity is shown on figure 1. The terminal settling velocity u_t is shown on table 1. These two parameters are needed for the calculation of the voidage function. The terminal settling velocity is that velocity, when the

fluidization process finish. The increased of water velocity over the terminal settling velocity leads to hydraulic transport of the solid phase. This means that the terminal settling velocity is critical for the fluidization process. Moreover according to equation (3) the drag force of the single particle is equal to the drag force during the settling process.

Table 1
Main characteristics of the polymer particles – size; terminal settling velocity; particle density; drag coefficient;

Particles	Particles' density	$d \pm \sigma$	u_t	Re_t	C_{dt}
-	kg/m^3	mm	m/s	-	-
<i>Alginate 1055</i>	1055	$2,59 \pm 0,23$	0,0218	56,46	3,791
<i>Alginate 1125</i>	1125	$2,025 \pm 0,132$	0,0365	73,73	2,222
<i>Alginate 1175</i>	1175	$2,49 \pm 0,189$	0,0469	116,78	2,117
<i>Polymer 1600</i>	1600	$2,02 \pm 0,20$	0,185	373,70	0,463

The expansion of the fluidized bed was described using the following equation:

$$u = k\varepsilon^n \tag{8}$$

Richardson and Zaki [14] shows that the parameter k is equal to the terminal settling velocity and the parameter n is $n=f(Re)$. If we compare the terminal settling velocity u_t (*table 1*)

with the experimental parameter k (table 2), we can see that the parameter k is smaller than u_t . This fact is confirmed by many authors: *Garside and Al-Dibouni* [7], *Grbavic* [9]. This is due to two main reasons: the existence of different types of fluidization [6] and discussed in the literature deceleration of particles due to the interaction between them.

The values of k and n are represented in table 2. Our research shows that the value of the expansion coefficient n differs greatly from that calculated according with the models of *Richardson and Zaki*, *Rowe*, *Garside and Al-Doubini*, *Khan and Richardson* [7, 10, 14, 15]. This is mainly due to the nature of light particles. Firstly, the fluidization begins at relatively low water velocities'. Secondly, the fluidized bed exists in layer is relatively short intervals of fluidized velocities. In this paper we will focus

on the force interaction and the determination of the empirical coefficients in equation (8).

If we examine the data for Re_t , we will find that the sedimentation of the examined particles was developed in the transition zone between laminar and turbulent regime. Therefore, it will be very difficult to choose, for this type of particles, how to expressed the voidage function – wit equation (4.1) or with equation (4.2).

There are additional difficulties in the choice of equation (4.1) or (4.2). They are mostly related with the nature of fluidization process in the case studies. We had chosen to model the voidage function with equation (4.1). The attempts to model the process with equation (4.2) give illogical results that need further refinement, testing and analysis. We shall therefore confine our comments only to study and characterized dependence (4.1).

Table 2

Values of different constants in equations (8), (9), (10), (4.1)

Particles	Empirical parameters		Equation (9, 10)	
	k	n	β	(1-n)
<i>Alginate 1055</i>	0,0136(±0,012)	1,78(±0,04)	-0,786	(-0,78)
<i>Alginate 1125</i>	0,0266(±0,004)	1,76(±0,012)	-0,76	(-0,76)
<i>Alginate 1175</i>	0,0304(±0,004)	2,32(±0,022)	- 1,35	(-1,32)
<i>Polymer 1600</i>	0,137(±0,019)	1,61(±0,04)	-0,82	(-0,61)

3.2. The voidage function and its modeling according equation (4.1)

The voidage function is represented on figure 3. The experimental data were compared with the equation:

$$f(\varepsilon) = \alpha \varepsilon^{-\beta} \quad (9)$$

In the comparison between models and experimental data were obtained the following mathematical relationships:

✓ *Alginate 1055*
 $f(\varepsilon) = 1.6007\varepsilon^{-0.786}$; $R^2 = 0.9746$ (9.1)

✓ *Alginate 1125*
 $f(\varepsilon) = 0.821\varepsilon^{-0.761}$; $R^2 = 0.9946$ (9.2)

✓ *Alginate 1175*
 $f(\varepsilon) = 0.711\varepsilon^{-1.351}$; $R^2 = 0.9948$ (9.3)

✓ *Alginate 1600*
 $f(\varepsilon) = 0.1489\varepsilon^{-0.828}$; $R^2 = 0.9638$ (9.4)

In his work *Di Felice* [5] showed that the voidage function could be expressed by the

equation $f(\varepsilon) = \varepsilon^{-\beta}$. But, he examines cases in which the density of particles is at least twice higher than that of the fluid. In these cases the resistances in the bed are significantly larger than those in this case. In our case the alginate particles can be regarded as "rigid water". Therefore, the drag forces in the fluidized bed are smaller than in the conventional fluidized beds.

According to *Di Felice*, 1994 the voidage function could be connected with the expansion with following equation:

$$-\beta = 1 - n \quad (10)$$

The careful examination of the exponent in the equations (9.1-9.4) shows that their exponent satisfies the requirement of equations (10). The results are shown in Table 2. The actually exponent has a value, which can be easily calculated from the expansion rate n , as can be seen from the results. Slight difference was observed only in the value of β for the polymer particles, probably due to the transitional regime. *Di Felice*, 1994, 1995 e found that $\beta = f(Re_t)$ [5, 6]. He reports for changes in the value of β in the

transition zone between laminar and turbulent flow.

As interesting is the value of α in the equations (9). We can do suggest that, this value is a function of particle parameters, but this hypothesis requires further studies that will be

subject to other publications. The most likely parameter that affects this factor is the particles' density. Another important parameter is their diameter.

Figure 2. Expansion characteristics of light-beads fluidized bed

Figure 3. The voidage function and its expression according equation (4.1)

4. Conclusion

In the present investigation was made modeling of fluidization hydrodynamics of the process using the voidage function. It was found

that some parameters of the function can be described by the expansion characteristics. In these types fluidized bed was observed deviation from those described in the literature as conventional fluidized beds.

The observed deviations are due primarily to the characteristics of the solid phase – water-like surface and low density. With these features the fluidization was developed in a relatively small range of flow rates and the drag forces were relatively low. The expansion process also differs from the described data for conventional fluidized beds.

As guidelines for the future work may be included modeling the voidage function using other equations and full characterization of the coefficients in its equation.

References

1. Al-Dibouni, M. R., Garside, J.: 1979, *Particle mixing and classification in liquid fluidised beds*. Trans. Instn. Chem. Engrs. 57, 1979, p. 94-103.
2. Asif, M., Abasaheed, A.E.: *Modeling of glucose isomerization in fluidized bed immobilized enzyme bioreactor*, Bioresource Technology, 64, 1998, p. 229-235;
3. Buffiere, C.F., Moletta, R.: *Liquid mixing and phase hold-ups in gas producing fluidized bed bioreactor*, Chem. Eng. Science, vol.53, 1998, p.617-627
4. Chhabra, R.P.: *Wall effects on free-settling velocity in viscous media in cylindrical tubes*, Powder technology, 85, 1999, p.83-90
5. Di Felice, R.: 1994, *On the voidage function in two-phase multiparticle systems*. Int. J. Multiphase Flow 20, 1984, p.153-159.
6. Di Felice, R.: *Hydrodynamics of liquid fluidization*, Chem. Eng. Science, vol.50, 1995, p.1213-1245
7. Garside, J., Al-Dibouni, M.R.: *Velocity-voidage relationships for fluidization and sedimentation in solid-liquid systems*, Ind. Eng. Chem. Process Des. Dev., vol.16, 1977, p.206-213
8. Godia, F., Sola, C.: *Fluidized-bed bioreactors*, Biotechnology Progress, 11, 1995, p.479-497
9. Grbavcic Z.B, Garic, R.V., Hadzismajlovic, D.Z.E., Jovanvic, S.: *Variational model for prediction of the fluid-particle interphase drag coefficient and particulate expansion of fluidized and sedimenting beds*, Powder Technol., vol.68, 1991, p.199-211
10. Khan, A. R., Richardson, J.F.: *Fluid-particle interactions and flow characteristics of fluidized beds and settling suspensions of spherical particles*, Chem. Engin. Commun., vol.78, 1989, p111-130
11. Kourkoutas Y., Bekatorou, A., Banat, I.M., Marchant, R., Koutinas, A.A.: *Immobilization technologies and support materials suitable in alcohol beverages production: a review*, Food Microbiology, 21, 2004, p.377-397
12. Miura H., Kawase, Y.: *Minimum fluidization velocity in two- and three-phase fluidized beds with non-Newtonian fluids*, Powder technology, vol.97, 1998, p.124-128
13. Nedovic, V., Willaert, R.: *Fundamentals of cell immobilization biotechnology*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2004, p.411-436
14. Richardson, J. F. and Zaki, W. N.: 1954, *Sedimentation and fluidisation. Part I*. Trans. Inst. Chem. Eng. 32, 1954, 35-53
15. Rowe, P. N.: *A convenient empirical equation for estimation of the Richardson-Zaki exponent*. Chem. Engng. Sci., vol.43, 1987, p.2795-2796
16. Wijffels, R.: *Immobilized cells*, Springer, 2001, p.6-30
17. Zessen, E., Tramper, J., Rinzema, A., Beeftink, H.: *Fluidized-bed and packed-bed characteristics of gel beads*, Chemical Engineering Journal 115, 2005, p.103-111

Acknowledgment

The work was made by the Financial support of Project DTK 02/27 “Increasing the efficiency of bio-fuel purpose ethanol production” financed by “National Science Fund”.

Using Symbols

- $f(\varepsilon)$ – voidage function;
- Ga – Galileo’s number;
- C_D – drag coefficient;
- C_{Dt} – drag coefficient at terminal settling velocity;
- u – water velocity, m/s
- u_t – terminal settling velocity, m/s
- ε – bed porosity;
- d – particle diameter, m
- k, n – parameters in Richardson-Zaki’s equation
- α, β – parameters of the voidage function;

INVESTIGATION AND MODELING OF JET COLUMN BIOREACTOR: MIXING TIME IN THE APPARATUS

G. KOSTOV¹, I. MIHAYLOV², D. BLAZHEVA³, M. ANGELOV⁴

Abstract: *This publication is considered research and modeling of the average mixing time in jet-column bioreactor. The mixing time was investigated using two different tracers. Using the obtained experimental data and mathematical models has been found that the average mixing time is influenced by the physicochemical characteristics of the phases. It was found that the the gas and liquid superficial velocities have different influence on the hydrodynamic conditions in the apparatus. The average mixing time in the bioreactor was modeling using exponential-logarithmic dependences.*

Keywords: *jet column bioreactor; mixing time; modeling; pH-method*

1. INTRODUCTION

Bubble column reactors are popular in the chemical and biochemical industry because of their versatile use and economic advantages i.e., low investment costs due to their simple construction and low variable costs of production due to low energy requirement of their operation, which is maintained by fluid dynamical mixing and dispersion of the phases. All these advantages are also valid for their application in biotechnology. However, with few exceptions, bubble column bioreactors have not been introduced into industry yet because of the lack of the necessary know-how in their design and operation. The replacement of sterile stirred tank bioreactors by new, more economical, reactor types is often unattractive due to high initial costs and long durability of the existing equipment. In stirred tank bioreactors the construction of the equipment, especially that of the aerator, is not as decisive as in the case of bubble column bioreactors, since the performance of the stirred tank bioreactor can be improved up to a limit by an increase of the mechanical energy input. The lack of such a safety factor increases the risk of the applied bubble column bioreactor not giving the required performance [1, 9 and 10].

In aerobic cultivation of microorganisms, the problem of oxygen supplying of the cells is decisive, especially for processes in large volume

bioreactors. Providing highest mass transfer surface and consequently higher volume mass transfer coefficient K_{LA} is essential for the operation of the column bioreactor. Simultaneously, in carrying out aerobic fermentation of particular importance are the hydrodynamic conditions into the bioreactor. The degree of substrate conversion into biomass or metabolic product depends strongly on the flow structure. Ensuring optimum working conditions in the column bioreactor can be achieved in different ways: sectioning of the apparatus, the use of optimized aeration devices, and use of ejectors as aeration devices [1, 9].

The mixing process is widely used in biotechnological industries. It can be spontaneous - through diffusion between the components of the system, or forced - through introduction of mechanical energy. The purpose of mixing is to obtain homogeneous solutions (emulsions, suspensions) and to intensify the heat and mass transfer processes [1, 2, 3, 4, 11].

Mixing is indispensable in biotechnology, as it defines the environment during the cultivation in bioreactors. The development of the biomass in a reactor leads to continuous modifications of the medium. In these conditions, one of the most important problems is to establish an optimum hydrodynamic regime. Mixing time contains useful information about flow and mixing within

¹ Assoc. prof. PhD Georgi Kostov, University of Food Technology, Department of wine and brewery, Blvd. Maritza № 26,4002, Plovdiv, Bulgaria, george_kostov2@abv.bg

² Assist. prof. PhD Ivan Mihaylov, University of Food Technologies, Department of Technical mechanics and machine engineering, dkmss@abv.bg

³ Assist. prof. PhD Denitza Blazheva, University of Food Technologies, Department of Organic chemistry and microbiology, dblazheva@gmail.com

⁴ Prof. PhD Mihail Angelov, University of Food Technologies, Department of Biotechnology, mpanguelov@yahoo.com

the vessel and can be useful for biosynthesis processes scale-up [1, 2, 3, 4, 11].

The mixing time, (t_{mix}), denotes the time required for the tank composition to achieve a specified level of homogeneity following addition of a tracer pulse at a single point in the vessel. This uniformity should be available for determination, not only to be examining the molecular level, which can be done only as a result of diffusion molecules after infinitely long time. Therefore, the mixing time is conditional value, which depends on the method for determination and the volume of the samples. If this volume is equal to the entire volume of the apparatus for mixing time is equal to 0; if it is reduced to the molecular level, the homogeneity of the system is controlled in the molecular scale, such uniformity is reached after infinitely long time. Both cases are technologically unrealistic and therefore the optimal volumes of samples are determined experimentally [1, 2, 3, 4, 11].

The mixing time for is one of the most important parameters characterizing the intensity and efficiency of mixing. Furthermore, t_{mix} characterized the structure of flows in the apparatus and respectively - the ratio between active and stagnant zones. For geometrically similar apparatus the mixing time can be a scale-up parameter, when it is necessary to maintain mixing conditions in apparatus with large volume.

Main impact on t_{mix} in the apparatus with mechanical agitation has the diameter of the stirrer, the number of disks, the rotation speed and the viscosity of the culture medium. To calculate the mixing time in apparatus to with 6-blade stirrer could be used the following dependence:

$$t_{\text{mix}} = 6V_R (0,16nd^3)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

For column type apparatus the mixing time is determined by the gas and liquid superficial velocities [2, 3].

The measuring methods for the mixing time are based on the output of the system from one steady state using pulse or step function at the system inlet. The mixing time is that time, which is necessary to reach new steady state. The methods for determination of t_{mix} can be divided into several groups: thermal, chemical, optical and colorimetric [2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 11].

Thermal are those methods that measure the time to equalize the temperature throughout the volume, after pulse function. The amplitude of the pulse is limited by possible changes in the

physicochemical properties of the model solution, thus requiring too sensitive temperature sensors [2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 11].

There are methods for optical determination of the mixing time based on certain phenomena of optical physics: interference and fluorescence [3, 11]. Colorimetric methods are not applicable for aerated mixing systems [11].

Chemical methods can be divided into subgroups depending on the measuring method. The state of homogenization for conductive measurements is reached when the variation of the concentration of the indicator is less than 0.1%.

The mixing time, determined by measuring the concentration of hydrogen ions (pH), is defined as the transition time to reach 95% of new pH after an unsettling effect of a certain volume of acid or base. Real values for t_{mix} are obtained in the range of pH = (3-6). The area of pH = (6-8) is not suitable for bases, and the interval (7.5 to 9) - for acid. In these critical areas the homogenization is slower and it is determined by the influence of reactions:

The optimal amount of acid or base for the pulse function is approximately 10^{-4} of the bioreactor volume. This leads to higher indicator concentration. pH-metric determination of mixing time should be taken into account inertia of the measuring system, which consists of an electrode amplifier and a storage device. The time delay of the system is approximately 1% [11].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Experimental set-up

Jet column bioreactor (fig.1) is consist of column 1, which includes working sections 2 with contact devices and heat exchangers 3. At the bottom of the apparatus is situated modified jet ejector 4 with the air intake 5 solenoid valve 6 and mixing chamber 7, separated from the neck. An important feature of the ejector is that the gullet is located below or at the lower bottom of the mixing chamber. The upper part is gas separator 8. The circulation of the liquid is carried out by a centrifugal pump 10 through an external circuit 9. Constant volume in the bioreactor is maintained through the overflow 11.

The bioreactor works as follows: after filling the column 1 and circulation loop 9 with a working fluid, the centrifugal pump 10 and solenoid valve works 6 were started. The velocity of the liquid was 20-25 m/s, which creates dilution in the ejector. This leads to air suction into the mixing chamber. At the same time creates an internal loop of gas-liquid system that spans the space under the mixing chamber. The active acidity (pH) in the bioreactor is measuring by the following system: glass electrode 12a and pH-meter 12b, connected with data archiver 12c. The temperature control system is consisting from thermo-resistance 13a, regulator 13b and valve 13c. The temperature was regulated using two functions – cooling water and the temperature from the pump. The pressure of the fluid to the ejector nozzle is measured with precision pressure gauge 14 and the flow of air with a rotameter 15 [1].

Fig. 1. Experimental set-up

1 – column, 2 – working sections with contact devices, 3 – heat exchangers, 4 – modified jet device; 7 – mixing chamber; 8 – separator; 9 – external loop; 10 – centrifugal pump 11 – overflow; 12a – combined pH electrode; 12b – pH meters, 12c – storage device; 13a – resistance thermometer; 13b – knob for temperature, 13c – valve, 14 – precision manometer, 15 – rotameter

2.2. Experiments and operating conditions

The average mixing time in the jet column bioreactor was measured at five different liquid superficial velocities – 1,14; 2,42; 2,78; 3,68; 5,62 cm/s and at nine different superficial velocities of the aerated gas – 0; 1,05; 2,1; 3,15; 4,2; 5,25; 6,25; 7,35; 8,5 cm/s.

The average mixing time was determined using pH method. The tracer was introduced as δ -function (impulse function) horizontally to the bioreactor cross-section. The location of the pH electrode in the column is selected so as to record the response of the object after the tracers travel the longest possible path through the system.

Typical experimental curve for determination of average mixing time is shown at figure 2. H is the amplitude of the transition to the new steady state. Mixing time is defined by the basic methods mentioned in literature [11].

Fig. 2. Typical experimental curve for determination of average mixing time

The number of observations to calculate the average time of mixing (t_{mix}) is determined by the statistical parameters of the experiment and especially the dispersion of the experiment.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to characterize in detail the bioreactor's hydrodynamics, the functional dependence of the average mixing time was studied for different superficial gas and liquid velocities.

For that purpose was used two types of tracers: 4N solutions of NaOH and HCl. The results from the experiment are shown at figures 3 and 4 (points).

The two figures shows that the nature of the dependence for t_{mix} in both cases is qualitatively

the same. Quantitative differences are determined by the values of W_{sl} and the properties of the used indicator.

For $W_{sl} < 5.62$ cm / s, the average mixing time for the studied range of W_{sg} is greater, when was

used tracer NaOH. A similar phenomenon without being commented is shown in [2,3] by Einsele.

Fig. 3. Average mixing time using tracer NaOH

Fig. 4. Average mixing time using tracer HCl

The average mixing time was described using exponential-logarithm dependence:

$$t_{mix} = a + be^{-W_{sg}} + c \ln(W_{sl}) \quad (2)$$

The parameters of the model were received using least-square method. As a result of the mathematical and statistical analysis were obtained following two equations:

○ **Using 4N NaOH**

$$t_{mix} = 61.41 + 35.13e^{-W_{sg}} - 21.28 \ln(W_{sl}) \quad (2.1)$$

$$R^2 = 0.926$$

○ **Using 4N HCl**

$$t_{mix} = 40.85 + 37.17e^{-W_{sg}} - 10.66 \ln(W_{sl}) \quad (2.2)$$

$$R^2 = 0.886$$

The resulting mathematical models for the average mixing time for described with high accuracy the process. The results are shown in fig.5 and fig.6.

The free members in the two equations show that depending on the tracers were obtained different average mixing times. Such behavior in the mixing time can be explained by different physicochemical properties of the two tracers - the size and mobility of hydrogen and sodium

ions. This fact necessitates a precise definition of conditions for determination of the mixing time. Otherwise, it can be preventing large errors in the comparison of bioreactor.

Fig. 5. Distribution of residuals between experimental and model data (tracers NaOH)

Fig. 6. Distribution of residuals between experimental and model data (tracers HCl)

Mathematical models provide some interesting relationships for the mixing process into the bioreactor. The results shown in the figures reflect two substantially different modes of agitation; the transition zone between them is $W_{sg} \approx 2$ cm/s. Up to this point, the average mixing time is strongly influenced by gas superficial velocity. Therefore, the nature of the movement of liquid flow in the bioreactor is

determined not only by the circulation velocity (W_{sl}), but by the number and velocity of the gas bubbles.

Obviously the coalescence of gas bubbles occurring in $W_{sg} > 2$ cm/s, limited the increase in flow turbulence. This leads to limitation in mixing time. This mode is described by Peebles et al. [cited by Margaritis et. al., 6] and it is known as piston-turbulent regime.

Margaritis et. al.[6] established same mixing regime in airlift bioreactor with double circulation, but the transition point was at $W_{sg}=0.7$ cm/s.

The analysis of results and the literature data indicate that there are two modes of agitation. The transition between them is determined by the type of aeration system and design characteristics of the bioreactor.

The influence of two streams - the gas and liquid has also of different sizes. The average mixing time decreases exponentially with the increasing gas flow rate. Mathematical model shows that, regardless of the tracers, the influence of this parameter is the same. This could be explained by the closer values of the coefficients in front of the exponent.

Confirmation that there are two modes of mixing in the apparatus can be found in the influence of linear velocity of the liquid. In equations it participates in the logarithm, but the odds before him have a different value. The impact of liquid velocity is two times higher, when it was NaOH as a tracer, than using HCl. This is probably due to the already described behavior of ions of tracers in the aquatic environment.

Another explanation for the presence of two modes of mixing in the apparatus can be found in the work of the modified jet device. Probably these two mixing regimes is determined by the ejection ratio, which depends on the parameters of the modified jet device. However, this must be confirmed experimentally or by conducting numerical simulations using.

4. CONCLUSION

In the present publication has been described the modeling one of the important parameters for the bioreactor work - the average mixing time.

Based on experimental data and mathematical models has been found that the process of mixing is influenced by the ratio between gas and liquid superficial velocity. This leads to two different mixing regimes

It also found that in determining the average mixing time is important the type of the used tracer.

Acknowledgment

The work was made by the Financial support of Project DTK 02/27 "Increasing the efficiency of bio-fuel purpose ethanol production" financed by "National Science Fund".

References

1. Angelov, M.: *Intensification of the processes in column bioreactors*, Thesis, Plovdiv, 1986 (in Bulgarian)
2. Einsele, A., *Charakterisierung von Bioreaktoren durch Mischzeiten*. Chem. Rundschau, 1976, 29, p. 53-55
3. Einsele, A., Ristroph, D.L., Humphrey, A.E. *Mixing time and glucose uptake measured with a fluorometer*, In: Biotechnology and Bioengineering, vol. XX, 1978, pp. 1487–1492.
4. Hadjiev, D., Sabiri, N., Zanati, A., *Mixing time in bioreactors under aerated conditions*, Biochemical Engineering Journal, Volume 27, Issue 3, January 2006, Pages 323-330
5. Hiby, J.W., Definition and measurement of the degree of mixing in liquid mixtures, Int. Chem. Eng., 21, 2, 1981, p.197-204
6. Margaritis, A., Sheppard, J.D., Mixing time and oxygen transfer characteristics of a double draft tube air-lift fermentor, Biotechn.Bioeng.,23, 9, 1981, p.2117-2135
7. Moser, A., *Bioreactors with thin-layer characteristics*, Biotechnology letters, 4, 5, 1982, p.281-286
8. Poulsen, B.R., Iversen, J.J.L., *Mixing determinations in reactor vessels using linear buffers*, Chem Eng Sci, 1997, 52(6) p. 979-984.
9. Schiigerl K., Liicke, J., Oels, U.: *Bubble Column Bioreactors*. In: Advances in biochemical engineering, vol.7, Springer-Verlag, 1977, p. 1-84
10. Sokolov. E., Zinger, N.: *Jet apparatus*, "Energy", Moscow, 1970 (in Russian)
11. Strenk, F., *Mixing and mixing apparatus*, "Chemistry", Sankt Petersburg, 1975 (in Russian)

Using Symbols

W_{sl} – liquid superficial velocity, cm/s

W_{sg} – gas superficial velocity, cm/s

t_{mix} – average mixing time, s

V_R – bioreactor volume, m³

PHYTOTHERAPY AS A SUPPORT FOR TRAVELERS AND TOURISTS HEALTH

Manea Stefan¹, Viorica Tamas, Gabriela Rizea, Daniela Ionescu, Andreea Cozea, Ionescu Florian, Angela Marculescu²

Abstract: Starting with the « Travel Medicine's » objectives ("Travel Medicine" – as a new branch of the contemporary medicine), this paper is presenting the risk factors involved in generating health imbalances and phytotherapy advantages in it's maintenance and recovery .

We are considering the stress of over- and under- solicitation during trips, diet changes, cronobiological and meteobiological factors, biological and microbiological agents witch could could jeopardize our defense system (by an complex definition – genetical, age, sex, previous health state). Pathological condition and disorders states most frequently encountered in Travel Medicine can show up starting from the transport stages and increasing as the mentioned risk factors occur.

Phytotherapy can provide efficient solutions biocompatible, preventing disorders and health care, by avoiding excessive chemical stress induced by synthetic drugs intake.

From interventional natural products in this cases we can mention Hofigal's products: adaptive products, increasing capacity of body's defense, stress diminution, protection and support for digestive functions, fixing sleep disorders, hygiene and cosmetics.

Keywords: Phytotherapy, cronobiological and meteobiological factors, Hofigal.

1. Introduction

Travel Medicine, having as purpose to reduce the illness risk of travelers, it starts to outline in USA in 1987 by accumulation of medical expertise on infectious and tropical diseases caused by travelling. Health information for international travel compiled by the U.S. Department of Health are updated weekly. Cataloging work and medical reports on travel-related diseases (infectious and parasitic disease, motion and flight sickness, digestive and sleep disorders, etc..) awaked an vivid interest of tourist organizations and applicants for turist services to increase health safety travel, taking action for preventive measures, monitoring and health care, immunizations, health insurance issue, travel medical advice, organizing treatments for specific trip risks, including the post-travel stage.

In 2002 the Travel Medicine Center in Hamburg and the Bielefeld University had undertake a balance of health state in the European tourism according to continental or extra-continental destinations, registered diseases and recreational programs. The search

results shows that a good organizational and medical training does not increase costs, but increase the comfort and safety of travel and association of recreational programs improves health recovery and vital tone of the participants avoiding monotony and adaptation stress. Thus, morbidity recorded in 2002 at European level for continental destinations was the only 6% and for those extra-continental of 16,2 Health risks and complementary curative-profilactic solutions offered by phytotherapy.

2. Materials and method

2.1. Motion sickness (kinetoza) is encountered less then 1% to those who travel by plane and reaches maximum rate on sea navigation.

The first sign is the the excessive irritation of the vestibular of the inner ear, due to vechicule rolling motion, swing motion, of weightlessness and the shock when is affected the inner ear fluid circulation. This disturbance is transmitted through the cranial nerves to nerve centers being translated as danger signals that causes vagotonic reactions and histaminergy, interrupting blood

¹S.C. HOFIGAL EXPORT IMPORT S.A Intrarea Serelor nr.2, sector 4, Bucharest, Romania, Research and Development Departament

² Transilvania University of Brasov, marculescu_angela@yahoo.com

supply of the inner ear and signals transmission to the brain.

Motion sickness is encountered not only during trips but also can appear for example when playing for too long computer video games. We can observe digestive symptoms, salivation, nausea, vomiting which associates with pallor, sweating and sleepiness.

In those situations phytotherapy uses gentle means to ameliorate the symptoms by taking products with mint extracts (as tinctures, oily extract, volatile oils or tea). Peppermint oil extract is also used in reflexogenic massage on hands and forehead. There are also recommended Fennel seeds (as tea, oily extract or volatile oils), in association with lemon juice and cinnamon powder to improve cerebral circulation.

Another group of products found as single-doses, very efficient and easy to administrate, made from the youngest medicinal plants bodies, are able to calm and improve blood circulation on ear area and brain.

2.2. Digestive phenomena discomfort and diseases of the digestive

These are the most frequent disorders and illness of the digestive, due to alimentation, water, changing eating habits, etc. These state of discomfort can be: burns, stomach cramps, vomiting, diarrhea, constipation, etc. Depending on the symptoms can be used in the following preparations: MagAnghinar, Redigest, Redigest Plus

- tablets and capsules, Reglacid, Hepastim – capsules, and some Gemoderivate that may be recommended by health experts.

- Eucolon (oral drops), an extract of aromatic plant with stomachic carminative and spasmolytic qualities.

- Anti bloating tea, compound of Sage and Jerusalem artichoke - combines the antiseptic qualities, antispasmodic and calming of Sage, with prebiotic properties of fructo-oligosaccharide/FOS found in Jerusalem artichoke, which stimulates colon resettle with beneficial saprophytic flora and inhibit the microbial pathogens adherence to mucosal.

Alimentation also has an important role; it has to be adapted according to the disease and is recommended a diet seasoned with fresh parsley rich in digestive enzymes

2.3. Cardiovascular disorder are also very common.

Reduced atmospheric pressure during flights or mountain climbing increase the risk of cardiac illnesses.

Phytotherapy Medicine recommends the following natural products:

- Q10 Coenzyme found in boxthorn 15, 30, 60 mg, improves coronary circulation, regulates blood pressure, improves myocardial oxygenation and prevents oxidation of LDL cholesterol.

- L-Carnitina complex – capsules increases resistance to stress and general tissue oxygenation and improves myocardial tonus.

- Fish Oil - 600 mg and 900 mg – such as ω3- ω6 vegetal –capsules reduce blood cholesterol level and triglycerides, reduces blood viscosity and coronary artery inflammation.

- Tincture of cayenne pepper help eliminate arterial and coronary spasms reducing blood pressure.

- Passisclerotin- capsules - combining some plant extracts with sedative action and vascular spasmolytic, it is useful in eliminating cardiovascular crisis caused by stress.

- Natural multi-vitamins made by Hofigal with Calcium and Magnesium, this product is useful in curative-prophylactic treatment of arterial and coronary spasm.

- Hoflipomin – tablets and Colerd – tablets by it's components of plant extracts and propolis stimulates lipolytic processes, diminishing blood lipid levels and atheromatous deposits.

- Gemoderivates with some indications are very efficientes in prevention and treatment of angina pectoris, thrombosis and myocardial stroke: single dose of Sanger, hawthorn, blackthorn and lilac.

2.4. Anemia its severe forms of hemoglobin below 0.5g% and erythrocytes under 3 million / ml, prevents efficient tissue oxygenation being an obstacle when reduced atmospheric pressure during flights or mountain climbing. In this case diet also plays an important role in preventing states from anemia, it should be avoid excessive consumption of foods containing oxalic acid (ex: spinach, tomato, chocolate), tannin (Coffee and black tea) sodas which prevents gastric absorption of iron; also it should be avoid excessive consumption of cow's milk by children, which causes intestinal tract irritation. Whole grains are recommended, boiled, soy products, vegetables and fresh fruit. As phytotherapeutic products are indicated the following:

- Spirulina (tablets or capsules) stimulates the bone marrow by phycocyanin content, B12, minerals and amino acids.
- Nettle and dandelion (tea or tincture) with a high content of chelated iron with organic acids are also indicated. In the same time dandelion has depurative properties over the liver and a high content of folic acid and B complex, witch stimulates hematopoetics.
- Alfalfa Complex (tablets), containing Alfalfa juice and Spirulina, is particularly efficient in combating anemia, being also an effective general body tonic.
- Horsetail and Echinacea as tea or tincture also as Echinavit C-capsules and tablets are considered efficient stimulators of bone marrow
- Armuhep (tea and tincture) and Chamomile (tea and tincture) have detoxifying qualities antioxidant and hematopoetic support.

2.5. Venous stasis, Favored by lack of movement during transport (road, air, water) causes tired legs syndrome, heavy, favoring the occurrence of venous thrombosis.

To prevent these states is recommended a predominant vegetarian diet containing mainly dietary fiber, reducing saturated fat intake, avoiding heat processed oils, reducing sugar and refined flour, as coffee and alcohol, witch dehydrate the tissues and predispose to venous inflammation

Natural products recommended:

- Venhof si Supliform as gel applied on massages, local upward, being efficient in stimulating venous circulation and combats sensation of heavy legs.
- Coenzyme Q10 de 15, 30, 60 mg in sea buckthorn oil – it improves the central and peripheral circulation, oxygenation and trophicity of venous tissue.
- Fish Oil 600, 900 mg capsules fluidized blood, reduces lipidemia and oxidative stress in blood vessels blood.
- Horse chestnut tincture, by escina contribution, it tonify venous wall and venous valves.
- Flavovit C 500 mg / tablet by its content of rutin and hesperidin, next to C vitamin it acts as nutritive for venous structures and reduces oxidative stress at this level.
- Bilberry tincture, tonify venous and capillary wall by its of proantociani content.
- Hawthorn, Horsetail and Yarrow Tinctures - administered orally, acts as trophic, tonic and venous constrictor, improving venous circulation.

- Gemoderivat black alder (single-dose) - is also an efficient remedy in prevention and treatment of venous insufficiency.

2.6. Syndrome „ athlete's foot “ is a fungal disease of the planting area accompanied by inflammation, crusting, cracking and other damage – brought up by prolonged wearing of shoes, by sweat and poor hygiene.

Recommended products:

- Pedishan gel, heels and planting area care cream, by its antiseptic components, healing and moisturizing, soothes and reduces irritation and inflammation occurred, accelerating healing.
- Oil extract from Thyme, Sage and Marigold, by local applications they interfere in fighting against infection and inflammation and scarring lesions.
- ω 3 and ω 6 vegetal product – capsules by its trophic and anti-inflammatory qualities, it hurry recovery phenomena and inflammatory lesions.

2.7. Travelers Insomnia it appears due to disrionii circadiene by changing 5-6 time zones (mainly from West to East) and manifests by intense insomnia, fatigue, headaches, poor attention and loss of appetite for about 3-5 days.

Diurnal waking / sleep cycle corresponds to daylight / darkness. Exposure to light during the day, stimulates the suprachiasmatic nucleus (“biological clock”) and indirectly pineal gland to produce serotonin, neuro-chemical mediators, necessary for tonus and nervos balance.

Night darkness causes cease in serotonin production, stimulating its conversion to melatonin by the pineal gland (neurochemical mediators) witch induces a state of quiet, of sleepiness.

Complementary medicine recommends avoiding consumption of foods containing tyramine in the evening, for the reason that it induces norepinephrine, an nervous excitement, into the brain; also avoidance of: fermented cheese, chocolate, spinach, tomatoes, eggplant, fat, red wine, sugar, etc.. It is recommended to drink warm milk sweetened with honey.

Current medicine explain the mechanism of this remedy by honey’s attribute to facilit crossing the blood-brain barrier, tryptophan milk, followed by a series of melatonin biotransformation (occurring in „reseting the biological clock”). Also milk interferes by its calcium contribution that have an important role in muscle relaxation and assures a state of calm.

As phytotherapeutic preparations we are recommending the following:

- Pssisclerotin-tablets or Passiflora tablets, Valerian - capsules.
- Natural multi-vitamins by Hofigal with calcium and magnesium taken in the evening can also help to achieve a calm and sleepy state.
- Chamomile tincture taken after dinner can help to achieve sleepy state.
- Single-doses "A" – Chase away mosquito – containing a repellent gel / that protect sleep.

Phytotherapeutic products listed on the firm Hofigal can compile kits / kit handy travel organizers and tourists and travelers reach, able to prevent, resolve and even treat illnesses that

can be caused by travel risks and changing dietary habits.

3. Conclusions

On phytotherapeutic products listed above, Hofigal firm can compile kits travel at organizers. tourists and travelers reach, able to prevent, ameliorate and even treat illnesses that can be caused by travel risks and changing dietary habits.

References

- 1.Andreoli Th., Carpenter ChC., Plum F., Smith L.A., „Cecil essential of medicine” ed. 2, Ed. WB Saunders Co., Philadelphia, Tokyo, 1996, p. 630-632.
- 2.Dennis L. Kasper si col: „Harrison’s principles of Internal medicine”, ed. 16,Ed. McGran-Hill, N. York-Toronto, 2005, p 725- 730
- 3.Walker R, Edwards C.: „ Clinical pharmacy and therapeutics”, ed. 3, Ed. Churchill, Edinburgh – Toronto, 2003, p. 185-191.
- 4.Susanne Flech, si colab: „, Travel and Health Status: a survey follow-up study in „, European Journal of Public Health, 200, p.96-100
- 5.Bears Mh et col. „, The Merck manual of diagnosis and therapy”, Ed. Merck Res. Lab, Washington NY, 2005, p. 2737-2742.
- 6.Phyllis A. Balch: „Prescription for nutritional healing” Ed 4, Ed. Avery, NY, 2006, p. 577-579

QUESTS CONCERNING THE CORRELATIONS BETWEEN FOOD QUALITY AND THAT OF THE FARM TROUT MEAT

V. NECULA, MIHAELA BABII, MONICA POTROVITA, D. ENACHE, G. PUCHIANU, B. DUMITRU

Abstract: *The present paper investigates the possible connections between the quality of fodder and that of the consumers meat from farm trout. The high content in fat of the fodder from those fish has a negative impact on the quality of their meat, through the higher content of fat in the meat, besides the change in the sensory and qualitative features of the meat. The research was done on a lot of trout from a trout farm, where trout were provided, at will, fodder with high level of fat. The results came soon after and had serious consequences upon the fish, with a mortality as high as 12%, ruling out first, through microbiological tests, the possibility of a bacterial, viral or fungal infestation.*

Key words: *trout, fodder, fat, meat, sensory features.*

1. Material and methods

The level of fat from the food the fish were provided with has been determined by the etheric extraction or Soxhlet method. The same determination was performed upon the meat of the fish fed with the above fodder.

Following the observation that during the cutting of fish for the removal of bone and skin, as well as for the separation of the muscular masses to determine the fat content, not to mention that the blade of the knife was stuck with fat drops, while the hepatopancreas was an intense yellowish color and highly friable, we proceeded to the histopathology examination. Due to the high fat content, the meat had a "greasy" appearance.

The determination of fat from the administered fodder and from the muscular mass by the Soxhlet method involves the following steps:

The lot of fish to be tested was removed the skin, the viscera, the bones, then it was very small chopped and homogenized. Up to 5 g per sample has been weighed to be introduced in the paper sachet for the extraction, with the 10⁻⁴g precision, then it was dried in an oven at 105°C for a couple of hours. The sachet was pulled out and introduced in the dryer covered with the lid. Than it is left to cool in the dryer for about 30 min. The procedures of weighing, drying and cooling are repeated until constant mass,

than it was determined the moist of the sample.

The difference between the constant weigh of the sachet and the sample before and after the drying was determined, thus calculating the weigh of the sample. The sachet with the sample, processed as above, was put in the extraction bowel of the device, in which app.250 cc of petroleum ether and previously degreased and dried pebbles had been introduced.

The extraction was then performed for about 8 hours, during 2 days time, then the sachet was removed and it was dried in the oven at 105°C, until constant mass.

2. Calculation and expression of the results

The content in fat of the fish sample was calculated by the following formula:

$$G = \frac{m1 - m2}{m} \times 100 - U \text{ [%]}$$

In which:

m1 – the mass of the sachet with the test sample, before drying, in grams.

m2 – the mass of the sachet with the test sample degreased and dried, in grams.

m – the mass of the test sample, in grams

U – humidity of the test sample, in grams.

The sections from the hepatopancreas were stained by the tri-chromic method, Hematoxylin, Eosin and Blue Methilene. This technique involves the following steps:

Harvesting the samples

Harvesting was done immediately after evisceration, being preserved the hepatopancreas, of which 5 mm sections were performed, to be, then, fastened with the Orth fastening device for 48 hours. After fastening the samples were washed and included in paraffin.

Paraffin inclusion technique

This is a universal method suitable for any tissue. It allows taking very thin and even serial sections. Paraffin inclusion presumes that the samples (tissue fragments already fastened) to take the following process: dehydration, clearing, paraffining and inclusion in paraffin blocks.

Staining the sections

The table below details the specific steps of the staining as per the working procedure:

Table 1.

The specific steps of the staining as per the working procedure, H.E.A.:

Mayer Hematoxylin	7 min.
Tap water	5 min.
Litinated water	30 sec.-3 min.
Tap water	Rinsing
Distilled water	Rinsing
Eosine, aqueous sol. 1%.	6 min.
Distilled water	Rinsing
Phospho-molibbdenic acid	10 min.
Blue methylene	30 sec. – 1 min.
Distilled water I	Rinsing
Distilled water II	Rinsing

Staining process results: On examining the sections prepared with this method, we noticed: dark purple nuclei, pink or dark purple cytoplasm, brick stained red blood cells, dark blue conjunctive fibers, light blue fundamental substance, muscle fibers stained in red, gold-brown hemosiderin, hyaline tissue stained sometimes in pink, sometimes lightly basophilic, amyloidal tissue stained in light pink, oxyphil or basophile viral inclusions, Gram positive germs stained in dark purple and mycets in purplish blue.

Next: dehydration, clarification and mounting of the stained sections.

For a better result in the last clarifying bath, we have used fenolated xylen, while for the

mounting of the stained sections the balm of Canada was used.

3. Results

After the physical and chemical determinations and the histopathology examination had been performed, the following aspects were noticed:

After testing the moisture and the fat level in the fodder, we had the values below:

- Moisture: 5.12%
- Fat: 33.7%

After testing the moisture and fat level from the muscular masses of the fish, we had the values below:

- Moisture: 25.2%
- Fat: 11.27%

Examining the histological sections stained by the H.E.A. method, we noticed the following aspects:

Fig.1. Hepatopancreas-Zones of dystrophy and focal encapsulated necrosis, with cellular elements inflow. – H.E.A. staining, X 20- Original

Fig.2. Pancreatic acini with fat dystrophy and necrosis areas. - H.E.A. stainin – imersion x 100-Original.

Fig. 3. Area of necrosis and severe fat dystrophy in the hepatopancreatic islands, with high lymphocyte inflow. - H.E.A. staining, immersion x 100 –original

Fig.4. Hepatopancreatic junction with an area of necrosis. A mass if of necrotic debris was noticed, with a powdery look and pancreatic acini next to hepatic cells islands with fat dystrophy.- H.E.A., immersion, x 100-Original.

Fig. 5. Hepatopancreas- Notice in the front plane hepatic cells with fat dystrophy, represented by the accumulation of fat drops in the cytoplasm, and cariolysis H.E.A. immersion, x 100-Original.

4. Discussions

The lot of trout was provided with food at will, food for which the tests showed it contained a high level of fat. Following the determination of the level of fat in the fodder, we noticed a moisture of 5.12% and a level of fat of 33.7%, despite the technical folder of the product which indicated a lower level of fat, i.e. 27%.

Testing the consumer's meat of those fish, we identified a moisture of 25% and a high level of fat of 10.27%, which is way above the limits for the fat meat fish, namely 6-8%.

This was also noticeable following the sensory testing of the meat which, through sectioning, was leaving a heavy amount of fat drops on the knife blade, and by palpation gave an intense greasy sensation. Following the boiling test the bullion (soup) that resulted showed a great amount of fat, that appeared as a thin neat layer, with a pleasant smell and yellowish color, but in abundance.

The taste of the meat showed also, an intense greasy feeling, which generated a disagreeable sensation, unfit for the consumption of the trout meat with an allowed level of fat.

On the histopathology examination of the hepatopancreas, which presented with a intense yellow color and high friability, we noticed a wide range of lesions. Distropy and necrosis of the hepatopancreas were the most frequent lesions,

besides a high cellular inflow (Fig.1), represented by the presence of the lymphocytes, that have been observed at examination with immersion. (Fig.2,3 and 5)

The necrosis areas extended to wide fields, being represented, either by a necrotic debris with a powdery aspect, as shown in Fig.4, or by damaged cells, lacking the nuclei and in an incipient faze of cytolysis, both in the pancreas, and in the hepatic islands. (Fig.2 and 5)

It was noticeable that in all the hepatopancreas cells, affected by the fat dystrophy, fat drops were present, either isolated, as in Fig.5, or confluent, which, on the background of necrosis areas, gave a "foamy" aspect. (Fig 2)

5. Conclusions

There must be a direct correlation between the technical file of the product and the stated content of nutrients.

The fat content from fodder, as well as the amount of administered fodder, both have direct consequences over the trout farming and the level of fat in their meat.

The absence of certain bacterial, viral or mycotic diseases, may lead to the incrimination of fodder as determinant for certain metabolic conditions.

The sensory changes of meat may conduct to performing certain physical, chemical and histopathology examinations.

The fat level of 10,27% from the trout meat is very high, compared to that of 6-8%, representing the normal level of fat in trout meat.

Intense elevation of the fat level from meat is followed by the sensory features of the meat and to the appearance of certain dystrophic and necrotic lesions at the level of the hepatopancreas, determining high mortality and low quality of the trout.

There is a traceability represented by the indestructible connection between the nutritious quality of the fodder given as food and the quality of the consumer's quality of the meat from these fish.

References:

1. Constantin Savu - Igienna și controlul produselor de origine animală, 2002 - Ed. SemnE - București

2. Enache.T, Paul.I ,StănescuV., 1994 -
Medicină legală veterinară -Ed. All-
București
3. Gheorghe Puchianu, Vasile Secașiu,
2012. Patologia faunei de interes
cinegetic, Editura Universității
Transilvania din Brașov.
4. Valentin Necula, Georgeta Macarie,
Maria Moisiu, Petrișor Tănăsie, 1998.
Anatomie patologică și fiziopatologie -
Ed. Ceres-București.
5. Valentin Necula, Mihaela Babii, 2010.
Alimente alimentație și impactul
acestora asupra sănătății
consumatorului - Ed. Universității
Transilvania din Brașov- Brașov.
6. Ordinul MAAP NR 329 / 2002 pentru
aprobarea normei sanitare veterinare,
privind condițiile sanitare veterinare
pentru producerea și comercializarea
produselor din pescuit. - București .
7. STAS: SR ISO 6492/ 2006

VISCOELASTICAL BAHEVIOUR OF HONEYS

MIRCEA-ADRIAN OROIAN¹, GHEORGHE GUTT¹

Abstract: *The purpose of this work was to investigate the viscoelastical properties of 6 honeys with various °Brix concentrations (80.4 – 82°Brix) at different temperature (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 40°C) and was then correlated with the °Brix concentration. From the rheological point of view, honey is a Newtonian fluid presenting a high viscous part (the loss modulus it is much greater than the elastic modulus); the loss modulus (G'') increased with the decreasing of the temperature and the increasing of the °Brix concentration. The effect of temperature on the elastic and loss modulus can be described by means of Arrhenius model.*

Keywords: *honey, viscoelasticity, Arrhenius model*

1. Introduction

Honey is the sweet, viscous substance elaborated by honeybee from the nectar plants and has been considered as an important part of traditional medicines since ancient times (1). Honey is a semi-liquid produce (water: 15–20% approx.) which contains a complex mixture of carbohydrates, mainly glucose and fructose; other sugars are present as traces, depending on the floral origin. Moreover, organic acids, lactones, amino acids, minerals, vitamins, enzymes, pollen, wax and pigments are present (2). The knowledge of the flow behaviour of concentrated food stuff is useful in quality control, calculating energy requirements, process control, and selection of proper process equipment (3). Recently, the influence of temperature on the flow behaviour of honeys varieties have been studied (4-9).

Many researches had treated the problematic of the viscosity modelling according to the influence of temperature using different models (Arrhenius, VTF, WLF, Power Law). In the literature appear a few articles about the effect of the temperature on the viscoelastical behaviour of honeys (10). In particular, little information is available on the viscoelastical properties of the Spanish honeys of different sources.

The purpose of this study is to model the viscoelastical behaviour of honeys using the Arrhenius model.

2. Materials and methods

The honey used was obtained from Spanish market. Rheological properties of honey can be influenced by the presence of crystals and

air bubbles (4, 11, 12). Before being used they were warmed up to 55°C to dissolve any crystals, and kept in flasks at 30°C to remove air bubbles that could interfere in rheological studies.

2.1. Moisture content

The moisture contents of honey samples were obtained by measuring the refractive index at 20°C using a digital refractometer (3T Atago Abbe refractometer, Atago Co., Tokyo, Japan). The water content and °Brix concentration were determined based on a Chataway table (13). Each measurement was taken in duplicate.

2.2. Viscoelastical measurement

The dynamic rheological properties of honey samples were obtained with a RheoStress 1 rheometer (Thermo Haake, Germany) at different temperatures (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 40°C), using a parallel plate system (Ø 60 mm) at a gap of 500 µm. A batch of each composition was prepared and at least two measurements were performed on each batch, using a fresh sample for each measurement. After loading the sample, a waiting period of 5 min was used to allow the sample to recover itself and to reach the desired temperature. In order to determine the linear viscoelastic region, stress sweeps were run at 1 Hz first. Then, the frequency sweeps were performed over the range $\omega=0.62-62.83\text{Hz}$ at 1 Pa stress. The 1 Pa stress was in the linear viscoelastic region. Rheowin Job software (v. 2.93, Haake) was used to obtain the experimental data and to calculate storage (or elastic) modulus (G'), loss (viscous) modulus (G''), and complex viscosity (η^*).

3. Results and discussion

In the figure 1 is presented a typically rheogram of a honey sample in a 0.62–62.83 rad/s frequency domain at 5–40 °C; it shows the changes in storage modulus (G'), loss modulus (G''), and complex viscosity (η^*) with the frequency. The viscoelastic parameters (G' and G'') increased with the increasing of the frequency applied to the sample, showing that G'' had a greater magnitude than G' . All the viscoelastic parameters are positively influenced by the °Brix concentration. In general, G' is less important than G'' ($G'' > G'$) as indicated by Doubly and Cavalier (14). This study presents below the influence of temperature on the loss modulus of honeys using Arrhenius model. The viscoelastic behaviour of the honeys was further described by the Arrhenius model:

- Arrhenius model (eq.1 & 2)

$$G' = G_0' \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right] \quad (1)$$

$$G'' = G_0'' \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right] \quad (2)$$

Where G_0' , G_0'' is a constant, R is the gas constant [$\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$], and E_a activation energy (is an energy barrier to flowing) [$\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$], T – absolute temperature [K].

The activation energies (E_a) values (tab.2), calculated by the Arrhenius model were ranged between 47.68 – 77.18 kJ/mol in the case of elastic modulus, while in the case of the loss modulus ranged between 83.24 – 92.15 kJ/mol. The magnitude of G'' and G' influence the activation energy magnitude. The activation energies are correlated positively with the °Brix concentration ($r = 0.875$ for elastic modulus and respectively $r = 0.813$ for loss modulus). In the case of the pre-exponential factor the elastic modulus factor is negatively correlated with concentration ($r = -0.259$), while the loss modulus is weakly positively correlated to concentration ($r = 0.174$). The Arrhenius model is much better for predicting the evolution of loss modulus with temperature then for the elastic modulus (the coefficients of regression were for all the honeys 0.99 for loss modulus, while in the case of elastic modulus, the coefficients of regression ranged between 0.83 – 0.90).

Fig.1. Typical rheogram of honey (Fig.1.a – elastic modulus and Fig.1.b - loss modulus) at different temperature: rhombus 5°C, square 10°C, triangle 15°C, multiplication symbol 20°C, cyrillic small letter zhe 25°C, circle 30°C and plus 40°C

Tab.1. °Brix concentration and Arrhenius model parameters of honey

Honey	°Brix concentration [%]	G'			G''		
		G_0' [mPa]	E_a [kJ/mol]	R^2	G_0'' [mPa]	E_a [kJ/mol]	R^2
H1	80.7	$8.9 \cdot 10^{-11}$	56.92	0.83	$9.2 \cdot 10^{-14}$	89.00	0.99
H2	80.4	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-10}$	56.32	0.90	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-14}$	84.99	0.99

H3	80.5	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-9}$	47.68	0.84	$8.8 \cdot 10^{-14}$	83.24	0.99
H4	80.7	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-10}$	54.25	0.84	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-14}$	86.86	0.99
H5	80.6	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-12}$	64.22	0.86	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-14}$	88.09	0.99
H6	82.0	$7.1 \cdot 10^{-14}$	77.18	0.88	$5.9 \cdot 10^{-15}$	92.15	0.99

4. Conclusions

Honeys presents a liquid-like rheological behaviour with loss modulus much greater than elastic modulus in the domain of the temperature used (0-40°C). The loss and elastic modulus are influenced negatively by the increasing of the temperature, and positively by °Brix concentration. The activation energies of the Arrhenius model are correlated positively with the °Brix concentration for the elastic and loss modulus. The Arrhenius model is much suitable for temperature modelling of viscous part then for elastic part.

Acknowledgments

This paper was supported by the project "Knowledge provocation and development through doctoral research PRO-DOCT - Contract no. POSDRU/88/1.5/S/52946 ", project co-funded from European Social Fund through Sectorial Operational Program Human Resources 2007- 2013.

References

- 1). White, J. W. (1979). Composition of honey. In E. Crane (Ed.), *Honey: A Comprehensive Survey* (pp. 157–158). London: Heinemann.
- 2). Fallico, B., Zappalà, M., Arena, E. and Verzera, A., (2004). Effects of heating process on chemical composition and HMF levels in Sicilian monofloral honeys. *Food Chemistry* 85(2), 305–313
- 3). Kaya, A., Ko, S., Gunasekaran, S., (2008). Viscosity and color change during in situ solidification of grape pekmez, *Food Bioprocess Technology* 4(2),241-246
- 4). Bhandari, B., D'Arcy, B., & Chow, S. (1999). Rheology of selected Australian honeys. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 41(1), 65–68
- 5). Chen, Y.W., Lin, C.H., Wu, F.Y., Chen, H.H., (2009). Rheological properties of crystallized honey prepared by new type of nuclei. *Journal of Food Process Engineering* 32, 512–527
- 6). Kang, K.M., Yoo, B., (2008). Dynamic rheological properties of honeys at low temperatures as affected by moisture content and

temperature. *Food Science and Biotechnology* 17 (1), 90–94.

7). Oroian, M., Amariei, S., Escriche, I., Gutt, G., Rheological aspects of Spanish Honeys, *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, DOI: 10.1007/s11947-011-0730-4, in press

8). Cohen, I., Weihs, D. (2010). Rheology and microrheology of natural and reduced-calorie Israeli honeys as a model for high-viscosity Newtonian liquids, *Journal of Food Engineering* 100(2), 366-371

9). Witczak, M., Juszczak L., Galkowska D. (2011), Non-Newtonian behaviour of heather honey, *Journal of Food Engineering* 104 (1) 532–537

10). Yoo B. (2004), Effect of temperature on dynamic rheology of Korean honeys, *Journal of Food Engineering* 65, 459–463

11). Abu-Jdayil, B., Al-Majeed Ghzawi, A., Al-Malah, K. I. M., & Zaitoun, S. J. (2002). Heat effect on rheology of light and darkcolored honey. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 51(1), 33–38

12). Mossel, B., Bhandari, B., D'Arcy, B., Caffin, N. (2000). Use of Arrhenius model to predict rheological behaviour in some Australian honeys. *Lebensmittel-Wissenschaft und Technologie*, 33, 545–552.

13). Bogdanov S., (2002) Harmonised methods of the international honey commission. Swiss Bee Research Centre, FAM, Liebefeld, CH-3003 Bern, Switzerland.

14). Doublier, J. L., & Cuvelier, G. (1996). Gums and hydrocolloids: functional aspect. In A. C. Eliasson (Ed.), *Carbohydrates in Food*. New York: Marcel Dekker Inc.

PRIMARY OXIDATION PRODUCTS ACCUMULATION IN WALNUT OIL DURING HEAT TREATMENT

C. POPOVICI* P. ALEXE** O. DESEATNICOVA*

Abstract: During this study walnut oil was heated at different technological conditions - 120 °C, 160 °C and 180 °C. Free fatty acid, conjugated dienes and trienes, peroxide value and refractive index were investigated immediately after heat treatment. The data obtained from the experiment indicate that heat treatment cause initiation of walnut oil oxidation. The conjugated dienes (CD) content of the walnut oil samples ranged from 6.23 to 12.75 µmol/g, while the conjugated trienes (CT) content ranged from 1.58 to 6.25 µmol/g. The peroxide value (PV) was in the range of 5.81 – 26.55 mmol/kg of walnut oil. These data should assist in selecting conditions that are suitable and better for walnut oil heat treatment. However it is necessary to note that these data are not enough to make a final conclusion about the behavior of walnut oil in thermal oxidation conditions. Currently we obtained preliminary data about accumulation of secondary oxidation products in walnut oil during heat treatment. These data should help us to describe oxidation mechanism of walnut oil and to recommend optimal conditions for walnut heat treatment.

Keywords: walnut oil, heat treatment, primary oxidation products, quality indices.

1. Introduction

Walnut (*Juglans regia* L) a member of Juglandaceae family is one of the finest nuts of temperate regions. It is the oldest cultivated fruit in the world (Ozcan, 2009). Walnut oil is prized as a specially oil because of its potential health benefits and organoleptic properties (Bada *et al.*, 2010; Pereira *et al.*, 2008).

The health benefits of walnut oil are usually attributed to its chemical composition. Walnut oil contains approximately 7% saturated, 20% monounsaturated and 73% polyunsaturated fatty acids (Rabrenovic *et al.*, 2011; Tsamouris *et al.*, 2002). These high levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids make walnut oil prone to oxidation and may mean that oil has a limited shelf-life.

A number of experiments have been carried out on the oxidation stability of walnut oil. Temperature, light, moisture and exposure to oxygen have been found to be the main contributing factors to oxidation (Salcedo *et al.*, 2010; Mexis *et al.*, 2009; Aranz *et al.*, 2008; Martinez *et al.*, 2008; Vanhanen *et al.*, 2006; Crowe *et al.*, 2003;). Stark *et al.* (2000) found that walnut oil stored at room temperature in the dark, in sealed bottles, showed only small rises in peroxide values after four months of storage and

remained an acceptable product in terms of its organoleptic properties.

The objective of this study was to investigate the intensity of primary oxidation products accumulation in walnut oil under different heat treatment conditions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Refined walnut oil was obtained from a local producer in the Republic of Moldova in April 2011. Walnut oil was heated during 20 min at different temperatures: 120°C, 160 °C and 180 °C. After heat treatment walnut oil samples were used in the experiment.

2.2. Chemicals

Ethanol (99.9%), methanol (99%), potassium hydroxide, phenolphthalein, potassium iodide, sodium thiosulfate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and starch were supplied by Eco-Chimie (Chisinau, Republic of Moldova). Chloroform, 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (isooctane) and glacial acetic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All reagents were of analytical grade. Distilled water was used throughout.

* Faculty of Technology and Management in Food Industry, Technical University of Moldova, e-mail: popovici.kristina@gmail.com

** Faculty of Food Science and Engineering, "Dunarea de Jos" University Galati, Romania, e-mail: petru.alexu@ugal.ro

2.3. Acid Value

Acid value was determined by potassium hydroxide titration as described in AOCS Official Method Cd 3d-63 (AOCS, 1999). The method was based on the number of milligrams of potassium hydroxide necessary to neutralize the free acids in 1 gram of oil sample. Results were expressed as milligram of potassium hydroxide per gram of walnut oil sample.

2.4. Refractive Index

The refractive index of walnut oil samples was measured following the process described in AOCS Official Method Cc 7-25 (AOCS, 1998). This index is related to degree of saturation but is affected by other factors such as acid value, oxidation, and heat treatment. Refractive index was determined using digital handheld refractometer Krüss Optronic DR 301-95 (Germany).

2.5. Peroxide Value

Oxidation rate was studied immediately after walnut heating by determination of the peroxide value (PV). This was determined according to AOCS Official Method Cd 8-53 (AOCS, 2003). PV was expressed as millimoles peroxide per kilogram of walnut oil.

2.6. Conjugated dienes and trienes

The experiment was carried out according to the AOCS Official method Ti la 64 (AOCS, 1993) with minor modifications. Approximately 0.02 g of walnut oil was placed into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The sample was dissolved in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane, brought to volume and mixed thoroughly. Absorbance of the dissolved walnut oil was measured in UV/Vis spectrophotometer HACH-LANGE DR-5000 (Germany) at 236 nm and 273 nm using quartz cuvette 10×10 mm. The CD and CT values were calculated using the following equations:

$$C_{CD/CT} = A_{236/273} / (\square \times l) \text{ and } CD/CT_{\text{value}} = [C_{CD/CT} \times (2.5 \times 10^4)] / W$$

where $C_{CD/CT}$ is the CD/CT concentration in mmol/ml (i.e., the molar concentration), $A_{236/273}$ is the absorbance of the oil solutions at 236 nm and 273 nm, \square is the molar absorptivity (i.e., the extinction coefficient) of linoleic acid hydroperoxide ($2.525 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$), l is the path length of the cuvette in cm (1 cm), 2.5×10^4 is a factor that encompasses the volume of 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (25 ml) used to dissolve the oil

sample as well as a unit conversion (1000 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mmol}$) so that the content of CDs and CTs can be expressed in μmol , and W is the weight of the walnut oil in gram. Results were expressed in micromole conjugated dienes and trienes per gram of walnut oil.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Variance analysis of the results was carried out by least square method with application of coefficient Student and Microsoft Office Excel program version 2007. Differences were considered statistically significant if probability was greater than 95% ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$). All assays were performed by triplicate at room temperature $20 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Experimental results are expressed as average \pm SD (standard deviation) (Snedecor *et al.*, 1989).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Acid value

Lipid oxidation of walnut oil samples was evaluated by measuring peroxide value, refraction index and conjugated dienes & trienes content. Changes in acid value are shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Changes in acid value of walnut oil samples as a function of heat treatment at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$, 160 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 180 $^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 1 shows the effect of heat treatment temperature on acid value of walnut samples. The initial acid value of fresh walnut oil sample was low (0.94 mg KOH/g walnut oil). Acid value of heated walnut oil samples is 0.96 mg KOH/g walnut oil for sample heated at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$, 0.97 mg KOH/g walnut oil for sample heated at 160 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 1.01 mg KOH/g walnut oil for sample heated at 180 $^\circ\text{C}$. These values are higher than those of

the fresh walnut oil sample. Differences are attributed to the accelerated process of the walnut oil lipid oxidation.

3.2. Peroxide value

Changes in peroxide value are shown in figure 2. The initial peroxide value of fresh walnut oil sample was very low (5.81 mmol/kg walnut oil). Figure 2 shows the effect of heat treatment on peroxide value at 120 °C, 160 °C and 180 °C.

Fig. 2. Changes in peroxide value of walnut oil samples as a function of heat treatment at 120 °C, 160 °C and 180 °C

All heat treatment conditions significantly affected peroxide value of walnut oil samples. After 120 °C of heat treatment walnut oil sample had a very low peroxide value 19.97 mmol/kg walnut oil. Respective peroxide value was 23.96 mmol/kg and 26.55 mmol/kg walnut oil for walnut samples heated at 160 °C and 180 °C. The observation is that given heat treatment temperatures lead to a rapid lipid oxidation of walnut oil.

3.3. Refraction index

Changes in refraction indexes are shown in figure 3. The initial refraction index of fresh walnut oil sample was 1.4510. Figure 3 shows the effect of heat treatment on refraction index at 120 °C, 160 °C and 180 °C.

Fig. 3. Changes in refraction index of walnut oil samples as a function of heat treatment at 120 °C, 160 °C and 180 °C

The difference from the acid value and peroxide value, heat treatment did not significantly affect refraction index. Respectively refraction index was 1.4514 for walnut oil sample heated at 120 °C, 1.4516 for walnut sample heated at 160 °C and finally 1.4518 for walnut oil sample heated at 180 °C.

3.4. Conjugated dienes & trienes

Changes in conjugated dienes & trienes are shown in figure 4. The initial conjugated dienes & trienes of fresh walnut oil sample were 6.23 μmol/g walnut oil and 1.58 μmol/g walnut oil respectively. Figures 4 and 5 show the effect of heat treatment at 120 °C, 160 °C and 180 °C on conjugated dienes & trienes content.

Fig. 4. Changes in conjugated dienes of walnut oil samples as a function of heat treatment at 120 °C, 160 °C and 180 °C

Fig. 5. Changes in conjugated trienes of walnut oil samples as a function of heat treatment at 120 °C, 160 °C and 180 °C

As with acid value and peroxide value, heat treatment significantly affected conjugated dienes & trienes content. Walnut oil sample heated at 120 °C had following conjugated dienes & trienes content - 8.98 µmol/g walnut oil and 2.54 µmol/g walnut oil respectively. Walnut oil sample heated at 160 °C had following conjugated dienes & trienes content - 11.99 µmol/g walnut oil and 4.04 µmol/g walnut oil respectively. And finally walnut oil sample heated at 180 °C had following conjugated dienes & trienes content - 12.75 µmol/g walnut oil and 6.25 µmol/g walnut oil respectively. As with all previous obtained results, the highest content of conjugated dienes & trienes were recorded for walnut samples heated at 180 °C and the lowest conjugated dienes & trienes content, for fresh walnut samples. Comparison of data in figures 4 and 5 leads to the conclusion that as the heat treatment was more severe the effect of temperature increased. Also for all walnut samples the effect of temperature was more pronounced at 160 °C and 180 °C.

4. Conclusions

The present study investigated the influence of heat treatment conditions on the intensity of primary oxidation products accumulation in walnut oil as a function of temperature value. It was shown that walnut oil retains acceptable quality for heat treatment at 120 °C and quality deteriorates significantly for heat treatment of walnut oil at 160 °C and 180 °C.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Agence Universitaire de la Francophonie (AUF) through the “Eugen Ionescu” postdoctoral scholarship 2010/2011 and financed by the Romanian Government.

References

1. AOCS. 1999. Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the American Oil Chemists' Society. *Method Cd 3d-63*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
2. AOCS. 1998. Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the American Oil Chemists' Society, 5th ed. *Method Cc 7 - 25*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
3. AOCS. 2003. Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the American Oil Chemists' Society. *Method Cd 8-53*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
4. AOCS. 1993. Official Methods and Recommended Practices of the American Oil Chemists' Society. *Method Ti la 64*. Champaign: AOCS Press.
5. Arranz, S., Cert, R., Perez-Jimenez, J., Cert, A., Saura-Calixto, F. *Comparison between free radical scavenging capacity and oxidative stability of nut oils*. Food Chemistry, **110**, 2008, p. 985-990.
6. Snedecor, G. W., Cochran, W. G. *Statistical Methods*. The Iowa State University Press, 8th edition, 1989, Ames.
7. Bada, J.C., Leon-Camacho, M., Prieto, M., Copovi, P., Alonso, L. *Characterization of walnut oils (Juglans regia L.) from Asturias, Spain*. J Am Oil Chem Soc, **87**, 2010, p. 1469-1474.
8. Crowe, T.D., White, P.J. *Oxidative stability of walnut oils extracted with supercritical carbon dioxide*. JAOCS, **80**(6), 2003, p. 575-578.
9. Martinez, M.L., Mattea, M.A., Maestri, D.M. *Pressing and supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of walnut oil*. Journal of Food Engineering, **88**, 2008, p. 399-404.
10. Mexis, S.F., Badeka, A.V., Riganakos, K.A., Karakostas, K.X., Kontominas, M.G. *Effect of packaging and storage conditions on quality of shelled walnuts*. Food Control, **20**, 2009, p. 743-751.
11. Ozcan, M.M. *Some nutritional characteristics of fruit and oil of walnut (Juglans regia L.) growing in Turkey*. Iran. J. Chem. Chem. Eng., **28**(1), 2009, p. 57-62.
12. Pereira, J.A., Oliveira, I., Sousa, A., Ferreira, I.C.F.R., Bento, A., Estevinho, L. *Bioactive properties and chemical composition of six walnut (Juglans regia L.) cultivars*. Food and

- Chemical Toxicology, **46**, 2008, p. 2103-2111.
13. Rabrenovic, B.E., Dimic, M. Maksimovic, S. Sobajic, L. Gajic-Krstajic. *Determination of fatty acid and tocopherol compositions and the oxidative stability of walnut (Juglans regia L.) cultivars grown in Serbia*. Czech J. Food Sci, **29**(1), 2011, p. 74–78.
 14. Salcedo, C.L., Lopez de Mishima, B.A., Nazareno, M.A. *Walnuts and almonds as model system of foods constituted by oxidisable, pro-oxidant and antioxidant factors*. Food Research International, **43**, 2010, p. 1187-1197.
 15. Stark, C., McNeil, D.L., Savage, G.P. *The effect of storage conditions on the stability of peroxide values of New Zealand grown walnuts*. Proceedings of the Nutrition Society of New Zealand, **25**, 2000, p. 43-54.
 16. Tsamouris, G., Hatziantoniou, S., Demetzos C. *Lipid analysis of greek walnut oil (Juglans regia L.)*. Z. Naturforsch, **57c**, 2002, p. 51-56.
 17. Vanhanen, L.P., Savage, G.P. *The use of peroxide value as a measure of quality for walnut flour stored at five different temperatures using three different types of packaging*. Food Chemistry, **99**, 2006, p. 64-69.

INFLUENCE RESEARCH OF THE VEGETATIVE ADDITIVE OF PICKLED VEGETABLES ON QUALITY INDICATORS OF MEAT PRODUCTS

O. SABIROV*

Abstract: Influence research of an pickled vegetables additive on quality indicators of meat products are resulted. The rational maintenance of brines for increase of is functional-technological properties of stock and increase of quality indicators of finished goods is defined.

Key words: meat-vegetative half-finished product, pickled vegetables, brine, penetration degree, ability to connect a moisture, product yield, organoleptic profiles.

Now the problem of deficiency of fiber in a people food is actual. Rational use of meat stock with the considerable maintenance of collagen can be the decision of this problem.

There are some ways of acceleration collagen disaggregation: processing by proteolytic enzymes, addition of organic acids, etc. In particular, under the influence of dairy acid occurs swelling of connective tissue fibers. It positively influences speed of transition of collagen in glutin at the further thermal processing.

It is known that a significant amount of dairy acid accumulates at vegetables souring. We offer to use in the combined meat-vegetative products brines from pickled vegetables which have no practical application. Use of the given kind of stock can accelerate collagen disaggregation.

Article purpose is researches of a rational investment of a vegetative additive at which the highest quality indicators of finished articles are reached.

Modelling pickle mixes consisted of brines from pickled vegetables (cabbage and cucumber),

salt and sugar. Control pickle mix was represented a water solution of salt (24 %) and sugar (1,5 %). The pickle mixes injected in meat stock with the considerable maintenance of collagen. Meat was maintained by 6 hours. Then investigated penetration pickle mixes in a muscular fabric. In pickle mix was added dye for definition of degree of penetration.

In samples with use pickle mixes with cabbage and cucumber brines it is observed more penetration pickle mixes in a fabric (Fig. 1).

It has been defined that in the control sample degree of penetration of a brine in a muscular fabric has made 1,0 mm, in a cucumber brine – 3,1 mm, in a cabbage brine – 3,2 mm.

For definition of rational quantity of injection a brine on a pickled vegetables basis, samples inject by mixes in quantity from 2 to 16 g on 100 g meat stock. In the control sample pickled mixes are absent (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Penetration depth determination of pickle mixes in a muscular fabric

* Dept. of Food Technology, Donetsk National University of Economics and Trade, Ukraine, e-mail: tehnol@kaf.donduet.edu.ua, junnesc@yandex.ru

Fig. 2. Dependence of brines penetration degree from contents pickle mixes:
 ◆ – with cabbage brine; ■ – with cucumber brine

The greatest penetration into a muscular fabric is observed at a mix with a cabbage brine.

Further we had been defined ability of stock to connect a moisture and a product yield.

Ability to connect a moisture is one of the most important is functional-technological properties of meat. It has direct influence on a product yield and juiciness of finished articles.

By us it is conducted researches by ability definition to connect a moisture by a pressing method. The area of the stain, the formed adsorbed moisture, calculate on a difference between a total area of a stain and the area of a stain formed by meat. We offer the following technique for calculation of stains.

On a filtering paper the measured piece long 1 cm was put.

Filtering paper were scanned. Then computer processing of the image (clearing of superfluous

stains) and an interval colouring between stains to black colour was spent. On a measured piece the square the area $1,6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$ was under construction.

By means of computer program Apfill 3.7 there was a filling share black colour of the received square.

The difference area between a total area of a stain and the area of the stain formed by meat, was defined as percent from $1,6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$.

Further calculations were spent according to a technique.

Results of calculations of ability to connect a moisture are resulted in Fig. 3.

The connected moisture in control makes 71,42 %, in the sample with a cabbage brine - 86,57 %, in the sample with a cucumber brine - 83,34 %.

Fig. 3. Dependence of connected moisture degree from contents pickle mixes:
 ◆ – with cabbage brine; ■ – with cucumber brine

Fig. 4. Dependence of product yield from contents pickle mixes:
 ◆ – with cabbage brine; ■ – with cucumber brine

The average increase of product yield makes 6-8 %. The biggest product yield is observed at addition of 8-10 % of an additive for all samples (Fig. 4).

For acknowledgement of fibers swelling it is necessary to investigate microstructural changes of a muscular fabric.

The colouring method by Ehrlich's hematoxylin was applied to definition of microstructural changes of a muscular fabric. For photographing there were areas most typical for the given sample. Microphotos are shown in Fig 5.

As it is possible to see, muscular fibres have the area of cross-section more than control. It testifies that fibers more swelling. Degree of swelling of fibers influences juiciness of products.

We define microstructural changes which occur in meat during technological processing, on the

basis of the analysis of the area of filling with a muscular fibre of a plane of an eyepiece (Fig. 6).

As we see the maximum area of a muscular fibre is observed at an injection of 12 % of a cabbage brine from weight of meat.

Proceeding from the received data, the rational quantity of pickle mixes makes 10-12 % to meat stock. At the given parametres the biggest penetration by pickle mixes in a muscular fibre is observed with simultaneous increase of ability to connect a moisture and a product yield, increase in juiciness of finished articles.

We develop concrete schemes of technologies meat-vegetative half-finished products with addition of pickled vegetables. The basic technological scheme of their manufacture is represented in Fig. 7.

Fig. 5. Microstructure of meat after an injection of pickle mix

Fig. 6. Dependence of the muscular fibre area from contents pickle mixes:
 ◆ – with cabbage brine; ■ – with cucumber brine

Fig. 7. The basic technological scheme of manufacture meat-vegetative half-finished products with addition of pickled vegetables:
 A, B, C - subsystems

Further research of organoleptic indicators for finished goods has been conducted. Researches spent after technological processing with

application of a method of a tasting estimation and the description by means of a profile method.

Criteria and factors of weightiness of indicators of an organoleptic estimation are resulted in table 1.

Table 1

Criteria of an organoleptic estimation of half-finished products in a storage time

№	The name of groups of indicators	Weightiness factor	№	The name of indicators	Weightiness factor
1	Appearance	0,15	1	The form	0,09
			2	Presence of the allocated brine	0,06
2	Consistence	0,15	3	Density	0,06
			4	Plasticity	0,09
3	Colour	0,2	5	Uniformity	0,05
			6	Intensity	0,05
			7	Conformity of a kind stock	0,1
4	Smell	0,2	8	Expressiveness	0,04
			9	Cleanliness	0,05
			10	Naturalness	0,05
			11	Conformity of a kind stock	0,06
5	Taste	0,3	12	Expressiveness	0,03
			13	Juiciness	0,045
			14	Tenderness	0,045
			15	Fibration	0,045
			16	Cleanliness	0,03
			17	Naturalness	0,045
			18	Conformity of a kind stock	0,06
		$\Sigma = 1$			1

Fig. 8. Organoleptic profilogram of meat-vegetative half-finished product with cabbage brine.

Fig. 9. Organoleptic profilogram of meat-vegetative half-finished product with cucumber brine.

At a profile method the difficult concept of one or several organoleptic indicators is presented in the form of making (descriptors). Experts estimate descriptors on quality, intensity and a display order. For an estimation used scales of intensity of separate signs which represented in the form of the profile diagramme (Fig. 8,9).

By results of the analysis of organoleptic profiles of meat products it is established that the most powerful indicator of quality is the form of products, plasticity and conformity on a smell, colour and taste to corresponding meat stock.

The organoleptic properties of all half-finished products is estimated as positive. At the sample with a cabbage brine there is an expressed smell of pickled cabbage. Decrease in injection of a brine for this sample to 8% is recommended. In all samples brine allocation, but within the limits of its normal losses is observed.

Further it is planned to conduct research of the basic chemical indicators of finished articles, biological value and degree of digestibility and their comparison with indicators of traditional analogues.

References

1. Лисицын А.Б. Производство мясной продукции на основе биотехнологии / Лисицын А.Б., Липатов Н.Н., Кудряшов Л.С., Алексахина В.А. – М.: ВНИИМП, 2005. – 369с.
2. Апраксина С.К. Технология мясных продуктов с использованием сырья с большим количеством соединительной ткани / Апраксина С.К. // Мясные технологии. – 2005. – №11(35). – С. 25-29.
3. Борисенко Л.А. Биотехнологические основы интенсификации производства мясных соленых изделий [Текст] / Борисенко Л.А., Борисенко А.А., Брацихин А.А. – М.: ДеЛи принт, 2004. – 163 с.

IMMUNOMODULATING AND ANTITUMOUR EFFECT OF EXTRACTS OF BASIDIOMYCETES

Mark Shamtsyan¹, Vera Spiridonova², Valentina Konusova³,
Nikolay Petrishev⁴, Andrey Symbirtsev⁵,

Abstract: Aqueous extracts from fruit bodies and submerged mycelia of various Basidiomycetes were studied in search of immunomodulating activity. Studied extracts demonstrated various types of marked biological actions: activation of phagocytosis - an increase generation of reactive oxygen forms by neutrophil cells of human peripheral blood; a significant mitogenic activity; stimulation on production of inflammatory cytokines by peripheral blood cells; increase in the levels of anti-body forming cells, anti-tumor activity against melanoma B-16 and Ehrlich's ascit carcinoma

Keywords: Basidiomycetes, Immunomodulation, Ehrlich's ascit,

1. Introduction

For the centuries mushrooms were used in different cultures for their medical and tonic properties. The major part of the traditional knowledge of mushrooms medical properties is coming from the Far East.

Historically, mushrooms were gathered from the wild for consumption and for medicinal use. While mushroom cultivation now spans many centuries, it is only over the last 2-3 decades that there have been major expansions in basic research and practical knowledge leading to the creation of a major worldwide industry.

Biological activity of aqueous extracts from fruit bodies and submerged mycelia of various higher Basidiomycetes were studied.

2. Materials and methods

Objects of our study were fruit bodies mycelium and cultural filtrate of submerge cultivation of species of mushroom species *Armillaria mellea*, *Auricularia auricula-judae*, *Bjerkandera adusta*, *Cerrena unicolor*, *Coprinus lagopides.*, *Hypsizigus ulmarius*, *Inonotus obliquus*, *I. radiatus*, *Flammulina velutipes*,

Fomes fomentarius, *Fomitopsis pinicola*, *Grifola frondosa*, *Ganoderma lipsiense*, *G. Lucidum*, *Lentinus edodes*, *Panus conchatus*, *Piptoporus betulinus*, *Pleurotus cornucopiae*, *P. ostreatus*, *Trametes ochracea*, *Trametes suaveolens*, *Tremella foliacea*, *Tricholoma portentosum*, and also aqueous extracts from cultural mycelium and/or fruit bodies.

Mushroom fruit bodies were collected in the forests of St. Petersburg region of Russia, or purchased from the local market, and several species of basidiomycetes were introduced into culture. The mycelium was obtained by a submerged cultivation of strains on mash (4% reducing sugars) at 28°C. For immunological assays mycelium and fruit bodies were treated using the method described by Wang et al. (1993) with several modifications. The biomass was dried at 70°C, crumbled up and treated with 85% ethanol at 78°C during 5 hours. The sediment was extracted twice by boiling water for 3 hours. The obtained filtrate was evaporated under vacuum, and the polysaccharide fractions were precipitated by 5 volumes of ethanol, dialyzed against distilled water and dried. Obtained powder extracts, before tested on

¹ Department of Technology of Microbiological Synthesis, St.Petersburg State Institute of Technology (Technical University), 26 Moscovsky pr., 198013 Saint Petersburg, Russia; e-mail: shamtsyan@yahoo.com

² Department of Technology of Microbiological Synthesis, St.Petersburg State Institute of Technology (Technical University), 26 Moscovsky pr., 198013 Saint Petersburg, Russia;

³ Laboratory of Immunopharmacology, State Research Institute of Highly Pure Biopreparations, 7 Pudozhskaya str., 197110 Saint Petersburg, Russia

⁴ Department of Pathological Physiology, Acad.I.P.Pavlov St.Petersburg State Medicinal University, 6/8 L.Tolstoy str.,197022 Saint Petersburg, Russia;

⁵ Laboratory of Immunopharmacology, State Research Institute of Highly Pure Biopreparations, 7 Pudozhskaya str., 197110 Saint Petersburg, Russia

immunomodulating and anti-tumor activities, were stored at the temperature of 18 – 20 °C.

Immunological reagents

For immunological studies, Hanks salt solution, acetate, agarose EEO, formyl-peptide fMLP 1640, cow fetal serum, prodigiosan, concanavalin A, luminol, phorbolmyristate (all “Sigma”) and donor fresh blood were used.

Blood cells isolation

The standard technique described by Boyum (1968) was used to isolate mononuclear and granulocyte cells from the donor blood, stabilized with heparin solution (20 IU per 1 ml of blood) in ficoll-paque gradient. Blood plasma was layered on to ficoll-paque gradient and centrifuged during 40 min on 400 g. The mononuclear cells were collected from the interphase between plasma and ficoll-paque. The neutrophilic granulocytes were gathered from the precipitate after isolation of mononuclear cells by a hypotonic shock with distilled water during 30 sec.

Study of the cytokin-inducing activity of the preparations

Mononuclear cell suspension (concentration 5 10⁶ ml⁻¹) resuspended in RPMI 1640 medium and included 10% fetal serum was placed in the 96-well flat-bottomed microplates (“Costar”) by 0.1 ml in each hole. Simultaneously, the investigating preparations in appropriate solutions were added in the same holes. The preparation of lipopolysaccharide nature prodigiosan, a strong inductor of antiinflammatory cytokines, was used as the positive control. The microplates were placed in CO₂-incubator during 24 h, after that the amount of cytokines in the cultural medium was detected by immunoenzymatic method (Dike, Forlin, 1998). Test-systems produced by “Cytokine” (Saint Petersburg, Russia) were used.

Study of the influence of mushroom extracts on the production of oxygen active forms by phagocytting cells

The formation of oxygen active forms by whole blood cells was detected with luminoldependent chemiluminescence method (LDCL) (Tono-Oro et al., 1990). The determination of LDCL was carried out in the 96-well white nontransparent microplates “Costar” with the device Victor-2 (Finland), connected with PC and provided sequent registration of chemiluminescence. The reaction result was termed as light sum (sum of impulse accumulated during the certain time period).

The base luminol solution (10⁻² M) was prepared in DMSO and stored at 4°C. The working solution (10⁻⁴ M) was prepared fresh by diluting the base solution with Hank’s solution (pH 7.2).

The experiments were carried out according to the following scheme: 120 µl of the Hank’s solution, 20 µl of the fresh donor blood, 40 µl of the working luminol solution and 20 µl of the investigating preparation in the appropriate dilutions were placed in the each well of the 96-well microplates. Each test was prosecuted in the three parallels. The solution of phorbol-miristate acetate (PMA) in the end concentration 10 ng ml⁻¹ was used as the standard positive control. The reaction was fixed during 1 h.

The preparations influence on the cell proliferation

The proliferative processes in the cells were studied with the reaction of blast-transformation of spleen cells of CBA strain mice (farm Rappolovo, Saint Petersburg, Russia). The mice were slaughtered by method of cervical dislocation, the spleen was extracted, grinded up with the scissors, washed out by syringing the cultural medium RPMI 1640, and then washed clean by twice centrifuging. The cell suspension (concentration 2 10⁶ ml⁻¹) in the RPMI 1640 medium containing 10% fetal serum was prepared. The cell suspension was placed by 0.1 ml in the 96-well microplates “Costar” together with the investigating preparations. Concanavaline A (Con A) in the concentration 0.1 and 0.2 mg ml⁻¹ was used as the standard inductor of proliferation. The microplates were placed in the CO₂-incubator (CO₂ 5%, 37°C) during 4 days. After 3 days the labeled tritium 3H thymidine was added in the cultural medium. Result of reaction was estimated in impulses per min with using beta-meter.

3. Results and discussion

Immunomodulating and anti-tumor activity

The main antitumour compounds presently isolated from mushroom fruit-bodies, submerged cultural mycelial biomass or liquid culture broth have been identified as either water soluble β-D-glucans with heterosaccharide chains of xylose, mannose, galactose or uronic acid or β-D-glucan-protein complexes – proteoglycans.

We conducted an experimental study on immunomodulating and anti-tumor activities of fruit bodies and submerged mycelia of several mushrooms: *Armillaria mellea* (Vahl: Fr.) P. Kumm., *Auricularia auricula-judae* (Bull. ex St.

Amans) Wettst., Bjerkandera adusta (Willd.: Fr.) P. Karst., Cerrena unicolor (Bulliard) Murrill, Coprinus lagopides P. Karst., Flammulina velutipes (Curt.: Fr.) Singer, Fomes fomentarius (L.: Fr.) Fr., Fomitopsis pinicola (Sw.: Fr.) P. Karst., Ganoderma lipsiense (Batsch) G.F. Atk. (= G. applanatum (Wallr.) Pat.), Hypsizygos ulmarius (Bull.:Fr.) Redhead, Panus conchatus (Bull.) Fr., Piptoporus betulinus (Bull.: Fr.) P. Karst., Pleurotus cornucopiae (Pau. ex Pers.) Rollan (= P. citrinopileatus Singer), P. ostreatus (Jacq.: Fr.) P. Kumm., Trametes ochracea (Pers.) Gilb. & Ryvardeen, Trametes suaveolens (Fr.) Fr., Inonotus obliquus (Pers.: Fr.) Pili & Inonotus radiatus (Sowerby: Fr.) P. Karst., Tremella foliacea Pers.: Fr., Tricholoma portentosum (Fr.) Quil., Grifola frondosa (Dicks.: Fr.) Gray, Lentinus edodes (Berk.) Singer.

The content of total saccharides in mushroom aqueous extracts was analyzed and was estimated to be in a range of 62 – 80 % of dry matter, for all

of the specimens. The protein content in the extracts was of up to 30 %.

Primary evaluation of biological activity of studied mushroom aqueous extracts was done by test-analysis of the reactive oxygen species generated by cells of a peripheral human blood by a method of luminol depended chemiluminescence. The test was selected on the basis of the supposition about stimulating effect of extracts on the system of phagocytes, since it is known, that the compounds of polysaccharide nature boost the phagocytosis. When activating the phagocytes of the blood the cascade of chain reactions is started accompanied with the increased oxygen consumption from the environment. Thus the cells pass on hexosomonophosphate path of respiration. The final products of the reaction contained the reactive oxygen species, which being combined with luminol caused a luminescence registered at a wave-length 425 nm.

Figure 1
The effect of extracts from mushrooms fruit bodies and mycelia on generation of reactive oxygen species by human blood neutrophils

The extracts from fruit bodies and / or mycelia of all mentioned species were studied in concentrations 0.001-1.0 mg ml⁻¹. Many of the experienced samples of mushrooms increased production of reactive oxygen species by neutrophils of a peripheral human blood. The maximal effect of all experienced extracts observed in a dose at 0.1 - 1.0 mg/ml. On the Fig. 1. data obtained for a doze of 1.0 mg/ml are presented. The effect of fruit bodies extracts was

slightly higher, then the effect observed for mycelia extracts of same species. In both cases the maximal effects were observed for extracts of mushrooms of *P. ostreatus* and *P. cornucopiae*. The mitogenic activity of fruit bodies extracts for mushrooms which possessed higher activity in generation of the reactive oxygen was studied (table 1). The research was carried out in blast-transformation reaction (BTR) on spleen cells of CBA mice.

Table 1

Influence of mushroom extracts on blast-transformation reaction of leucocytes from CBA mice spleen

Extracts from fruit bodies of mushroom species	Preparation concentration, mg ml ⁻¹						
	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.0625	0.03125	0.0156	0.0078
	Level of blust-transformation reaction, % of control						
<i>Bjerkandera adusta</i>	920	970	900	660	580	510	460
<i>Cerraena unicolor</i>	340	370	330	310	220	170	150
<i>Inonotus radiatus</i>	270	280	290	230	160	130	110
<i>Ganoderma lipsiense</i>	190	180	210	140	120	110	80
<i>Tricholoma portentosum</i>	340	360	320	270	190	140	130
<i>Trametes ochracea</i>	250	280	270	220	170	120	100
<i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	640	650	640	600	540	550	380
<i>Pleurotus cornucopiae</i>	150	460	540	550	590	480	360

Level of spontaneous BTR (control) - 8.3 thousands imp min⁻¹

Index of stimulation of BTR as response on ConA (0.1 mg ml⁻¹) – 390% of control

From the data of table 1 it is clear that the extracts of all tested mushrooms have marked mitogenic activity in a wide range of concentrations. In this tests the maximal activity levels were detected for the extracts of *B. adusta*. Both species of *Pleurotus* mushrooms were also active in a wide range of concentrations.

It was studied the ability of extracts from fruit bodies of several mushrooms to participate in synthesis by human blood cells of immunoregulating proteins – cytokines, particularly of interleukine-1 β and interleukine- 8, being a key mediator of inflammatory and immune response of an organism. The ability of a mushroom extracts to influence lipopolysaccharide induced

cytokine production was studied. The data obtained are shown in table 2.

It can be seen from the table 2 that preparations display a co-stimulating effect

on both cytokines production by peripheral blood cells. Most effective were preparations from *I. radiatus* and *T. Portentosum*

Table 2

Influence of an extracts of mushroom fruit bodies on production of inflammatory cytokines by human blood cells

Preparation concentration, mg ml ⁻¹	Exreacts from fruit bodies											
	B.adusta		I. radiatus		P. cornucopiae		P. ostreatus		C. unicolor		T. portentosum	
	Level of cytokine production, % of control											
	IL 1-β	IL-8	IL 1-β	IL-8	IL 1-β	IL-8	IL 1-β	IL-8	IL 1-β	IL-8	IL 1-β	IL-8
5.0	320	310	370	>500	210	220	330	150	230	290	280	360
0.5	210	180	270	>500	280	310	280	140	280	320	330	>500
0.05	140	130	140	420	230	180	190	130	190	210	260	170
0.005	106	103	120	190	150	110	150	110	130	150	190	104
0.0005	100	100	106	130	130	100	120	100	110	120	130	100

Level of spontaneous production of IL 1-β: 670 ng ml⁻¹, IL-8: 2169 ng ml⁻¹
 Level of production induced by LPS of

IL 1-β: 250 % of control, IL-8: 310 % of control

The studies of the influence of uptake of aqueous extracts of mycelia of *B. adusta*, *P. ostreatus* and *P. cornucopiae* demonstrate

the doze-depending increase of the levels of antibody forming cells in the experimental groups of mice (Fig. 2.)

Figure 2.

The influence of p .. administration of mycelia extracts on the levels of antibody forming cells in mice.

The outcomes obtained in the experiments in vitro have predetermined check of these extracts on antitumor effect in

experiment in vivo. As a model of tumor growth melanoma B16 and Ehrlich's ascit carcinoma were selected.

The experiments have been done in 16 C57BL female mice (average body weight 23 g) purchased from animal facility “Rappolovo”, Russian Academy of Science. Animals were kept 8 per one standard polypropylene chamber. The light regimen was standardized to 12 hours light/dark cycle. All animals received water ad libitum. Animal were divided into two groups – control and experimental. The control group was given usual fodder. The second group animals were given modified fodder with extract (daily dosage 10 mg kg⁻¹ body weight in recalculation on a dry extract).

During two week periods from a beginning of extract administration the average body weight did not differ significantly as compared to control.

At 15 day melanoma B16 was transplanted to all animals (10⁶ cells of a melanoma B16 subcutaneously to the right

abdomen side). In further measurement of parameters of tumor growth and life duration was conducted.

The progressive and irregular decrease of average body weight was noted in both groups after tumor transplantation but less in group received extract. At 26 day after tumor transplantation average body weight was significantly higher in experimental group. This is the evidence of decrease the body intoxication by mushroom supplements, and thus the increase of the quality of life.

The average tumor size changes are represented in table 3. In control group average tumor size increased during tumor development. In experimental group average tumor size decrease 30-80 % was marked with maximal effect during first 14 days.

Table 3.
The effect of *Pleurotus ostreatus* extract peroral intake on tumour development in mices bearing melanoma B16

Time after tumour transplantation, days	Tumour volume, sm ³		Suppression, %
	Experimental group	Control group	
8	0.02 ± 0.02	0.03 ± 0.01	30
12	0.14 ± 0.09	0.43 ± 0.18	70
15	0.55 ± 0.33	2.19 ± 0.45	75
22	1.52 ± 0.52	4.34 ± 1.24	65
26	1.84 ± 1.30	9.37 ± 2.64	80
29	0.28 ± 0.17	-	-
33	0.11 ± 0.02	-	-
36	0.34 ± 0.01	-	-
40	0.67 ± 0.02	-	-
43	1.22	-	-

Figure 3.
Survival of mice with melanoma B16

The survival rate of mice with a melanoma B16 feed with aqueous extract from pleurotus ostreatus is represented in a fig.3.

Thus, the extract from *Pleurotus ostreatus* fruit bodies makes reliable inhibiting effect on melanoma B-16 growth and decreases a manifestation of tumor intoxication as it confirms by the weight differences between control and experience mice. These effects perhaps are connected

with the stimulation of immune system which has a large importance for a pathogenesis of the tumor growth.

Experiments on mice with Ehrlich's ascit carcinoma shows the oncostatic effect of supplements from another mushroom mycelia – *Cerrena unicolor* (fig.4), while several other species, including *Pleurotus ostreatus* were not efficient in this case.

Figure 4.
Survival of mice with Ehrlich's carcinoma

Data obtained during our investigations suggest that aqueous extracts of studied Basidiomycetes, mainly of polysaccharide

origin, have marked biological effects. The highest activity was determined for the extracts from *Bjerkandera adusta*, *Pleurotus*

cornucopiae, *Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Auricularia auricula-judae*, *Inonotus radiatus*, *Tricholoma portentosum*, *Grifola frondosa* and *Lentinus edodes*. The levels of stimulation of different immunocompetent cells, significantly varies for the extracts of different mushroom species. Probably, this can explain also the different effect towards different tumors, possessing by extracts from various mushroom species.

References

1. Beiyer, V. A. (1973). Short manual of haematology. Chimiya, Leningrad, 118p. (in Russian).
2. Boyum, A. (1968). Isolation of mononuclear cells and granulocytes from human blood. Isolation of mononuclear cells by centrifugation. Scand. J. Clin. Labor. Invest., 41, 77-89.
3. Chang, S.T. (1999). Global impact of edible and medicinal mushrooms on human welfare in the 21st century: nongreen revolution. Int. J. Med. Mushrooms, 1, 1-7.
4. Chihara, G. (1992). Immunopharmacology of lentinan, a polysaccharide isolated from *Lentinus edodes*: its application as a host defense potentiator. International Journal of Oriental Medicine, 17, 57-77.
5. Collins, R.A. and Ng, T.B. (1987). Polysaccharopeptide from *Coriolus versicolor* has potential for use against human immunodeficiency virus type 1 infections. Life Science 60, 383-387.
6. Dike, M.M. and Forlin, J.K. (Eds.) Manual of immunopharmacology. Mir, Moscow, 1998. 332 pp. (in Russian)
7. Espenshade, M.A. and Griffith, E.W. (1966). Tumor –inhibiting basidiomycetes. Isolation and cultivation in the laboratory. Mycologia, 58, 511-517.
8. Gregory, F.J., Healy, E.M., Agersborg, H.P.K. Jr., and Warren, G.H. (1966). Studies of antitumor substances produced by basidiomycetes. Mycologia, 58, 80-90.
9. Hishida, I., Nanba, H. and Kuroda, H. (1988). Antitumor activity exhibited by orally administered extracts from fruit-body of *Grifola frondosa* (maitake). Chemical and Pharmaceutical Bulletin 36(5), 1819-1827.
10. Ikekawa, T., (1995). Enokitake, *Flammulina velutipes*: antitumor activity of extracts and polysaccharides. Food Review International 11, 203-206.
11. Ikekawa, T., Uehara, N., Maeda, Y., Nakanishi, M., and Fukuoka F. (1969). Antitumor activity of aqueous extracts of edible mushrooms. Cancer Res, 29, 734-735 .
12. Jong, S.C. and Birmingham, J.M. (1992). Medicinal benefits of the mushroom *Ganoderma*. Advances in Applied Microbiology. 37, 101-134.
13. Kanatsu, N., Terakawa, H., Nakanishi, K., Watanabe, Y. (1963). Flammulin, a basic protein of *Flammulina velutipes* with antitumor activities. J. of Antibiotics. Ser. A., 16, 139-143.
14. Liu, G-T. (1999). Recent advances in research of pharmacology and clinical applications of *Ganoderma* (P. Korst.) species (Aphyllophoromycetidae) in china. International Journal of Medicinal Mushrooms 1, 63-67.
15. Mizuno, T. (Ed.). (1995). Mushrooms: the versatile fungus-food and medicinal properties. Food Rev. Int. (special issue), II, 173-178.
16. Mizuno, T. (1999). Medicinal effects and utilisation of *Cordiceps Fr. Link* (Ascomycetes) and *Isaria Fd.* (Mitosporic Fungi) Chinese caterpillar fungi ‘Tuchukaso. Int. J. Med. Mushr, 1, 251-261.
17. Mizuno, T. (1999). The extraction and development of antitumor-active polysaccharides from medicinal mushrooms in Japan, Int. J. Med Mushr, 1, 9.
18. Mizuno, T. (2000). Development of an antitumor biological response modifier from *Phellinus linteus* (Berk. Et Curt.) Teng (Aphyllophoromycetidae) (Review). International Journal of Medicinal Mushrooms 2, 21-33.
19. Nelson, K. D. Chemotaxis under agarose. J. Immunol, 115, 1650– 1656 (1975).
20. Tono-Oro, T., Ueno, N., Matsumoto, T. (1990). Chemiluminescence of Whole Blood, a simple and rapid method for the testimation of phagocytic function of the granulocytes and opsonic activity in whole Blood. Clin. Immun. Immunopath., 26, 66-75.
21. Wang G., Zhang J., Mizuno T., Zhuang C., Ito H., Mayuzumi H., Okamoto H., Li J., (1993). Antitumor active polysaccharides from Chinese mushroom *Songhan lingzhi*, the fruiting body of *Ganoderma tsugae*. Biocsi. Biotech. Biochem. 57, 894-900.
22. Wasser S.P., Weis A. (1999). Medicinal properties of substrates occurring in higher Basidiomycetes mushrooms: current perspectives. Int. J. Med. Mushrooms, 1, 31-62.
23. Wasser S.P., 2002. Medicinal mushrooms as a source of antitumor and immunomodulating polysaccharides. Appl Microbiol Biotechnol, Vol. 60, 3, 258- 274.

ANTIOXIDANT CAPACITY OF FROZEN STRAWBERRIES AS AFFECTED BY THE VACUUM IMPREGNATION IN POLYPHENOL-RICH EXTRACT

V. SHIKOV*, K. MIHALEV*, N. YONCHEVA**, V. KARAGYOZOV*, P. MOLLOV*

Abstract: Total polyphenols, total anthocyanins and DPPH radical-scavenging ability of three strawberry cultivars (*Fragaria x ananassa* Duch. cv. 'Stabella', 'Senga Sengana' and 'Belrubi') were studied depending on the vacuum impregnation in rose (*Rosa damascena* Mill.) petal extract. Total polyphenolic content and radical-scavenging ability values increased, 15-26% and 11-32%, respectively, due to the pre-freezing treatment. Total anthocyanin content decreased during the 6 months of storage at -18°C , but 5-13% higher pigment retention was observed for the strawberries fortified with rose petal polyphenols. Correspondingly, colour stability, as assessed by the CIELCh measurements, increased since the total colour difference values were smaller upon frozen storage of polyphenol-fortified strawberries. Radical-scavenging ability correlated well both with the bioactive compounds ($R = 0.78-0.86$) and total colour difference ($R = 0.89$). The results obtained demonstrate that the incorporation of rose petal polyphenols enhances the antioxidant capacity of frozen strawberries, especially after long-term storage, thus allowing development of new functional foodstuffs. Moreover, this fortification could be worthwhile from technological point of view, improving colour stability without affecting the flavour quality of processed strawberries.

Keywords: functional foods, plant by-products, DPPH, colour stability, *Fragaria x ananassa*.

1. Introduction

The epidemiological studies have shown an inverse correlation of increased fruit and vegetable consumption with a reduced risk of chronic diseases including cardiovascular diseases (Hu 2003; Ness and Powles 1997). Plant-derived foods contain a broad spectrum of secondary plant metabolites such as polyphenols that inhibit human low density lipoprotein oxidation and thus could account for the beneficial effects on human health (Frei 1995; Liu 2003).

By-products of fruit and vegetable processing represent a major disposal problem for the industry concerned, but they are also promising sources of polyphenols (Kammerer *et al.* 2005a; Llorach *et al.* 2003; Schieber *et al.* 2001; Xu *et al.* 2007) and various processes for their recovery have been developed (Berardini *et al.* 2005; Kammerer *et al.* 2005b; Schieber *et al.* 2003).

Moreover, strategies for exploitation of polyphenol-rich extracts as functional (Llorach *et al.* 2002; Llorach *et al.* 2005) or technological (Ivanov *et al.* 2009) food ingredients have been proposed.

Rose essential oil, also known as rose otto, is a highly prized product used in perfumery, cosmetics and pharmacy (Kaul *et al.* 2000; Kovats 1987). Bulgaria and Turkey are the main rose petal processing countries in the world which extract the rose oil by water-steam distillation of *Rosa damascena* Mill. Since more than 3000 kg of petals yield 1 kg of rose oil, several thousand tons of waste materials annually result from the distilleries in Bulgaria alone. Recently, industrially distilled (de-aromatised) rose petals were established as a rich source of polyphenols, particularly flavonols (Schieber *et al.* 2005), which have been demonstrated as potent both *in vitro* (Soobrattee *et al.* 2005; Wang *et al.* 2006) and *in vivo* (Kim *et al.* 2003)

* Dept. of Food Preservation and Refrigeration Technology, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria. Email: vshikov@yahoo.com (V. Shikov)

** Dept. of Analytical Chemistry, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

antioxidants. *Rosa damascena* flowers are also known as edible plants and are used for manufacturing of rose petal jam (Velioglu and Mazza 1991). Different rose flower cultivars have been evaluated as caffeine-free sources for preparing rose petal tea, with *Rosa damascena* being among the cultivars exhibited the highest antioxidant activity (Vinokur *et al.* 2006). In addition to the antioxidant properties, extracts from rose petals have been reported for their antibacterial activity (Özkan *et al.* 2004).

The large industrial scale of strawberry freezing can be attributed to the short shelf-life of the fresh fruit on one side and significance of frozen strawberries as a raw material in jam/juice manufacturing on the other side (Oszmiański *et al.* 2009). Recently, vacuum impregnation pretreatment has been used to incorporate micronutrients such as zinc and calcium into frozen strawberries (Xie and Zhao 2004).

Therefore, the present study aimed to assess the potential of rose petal by-product for polyphenols fortification of frozen strawberries using vacuum impregnation. In addition to the antioxidant capacity, pigment stability and colour changes were monitored during 6 months of storage at $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Reagents used for analytical purposes were as follows: DPPH [2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl] and Trolox [(±)-6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchromane-2-carboxylic acid] (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany); Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany); gallic acid monohydrate (Fluka, Buchs, Switzerland). Reagents used to prepare the McIlvaine buffer system, citric acid monohydrate and disodium hydrogen phosphate dodecahydrate, were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). All other reagents and solvents used were of analytical grade.

2.2. Plant materials and processing

Waste material, originating from water-steam distillation of rose (*Rosa damascena* Mill.) petals, was supplied by Nara-Geo Distillery (Plovdiv, Bulgaria). After pressing, the wet pomace obtained was hot air-dried ($60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 6 h). Rose petal polyphenols were extracted with 30% aqueous ethanol using finely milled (particle size $<0.4\text{ mm}$) dried pomace at solvent-to-solid ratio of 20:1 (v/w). After stirring for 1 h at ambient

temperature, the extraction mixture was filtered and the organic solvent was evaporated under vacuum ($40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). The total solids content of the rose petal extract was determined gravimetrically by heating 10-mL aliquots to dryness ($105\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 3 h). The impregnation solution was prepared diluting the extract with distilled water to get total solids content of 4 g/L.

Strawberries (*Fragaria x ananassa* Duch., cultivars 'Siabella', 'Senga Sengana' and 'Belrubi', harvest 2006) at a commercial maturity stage were obtained from local producer and processed within 4-6 h after harvest. Fruits were washed, sorted on the basis of size and colour and 1-kg batches were treated under vacuum (10 kPa, 15 min) in the impregnation solution (distilled water as a control) at solvent-to-solid ratio of 1:1 (v/w). After releasing the vacuum, strawberries were drained for 10 min, frozen in an air-blast freezer at $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, packed into polyethylene bags (250 g portions), and stored at $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Samples were analysed after 0 and 6 months of frozen storage.

2.3. Sample preparation

Frozen strawberries (~100 g) were thawed for 90 min at room temperature before they were crushed into purée using a hand-held blender (MR 300 Minipimer compact, Braun, Kronberg, Germany). Aliquot (20 g) of the homogenized fruits was mixed in 100 mL of acidified methanol (0.01 M HCl) and extracted overnight at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The mixture was filtered through a paper filter (390, Filtrak, Niederschlag, Germany) on a Büchner funnel and the extract obtained was used for chemical analyses.

Aliquot (20 g) of the strawberry purée was diluted with 80 mL of McIlvaine buffer (0.1 M, pH 3.4) prepared according to Elving *et al.* (1956). The mixture was homogenized in a laboratory blender (MPW-309, Mechanika precyzyjna, Warsaw, Poland) at maximum speed for 5 min. After centrifugation ($20000\times g$, 15 min), the supernatant was filtered through a membrane filter ($0.6\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, Sartorius Membranfilter, Göttingen, Germany) and used for colour analysis.

All extractions were performed in duplicate.

2.4. Chemical analyses

Total polyphenols were assessed according to the Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent procedure (Singleton and Rossi 1965). Briefly, appropriately diluted extract (0.2 mL) was mixed with 0.5 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (diluted

with distilled water 1:10, v/v) and 0.8 mL of sodium carbonate solution (7.5%, w/v). The mixture was incubated for 30 min at room temperature before absorption was measured at 765 nm. Total polyphenolic content was expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE) in milligrams per 100 g of fruits on a fresh weight (FW) basis.

Total anthocyanin content was determined by the pH-differential method (Giusti and Wrolstad 2001). The extract was diluted both in buffer pH 1.0 (0.025 potassium chloride) and buffer pH 4.5 (0.4 M sodium acetate). After 15 min of incubation at room temperature, absorption was measured at 496 and 700 nm. Results were calculated using molar absorptivity of 27300 L/(mol cm) and molecular weight of 433.2 g/mol (Aaby *et al.* 2005) and expressed as pelargonidin 3-glucoside equivalents (PGE) in milligrams per 100 g fresh weight.

Antioxidant capacity was evaluated using the DPPH free radical method (Brand-Williams *et al.* 1995) modified as follows: 1.5 mL of DPPH methanolic solution (6×10^{-5} M) was mixed with 0.2 mL of extract (diluted with distilled water 1:3, v/v); absorption at 515 nm was measured after 20 min of reaction in a cap-sealed cuvette kept at room temperature. Results were expressed as Trolox, a water-soluble vitamin E analogue, equivalents (TE) in milligrams per 100 g fresh weight.

2.5. Spectrophotometric measurements and colour analysis

All measurements were performed with a PU 8800 UV/Vis spectrophotometer, equipped with a UV/Vis and a colour (Issue 2) software (all from

Pye Unicam, Cambridge, UK), using 1 cm path length glass cuvettes. Before colour analysis, the samples were diluted with McIlvaine buffer (pH 3.4) to reach maximum absorbance values of 0.400 ± 0.005 . After 30 min of equilibration at room temperature, visible spectra from 380 to 770 nm, with a 10 nm bandwidth, were recorded. CIELCh colour coordinates were determined using illuminant D₆₅ and 10° observer angle. Total colour difference values of the frozen stored strawberries, with the colour coordinates after freezing as a reference, were calculated as proposed by Gonnet (1998).

3. Statistical analysis

The results reported in the present study are the mean values of at least three determinations and the coefficients of variation, expressed as the percentage ratio between the standard deviations and the mean values, were found to be <3% in all cases. Linear regression analysis was performed using the statistical package from Microsoft Excel™.

4. Results and discussion

Although contents of total polyphenols and total monomeric anthocyanins (TMA) vary with factors such as cultivar, maturity degree, growing practices, storage conditions and analytical procedures, the values obtained in the present study (Table 1) were in the same ranges as previously reported for frozen strawberries (Ngo *et al.* 2007; Oszmiański *et al.* 2009).

Table 1. Total polyphenolic and anthocyanin contents and radical-scavenging ability values of frozen stored (−18 °C) strawberries depending on the impregnation in rose petal extract (RPE).

Strawberry cultivar	'Siabella'		'Senga Sengana'		'Belrubi'	
Storage time (months)	Control	RPE	Control	RPE	Control	RPE
Total polyphenols (mg GAE/100 g fw) ^a						
0	190.4	239.3	246.5	309.8	255.4	294.8
6	169.6	214.9	179.1	199.8	180.1	215.3
Total monomeric anthocyanins (mg PGE/100 g fw) ^a						
0	57.8	59.3	63.2	65.0	49.6	52.3
6	40.4	49.2	33.4	41.5	6.8	9.5
Radical-scavenging ability (mg TE/100 g fw) ^a						
0	267.9	353.0	370.7	412.4	321.0	413.2
6	219.4	325.1	290.0	342.6	165.6	276.5

^a All values are calculated to a standard (AIJN Code of Practice) total soluble solids content of 6.3 °Brix.

Anthocyanin content decreased significantly upon storage at $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, 4.5-13.1% higher pigment retention ($\text{TMA}_6 \times 100/\text{TMA}_0$) was observed for the strawberries impregnated in polyphenol-rich extract from rose petals. Recently, anthocyanin-stabilising effect of rose petal polyphenols acting as copigments was demonstrated during heating in model systems (Shikov et al. 2008). In the case of frozen stored strawberries, pigment degradation could be attributed to the oxidative enzymes such as polyphenol oxidase (PPO), which activity is triggered during thawing, especially in the conventional slow process, as a result of the freezing-induced plant cell decompartmentation. In fact, the oxidation by PPO of phenolic compounds leads to the formation of o-quinones, which might contribute to the anthocyanin degradation by coupled oxidation mechanism (Nunes et al. 2005). Cultivar dependence of the stabilising effect observed is possibly due to the differences in PPO activity levels and/or composition of endogenous polyphenols. On the other side, polyphenolic profile of the rose petal extract is dominated by flavonols, particularly kaempferol and quercetin glycosides (Schieber et al. 2005), which are not direct substrates for strawberry PPO (Wesche-Ebeling and Montgomery 1990). Moreover, enzyme inhibitory activity of some flavonol glycosides naturally occurring in rose petals could also be considered (Chang 2009).

Total polyphenolic content and radical-scavenging ability (RSA) values increased, 15.4-25.7% and 11.2-31.8%, respectively, due to the pre-freezing impregnation in rose petal extract. As reported for the anthocyanin content, total polyphenols and RSA decreased upon frozen storage. While relative losses in polyphenolic content were similar, 1.3-2.3 times lower changes in RSA values were observed for the polyphenol-fortified strawberries as compared to the corresponding control samples, thus resulting in 4.9-15.3% higher RSA retention ($\text{RSA}_6 \times 100/\text{RSA}_0$). These facts imply that the exogenous polyphenols contribute strongly to the antioxidant capacity of strawberries impregnated in rose petal extract, especially after their long-term frozen storage. The latter assumption is supported by the increase in correlation coefficient between RSA and total polyphenols observed due to the impregnation in rose petal extract (Table 2). In accordance with González *et al.* (2003), antioxidant capacity of frozen stored

strawberries, both non-fortified and polyphenol-fortified, correlated well ($R = 0.78\text{-}0.86$) with the contents of bioactive compounds.

Table 2
Correlation between radical-scavenging ability and various bioactive compounds of frozen stored ($-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) strawberries depending on the impregnation in rose petal extract (RPE).

Bioactive compounds	Correlation coefficient (N \geq 36)	
	Control	RPE
Total polyphenols	0.78	0.86
Total anthocyanins	0.82	0.82

Currently, with regard to growing consumer demand for functional foods, the main technological challenge is to optimize fruit processing with respect to increased bioactive compounds content, while maintaining a high sensory quality. Whereas the application of a new firming process, which has recently been developed (Carle *et al.* 2001), significantly improves strawberry texture, colour retention, particularly after frozen storage, still remains a technological problem.

Colour changes of frozen stored strawberries were monitored depending on the pre-freezing impregnation in rose petal extract (Table 3). Since frozen strawberries are most commonly used in processed/comminuted form e.g. in the jam manufacturing, extractable colour properties were determined in the present study. The extracts were adjusted to identical tinctorial strengths, which allows direct comparison of lightness (L^*), chroma (C^*) and hue angle (h°) values (Stintzing *et al.* 2002). Fortification with rose petal polyphenols induced a slight decrease in L^* and an increase in C^* values at the beginning of the frozen storage (month 0), confirming the effects of copigmentation as assessed by the colorimetric approach (Gonnet 1999). In general, decreasing pigment concentrations during frozen storage were associated with increasing h° values, reflecting a more yellowish colour tonality. However, the relative changes were much smaller than the corresponding decrease in anthocyanin concentrations, which implies that the effects induced by exogenous and/or endogenous copigments could mask the pigment degradation that took place during thawing after long-term frozen storage.

Table 3.

CIELCh colour coordinates and total colour difference values of frozen stored (-18 °C) strawberries depending on the impregnation in rose petal extract (RPE).

Strawberry cultivar	'Siabella'		'Senga Sengana'		'Belrubi'	
Storage time (months)	Control	RPE	Control	RPE	Control	RPE
Lightness (L^*)						
0	90.0	89.8	89.9	89.3	90.8	89.7
6	88.4	89.0	89.1	89.2	89.0	88.7
Chroma (C^*)						
0	24.9	25.2	24.7	25.5	25.0	25.1
6	26.0	25.9	25.9	25.9	26.3	26.6
Hue angle (h°)						
0	36.2	35.4	36.5	36.4	37.5	37.0
6	36.4	35.6	37.1	36.7	37.5	37.7
Total colour difference (ΔE^*)						
	1.9	1.1	1.6	0.5	2.3	1.9

Interestingly, significant correlation ($R = 0.89$) was obtained between ΔE^* and RSA values (Fig. 1). Thus, besides assessing the total antioxidant capacity, DPPH method may be used to predict the shelf-life of frozen strawberries.

Fig. 1. Correlation between radical-scavenging ability (month 6) and total colour difference of all (control and impregnated in rose petal extract) frozen stored (-18 °C) strawberries.

Sensory evaluation (data not shown) confirmed better colour retention for the jam (35% fruit content, 63 °Brix) prepared from polyphenol-fortified strawberries (cv. 'Siabella') after their frozen storage for 6 months, while the overall quality perception was not negatively affected by the pre-freezing impregnation in rose petal extract.

5. Conclusions

The results obtained demonstrate the utilisation of rose petal by-product rich in polyphenols to enhance the antioxidant capacity of frozen strawberries and thus for developing new functional foodstuffs (Diplock *et al.* 1998). Moreover, this fortification could be worthwhile from technological point of view, allowing improved colour stability without affecting the flavour quality of processed strawberries. However, before incorporation of rose petal polyphenols into functional food matrices, further studies, particularly concerning their *in vivo* antioxidant activity and bioavailability, should be carried out.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Nara Geo Ltd., Plovdiv, Bulgaria, for providing distilled rose petals.

References

1. Aaby K., Skrede G., Wrolstad R.E. 2005, *Phenolic composition and antioxidant activities in flesh and achenes of strawberries (Fragaria ananassa)*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 53, 4032-4040.
2. Berardini N., Knödler M., Schieber A., Carle R. 2005, *Utilization of mango peels as a source of pectin and polyphenolics*. Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies 6, 442-452.
3. Brand-Williams W., Cuvelier M.E., Berset C. 1995, *Use of free radical method to evaluate*

- antioxidant activity*. LWT - Food Science and Technology 28, 25-30.
4. Carle R., Borzych P., Dubb P., Siliha H., Maier O. 2001, *A new process for firmer canned cherries and strawberries*. Food Australia 53, 343-348.
 5. Chang T-S. 2009, *An updated review of tyrosinase inhibitors*. International Journal of Molecular Sciences 10, 2440-2475.
 6. Diplock A.T., Charleux J-L., Crozier-Willi G., Kok F.J., Rice-Evans C., Roberfroid M., Stahl W., Viña-Ribes J. 1998, *Functional food science and defense against reactive oxidative species*. British Journal of Nutrition 80, S77-S112.
 7. Elving P.J., Markowitz J.M., Rosenthal I. 1956, *Preparation of buffer systems of constant ionic strength*. Analytical Chemistry 28, 1179-1180.
 8. Frei B. 1995, *Cardiovascular disease and nutrient antioxidants: role of low-density lipoprotein oxidation*. Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition 35, 83-98.
 9. Giusti M.M., Wrolstad R.E. 2001, *Characterization and measurement of anthocyanins by UV-visible spectroscopy*. In: Wrolstad R.E. (Ed) Current Protocols in Food Analytical Chemistry, John Wiley & Sons, New York, pp F1.2.1-F1.2.13.
 10. Gonnet J-F. 1999, *Colour effects of co-pigmentation of anthocyanins revised-2. A colorimetric look at the solutions of cyanin co-pigmented by rutin using the CIELAB scale*. Food Chemistry 66, 387-394.
 11. Gonnet J-F. 1998, *Colour effects of co-pigmentation of anthocyanins revised-1. A colorimetric definition using the CIELAB scale*. Food Chemistry 63, 409-415.
 12. González E.M., de Ancos B., Cano M.P. 2003, *Relation between bioactive compounds and free radical-scavenging capacity in berry fruits during frozen storage*. Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture 83, 722-726.
 13. Hu F.B. 2003, *Plant-based foods and prevention of cardiovascular disease: an overview*. American Journal of Clinical Nutrition 78(suppl.), 544S-551S.
 14. Ivanov G., Balev D., Nikolov H., Dragoev S. 2009, *Improvement of the chilled salmon sensory quality by pulverisation with natural dihydroquercetin solutions*. Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science 15, 154-162.
 15. Kammerer D., Schieber A., Carle R. 2005a, *Characterization and recovery of phenolic compounds from grape pomace – review*. Journal of Applied Botany and Food Quality 79, 189-196.
 16. Kammerer D., Claus A., Schieber A., Carle R. 2005b, *A novel process for the recovery of polyphenols from grape (Vitis vinifera L.) pomace*. Journal of Food Science 70, 157-163.
 17. Kaul V.K., Singh V., Singh B. 2000, *Damask rose and marigold: prospective industrial crops*. Journal of Medicinal and Aromatic Plant Sciences 22, 313-318.
 18. Kim H-Y., Kim O-H., Sung M-K. 2003, *Effects of phenol-depleted and phenol-rich diets on blood markers of oxidative stress, and urinary excretion of quercetin and kaempferol in healthy volunteers*. Journal of the American College of Nutrition 22, 217-223.
 19. Kovats E. 1987, *Composition of essential oils. Part 7. Bulgarian oil of rose (Rosa damascena Mill.)*. Journal of Chromatography 406, 185-222.
 20. Larrosa M., Llorach R., Espín J.C., Tomás-Barberán F.A. 2002, *Increase of antioxidant activity of tomato juice upon functionalisation with vegetable byproduct extracts*. LWT - Food Science and Technology 35, 532-542.
 21. Liu R.H. 2003, *Health benefits of fruit and vegetables are from additive and synergistic combinations of phytochemicals*. American Journal of Clinical Nutrition 78(suppl.), 517S-520S.
 22. Llorach R., Tomás-Barberán F.A., Ferreres F. 2005, *Functionalisation of commercial chicken soup with enriched polyphenol extract from vegetable by-products*. European Food Research and Technology 220, 31-36.
 23. Llorach R., Espín J.C., Tomás-Barberán F.A., Ferreres F. 2003, *Valorization of cauliflower (Brassica oleracea L. var. botrytis) by-products as a source of antioxidant phenolics*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 51, 2181-2187.
 24. Ness A.R., Powles J.W. 1997, *Fruit and vegetables, and cardiovascular disease: a review*. International Journal of Epidemiology 26, 1-13.
 25. Ngo T., Wrolstad R.E., Zhao Y. 2007, *Color quality of Oregon strawberries – impact of genotype, composition, and processing*. Journal of Food Science 72, C25-C32.
 26. Nunes M.C.N., Brecht J.K., Morais

- A.M.M.B., Sargent S.A. 2005, *Possible influences of water loss and polyphenol oxidase activity on anthocyanin content and discoloration in fresh ripe strawberry (cv. Oso Grande) during storage at 1 °C*. Journal of Food Science 70, S79-S84
27. Oszmiański J., Wojdyło A., Kolniak J. 2009, *Effect of L-ascorbic acid, sugar, pectin and freeze-thaw treatment on polyphenol content of frozen strawberries*. LWT - Food Science and Technology 42, 581-586.
28. Özkan G., Sağdıç O., Baydar N.G., Baydar H. 2004, *Antioxidant and antibacterial activities of Rosa damascena flower extracts*. Food Science and Technology International 10, 277-281.
29. Schieber A., Mihalev K., Berardini N., Mollov P., Carle R. 2005, *Flavonol glycosides from distilled petals of Rosa damascena Mill.* Zeitschrift für Naturforschung C 60, 379-384.
30. Schieber A., Hilt P., Streker P., Endress H-U., Rentschler C., Carle R. 2003, *A new process for the combined recovery of pectin and phenolic compounds from apple pomace*. Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies 4, 99-107.
31. Schieber A., Stintzing F.C., Carle R. 2001, *By-products of plant food processing as a source of functional components - recent developments*. Trends in Food Science and Technology 12, 401-413.
32. Shikov V., Kammerer D.R., Mihalev K., Mollov P., Carle R. 2008, *Heat stability of strawberry anthocyanins in model solutions containing natural copigments extracted from rose (Rosa damascena Mill.) petals*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 56, 8521-8526.
33. Singleton V.L., Rossi J.A. 1965, *Colorimetry of total phenolics with phosphomolybdic-phosphotungstic acid reagents*. American Journal of Enology and Viticulture 16, 144-158.
34. Soobrattee M.A., Neergheen V.S., Luximon-Ramma A., Aruoma O.I., Bahorun T. 2005, *Phenolics as potential antioxidant therapeutic agents: mechanisms and actions*. Mutation Research 579, 200-213.
35. Stintzing F.C., Stintzing A.S., Carle R., Frei B., Wrolstad R.E. 2002, *Color and antioxidant properties of cyaniding-based anthocyanin pigments*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 50, 6172-6181.
36. Velioglu Y.S., Mazza G. 1991, *Characterization of flavonoids in petals of Rosa damascena by HPLC and spectral analysis*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 39, 463-467.
37. Vinokur Y., Rodov V., Reznick N., Goldman G., Horev B., Umiel N., Friedman H. 2006, *Rose petal tea as an antioxidant-rich beverage: cultivar effects*. Journal of Food Science 71, S42-S47.
38. Wang L., Tu Y-C., Lian T-W., Hung J-T., Yen J-H., Wu M-J. 2006, *Distinctive antioxidant and antiinflammatory effects of flavonols*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 54, 9798-9804.
39. Wesche-Ebeling P., Montgomery M.W. 1990, *Strawberry polyphenoloxidase: extraction and partial characterization*. Journal of Food Science 55, 1320-1324.
40. Xie J., Zhao Y. 2004, *Use of vacuum impregnation to develop high quality and nutritionally fortified frozen strawberries*. Journal of Food Processing and Preservation 28, 117-132.
41. Xu G., Ye X., Chen J., Liu D. 2007, *Effect of heat treatment on the phenolic compounds and antioxidant capacity of citrus peel extract*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 55, 330-335.

INFLUENCE OF SEA KALE ON QUALITY OF DOUGH

O. SIMAKOVA*, A. KORSHUNOVA, L. SEMENOVA

Abstract: *The results of studies of the effect of sea kale on quality indicators dough. The advantages of the use of additives in the production of dough.*

Keywords: *yeast dough, seaweed, amylolytic activity and amylase, wheat flour.*

1. Introduction

Statement of the problem and its relationship with the major scientific and practical tasks. An important place in the range of products, which are realized by enterprises occupy a pastry supply. Particularly in demand are products of yeast dough. Given that diets need to reduce the total weight of products with high energy, there is a need develop products with less energy-intensive components while maintaining the quality properties, which are inherent in dough [1]. The question can be solved by partial replacement of wheat flour in the recipe to other non-traditional pastry kind of raw material. We offer this purpose seaweed (kelp sugar), which is due to the peculiarities of its chemical composition and technological properties can provide a high quality finished products [2].

The purpose of this paper is to study the influence of seaweed on the quality indicators of dough.

The presentation of the basic material research. In order to be able to talk about the use of seaweed (kelp sugar) as an impurity, rich in vitamins, minerals and other beneficial substances to the body, increases the nutritive and biological value of products made from wheat flour, you should examine in detail its influence on amylase activity.

2. Materials and method

We have investigated the activity of amylase dry seaweed with a model substrate - 2% solution of partially starch.

The activity of enzyme preparation was assessed by the number formed in the reaction

mixture of maltose - product of starch hydrolysis deep. Enzyme preparation used in the form of flour, which was received from the dry seaweed and 5% aqueous extract.

It should be noted that in the first place should determine the resolution of the activity of α - and β -amylase, an enzyme present in raw materials. α -amylase hydrolyzes the 1,4-bond in the molecule of sugars. Starch molecule is cleaved at the same time for large pieces. One of the most characteristic features of the influence of α -amylase is a fast colliquation of starch. The process of disintegration of starch in the high activity of α -amylase occurs most intensively at high temperatures during baking, and can cause a significant reduction in the quality of crumb products. α -amylase breaks down every second bond. Thus, from the start of the α -amylase in the reaction mixture creates a reducing sugar formed favorable conditions for the fermentation test. When heated, the enzyme mixture for 15 min. at 70 ° C α -amylase is almost completely preserved. To stabilize the α -amylase with this method of inactivation of β -amylase is recommended to add a small amount of calcium acetate. Defined in this way the amount of reducing sugars characterizes the activity of α -amylase activity of β -amylase is defined as the difference between total activity and the activity of α -amylase. Data on the activity of α -amylase, as well as the total amylase activity are shown in Table 1.

* E-mail: simakov@telenet.dn.ua

Table 1 - Definition of α - and β -amylase in the flour of dried seaweed (kelp sugar).

№	enzyme preparation	The contents of maltose,%
1.	5% water extract of dried seaweed with non-inactivated β -amylase	11,4
2.	5% water extract of dried seaweed with inactivated β -amylase	1,1
3.	Estimated value of the β -amylase activity	10,3

The data in Table 1: Activity α -amylase very low, which is characteristic of plant material. However, the activity of amylase complex can be

enhanced through the use of small additions of Ca²⁺, which are involved in the formation and stabilization of the active center and the whole of the tertiary structure of the enzyme.

Table 2 - hydrolysis of starch under the action of amylases dry seaweed (kelp sugar).

№	substratum	enzyme preparation	maltose content,%
1.	2% starch solution	5% aqueous extract of barley malt	17,2
2.	-II-	5% extract of dried seaweed	12,3
3.	-II-	5% probability of dry extract of seaweed on the solution of calcium chloride (CaCl 0.01 g / l)	16,3

Indeed, a small addition of calcium chloride to the reaction mixture dramatically increases the amylase activity of the drug and displays it almost on a par with barley malt.

The results obtained made it possible to ascertain amylase activity of the dry seaweed. But it was necessary to select the optimal concentration of impurities. At the same time took into account that the impurity was enough to make dough and products rich in vitamins,

iodine, alginic acid, so that impurities do not overdose rheological properties of the test [3]. The concentration should be such so as not to affect the color of the flour and the crumb color of the product.

Dependence of the main biologically active substances in wheat flour on the impurity concentration is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 - Dependence of the content of the main biologically active substances in wheat flour on the impurity concentration of dried seaweed (kelp sugar).

№ п /п	the impurity concentration, %	The content of the flour biologically - active substances					
		protein, %	vitamine C, %	carotene, mg %	alginic acid, %	iodine, mg %	selenium, mg %
1.	0	12,7	-	-	-	-	-
2.	0,50	12,7	0,36	0,1	0,18	0,02	0,01
3.	0,75	12,8	0,41	0,25	0,24	0,04	0,02
4.	4,0	12,9	1,2	0,30	0,32	0,08	0,025
5.	2,0	13,1	1,6	0,32	0,41	1,0	0,038
6.	2,5	13,3	2,6	0,39	0,62	1,5	0,056
7.	3,0	13,4	2,8	0,41	0,71	1,8	0,068
8.	4,0	13,8	3,1	0,43	0,79	2,1	0,069
9.	5,0	14,1	3,3	0,45	0,83	2,5	0,073

The data in Table 3 indicate that low concentrations of dry seaweed few determined on the quality of wheat flour and only from admixtures 2.0 - 2.5%, it affects the biological value of the flour.

Adding an impurity at a concentration of 3.0 - 5.0% and above degrade the dignity of baking flour.

Thus, the addition of impurities in an amount of 2.0 - 2.5% of the dry seaweed is appropriate. This concentration of the impurity enriched wheat flour, the main

biologically active substances, and on the other hand - is not large enough to impair the quality of gluten.

As a criterion for the dignity of baking flour, we have chosen the quality of its gluten, which is determined by balls with 10 g of gluten after an hour.

Data on balls gluten washed from wheat flour, contains different concentrations of dry seaweed (kelp sugar"), are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 - Dependence of the dilution of gluten washed from wheat flour, the impurity concentration of dry seaweed.

№	the impurity concentration, %	ball diameter, mm
1.	0	41
2.	0,50	41
3.	0,75	42
4.	1,0	43
5.	2,0	45
6.	2,5	48

7.	3,0	56
8.	4,0	85
9.	5,0	110

As the data in Table 4, small amounts of impurities does not weaken the gluten flour, until the concentration does not exceed 2.5%, with a mixture of flour and 2.5% is slightly tinged with gray, but that the color of wheat flour does not go beyond the requirements.

Data of the amylase activity of wheat flour with the addition of impurities, dry seaweed (kelp sugar) and its aqueous extract are shown in Table 5.

Table 5 - amylase activity of wheat flour with a mixture of dry seaweed (kelp sugar).

№	enzyme preparation	content of maltose, %
1.	dry barley malt	9,8
2.	dry seaweed	8,0
3.	5% water extract of dried seaweed (kelp sugar)	9,1
4.	control	3,9

As can be seen from Table 5 sugar property of flour rises sharply with the addition of impurities. This makes it possible to consider a dry seaweed (kelp sugar), a full-fledged drug amylase activity, in the case of β -amylase.

When using dry seaweed (kelp sugar), we determined the pH of yeast in the dough and small (the same used in admixture: 2 - 2.5% by weight of flour).

Table 6 – p H

№	characteristics	yeast dough		unleavened dough	
		control	Doped sample (2,5%)	control	Doped sample (2,5%)
1.	p H	4,7	4,6	5,1	5,0
finished goods					
2.	p H	4,7	4,6	5,1	5,0

When analyzing the data in Table 6, it can be concluded that the addition of the flour, dry seaweed (kelp sugar), the pH in yeast and small test does not change the pH value is also unchanged, and in the finished product. According to OST 28.5 - 78 acidic products should be in the pH range from 4.5 to 5.2 units.

In products with the addition of seaweed value does not exceed 5.0.

Thus, the admixture of seaweed (kelp sugar) does not change the acidity of the dough and the finished products.

We examined quality indicators dough with a touch. The data presented in Tables 7.8.

Table 7 - Indicators of growth and fermentation of dough.

№	Type of dough	time of initial rise, min.	difference from control, %	fermentation time, min	difference from control, %
1	Dough (control)	30	-	100,0	-
2	Dough with seaweed	25	+16,7	60	40

Table 8 - Indicators of the quality of dough.

№	indicators	control	doped sample (2,5%)	difference, %
1.	total moisture, %	34,9	39,6	+13,5
2.	dry matter, %	12,3	15,4	+25,2
3.	amount of gluten, %	82,3	71,8	-12,3
4.	swelling of gluten, %	18,1	17,5	-3,3
5.	density of the dough, kg/c m ²	54,9	48,8	-11,1

Analyzing the data in Table 8, we can conclude that the addition of wheat flour, dry seaweed in the test increased by 13.5% moisture, 2.52% on dry matter, but the amount of gluten is reduced

by 12.8%. Decreases as indicators such as swelling test and its density - 3.3 and 11.1%.

Product quality depends on the structural and mechanical properties of the test. Data are presented in Table 9.

Table 9 - Structural and mechanical properties of the dough.

indicators	control	doped sample	difference, %
height of the semifinished product (20min.), c m	4,0	3,9	-2,5
modulus of elasticity E*10 ⁵ Pa	74,0	75,5	+2,02

plasticity, %	39,3	38,8	-1,3
recovery time after deformation, min	2 h 42 min.	2 h. 55 min.	-13 min.

The results show that the pastry after the same time, proofing (20 min.) Are not the same lift.

Have a maximum height control products - 4.0 cm, while at the same time, products with a mixture of seaweed (kelp sugar) was slightly lower rise of -3.8 cm (2.5%). Most are installed without any admixture of semi-finished products (for 13 min.). Studies have also shown that the difference in the structural and mechanical properties. Modulus of elasticity in the experimental samples increased by 2.02%.

With the increase of the indicator module of elasticity in test samples marked increase in the viscosity of the test (1.4%). Plasticity in the samples decreases with the addition of seaweed (kelp sugar) by 1.3%.

Structural and mechanical properties of the control and experimental samples are slightly different, so we can assume that the dough is elastic and expandable well, has a high plasticity. Therefore, as a batter in the control samples, as well as in research, the same.

3. Conclusions

Thus, we can conclude that the seaweed (kelp sugar) contains the necessary nutrients, is set to make the optimum dose of the impurity in the yeast dough, the influence of impurities on the structural - mechanical properties of the test. Prospects for further research in this direction. In the future we plan to develop the latest technology products from the dough with sugar kelp.

References

1. A. Kondratyev, NB, LE Skokan, Funtikov NS, N. Degtyarev The use of antioxidants in pastry. A.B.Kondratev, L.E.Skokan, N.S.Funtikov. - Moscow: Food Industry, 2003-№4-25p.
2. Matveeva IV, IG Belyavskaya Food additives and bread improvers in the production of bakery products I.V.Matveeva, I.G.Belyavskaya - M: Food Industry, 2000 – 15p.
3. Shakirova RZ, Koryachkin SJ The use of local native materials in the manufacture of bakery products Shakirov S.Koryachkina - Moscow: Nauka, 2005 – 7p.

RHEOLOGICAL PARAMETRES OF A CREAM FILLING USED FOR THE PRODUCTION OF CO-EXTRUDATES

A. SIMITCHIEV*, V. NENOV**, M. DUSHKOVA***, N. TOSHKOV****

Abstract: The authors performed the rheological studies of the cream filling “creamfill classic” used for the production of co-extruded products. Based on the results of the studies, the drawn graphics and the rheological curves, conclusions were made about the rheological properties of the cream.

Keywords: rheology, co-extrusion

1. Introduction

The flow behavior of the food products through nozzles, orifices and pipes of various shapes and diameters with the purpose to obtain an optimal design have been studied by the rheology science [2, 4]. In the co-extruded products with various structural and mechanical properties, such as the pipe of the corn semolina and the filling pastry cream, the behavior knowledge of the individual materials is essential in the analytic process - modeling and structural design of the individual details of the dosing head [1]. The summary equation which describes the flow behavior of the products in consequence of the applying pressure is as follows [8]:

$$\tau = \tau_0 + k \cdot \dot{\gamma}^n \quad (1),$$

where: τ – shear stress, [Pa];
 τ_0 – yield stress, [Pa].
 k – consistency coefficient. When $n=1$,
 $k = \mu$ – dynamic viscosity, [Pa.s];
 $\dot{\gamma}$ – shear rate, [s^{-1}];
 n – flow behaviour index.

Where: $n = 1$ and $\tau_0 = 0$ the product is a Newtonian fluid; $n=1$ and $\tau_0 \neq 0$ the product is a Bingham plastic; $n < 1$ and $\tau_0 = 0$ – pseudoplastic product; $n < 1$ and $\tau_0 \neq 0$ – Herschel-Bulkley fluid; $n > 1$ and $\tau_0 = 0$ – dilatant fluid [9].

There exist fluids in the practice which are characterized by the concept of relaxation time:

* Dept. of Machines and apparatus for The Food Industry, UFT- Plovdiv, Bulgaria, E-mail: asimitchiev@mail.bg.

** Dept. of Machines and apparatus for The Food Industry, UFT- Plovdiv, Bulgaria E-mail: vnenov2001@yahoo.co.uk.

*** Dept. of Process engineering, UFT-Plovdiv, E-mail: maria_douchkova@yahoo.fr

**** Dept. of Process engineering, UFT-Plovdiv, E-mail: nesho.i@abv.bg

$$\tau = \frac{\mu}{G} \quad (2),$$

where: μ – dynamic viscosity, [Pa.s];

G – shear relaxation modulus, [Pa].

Fluids with similar behaviour are called Maxwell fluids and have both elastic and plastic properties. After the removal of the mechanical effects these fluids automatically recover part of their previous state [3, 10].

The body properties in rheology are studied at different shear rates versus the shear stress.

Fig.1 Rheogram for time-independent viscous fluids

In the production of co-extrudates the filling is a creamy-shaped product which is syringed in the tube of corn semolina formed by extrusion, using a system of a pump, a piping and a dosing needle [6, 7]. Fig.2 shows the principal scheme of the laboratory

equipment for production of co-extrudates used for supply of the filling mass. During the supply to the extrusion head, a part of the cream circulated between the pump and the hopper before it falls into the final product.

Fig.2 Laboratory equipment for supply of the filling mass.

1. Substructure; 2. Thermostat; 3. Subtrahend with a nozzle for flexible connection; 4. Water jacketed lobe pump 5. Soft pipe; 6. Chain-driven engine; 7. Hard pipe;
8. Ball valve; 9. Water jacketed hopper.

2. Purpose

The purpose was to investigate the rheological parameters of the cream filling used for the production of co-extrudates before and after circulation in the equipment shown on fig.2 and determine its type according to the known products in rheology science.

3. Materials and methods

The used cream filling is a “creamfill classic”. This product represents a ready to use cream filling with a 9 months durability of the final product. In the first part of the experiments, the cream was tempered for 30 minutes at different temperatures in a “Zemail Horyzont” thermostat. Then its viscosity was

measured at different temperatures and shear rate – rotation frequency of the cylindrical spindle, using the “Brookfield RV-DV II + Pro” viscometer. The spindle used was RV – 7. The experimental data for the viscosity at different rotation frequencies were obtained on the basis of threefold repetition

In the second part of the experiments, the “creamfill classic” passed through the laboratory equipment for supply of the filling mass (fig.2), and then the viscosity was measured again, using the same independent variables.

4. Results and discussion

The “Brookfield RV-DV II + Pro” viscometer equipped with a cylindrical spindle

RV-7 was used to determine the cream viscosity. The experimental results with “creamfill classic” before and after its passage through the laboratory equipment for supply of the filling mass are presented on Tables 1 and 2. The parameters presented on Tables 1 and 2

are: n – rotation frequency of the spindle, min^{-1} ; μ - dynamic viscosity, [Pa.s]; $\dot{\gamma}$ - shear rate, [s^{-1}] and τ – shear stress, [Pa].

*Table 1
Rheological properties of “creamfill classic” before its passage through the laboratory equipment.*

№	n, min^{-1}	$\dot{\gamma}$, s^{-1}	t=30°C.		t=35°C.		t=40°C.	
			μ , Pa.s	τ , Pa	μ , Pa.s	τ , Pa	μ , Pa.s	τ , Pa
1	10	2,09	119,4	247,73	108	225,72	89,873	187,835
2	20	4,18	99,6	412,28	70,223	293,533	57,153	238,900
3	30	6,27	71,267	446,49	54,216	339,938	42,933	269,192
4	50	10,45	53,76	560,53	34,003	355,334	29,143	304,547
5	100	20,9	35,95	750,10	22,82	476,938	19,806	413,959

*Table 2
Rheological properties of “creamfill classic” after its passage through the laboratory equipment.*

№	n, min^{-1}	$\dot{\gamma}$, s^{-1}	t=30°C.		t=35°C.		t=40°C.	
			μ , Pa.s	τ , Pa	μ , Pa.s	τ , Pa	μ , Pa.s	τ , Pa
1	10	2,09	71,96	150,410	70,7	147,763	59,933	125,26
2	20	4,18	48,466	202,590	47,8	199,804	39,75	166,15
3	30	6,27	40,333	252,89	39,332	246,613	32,633	204,61
4	50	10,45	29,94	312,873	28,673	299,636	25,813	269,74
5	100	20,9	21	438,9	18,866	394,313	18,866	341,50

The calculations of the shear rate and the shear stress when working with the digital “Brookfield” viscometer were performed using the equations listed in the manual of the device [5]. The shear rate was calculated by the equation:

$$\dot{\gamma} = \text{SRC} \cdot n, [\text{s}^{-1}] \quad (3),$$

where: - SRC shear rate constant. For the RV-7 spindle, $\text{SRC} = 0,209$. [5]

- n – rotation frequency of the spindle, [min^{-1}].

The shear stress is determined by the equation:

$$\tau = 0,1 \cdot \text{TK} \cdot \text{SRC} \cdot \text{SMC} \cdot M, [\text{Pa}] \quad (4),$$

where:

- TK – viscometer constant.

For “Brookfield”RV-DV +Pro, $\text{TK} = 1$ [5]

- M - torque, N.m. The value was taken directly from the display.

- SMC – multiplier constant of the spindle. For the RV-7 spindle, $\text{SMC} = 400$. [5]

Fig.3 and fig.4 show the graphical dependencies of the dynamic viscosity on shear rate before and after the passage of the cream through the laboratory equipment. The derived power equations, which describe these dependencies, with the highest coefficient of determination R^2 , correspond to the Oswald-de Waele power law which describes the pseudoplastic fluids (table 3).

Fig.3 Viscosity dependence on shear rate

Fig.4 Viscosity dependence on shear rate after a single passage of the cream through the laboratory equipment

Table 3

Power equations and coefficients of determination

Temperature, °C	$\mu = f(\dot{\gamma})$	R^2
Before the passage through the laboratory equipment		
30	$\mu = 190,75 \dot{\gamma}^{-0,5389}$	0,9785
35	$\mu = 183,95 \dot{\gamma}^{-0,6913}$	0,9947
40	$\mu = 146,34 \dot{\gamma}^{-0,6675}$	0,9976
After the passage through the laboratory equipment		
30	$\mu = 105,87 \dot{\gamma}^{-0,5339}$	0,9992
35	$\mu = 109,12 \dot{\gamma}^{-0,5721}$	0,9986
40	$\mu = 89,761 \dot{\gamma}^{-0,5517}$	0,9961

In both cases it can be seen a decrease in viscosity when the shear rate increased. Such behaviour is typical for the pseudoplastic non-Newtonian fluids, whose flow is described by the Oswald-de Waele power law:

$$\tau = \kappa \cdot \dot{\gamma}^n \quad (5)$$

There is an inverse correlation between the temperature of the cream and its shear rate. The highest average values of the viscosity were obtained before the passage of the cream through the laboratory equipment at a temperature of 30°C (119,4 Pa.s), and the lowest – after its passage through the

equipment at a temperature of 40°C (18,866 Pa.s). It can also be seen that after the passage through the laboratory equipment, the viscosity of “creamfill classic” decreased by about 15 to 40 %, which is due to the mechanical impact of the lobe pump through which the product has been passed.

Fig.5 and fig.6 show common diagrams for both studied cases, showing the shear stress dependency on shear rate at different temperatures of the cream.

In both cases the flow curves are non-linear, which means that “creamfill classic” belongs to the non-Newtonian liquids group.

Fig.5 Flow curves of "creamfill classic"

Fig.6 Flow curves of "creamfill classic" after a single passage through the laboratory equipment

Table 4

Power equations and coefficients of determination

Temperature, °C	$\tau = f(\dot{\gamma})$	R^2
Before the passage through the laboratory equipment		
30	$\tau = 105,87 \dot{\gamma}^{0,4661}$	0,9989
35	$\tau = 109,12 \dot{\gamma}^{0,4279}$	0,9975
40	$\tau = 89,761 \dot{\gamma}^{0,6675}$	0,994
After the passage through the laboratory equipment		
30	$\tau = 190,75 \dot{\gamma}^{0,4611}$	0,9708
35	$\tau = 184,08 \dot{\gamma}^{0,5721}$	0,9733
40	$\tau = 146,34 \dot{\gamma}^{0,3325}$	0,9903

Power equations which define the flow of "creamfill classic" at different temperatures were derived for both cases at Table 4.

It can be concluded that the increase in shear rate led to an increase in shear stress, which is the lowest after the passage of the cream through the laboratory equipment at a temperature of 40°C (125,26 Pa) and reach maximum values after the passage through the equipment at a temperature of 30°C (750,10 Pa).

5. Conclusions:

1. Considering the cream filling behavior at different shear rates and comparing the flow curves with the non-Newtonian liquids diagram (fig.1), we can conclude that "creamfill classic" belongs to the non-Newtonian pseudoplastic products

group, for which the shear stress is expressed with the Oswald-de Waele power law – the values of the coefficient of determination R^2 for all equations were almost equal to 1, which means that the dependence between the parameters is linear.

2. The experimental results show that before its passage through the laboratory equipment "creamfill classic" has higher values of the dynamic viscosity and the shear stress. The percentage difference in the viscosity values for both cases varies from 15 to 40 %.

3. The experimental results show that in both studied cases the increase in temperature led to a decrease in viscosity and shear stress. An interesting fact is, that at the non-circulated cream, the change of

the viscosity and the shear stress was higher in the range from 35 to 40⁰C, and at the circulated cream – in the range from 30 to 35⁰C.

6. References:

1. Abbott Paul (1987) - Coextrusion: Recent developments using cooker-extruders "Cereal Foods World".
2. Chhabra R. P. (2010), Non-Newtonian Fluids: An Introduction, Rheology of Complex Fluids, eds. A. P. Deshpande, J. Murali Krishnan & P. B. Sunil Kumar, Springer, Munich, Chapter 1.
3. Hendrickson, T: "Massage for Orthopedic Conditions", page 9. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins, 2003.
4. Matshihin, A. (1990) – "Rheology of food products – a manual".
5. "More solutions to sticky problems: Table of contents" (2007)
6. Nenov, V., Penov, N., Yovtshv, V., Yiankulov, T. (2003) – "Mechanism shaped co-extrudates"
7. Peressini D., A. Sensidoni, C. Pollini, D. Gabrielle, M. Migliori, B. De Cindio, (2001) – „Filled snack production by co-extrusion cooking“.
8. Reiner, M., and Scott Blair, Rheology terminology, in Rheology, Vol. 4 pp. 461, (New York: Achedemic Press, 1967)
9. Simitchiev, Ap., Nenov, V., Lambrev, At. (2010)– „Co-extrusion of food products – main points and technical characteristics“.
10. Steffe J.F. – "Rheological methods in food process engineering" Freeman Press, E. Lansing, MI, 1996.

DYNAMIC VISCOSITY OF A CREAM FILLING

A. SIMITCHIEV*

Abstract: *The author have investigated the process variables of the dynamic viscosity – rotation frequency of the viscometer spindle, time of mechanical impact and temperature of the material. The summarized conclusions were made, according to the derived regression mathematical model and the drawn contours of equal output.*

Keywords: *rheology, viscosity, co-extrusion*

1. Introduction

The modern quest for the production of healthy foods, and the increased demand from the consumers, have lead to the emergence of new technologies and products that meet the requirements of the constantly evolving food industry. One of those relatively new technologies is the co-extrusion of food products [5], [6]. This is one of the most modern ways for the production of foods with fillings from a different kind. This method allows the production of food products in lower forms (candies) and elongated forms (muffins, baguettes) which contain a filling [8].

The knowledge of the structural and the mechanical properties of the filling mass is very important in the production of co-extruded products.

The structure of the coextrusion head has been largely determined by the structural and the mechanical properties of both products. The material of the tube, made by extruded corn or wheat semolina, has it's own behaviour and properties, which are dependent from the extrusion regimes – temperatures, rotations per minute of the main and the dosing screw, compression of the main screw and etc. The properties of the filling, which is usually a pastry product, are influencing the quality of the product, although these properties can be influenced only by the device that has submitted the filling. In [9] were investigated the change and the behaviour of the viscosity of the cream filling during it's passage through a laboratory equipment with single circulation and without circulation. It's determined that "creamfill classic" is a pseudoplastic fluid, which is described by the Oswald-de Waele power law.

In the production of co-extrudates the most important thing for modelling and optimizing the process, is the dependence of the viscosity of the filling from the influencing factors[5].

2. Materials and methods

The investigated product is a cream filling "creamfill classic". It is a ready to use vanilla pastry cream with a 9 months durability in the final product that have been used for the production of croissants, waffles and etc.

The cream was tempered for 30 minutes at different temperatures in thermostat "Zemail Horizont" and then its viscosity was measured, using the "Brookfield RV-DV II + Pro" viscometer. Threefold repetition was made for each test, and after that were calculated the average values of the viscosity.

The independant variables that were changed are:

- rotation frequency of the spindle - x_1 , [min⁻¹];
- time of mechanical impact – x_2 , [min];
- temperature of the material - x_3 , [°C];

The response variable was the dynamic viscosity μ , [Pa.s].

A full factorial 2³ design was used for the investigation. The varying levels, the names and the indications of the independent variables are presented at table 1.

The mathematical processing of the results, as well as the contours of equal output were made by a specialized statistical softwear "Statgraphics Centurion XV".

* Dept. of Machines and Appartus for The Food Industry, UFT- Plovdiv, Bulgaria, E-mail: asimitchiev@mail.bg.

The matrix of the plan in natural and coded kind is presented at table 2. Threefold repetition was made

for each test, regarding the general procedure for multi-factorial experiment planning .

Varying levels for the independent variables

Table 1

Independent variables	High level, $z_i^r(x_i^r)$	Low level, $z_i^l(x_i^l)$	Center of the plan, $z_i^0(x_i^0)$	Varying interval
Rotation frequency of the spindle, n, min ⁻¹ , (x ₁)	50	10	30	20
Time of mechanical impact, T, min, (x ₂)	6	2	4	2
Temperature of the material, t, °C, (x ₃)	40	30	35	5

Plan of the experiment in natural and coded kind

Table 2

No	Natural kind			Coded kind		
	X₁,(min⁻¹)	X₂,(min)	X₃, (°C)	X₁,(min⁻¹)	X₂,(min)	X₃, (°C)
1	10	2	30	-	-	-
2	50	2	30	+	-	-
3	10	6	30	-	+	-
4	50	6	30	+	+	-
5	10	2	40	-	-	+
6	50	2	40	+	-	+
7	10	6	40	-	+	+
8	50	6	40	+	+	+

3. Results and discussions:

The values of the independent variable, and the average results for the response variable are presented at table 3.

The lowest values of the viscosity were measured when all of the independent variables have been at their high level (24,5 Pa.s), and the highest values were obtained when all of the independent variables have been at their low level (118,53 Pa.s).

Table 4 presents the regression coefficients and the statistical significance of each effect that were calculated by comparing the mean square against an estimate of the experimental error. In this case, seven

of the effects had P-values less than 0,05 which means that they are significantly different from zero at 95% confidence interval. The R² statistic has indicated that the model as fitted explains over 99,91 % of the variability in the dynamic viscosity. The value of the mean square is 0,9539, and the mean absolute error MAE = 0,4913. The value of the Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic test was 1,44825 which is higher than the critical value (1,4). This means that there is indication of serial autocorrelation in the residuals at the 5.0% significance level .

Results of the investigation

Table 3

N ₂	X ₁ , min ⁻¹	X ₂ , min	X ₃ , °C	μ, Pa.s
1	10	2	30	118,53
2	50	2	30	53,64
3	10	6	30	99,67
4	50	6	30	46,56
5	10	2	40	89,87
6	50	2	40	29,14
7	10	6	40	75,83
8	50	6	40	24,5

Regression coefficients

Table 4

	Regression coefficients	P-values
A: rotation frequency of the spindle	-28.7579	0,0000*
B:Time of mechanical impact	-5.57875	0,0000*
C:Temperature of the material	-12.3812	0,0000*
AB	2.64792	0,0000*
AC	0.742083	0,0019*
BC	0.907917	0,0003*
ABC	-0.29875	0,1535
Constant	67.2187	0,0000*

*Significant coefficients

The coefficients of the effects are represented at the standardized Pareto chart (fig 1). It consists by horizontal blocks with lengths proportional to the absolute values of the estimated effects, divided by their standard errors. A vertical line that represents the value of the Student criterion at 95 % confidence level has been added to facilitate the chart. From the diagram it can be concluded, that the linear effect of the rotation frequency of the spindle have had the highest impact over the dynamic viscosity, followed by the linear effects of the temperature and the time of the mechanical impact.

Fig. 2 presents the diagram for the distribution of the residual values of the regression model. It shown that the residuals have been equally distributed around the zero line, and there haven't been values that surpassed the standard error value.

After processing the experimental results and elimination of the insignificant factors the following regression model was obtained:

$$\mu_1 = 67,2187 - 28,7579X_1 - 5,5785X_2 - 12,3812X_3 + 2,64792X_1X_2 + 0,742083X_1X_3 + 0,907917X_2X_3, [\text{Pa.s}]. \quad (1)$$

The regression model is adequate, because at 16 degrees of freedom and $\alpha=0,05$, the Fischer criterium is $F= 0,52$, which is lower that the critical value $F_t = 4,5$.

The equal output contours, showing the amendment of the dynamic viscosity depending on the rotation frequency of the spindle n , [min^{-1}] and the temperature of the cream t , [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] at the time of mechanical impact $T=2$ min are presented at fig.3. Lower values of the viscosity were obtained at the combination of high cream temperature and high rotation frequency of the spindle. The highest values of the viscosity were obtained at low temperature of the cream and low rotation frequency of the spindle. These two findings are logical, because "creamfill classic" belongs to the non-Newtonian pseudoplastic liquids [9], that are characterized by decreased

viscosity during a mechanical impact [1], [4]. The rise of the temperature and the rotation frequency of the spindle have lead to a gradual destruction of the

structure of the cream, and hence to a decrease in viscosity.

Fig.1 Pareto chart

Fig.2 Residual distribution diagram

Fig.3 Amendment of the dynamic viscosity depending on the rotation frequency of the spindle and the temperature of the cream at the time of mechanical impact 2 minutes

Fig.4 Amendment of the dynamic viscosity depending on the rotation frequency of the spindle and the time of mechanical impact at a temperature of the cream 40°C.

Fig.4 shows the equal output contours which depicted the change of the viscosity depending on the rotation frequency of the spindle n , [min^{-1}] and the time of mechanical impact T , [min] at a temperature of the cream $t=40^\circ\text{C}$.

The graph have shown that the increase of the time of mechanical impact have lead to a decrease of the viscosity. Such behavior is typical for the thixotropic time dependent liquids. According to [7] and [10] thixotropy is the property of non-Newtonian, pseudoplastic fluids that show a time-dependent change in viscosity. There are cases in

rhology in which thixotropy may occur in combination with pseudoplasticity or only at certain shear rates. The time element is extremely variable – under conditions of constant shear rate, some fluids reach their final viscosity value in a few seconds, while others may take up to several days [2], [3]. In the concrete case for “creamfill classic” a constant change of the dynamic viscosity was seen, which is the ground for its associate to the thixotropic time dependent fluids.

4. Conclusions

1. The derived mathematical model, that describes the amendment of the viscosity from the independent factors, is adequate according to the statistical theory. The highest impact over the dynamic viscosity of the cream has the linear effect of the rotation frequency of the spindle, followed by the linear effects of the material temperature and the time of the mechanical impact.

2. The highest values of the viscosity (118,53 Pa.s) was measured at rotation frequency of the spindle 10 min^{-1} , time of mechanical impact 2 minutes, and temperature of the product 30°C .

3. The lowest values of the viscosity (24,5 Pa.s) was obtained at rotation frequency of the spindle 50 min^{-1} , time of mechanical impact 6 minutes, and temperature of the product 40°C .

4. In consequence of the time of mechanical impact influence, it can be argued that "creamfill classic" is both pseudoplastic and thixotropic liquid.

References

1. Chhabra R. P. (2010), Non-Newtonian Fluids: An Introduction, Rheology of Complex Fluids, eds.

A. P. Deshpande, J. Murali Krishnan & P. B. Sunil Kumar, Springer, Munich, Chapter 1.

2. Cognard P. (2005), "Handbook of adhesives and sealants", Volume 1

3. More solutions solutions to sticky problems – table of contents, (2007).

4. Machihine Y.(1990) – „Rheometry of food raw materials and products – a guide”.

5. Nenov V., Penov N., Yovtchev V., Yankulov T.(2003) "A mechanism that formes co-extrudates".

6. Peressini D., A. Sensidoni, C. Pollini, D. Gabrielle, M. Migliori, B. De Cindio, (2001) – „Filled snack production by co-extrusion cooking“.

7. Reiner, M., and Scott Blair, Rheology terminology, in Rheology, Vol. 4 pp. 461, (New York: Achedemic Press, 1967)

8. Simitchiev Ap., Nenov V., Lambrev At. (2010) – "Co-extrusion of food products – nature and techical characteristics"

9. Simitchiev Ap., Nenov V., Dushkova M., Toshkov N. (2012) - „Rheological parametres of a cream filling used for the production of co-extrudates.”

10. Tanner R.I. (2000) Engineering rheology. 2nd edn. Oxford university press, London.

COEFFICIENT OF DIFFUSION OF AROMATIC EXTRACTION PRODUCTS FROM HAWTHORN (*Crataegus monogyna* Jaqc.)

S. TASHEVA* S. DAMIANOVA** M. ERGEZEN***
P. MERDZHANOV*** A. STOYANOVA***

Abstract. The coefficient of diffusion (D) of aromatic products – concrete and resinoid, obtained through extraction of leaves and fruits from hawthorn (*Crataegus monogyna* Jaqc.) have been determined. The highest values of D with respect to resinoid extraction from leaves and fruits are calculated at 70 °C ($9,02 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) and 60 °C ($17,77 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$), respectively and with respect to concrete extraction from leaves and fruits – at 30 °C ($8,93 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) and 40 °C ($9,49 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$).

Keywords: fruits and leaves from hawthorn, ethanol extracts.

1. Introduction

Fruits and leaves of hawthorn (*Crataegus monogyna* Jaqc.), as well as different water and water-alcohol extracts obtained from them, have found application in traditional and official medicine [9, 11, 12, 14].

In our previous work we have obtained extracts from hawthorn with three different concentrations of ethanol, aiming at their application in cosmetics [4, 6]. The extracts have been characterized in terms of tannin content, diffusion of tannins have been estimated [8, 13], as well as the antimicrobial activity of the extracts [5, 7].

There is no data on obtaining specific extraction products – concrete and resinoid, from hawthorn, as well as on the determination of extracts` molecular diffusion coefficients, which is the aim of the current work.

2. Experimental

Plant material: Fruits and leaves of hawthorn (*C. monogyna*) from the market from Bulgaria were used in the investigation. The raw material was characterized in terms of: moisture content by drying it up to constant weight, at 105°C [10].

Determination of the diffusion coefficients: Extraction was carried out as a batch static process by maceration in the solvent at a ratio of raw material to solvent = 1:10 under the following conditions: for concrete: solvent – petroleum ether; temperature - 20, 30 and 40°C;

for resinoid: solvent – 96 vol % ethyl alcohol; temperature - 20, 40, 60 and 70°C. For both aromatic products - size of material particles - 0,04 cm (fruits) and 0,11 cm (leaves); duration of extraction 1 h, with the solvent replaced and analyzed for extracted tannins after each 10 min interval. As a criterion for effectiveness of the process the quantity of concrete and resinoid was determined.

The diffusion coefficients were estimated by Minosian's equation [1]:

$$D = \frac{l^2 \cdot 2,3 \lg(E_1 - E_2)}{\pi^2 (\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \quad (1)$$

where: l - size of the material, cm;

τ_1, τ_2 – duration of extraction, s;

E_1, E_2 – initial and final concentration of concrete or resinoid, %.

All experiments were carried out in threefold repetition and mean values with the respective error are presented in the figures below.

Data presented on the figures are processed with Microcal Origin Micro Soft tool.

Results and discussion: The analyzed hawthorn leaves and fruits were with 11.1% and 12.5% moisture level, respectively.

* Dept. of Heat Engineering, Plovdiv, University of Food Technologies, Bulgaria, e-mail: st_tasheva@abv.bg

**Subsidiary of the University of Ruse, 47 Aprilsko Vastanie Blvd., 7200 Razgrad, Bulgaria, e-mail:sdamianova@uni-ruse.bg

*** Dept. of Technology of tobacco, sugar, plants and essential oils, Plovdiv, University of Food Technologies, Bulgaria, e-mail: kimyager_mehmet@myinet.com; pmerdzhanov@abv.bg; alstst@yahoo.com

Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 present the schemes of the experiments that have been carried out and the obtained results. Data reveal that with the increase in extraction duration the quantity of the obtained aromatic products decreases. Regardless of the plant material – leaves or fruit, maximum amount of concrete is extracted at temperature 40°C, and respectively, maximum amount of resinoid – at temperature 70°C, which finding is attributed to the influence of temperature on the extractive potential of the solvent.

On the basis of the experimental results from figures 1 – 4 the diffusion coefficients of concrete and resinoid are calculated, and their variations are presented on figures 5, 6, 7 and 8. With the increase in the temperature of extraction the values of the diffusion coefficients also increase.

Fig. 1. Content of resinoid from leaves.

Fig. 2. Content of concrete from leaves.

Fig. 3. Content of resinoid from fruits.

Fig. 4. Content of concrete from fruits.

The highest values for resinoid from leaves and fruits are calculated at 70°C ($9,02 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) and 60°C ($17,77 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$), respectively, and for concrete extraction from leaves and fruits – at 30 °C ($8,93 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) and 40 °C ($9,49 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$), which could be explained by the facilitated diffusion. The differences in the values of the diffusion coefficients for the two studied aromatic products are due to the different structure of the plant organs and the applied solvent.

Compared to the values of diffusion coefficients cited in the literature for other plant materials, our results appear to be lower by one order, for example – concrete from lavender (*L. angustifolia*) flowers ($42,7 - 82,6 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) and pine (*P. sylvestris*) needles ($33,9 - 50,8 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) [3]; resinoid from oakmoss (*E. prunastri*) ($0,05 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$) [2], etc. [3]. These results are connected to the nature and the size of the raw material, the included aromatic substances and the specific conditions of the extraction process – solvent and temperature.

Fig. 5. Diffusion coefficients of resinoid from leaves.

Fig. 8. Diffusion coefficients of concrete from fruits.

Fig. 6. Diffusion coefficients of concrete from leaves.

Fig. 7. Diffusion coefficients of resinoid from fruits.

3. Conclusion: The highest values of coefficient of diffusion with respect to resinoid extraction from leaves and fruits from hawthorn (*Crataegus monogyna* Jacq.) are calculated at 70°C ($9,02 \cdot 10^{-8}$ cm²/s) and 60°C ($17,77 \cdot 10^{-8}$ cm²/s), respectively and with respect to concrete extraction from leaves and fruits – at 30°C ($8,93 \cdot 10^{-8}$ cm²/s) and 40°C ($9,49 \cdot 10^{-8}$ cm²/s).

References

1. Beloborodov, V., Dementii, V., Voronenko, B. *Valuation of methods from extraction of the oils.* In: Scientific Work VNIJ, vol. 28, 1971, p. 102-108.
2. Georgiev, E., Damianov, D., Damianova, S., Stereva, R. *Diffusion coefficients of extraction from lichen (Evernia furfuracea Fr.).* In: Scientific Works of University of Food Technologies, 32(1), 1987, p. 101-108.
3. Georgiev, E., Stoyanova, A. *A guide for the specialist in aromatic industry.* Plovdiv, 2006.
4. Damianova, S., Tasheva, S., Stouanova, M., Denev, P., Stoyanova, A. *Technology of plant extracts for cosmetics. 14. Fruits from hawthorn (Crataegus monogyna Jacq.)* In: Scientific Works University of Ruse, vol. 49(9.2), 2010, p. 109-113.
5. Damianova, S., Encheva, R., Stoyanova, M., Stoyanova, A. *Antimicrobial activity of extracts from hawthorn (Crataegus monogyna Jacq.)* In: Scientific Works of University of Ruse, vol. 50(9.2), 2011, p. 76-79.
6. Damianova, S., Tasheva S., Ergezen, M., Stoyanova, A. *Technology of extracts from hawthorn leaves (Crataegus monogyna Jacq.) for cosmetic applications.* In: The 18th "George Baritui" University -International Conference

- on CONTROL, DEVELOPMENT and APPLIED INFORMATICS in BUSINESS and ECONOMICS, Brasov, Romania, 24-25 November, 2011.
7. Damianova, S., Kostova I., Todorova, S., Encheva, R., Ergezen, M., Stoyanova, A. *Antimicrobial activity of extracts from leaves of hawthorn (Crataegus monogyna Jacq.)*. In: Food Science Engineering and Technologies, UFT-Plovdiv, vol. 3, 2011, p. 17-20.
 8. Damianova, S., Tasheva, S., Ergezen, M., Stoyanova, A. *Coefficients of diffusion in the process of obtaining extracts from hawthorn leaves (Crataegus monogyna Jacq.)*. In: The 18th "George Baritiu" University -International Conference on CONTROL, DEVELOPMENT and APPLIED INFORMATICS in BUSINESS and ECONOMICS, Brasov, Romania, 24-25 November, 2011.
 9. Donmez, A. *The genus Crataegus L. (Rosaceae) with special reference to hybridization and biodiversity in Turkey*. In: Turkish Journal of Botany, vol. 28, 2004, p. 29–37.
 10. Russian Pharmacopoeia, Moscow, 1990.
 11. Samec, D., Piljac-Zegarac, J. *Postharvest stability of antioxidant compounds in hawthorn and cornelian cherries at room and refrigerator, temperatures—Composition with blackberries, white and red crapehes*. In: Scientia Horticulturae, vol. 131, 2011, p. 15-21.
 12. Serteser, A., Kargioğlu, M. Gök, V., Bağci, Y., Özcan, M., Arslan D. *Determination of antioxidant effects of some plant species wild growing in Turkey*. In: International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition, vol. 59, 2008, p. 643–651.
 13. Stoyanova, M., Damianova, S., Tasheva, S., Stoyanova, A., Damianov, D. *Coefficients of diffusion in the process of obtaining extracts from hawthorn (Crataegus monogyna Jacq.)*, In: Scientific Works of the Union of Scientists in Bulgaria, vol. VIII, 2010, p. 121-128
 14. Yanar, M., Ercisli, S., Yilmaz, K., Sahiner, H., Taskin, T., Zengin, Y., Akgul, I., Celik, F. *Morphological and chemical diversity among hawthorn (Crataegus spp.) genotypes from Turkey*. In: Scientific Research and Essays, vol. 6(1), 2011, p. 35-38.

VARIATION OF ESSENTIAL OIL CONTENT FROM HERBS USED IN DIET AND PHYTOTHERAPY, FROM SPONTANEOUS FLORA -- ALBANIA AND CULTURE FLORA – ROMANIA

V.TAMAS, N. BORDEI , G. A. TRAISTARU, G. IVOPOL, A. COZEA, L. SHUKA, M MERSINLLARI

Abstract: *This paper presents studies on essential oil content of three herbs, the most widely used in food and phytotherapy: Thyme (Thymus vulgaris culture flora - Romania and Thymus longicaulis spontaneous flora - Albania), Sage (Salvia officinalis culture - Romania spontaneous flora and Albania) and St. John's Wort (Hypericum perforatum culture - Romania and the spontaneous flora - Albania).*

Comparative study on plants listed on essential oil content aimed to obtain information for their recovery as well as both scientific and economic aspect.

Since ancient, aromatic plants were used both as food flavorings, which besides the ability at taste and food preservation offers health benefits for body. For example, thyme oil was considered poor man's antibiotic because at antiseptic favorable effects, cough and asthma, lung and digestive diseases.

In modern herbal medicine and nutrition, essential oils have gained very wide use because of this cumulative effects – therapeutic, food – flavorings, at the same time.

The results indicate elevated content of essential oil of plants culture in Romania, but at the same time, some plants such as Salvia in Albania - spontaneous flora, sometimes is significantly exceed from the culture sage essential oil content in Romania.

Keywords: *essential oil, Sage, Thyme, St. John's wort*

1. Introduction

Essential oils are concentrated extracts of herbs, with a highly complex chemical composition, predominantly terpenes, chemical compounds and their oxygenated derivatives, with broad spectrum antimicrobial (natural antibiotic) and sanogenetic special effects and more popular flavors.

As the main properties of essential oils of three species of plants selected for study (Thyme, Sage and St. John's Wort) may be mentioned:

Thyme-oil has the highest index phenolic and is particularly appreciated in the diet as well as its use in phyto beneficial effects. For example, in diseases of upper respiratory tract (colds, coughs, bronchitis, emphysema, fungal, etc..) and for many diseases of the digestive (gastrointestinal atony, intestinal infections, etc..). Administered orally in phytotherapeutic preparations or food has sanogenetic special effects. Its properties make it useful in treating infections, urinary tract infections. It is also used in external use in dermatoses, joint and muscle pain, etc.. because of its antiseptic and revulsiv principles.

Sage-oil is used to flavor food and as a plant preparations in menstrual disorders, and vaginal preparations, diseases of the mouth,. In external use is used in cosmetic antiperspirants, antiseptic, antibacterial and antifungal.

St. John's Wort-oil besides its use as tea extracts in soothing, relaxing properties antidepressants, painkillers, cholagogue, choloretic, and properties of liver function and stimulating the entire digestive system. In external use is used in massage cream to improve: rheumatic pains, wounds and burns, and because of its antispasmodic.

2. Materials And Methods

Plant material used is: Thyme (Thymus vulgaris and Thymus longicaulis), Sage (Salvia officinalis) and St. John's wort (Hypericum perforatum), collected in two consecutive years, 2010 and 2011. Plants were dried in spared conditions, finely ground and extracted in the laboratory by involving water vapor essential oil, according to the methods of pharmacopoeias: European and Romanian, editions in use.

3. Results And Discussion

The graphically results compared plants from Romania and Albania.

Fig. 1 Comparative content of essential oil from plants collected in 2010 - (thyme, sage, St. John's wort) in Romania and Albania.

For plants harvested in 2010 can make the following observations:

- Thyme in Romania has a content of essential oil, double that of Albania from the spontaneous flora;
- and, Salvia in Albania, spontaneous flora has a significantly higher content of essential oil from Sage culture in Romania.

St. John's wort in both countries is low in essential oil, which is slightly increased

compared to the St. John's wort in Albania in Romania;

The big difference between the values of essential oil at Thyme in Romania and Albanian one, can be attributed at different species (*Thymus vulgaris* - Romania- *Thymus longicaulis* -Albania), the big difference in Sage essential oil obtained in favor of Albania species may be related only account climatic factors (temperature of the sunny Adriatic coast).

Fig. 2 Comparative herbal content in essential oil collected in 2011 - (thyme, sage, St. John's wort) in Albania and Romania

Plants collected for 2011, content of essential oil plants in Romania is higher than those in Albania.

-Thyme in Romania, collected in 2011, essential oil content is greater than that of Albania.

-Sage in Albania, regardless of soil that was collected (a, b) has lower values than the

Sage of Romania. In that case essential oil collected from Romania, can be explained by very high temperatures and drought year in 2011.

-Meanwhile, St. John's wort for culture in 2011 in Romania, for the same reasons essential oil content is higher than St. John's Wort in Albania.

Fig. 3 Comparative presentation of content in essential oil (thyme, sage, St. John's Wort), in Romania and Albania in two consecutive years 2010, 2011.

Comparing the values of three plants of the years 2010, 2011, Romania and Albania, is seen much better that crops in Romania, have higher values for essential oils derived from plants grown in 2011 from those in Albania. These differences are as expected and in close correlation with climatic factors, with rain from 2010 to those in 2011 with drought and high temperatures.

-Some plants from spontaneous flora - Albania, savior emerges in both years and both soils (a, b) is high in volatile oil.

Also thyme spontaneous flora - Albania has volatile oil content exceeding 0.5%, which indicates the possibility of being considered for industrial processing.

St. John's wort, in Albania which generally has low volatile oil content, and in this case indicate values 10 times higher than the plant in Romania in 2011.

4. Conclusions

The study provides useful information on both countries to exploit the possibilities of aromatic plants of wide interest, from the spontaneous and culture flora, in close correlation with economic issues.

Thus, Salvia in Albania, the spontaneous flora emerges from the other two plants in Albania with high content of essential oil, comparable to that of the sage of culture in Romania.

Note that this high is obtained without the high costs involved crops. Likewise, Thyme, containing the essential oil much smaller, about half the species in Romania (0.5% minimum content), deserves to be capitalized industry.

St. John's wort is generally has a low essential oil content, but it deserves to be considered for other molecular species composition rich with important phytotherapeutic properties.

5. References:

1. Belaiche, M.D., Paul - *Traite de Phytotherapie Et D'Aromatherapie*. Ed.Maloine, Paris, 1979.pag.38
2. Belvi, Viktor - *Aromatherapy*. Avon Books, New York 1993.pag.46-47
3. Darom, David - *Beautiful Plants of the Bible*. Palphot, Ltd., Israel.pag.145-170
4. Gattefosse, Ph.D., Rene-Maurice - *Aromatherapy*. Girardot, Paris 1937.pag.134
5. Guenther, Ernest - *The Essential Oils*. Malabar, FL 1950., pag.40
6. Mailhebiau, Philippe - *La Nouvelle Aromatherapie*. Editions, Jakin 1994.pag.33
7. Niazi, H. - *The Egyptian Prescription*. Elias Modern Press, Cairo, Egypt 1988.pag.68
8. Ryman, Daniele - *Aromatherapy, The Complete Guide to Plant and Flower Essences for Health and Beauty*. Bantam Books, New York 1993, pag.28

PROTEIN CHANGES OF CHICKEN LIGHT AND DARK MUSCLES DURING CHILLED STORAGE

K. VASSILEV *, G. IVANOV*, D. BALEV **, G. DOBREV***

Abstract: *Chicken breast and leg meat samples (representing light and dark muscles, respectively) were stored at 0-2 °C for seven days. Evaluation of the protein changes in light and dark muscles during chilled storage was performed by SDS-PAGE electrophoresis and free amino groups determination. The general aspects of chicken breast and leg meat proteolysis were associated with degradation of proteins with molecular weight about 100 kDa and 20-40 kDa, and with the appearance of new protein bands in the range of 110 to 150 kDa, 95 kDa and 30-40 kDa. Some differences in the proteolytic changes of light and dark muscles were also found. The higher pH values and free amino groups content, and lower total protein bands area of chilled stored leg (dark) muscles indicated for pronounced proteolysis associated with greater protein changes in comparison with the breast meat.*

Keywords: *protein, chicken, dark and light muscles, proteolysis, chilled storage*

1. Introduction

Chicken meat is one of the most nutritious foods. Immediately after slaughtering, chicken meat is soft, but it soon becomes very tough and unpalatable by rigor mortis. It is well known that during postmortem aging meat toughness decreases and its texture is improved. In general, chilled storage of chicken is performed at 0 to 4 °C for about 5 days. Meat flavor as well as texture is improved during storage at low temperatures. Postmortem biochemical changes transforming muscle into meat plays important role in determining the quality of meat (Sinku et al., 2003).

The most important functional components of the muscle are proteins. They determined many of the desirable physicochemical and sensory properties of muscle foods (Xiong, 1997). Muscle proteins include 15–22% of the total muscle weight and can be divided into three major groups on the basis of their solubility characteristics: stroma proteins (insoluble), sarcoplasmic proteins (water soluble) and myofibrillar proteins (salt soluble) (Vallejo-Cordoba et al., 2010). Proteolysis occurring in meat is responsible to a large extent for the development of meat flavor and tenderness,

which are the most important criteria for the consumer acceptability. The improvement of meat taste and flavor is associated with the increase in free amino acids and peptides in meats during postmortem aging (Nishimura, 1998). The increase in peptides is caused by the action of cathepsins B and L, and calpains on muscle proteins, while the increase in free amino acids is caused by the action of aminopeptidases C, H and P on the peptides during postmortem aging.

In the studies on cytoskeletal proteins the electrophoretic technique using polyacrylamide gel with SDS (SDS-PAGE) has been used so far and has facilitated the qualitative analysis of changes in meat proteins (Tomaszewska-Gras et al., 2002). The changes observed were most frequently evaluated by electrophoretic separation (Huff-Lonergan et al., 1995; Lusby et al., 1983; Paxhia & Parrish, 1988). Cytoskeletal proteins are of labile nature, they are sparingly soluble in buffers and show high molecular weight that make their examination and quantitative determination even more difficult (Tomaszewska-Gras et al., 2002).

Chicken muscles from different part of carcasses have different quantitative composition. Chicken breast muscle (light muscles) has higher

* Department of Food Preservation and Refrigeration Technology, Technological Faculty, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria. Corresponding author: Kiril Vassilev vassilevkiril@gmail.com

** Department of Meat and Fish Technology, Technological Faculty, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

*** Department of Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Technological Faculty, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

protein content (about 20%) than chicken leg muscles (dark muscles) (about 16%). In addition the stroma protein content of breast muscles is more than 2 times lower than leg muscles (Khan and Van den Berg, 1964). It is well known that, the proteolysis of different types of muscles is not universal because different cytoskeletal proteins are subject to different rates and degrees of degradation (Hwan and Bandman, 1989; Taylor et al., 1995; Morrison et al., 1998; Van Laack et al., 2000). The knowledge for the protein changes of chicken light and dark muscles during postmortem storage would be of crucial importance for the quality assurance of chilled stored poultry products.

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the protein changes of chicken light and dark muscles during chilled storage by using of SDS-PAGE.

2. Materials and methods

Meat samples: The chicken samples were delivered from local market. Breast and leg meat samples were on second day postmortem. The samples were stored at 0-2 °C for seven days. At the day of analyze meat was double minced in laboratory meat mincer.

Chemicals: Bovine serum albumin, ammonium persulphate, ninhydrin, fructose were purchased from Merck. Protein standard was delivered by Bio-Rad.

Moisture: Moisture content was determined by sample heating at 105°C to constant weight according to the standard methods (AOAC, 1980).

Ash: Ash content was determined by mineralization of meat as described in AOAC (1980).

Protein: Protein content in meat sample was determined according to the standard method of Kieldahl (AOAC, 1980) with automatic analysis on Keltec Auto, model 1030 (Tecator, Sweden).

Lipids: Determination of total lipids content was performed by method of Bligh and Dyer (1959).

pH: p H value was determined potentiometrically according to Korkeala et al.

(1986) by using of pH meter pH211 (HANNA instruments).

Extraction of muscle proteins: Extraction was conducted as described by Khan (1962), with some modifications. Meat sample with 2,5 g weight was homogenized with 48,5 cm³ PBS (phosphate buffered saline) buffer (49 mM Na₂HPO₄·7H₂O, 4,5 mM NaH₂PO₄·H₂O, KCl to obtain I=0,55). Homogenate was conditioned for 12 h in refrigerator and after that was centrifuged at 1000 g for 15 min. Protein content of supernatant was determined by Lowry method (Lowry, 1951).

Free amino groups: Free amino groups are determined as follow: 2cm³ of supernatant were transferred in test tube and 1cm³ solution of ninhydrin reagent (0,5% ninhydrin; 10% Na₂HPO₂·12H₂O; 6%KH₂PO₄; 0,3% fructose) was added. The mixture was heated in boiling water for 16 min. Sample was cooled at room temperature for 20 min and was diluted with 5 cm³ water-ethanol (3:2) solution of KIO₃ (2%). Absorbance was read at 570 nm against blank sample using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer Helios Omega, furnished with software VISIONlite (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madison, WI, USA). Concentration of free amino groups was calculated on standard curve made by leucine. Results were presented as mgLeucin/g meat.

Electrophoresis: The preparation and running of the SDS-PAGE electrophoresis were done according Laemli (1970). For separation of proteins in protein extracts 10% SDS-PAGE was used. Electrophoresis was performed with Omni PAGA Electrophoresis system and CVS10D (Cleaver Scientific Ltd.) at 20mA per gel. Gels were stained with solution of Coomassie Brilliant Blue (0,2% coomassie brilliant blue, 40% ethanol, 7% CH₃COOH) for 20 min and destained by solution without coomassie blue. Gels were scanned and analyzed with software - GelAnalyzer 2010. Band area of each protein was determined and band area of each protein/total proteins band area ratio was calculated. Molecular weight of the studied proteins was determined by using of protein standard (Bio-Rad).

Statistical analysis. Statistical analyses were carried out on the averages of the triplicate results. Data were analyzed by the analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) method with a

significant level of $P \leq 0.05$ (Draper and Smith, 1998). The Duncan's multiple comparison test (SPSS) with a significant difference set at $P \leq 0.05$ was used to compare sample means. Significant differences between means less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant (Kenward, 1987). All statistical procedures were computed using the Microsoft Excel 5.0 software.

3. Results and discussion

Physicochemical analysis: The physicochemical characteristics of studied chicken breast and leg samples are shown in Table 1. It is evident that leg and breast meat had similar moisture and ash contents.

Protein content of breast muscles was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher and fat content was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) lower than the leg muscles. The pH values of breast meat were slightly lower in comparison with leg meat. For both types of

muscles pH increased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) during chilled storage, thus indicating for proteolysis development. Greater increase of pH values was found in leg meat compared to the breast meat.

Electrophoresis: Electrophoresis of extracted salt soluble proteins from chicken breast and leg muscles showed from 18 to 24 protein bands. Fig. 1 presents electrophoregrams of salt soluble proteins of chicken breast muscles (A) and leg muscles (B) after 1st and 7th day of chilled storage (2nd and 9th day postmortem, respectively).

Identification of some typical meat proteins was performed by using of standard proteins. This way myosin, α -actinin, actin, troponin-T and tropomyosin were identified. It is evident (Fig. 1) that during postmortem storage of chicken light and dark muscles some proteins were partially or completely degraded. Significant decrease of myofibrillar proteins with molecular weight

Table 1

Chilled storage	Breast muscles (BM)					Leg muscles (LM)				
	Moisture, %	Protein, %	Lipid, %	Ash, %	pH	Moisture, %	Protein, %	Lipid, %	Ash, %	pH
1 day	72,05	19,31	1,63	1,07	6,15	68,35	15,65	8,22	0,88	6,45
7 day	71,87	19,35	1,71	1,10	6,25	68,66	15,36	7,96	0,97	6,95

Fig. 1. Electrophoregrams of salt soluble proteins of chicken: A - breast muscles (BM1 and BM7 at the 1st and 7th day of chilled storage, respectively) and B - leg muscles (LM1 and LM7 at the 1st and 7th day of chilled storage respectively).

about 100 kDa (bands 6, 7 and 8 for breast muscle and bands 7 and 8 for leg muscle) was found. For both muscle types bands 2 and 8 completely disappeared after 7 days of storage, whereas the α -actinin was partially degraded. Several differences in the protein changes of light and dark muscles were found. Results obtained showed that at the 7th day of chilled storage, protein with molecular weight 50-60 kDa (band 14) was accumulated in breast meat, whereas in thigh muscles the same protein totally disappeared. For both muscles, the proteins with molecular weight about 40 and 20-30 kDa (bands 17 and 21, respectively) decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$). The rate of degradation of these proteins in chicken light and dark muscles is different. Greater decrease of troponin-T (band

17) content was established in leg meat in comparison with breast meat. In contradiction, more rapid degradation of the protein presented with band 21 was found in breast meat. No significant changes of the main muscle proteins myosin and actin were observed in the present study (Fig. 1). That statement was in agreement with the findings of Kolczak et al. (2003).

The relative area representing band area of each protein to total protein bands area ratio was calculated for chicken breast and leg meat, respectively (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). It was established, that the total protein bands area of both muscle types decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) during chilled storage, indicating for proteolysis development.

Fig. 2 Band area of salt soluble chicken breast proteins to total band area ratio: BM1 and BM7 at the 1st and 7th day of chilled storage respectively.

Fig. 3 Band area of salt soluble chicken leg proteins to total band area ratio: LM1 and LM7 at the 1st and 7th day of chilled storage respectively

The total protein bands area of breast meat was higher compared to the leg meat (Fig. 1). Therefore, the proteolysis during postmortem storage of chicken dark muscles could be assumed as more intensive in comparison with that in the light muscles.

Four new bands were detected after 7 days of chicken breast and leg meat storage at 0-2°C. For both types of chicken muscles two of these bands were localized at the same place. First one (band 9) has molecular weight about 95 kDa, and second (band 18) about 40 kDa. Our findings were in agreement with the results obtained for calf and cow meat (Kolczak et al., 2003), and with suggestion of Taylor, et al. (1995) and Koohmaraie (1994). Greater ($P \leq 0.05$) accumulation of protein with molecular weight 95 kDa (band 9) was established in light muscles compared to the dark muscles. The rest two new bands, found after 7 days of postmortem storage were different for the both types of muscles. In the range of 110 kDa to 150 kDa appeared one new protein band 5 for the breast meat and two (bands 4 and 6) for the leg meat. Kolczak et al. (2003) also observed accumulation of new proteins with similar molecular weight in bovines aged muscles. According to these authors, the new proteins found, probably are a product of high molecular weight myofibrillar proteins hydrolysis. A new low molecular weight protein (about 15-20 kDa) (band 23) was detected in breast meat after 7 days of chilled storage, which was absent in leg meat.

Pronounced degradation of troponin-T and tropomyosin and accumulation of protein bands in range of 30 to 40 kDa during leg muscles storage was found (Fig. 3). A significant difference in protein changes between chicken light and dark muscles was observed in the range of 50 to 60 kDa (band 14). The content of this protein increased significantly in chicken breast muscles and decreased in chicken leg muscles during chilled storage. Generally the proteolytic changes of chicken dark muscles after 2th day post mortem seem to be more deeply. This is probably due to the higher activity of μ /m-calpain in *ictio tibialis* than *pectoralis superficialis* from chicken (Lee et al, 2007). Results obtained, showed that the pathway of chicken light and dark muscle proteolysis is not universal. Hwan and Bandman (1989), Morrison et al. (1998), Taylor et al. (1995) and Van Laack et al. (2000) also found that the rate and degree of protein degradation of meat proteins from different animal and muscle types are different.

Taylor et al. (1995), Koohmaraie (1994) suggested, that titin, nebulin, desmin, troponin-T and vinculin are most hydrolyzed proteins.

Free amino groups. Increasing of free amino groups is associated with accumulation of end products of proteolysis. Free amino groups content of chicken breast and leg meat is shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Free amino groups, mg Leucin/g meat		
Sample	1day	7day
BM	20,81±0,27	23,75±0,66
LM	15,74±0,52	20,04±0,24

During the 7 days chilled storage of chicken light and dark muscles, the free amino groups content significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) increased. Similar results were reported for bovine meat (Parrish et al., 1969) and chicken breast and leg meat (Khan and van den Berg, 1964). Free amino groups values reported by these authors were lower than ours, probably because of the differences in the extraction procedure. Higher increase of free amino groups content was found in chicken leg muscles (21,4%) in comparison with breast muscles (12,4%).

4. Conclusion

Proteolysis of chicken light and dark muscles had similar general aspects. Most substantial was degradation of proteins about 100 kDa and from 20 kDa to 40 kDa, and appearance of proteins in the range of 110 to 150, 95 and 30-40 kDa. Some differences in the proteolytic changes of light and dark muscles were also found. Although, the breast as well as leg high molecular weight proteins were degraded by accumulation of polypeptides about 110-150 kDa, in breast muscles is appeared one protein (band 5), whereas in leg muscles appeared two new protein bands, which were clearly indicated (bands 4 and 6). On the other hand, the accumulation of proteins with molecular weight about 95 kDa was more intensive in leg muscles than in breast muscles. The higher pH values and free amino groups content, and lower total protein bands area of chilled stored leg (dark) muscles indicated for more intensive proteolysis associated with greater protein changes in comparison with the breast (light) muscles.

References

1. AOAC (1980). *Official methods of analysis (13th ed.)*. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington D. C.
2. Bligh, E. and Dayer W. (1959). *A rapid method of total lipid extraction and purification*. Canadian Journal of Biochemistry and Physiology, 37, pp: 911 - 917.
3. Draper, N. and Smith, H. (1998). *Applied Regression Analysis*. 3rd Edition., John Wiley, New York, pp: 131-153.
4. Huff-Lonergan, E., Parrish, F. and Robson, R. (1995). *Effects of postmortem ageing time, animal age and sex on degradation of titin and nebulin in bovine longissimus muscle*. Journal of Food Science, 73, pp: 1064-1073.
5. Hwan, S. and Bandman, E. (1989). *Studies of desmin and α -actinin degradation in bovine*. Journal of Food Science, 54, pp: 1426-1430.
6. Kenward, M. (1987). *A method for comparing profiles of repeated manuscripts*. Appl. Stat., 36, pp: 296-308.
7. Khan, A. (1962). *Extraction and Fractionation of Proteins in Fresh Chicken Muscle*. Journal of Food Science, 27, pp: 430-434.
8. Khan, A. and van den Berg, L. (1964). *Some Protein Changes During Post-Mortem Tenderization in Poultry Meat*. In: Annual Meeting of the Institute of Food Technology., pp: 597-601.
9. Kolczak, T., Pospiech, E., Palka, K., Lacki, J. (2003). *Changes of myofibrillar and centrifugal drip proteins and shear force of psoas major and minor and semitendinosus muscles from calves, heifers and cows during post-mortem ageing*. Meat Science, 64, pp: 69-75.
10. Koohmaraie, M. (1994). *Muscle proteinases and meat aging*. Meat Science, 38, pp: 93-104.
11. Korkeala, H., Maeki-Petaeys, O., Alanko, T., Sorvettula, O. (1986). *Determination of pH in meat*. Meat Science 18 (2): 121 - 132.
12. Laemli, U. (1970). *Cleavage of structural proteins during the assembly of the head of bacteriophage T4*. Nature 227, pp: 680-685.
13. Lee, H., Santé-Lhoutellier, V., Vigouroux, S., Briand, Y and Briand, M. (2007). *Calpain specificity and expression in chicken tissues*. Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology - Part B: Biochemistry & Molecular Biology, 146, pp: 88-93.
14. Lowry, O., Rosebrough, N., Farr, A. and Randall, R. (1951). *Protein measurement with the folin Phenol reagent*. The Journal of Biological chemistry, 193: 265 - 175.
15. Lusby, M., Ridpath, J., Parrish, F. and Robson, R. (1983). *Effect of postmortem storage on degradation of the myofibrillar protein titin in bovine longissimus muscle*. Journal of Food Science, 48, pp: 1787-1795.
16. Morrison, H., Mielche, M. and Purlow, P. (1998). *Immunolocalisation of intermediate filament protein in porcine meat. Fibre type and muscle-specific variation during conditioning*. Meat Science, 20, pp: 91-104.
17. Nishimura, T. (1998). *Mechanism Involved in the improvement of Meat Taste during Postmortem Aging*. Food Science and Technology International Tokyo, 4, 241-249.
18. Parrish JR., F., Goll, D., Newcomb II, W. and de Lumen, B. (1969). *Molecular Properties of Post-Mortem Muscle. 7. Changes in Nonprotein Nitrogen and Free Amino Acids of Bovine Muscle*. Journal of Food Science, 34, pp: 196-202.
19. Paxhia, J. and Parrish, F. (1988). *Effect of postmortem storage on titin and nebulin in pork and poultry light and dark muscles*. Journal of Food Science, 53, pp: 1599-1601.
20. Sinku, R., Prasad, R., Pal, A., Jadhao, S. (2003). *Effect of plant proteolytic enzyme on the physico-chemical properties and lipid profile of meat from culled, desi and broiler chicken*. Asian - Australasian Journal of Animal Sciences, 16, pp: 884-888.
21. Taylor, R., Geesink, G., Thompson, V., Koohmaraie, M. and Goll, D. (1995). *Is Z-disk degradation responsible for postmortem tenderization?* Journal of Animal Science, 73, pp: 1351-1367.
22. Tomaszewska-Gras, J., Kijowski, J. and Schreurs, J. (2002). *Quantitative determination of titin and nebulin in poultry meat by SDS-PAGE with an internal standard*. Meat Science, 62, pp: 61-62.
23. Vallejo-Cordida, B., Rodriduez-Ramirez, R. and Gonzalez-Cordova, A. (2010). *Capillary electrophoresis for bovine and ostrich meat characterization*. Food Chemistry, 120, pp: 304-307.
24. Van Laack, R., Liu, C., Smith, M. and Loveday, H. (2000). *Characteristics of pale, soft, exudative broiler breast meat*. Poultry Science, 79, pp: 1057-1061.
25. Xiong YL. (1997). *Structure-function relationships of muscle proteins*. In: Damodaran S, Paraf A, editors. Food proteins and their applications. New York: Marcel Dekker pp: 341-92.

QUALITY CONTROL AND FOOD SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN THE BLUEBERRY JUICE PRODUCTION

Z. VELCHEV*, R. DINKOVA*, H. DINKOV**

Abstract: *The present paper presents the results of theoretical researches regarding the blueberry juice production and determination of optimal temperatures for pasteurization, in order to obtain a product with preserved high antioxidant capacity. The safety of the blueberry juice must be assured, in addition to the health beneficial properties appreciated by the consumer. In order to obtain such product food safety and quality management principles are met and a HACCP plan is made. A model for optimization of energy consumption during the pasteurization process is present.*

Key words: *quality management, food safety, blueberry, juice processing, HACCP, F-effect*

1. Introduction

Nowadays food safety and quality management becomes more and more important in food processing enterprises. After the first step to insure the food safety, it is necessary to prepare food with quality that can satisfy the requirements and needs of the costumers, like organoleptic and nutrition values.

Blueberries are important source of health beneficial substances. Prior (1998) reported that blueberries had the highest antioxidant activity amongst 42 evaluated fruits and vegetables. Regular intake of fruits and vegetables decreases the risk of development of certain diseases like some cancer and cardio-vascular diseases. Vaccinium species are reported to contribute to the improvement of blood vessel elasticity, urinary system infections and night vision (Szajdek and Borowska, 2008).

Several investigations have been made on health-related bioactivity of blueberries and their polyphenolic compounds. Wild blueberries are a product that is characterized by a high antioxidant capacity, as a basis for potential beneficial effect on human health, which reflects the high redox capacity of their polyphenolics, including anthocyanins. The activity of polyphenolic substances and their potential beneficial role in human health were studied and summarized by numerous authors (Crozier et al., 2009; Del Rio et al., 2010; Jager and Saaby, 2011; Spencer, 2010; Nichenametla et al., 2006).

The most popular food products based on wild blueberries are blueberry juices. However, blueberry fruits are harvested in a short period of the year (june–august) and in order to keep them available all over the year, it is necessary to preserve them by freezing or processing to juice.

However, several authors reported that traditional processing technologies can negatively affect bioactive and antioxidant properties of blueberry products. According to Brownmiller et al., (2008, 2009), thermal treatment, necessary for enzyme inactivation and product pasteurization, and storage of blueberry-based products result in significant degradation of anthocyanins. An oxidation of polyphenolics can be provoked by light (Carlsen and Stapelfeldt, 1997), oxygen (Jackman et al., 1987), enzymes (Kader et al., 1999) and products of sugars degradation (Queiroz et al., 2009).

The aim of this paper is to investigate the essential steps and related measures in preparing a safety juice with high antioxidant activity.

2. Food safety and quality management

Quality management is based on:

- Compliance with customer requirements
- Partnership with suppliers
- Development of specifications for materials and supplies
- Resource management

* Dept. of Food Preservation and Refrigeration Technology, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria. E-mail: z.velchev@gmail.com

**Dept of Applied circuit theory and Electronics, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

- Process to control measures
- Measurement, analysis and improvement

Today in EU it is obligatory to follow the HACCP approach, which relies on the application of control at all process steps from raw material to finished product and that focuses on preventing hazards that could cause food-borne illnesses. After the 5 preliminary steps HACCP: assembling HACCP team, product description, intended use, flow diagram construction and on-site confirmation; are carried out 7 basic steps (HACCP principles):

- **Principle 1.** Identify potential food safety hazards.
- **Principle 2.** Determine critical control points (CCPs).
- **Principle 3.** Establish critical limits for the identified CCPs.
- **Principle 4.** CCP monitoring system.
- **Principle 5.** Establish corrective action.
- **Principle 6.** Establish procedures for verification of the HACCP plan.
- **Principle 7.** Establish documentation and records.

The measures, applied for CCP in HACCP plan form a food safety plan.

The safety of fruit juices has become a concern due to outbreaks of food-borne illness associated with harmful bacteria in fruit juices. Berries and processed berry products generally have been considered safe from pathogenic (disease-causing) bacteria because of their high acid content. However, some strains of bacteria (e.g., *E. coli O157:H7*, *Salmonella*) can survive in acidic environments such as juice. Bacterial pathogens such as *Salmonella* and *Listeria monocytogenes* have been isolated from frozen blueberries. Viruses also can contaminate raw agricultural produce through contaminated water and employees who do not observe good personal hygiene. There are some examples of food-borne viruses, like Hepatitis A and Norwalk virus. Furthermore, *Giardia*, and *Cryptosporidium* have been found as contaminants on raw fruits. Fungi are typical postharvest spoilage agents of fruits. Yeast and molds can contaminate fresh produce. For example, *Botrytis cinerea* has been isolated from soils of berry fields and it is responsible for “gray mold” and postharvest of fruits (Samson and van Reenen-Hoekstra, 1988). As a result, processing of all juice products is subject to

Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP) requirements.

3. Thermal Treatment (Pasteurization)

Pasteurization is commonly used method of heat treatment for increasing the shelf-life and for prevention of microbial spoilage during storage. However, heat treatment affects negatively the antioxidants content. Lots of studies about the effects of pasteurization have been made, but reported by different researchers results contradict each other. Brownmiller and co-workers reported 8% and 5 % losses for non-clarified and clarified blueberry juices as compared with fresh berries at the pasteurization step (heating of bottled juice in a steam box till 90°C). Skrede et al. (2000) and Lee et al. (2002), in other hand, reported increased anthocyanin concentration after pasteurization: up to 10% for high temperature short time (HTST) pasteurization at 90°C for 90 seconds.

Therefore, a model for optimizing the pasteurization process is needed, in order to keep the product safe and preserving its quality. Molds, yeasts and non spore-forming microorganisms that can cause spoilage of the foods at $\text{pH} \leq 4.5$, which can be avoided by pasteurization at 93.3°C for 1 minute. Therefore, $F_{93,3}^{\circ\text{C}}$ be used as a unit to assess the lethal effect of the mode of sterilization of canned food with a $\text{pH} < 4.5$.

Blueberry juices are usually $\text{pH} \leq 4$ at an average pH of 3.3 fruit, which definitely puts them in a group of acidic products. In order pasteurization of such products in the flow plate, pipe or other sterilizers and subsequent aseptic filling, it is necessary to achieve sterilization effect F_0 greater than or equal to F_{min} . For products with $\text{pH} \leq 3.9$ and less, the necessary lethality $F_{93,3}^{\circ\text{C}}$ should be a notional minute (Haidutov et al., 2005).

It is that lower thermal stress, results in better exposition of beneficial properties of the product, and the main task in terms of safety in this case is to determine the temperature of heating and corresponding time of detention. Table 1 shows the exposition time depending on the selected pasteurization temperature, recalculated for necessary lethality rate at $F_{93,3}^{\circ\text{C}} = 1$ and $z = 8.8$ min.

The thermal stress is calculated according to the formula

$$C = \tau \cdot K^{(0.1T-3)}$$

Where:

K - constant in the range 1.7 to 5. We assume in this case K=3

T - pasteurization temperature [°C]

τ - exposition time, [min.]

z - thermal death time, [min]

F - F-value (amount of heat treatment imposed on a product)

Table.1. *Exposition time F-effect and temperature stress for blueberry juice*

Pasteurization Temperature [°C]	F-effect $F_{93,3^{\circ}C}$ at $z=8.8$ min	Exposition time [min]	Thermal stress C
75	0.008326	120.1007	16849.66
80	0.030806	32.46113	7888.055
82.5	0.059255	16.87612	5397.084
85	0.113977	8.773681	3692.740
87.5	0.219235	4.561324	2526.610
90	0.421697	2.371374	1728.732

4. Food Safety and Quality Plan

This work was developed for wild blueberries (the region of Velingrad) with high antioxidant activity. The juice that is produced should be eligible for microbiological, toxicological and chemical requirements for permissible contamination. In order to balance the flavor, an addition of fructose syrup is made, in order to obtain a product acceptable to consumers diabetics.

The technology for production of blueberry juice is presented in process flow diagram shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. *Flow diagram for blueberry juice processing*

An assessment of hazards, which could arise during the blueberry juice processing, should be made in order to release a safe product. Hazards, associated with juice processing are shown on Table 2.

Table 2. *Hazards, associated with blueberry juice processing*

Step	Identified Hazard			Control measures
	Biological	Physical	Chemical	
1.Receiving	- presence of pathogenic microorganisms	- supply of fruits contaminated with dirt, mud, sand, straw, glass, etc.;	- fruits obtained without valid contracts can contain residues of plant protection;	PRP Receiving control
2.Storing	- unacceptable increase in pathogens in unsuitable storage conditions - temperature and humidity; - contamination by pests, staff and production environment;	- accidental contamination from improper storage - pollution from the production environment;	- contamination with chemicals for cleaning, disinfection, maintenance of machinery and means for pest control	PRP Storage PRP Pest control PRP Personal hygiene

Step	Identified Hazard			Control measures
	Biological	Physical	Chemical	
3.Washing	- presence of the soil, dust, etc... dirt carrying pathogenic microorganisms	- presence of sand, compost of the votes for washing fruits	- presence of the residues of plant protection;	PRP Control of operations
4.Inspection	- admission of poorly washed and defective fruit importing unacceptable amount of pathogenic microorganisms	- contamination of fruit with foreign bodies from the production environment and personal belongings; - non-removal of foreign bodies of inspected fruits	- contamination with chemicals for cleaning, disinfection, maintenance of machinery and equipment	PRP Control of operations PRP Hygienic maintenance of enterprise PRP Personal hygiene
5.Smashing	- contamination of raw material from production environment and staff	- product contamination with metal shavings from the cutting device; - ingress of foreign bodies from the production environment and personal belongings	- contamination with chemicals for cleaning, disinfection, maintenance of machinery and equipment	PRP Control of operations PRP Hygienic maintenance of enterprise PRP Technological equipment support PRP Personal hygiene
6.Separation	-	- faulty filter that does not stop foreign bodies	-	PRP Technological equipment support PRP Control of operations
7.Pasteurisation	- non-complying with the thermal regimes - time, temperature, pressure, leading to survival and subsequent growth of pathogenic microorganisms; - unacceptable extension of exposition time before pasteurization, which can cause growth of bacteria, some of which can survive pasteurization; - incorrectly defined (inadequate) mode of pasteurization, allowing survival of pathogenic bacteria;	- ingress of foreign bodies from the production environment, personal	- contamination with chemicals for cleaning, disinfection, maintenance of machinery and equipment	PRP Control of operations PRP Hygienic maintenance of enterprise PRP Technological equipment support
8.Aseptic filling	- contamination with pathogenic microorganisms from the production environment and filling machine	-	- contamination with chemicals for cleaning, disinfection, maintenance of machinery and equipment	PRP Control of operations PRP Technological equipment support PRP Hygienic maintenance of enterprise
9.Storage	- unacceptable increase in pathogens in unsuitable storage conditions - temperature and humidity; - contamination by pests, staff and production environment;	-	- mechanical damage of packages that distort the seal creating preconditions for contamination by chemicals from the production environment	PRP Storage PRP Pest control PRP Personal hygiene

Table 3. Identification of critical control points and control points

Process step	CP/ CCP	Description	Prerequisite measures	Monitoring					Corrective actions
				What	Critical Limits	How	When	Who	
1. Receiving	CP 1	Presence of pesticides and heavy metals	Suppliers PRP Receiving control	Content of pesticides and heavy metals	Specification	Analysis	Before using in production	Supplier	Return of the lot, destruction of the lot
2. Storage	CP 2	Spoilage of the fruits, molds and yeast growth	PRP Storage	Temperature Time	25°C 48 h	Thermometer Warehouse diary	8 h Beginning shift	Store keeper Store keeper	Use immediately the fruits; move to another warehouse
7. Pasteurization	CCP 1	Survival of pathogens	PRP Control of operations	Pasteurization Mode	Temperature and time of pasteurization	Monitoring and archiving device	Continuously	Operator	Re-pasteurization; extension of the time for pasteurization
7. Pasteurization	CP 3	Antioxidant destruction due to high thermal treatment	PRP Control of operations	Pasteurization Mode	Temperature and time	Monitoring and archiving device	Continuously	Operator	n.a.
8. Aseptic filling	CCP 2	Contamination of the sterilized product by packaging or environment	PRP Control of operations	Package firmness	Hermetically closed package by electric resistance method	Electric current meter	1 h	Technician	Stop the machine, return the juice for re-pasteurization, adjust the machine
				<i>E. Coli</i>	ISO 7251	c= 2 n= 5 in 25g/	Every lot	Laboratory technician	Stop the machine, return the juice for re-pasteurization, adjust the machine

The identification of CP and CCP is made using the decision tree of Codex Alimentarius (Table 3).

Based on the analysis of health risks to the consumer and the quality of products, a plan for managing the quality and safety in the production of blueberry juice has been made.

5. Conclusions

The antioxidant potential of foods and beverages from blueberries depend on the processing conditions and storage. Production of blueberry juice with minimal thermal treatment can be achieved, applying temperature of 85 °C for 9 minutes. With a thermal stress of 3692.7, the harmful effect on the antioxidant capacity can be reduced. The application of HACCP plan and

assessment of biological, chemical and physical hazards revealed three control points and two critical control points, which monitored adequately will allow production of safe product with high quality.

References

1. Brownmiller, C., Howard, L. R. & Prior, R. L. (2008). *Processing and storage effects on monomeric anthocyanins, percent polymeric color, and antioxidant capacity of processed blueberry products*. Journal of Food Science 73(5), H72-H79.
2. Brownmiller, C., Howard, L. R. & Prior, R. L. (2009). *Processing and storage effects on procyanidin composition and concentration of processed blueberry products*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 57(5), 1896-1902.
3. Carlsen, C. & Stapelfeldt, H. (1997). *Light sensitivity of elderberry extract. Quantum yields for photodegradation in aqueous solution*. Food Chemistry 60(3), 383-387.
4. Crozier, A., Jaganath, I. B., & Clifford, M. N. (2009). *Dietary phenolics: chemistry, bioavailability and effects on health*. Natural product reports, 26(8), 1001-1043.
5. Del Rio, D., Borges, G., & Crozier, A. (2010). *Berry flavonoids and phenolics: bioavailability and evidence of protective effects*. The British journal of nutrition, 104 (3), S67-90.
6. Haidutov M. N. Penov, Ste. Delkinova. (2005) *Modes of sterilization, F_0 - values and their impact on safety, quality and energy consumption of canned sterilized*. Plovdiv UFT Academic edn.
7. Jacman, R. L., Yada, R. Y., Tung, M. A. , Speers, R. A. (1987). *Anthocyanins as food colorants – a review*. Journal of Food Biochemistry 11(3), 201-247.
8. Jager, A. K., & Saaby, L. (2011). *Flavonoids and the CNS*. Molecules (Basel, Switzerland), 16(2), 1471-1485.
9. Kader, F., Irmouli, M., Zitouni, N., Nicolas, J. & Metche, M. (1999). *Degradation of cyanidin 3- glucoside by caffeic acid o-quinone. Determination of the stoichiometry and characterization of the degradation products*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 47(11), 4625-4630.
10. Lee, J., Durst, R. W. & Wrolstad, R. E. (2002). *Impact of juice processing on blueberry anthocyanins and polyphenolics: comparison of two pretreatments*. Journal of Food Science 67(5), 1660-1667.
11. Nichenametla, S. N., Taruscio, T. G., Barney, D. L., & Exon, J. H. (2006). *A review of the effects and mechanisms of polyphenolics in cancer*. Critical reviews in food science and nutrition, 46(2), 161-183.
12. Prior RL, Cao G, Martin A, Sofic E, McEwen J, O'Brien C, Lischner N, Ehlenfeldt M, Kalt W, Krewer G, Mainland CM. (1998). *Antioxidant capacity as influenced by total phenolic and anthocyanin content, maturity, and variety of Vaccinium species*. J Agric Food Chem 46(7):2686-2693.
13. Samson R.A. & Van Reenen-Hoekstra E.S. (1988): *Introduction of foodborne fungi*. 3rd edn. Centraalbureau voor Schmelaturres.
14. Skrede G, Wrolstad RE, Durst RW. 2000. *Changes in anthocyanins and polyphenolics during juice processing of highbush blueberries (Vaccinium corymbosum L.)*. J Food Sci 65:357–64.
15. Spencer, J. P. (2010). *The impact of fruit flavonoids on memory and cognition*. The British journal of nutrition, 104 Suppl 3, S40-7.
16. Szajdek, A., & Borowska, E. J. (2008). *Bioactive compounds and health-promoting properties of berry fruits: a review*. Plant foods for human nutrition (Dordrecht, Netherlands), 63(4), 147-156.
17. Queiroz, F., Oliveira, C., Pinho, O. & Ferreira, I. (2009). *Degradation of anthocyanins and anthocyanidins in blueberry jams/stuffed fish*. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 57(22), 10712-10717.

STUDY THE STABILITY OF EMULSIONS PRODUCED BY COMPLETE REPLACEMENT OF MILK FAT WITH SOYBEAN OIL

R. VLASEVA, M. IVANOVA

Abstract: Analyses for the stability of emulsions of the type O/W received between soybean oil, skim milk and emulsifier glyceryl monostearate (GMS) were made. Model emulsions containing oil phase from 1 to 5%(w/w) and the use of emulsifiers in concentrations 0.2 and 0.5%(w/w) were prepared. It was found that complete replacement of milk fat with vegetable oil in order to obtain a stable emulsion can not be realized without the addition of emulsifier. Studied emulsions remain stable at a lower concentration of oil phase and a higher concentration of emulsifier.

Key words: emulsion stability, functional dairy products, vegetable oils, milk fat, ω -3 and ω -6 fatty acids;

1. Introduction

It was found that milk fat contains a high amount of saturated and significantly less unsaturated fatty acids (Bockisch, 1998). This fatty acid profile in combination with the presence of cholesterol in milk is a precondition for the development of cardiovascular diseases, obesity and others (Tamime, 2009).

It is known that vegetable oils are rich in unsaturated fatty acids, including ω -3 and ω -6 essential fatty acids (Gunstone, 2002). Rich in these acids are flaxseed oil, walnut oil, soybean oil, cotton oil and other. In addition with the increased content of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), some oils such as soybean oil, are characterized by high levels of other valuable bioactive components such as isoflavones, saponins, phytic acids, phytosterols, trypsin inhibitors, and peptides (Gunstone, 2002; Isanga & Zhang, 2008; Lawrence, 2010).

Globally it exists an increased interest in healthy nutrition and in particular in the creation of dairy products with partial or complete replacement of milk fat with liquid vegetable oil in order to improve the healthiness of the finished product (Aryana et al., 2004; Burton, 1986; Roberfroid, 2000; Siro, 2008; Westrate, 2002).

There are several ways to obtain stable emulsions - by using a high speed mixer, a colloid mill, a homogenizer with high pressure, an ultrasonic probe, an ultrasonic jet homogenizer, microfluidisation, and membrane homogenization using suitable emulsifiers (McClements, 2007).

The stability of emulsions of the type O/W is evaluated by different methods (McClements,

2007). Most used are the centrifugal test, the test for thermal resistance and the microscopic methods (McClements, 2000).

The purpose of this work is to investigate the influence of the amount of oil phase and concentration of emulsifier glyceryl monostearate (GMS) on the characteristics of stable emulsions obtained from skimmed milk and soybean oil.

2. Materials and methods

Materials

It is used an industrially glyceryl monostearate of the company Cognis, trade name Cutina® GMS V PH (Cognis, 2008), characterized by HLB 3.8. For the oil phase was used soybean oil with trade name Olitalia® which was previously characterized by the authors (Ivanova et al., 2012). For the dispersed phase is used skimmed milk with the following characteristics: milkfat 0.05% dry matter - 8.5%; total protein - 3.2%.

Equipment

The used equipment is laboratory homogenizer Polytron®PT45-80 Company Kinematika (Switzerland) with technical characteristics - 220V; 50Hz; 1600W; max 250s⁻¹, centrifuges and spectrophotometer - Camspec M107 (Kuncheva et al., 2007).

Emulsion preparation

Preparation of the emulsion is made by constant agitation and the emulsifier GMS is pre-added. The used concentrations for emulsifier are 0.2% and 0.5%(w/w), and for the oil phase - 1%, 3% and 5%(w/w). The difference in the temperatures before mixing the two phases should not exceed 5°C. In order to completely dissolve the GMS in the emulsion mixture, it is

heated at 55-60°C. The emulsion is stirred continuously until the emulsion's temperature becomes 20-22°C and the mixture is emulsified by laboratory mixer Polytron®PT45-80 at speed - 150.s⁻¹ for 5 min (Anonymus, 2008; Dłużewska et al., 2004)

Determine the emulsion stability

Emulsion stability was studied at regular periods of time by considering the degree of sedimentation, cremation, coalescence and separation of phases. For this purpose the following methods were used:

- Centrifugal test to determine the emulsion stability - 5ml of each emulsion was placed in graduated centrifuge tubes and was centrifuged for 10 min at 150.s⁻¹ without the caps. The rate of cremation was estimated by measuring the resulting layers: "oil" (top), "emulsification" in the center and "water - skimmed milk" (bottom). In some cases it is possible to observe only the first two layers. Emulsion stability S is defined by the formula: $S = [(V_o - V) / V_o] \times 100, \%$, where: S - emulsion stability,%, V_o - volume of the emulsion cm³, V - volume of separated oil phase, cm³ (Dłużewska et al., 2004; Reineccius G., 1994).

- Thermal test - 10ml of each emulsion was placed in tubes with identical diameters and caps and stored at three different temperature regimes - 4°C (refrigerator), ~ 23°C (room temperature) and 40°C (thermostat) for 24 hours.

Apparent onset of the ring shows that the emulsion is unstable and the rate of cremation is estimated in the same way as for the centrifuge test (Anonymus, 2008; Tan et al, 1988).

- Spectrophotometric method – the emulsion was diluted 1:1000 for measuring the absorbance at 400nm, 660nm and 800nm, compared to distilled water. The index of opacity (O) was determined by the value of absorbance at 660nm, and the size index (R) by the ratio of the absorbance values at 800 nm to 400nm. As a result of these measurements, the stability could be predicted (Dłużewska et al., 2004; Jayme et al., 1999).

Statistical analysis

Studies were repeated five times. The statistical analysis was done using special software - Sigma Plot 2002 and Microsoft Excel 2003 with confidence level $\alpha=0,05$.

3. Results and discussion

The results from the analysed emulsions stability were obtained by different methods of analysis.

Fig. 1 presents the results obtained by centrifugal test which influences the characteristics of the stability of emulsions as a function of concentration of emulsifier and oil phase.

Fig. 1 - Impact on the characteristics of the emulsions stability according to the amount of oil phase and emulsifier

The presented data shows that the stability of emulsions derived from soybean oil and skimmed milk depends on the concentration of oil phase and emulsifier. Stability increases with the

amount of emulsifier and decreases with increasing amount of oil phase. Moreover the results show that stable emulsions are obtained even at amount of emulsifier 0.1 (w/w) %.

Table 1
Results obtained from the temperature test, which influence the characteristics of the stability of emulsions depending on the concentration of oil phase and emulsifier.

GMS concentration, (w/w)%	Temperature of examination, °C	Separated phase, %		Emulsion, %
		Oil phase	Skimmed milk	
Emulsions with 1(w/w)% oil phase* ^a				
0 (control sample)	4	3	0	97
	23	2	0	98
	40	3	0	97
0.2	4	2	0	98
	23	2	0	98
	40	2	0	98
0.5	4	2	0	98
	23	3	0	97
	40	3	0	97
Emulsions with 3(w/w)% oil phase* ^b				
0 (control sample)	4	3.5	0	96.5
	23	2	0	98
	40	3	0	97
0.2	4	2.5	0	97.5
	23	3	0	97
	40	3	0	97
0.5	4	3	0	97
	23	2	0	98
	40	2	0	98
Emulsions with 5(w/w)% oil phase* ^c				
0 (control sample)	4	2.5	0	97.5
	23	2	0	98
	40	3	0	97
0.2	4	2.5	0	97.5
	23	3	0	97
	40	3	0	97
0.5	4	3	0	97
	23	2	0	98
	40	2	0	98

*standard deviation is calculated for a ± 0.527 ; for b ± 0.516 ; for c ± 0.535

The data presented in Table 1 shows that the emulsions preserved under different temperature regimes for 24 hours have different stability. The stability of these emulsions is highest in cold storage - 4°C. Storage at 23°C shows a decrease in the stability of the emulsions. The process of cremation is most clearly marked at the higher storage temperature - 40°C, which is associated

with reduced viscosity, which increases the rate of sedimentation and cremation. The results of this test confirmed that highly stable emulsions are obtained from 1%(w/w) oil phase and decreases with its quantity to 5%(w/w). The concentration of emulsifier shows that the emulsions are stabilized even at amount of emulsifier 0.2%(w/w).

Table 2
Results obtained from spectrophotometric test which influence the characteristics of the emulsion stability depending on the concentration of oil phase and emulsifier.

Oil phase, (w/w)%	GMS concentration, (w/w)%	Size index (R) $\lambda=800/400\text{nm}$		Index of opacity (O) $\lambda=660\text{nm}$	
		0 μ	24 μ	0 μ	24 μ
1 ^{*a}	-	0.741	0.761	0.079	0.099
	0.2	0.562	0.571	0.086	0.100
	0.5	0.558	0.562	0.106	0.128
3 ^{*b}	-	0.777	0.798	0.112	0.130
	0.2	0.697	0.705	0.137	0.157
	0.5	0.579	0.583	0.157	0.175
5 ^{*c}	-	0.917	0.923	0.136	0.167
	0.2	0.900	0.912	0.138	0.178
	0.5	0.887	0.893	0.158	0.200

*standard deviation is calculated for a ± 0.026 ; for b ± 0.015 ; for c ± 0.004

The data shows that the emulsions which were identified as most stable in the first two tests preserve this state after the spectrophotometric test was done. Index size (R) is highest in the absence of emulsifier and remains relatively similar in concentration of emulsifier 0.2%(w/w)

and 0.5%(w/w). The increasing values of opacity index (O) shows undesirable changes in the emulsion. Based on the obtained results, lowest stability, show emulsions containing the highest percentage of soybean oil and the absence of emulsifier.

4. Conclusions

1. The data obtained from these studies indicates that complete replacement of milk fat with vegetable oil and obtaining a stable emulsion can not be realized without the addition of emulsifier.
2. Emulsions containing lower amounts of oil phase show higher emulsion stability.
3. The characteristics of the emulsion stability of soybean oil and skimmed milk were statistically similar when using 0.2 (w/w)% and 0.5 (w/w)% amounts of emulsifier.

References:

1. Anonymus, (2008), Travaux pratiques intégrés de pharmacie galénique, biopharmacie et pharmacochimie, SÉANCE 1 : ÉMULSIONS, 1-38.
2. Aryana, K. J., Boeneke, C., Gough, R., (2004), Making dairy foods healthier, Louisiana Agriculture, Vol. 47, No. 3, pp. 15-17.
3. Bockisch M., (1998), Fats and Oils Handbook, 121-142, 803-809.
4. Burton, J., (1986), Novel products from milk, Agricultural Progress 1986 Vol. 61 pp. 43-45.
5. Cognis group, (2008), Certificate for Cutina® GMS V PH,1-3.
6. Dłużewska E., Panasiewicz M., Leszczyński K., (2004), Effect of gum Arabic and modified starch on stability of beverage emulsions, EJPAU 7(2), #10.
7. Gunstone F. D. (2002), Vegetable Oils in Food Technology, 18-59, 128-157, and 278-297.
8. Isanga, J., Zhang, G.N., (2008), Soybean bioactive components and their implications to health - A review, Food Reviews International, Vol. 24, Issue: 2, Pages: 252-276.
9. Ivanova M., R. Vlaseva, M. Perifanova-Nemska, P. Denev, N. Petkova, (2012), A comparative analysis, of the composition and the properties of vegetable oils with the

10. purpose to create functional dairy products, *Journal of food industry*, in press.
11. Jayme M.L., Dunstan D.E., Gee M.L., 1999. Zeta potentials of gum arabic stabilised oil in water emulsions. *Food Hydrocoll.* 13: 459-465.
12. Kuncheva M., K. Pavlova, I. Panchev, S. Dobрева, (2007), Emulsifying power of mannan and glucomannan produced by yeasts, *International Journal of Cosmetic Science*, Vol. 29, Issue 5, pages 377–384.
13. Lawrence G. D. (2010), The fats of life, *Essential Fatty Acids in Health and Disease*, 3-33.
14. McClements, D. J., (2000), *Food Emulsions, Principles, Practice and Techniques*, 191-239.
15. McClements, D. J., (2007), Critical Review of Techniques and Methodologies for Characterization of Emulsion Stability, *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 47:7, 611 – 649.
16. Reineccius G., 1994. *Source Book of Flavors*, Chapman & Hall, New York.
17. Roberfroid M.B., (2000), Concepts and strategy of functional food science: the European perspective., *Am J Clin Nutr.*, Vol. 71, No. 6, 1660S-1664s.
18. Siro I., Kapolna E., Kapolna B., Lugasi A., (2008), Functional food. Product development, marketing and consumer acceptance – a review. *Appetite.* 456-467.
19. Tamime A. Y. (2009), Dairy fats and related products, 42-45.
20. Tan C-T., Wu Holmes J., 1988. Stability of beverage flavor emulsions. *Perfumer Flavorist* 13: 23-41.
21. Westrate J.A., van Poppel G., Verschuren P.M., (2002), Functional foods, trends and future. *Brit J. Nutr.*, 88(2): 233-235.

IMAGE DATA OF CRUMB STRUCTURE OF BREAD WITH TOPINAMBUR FLOUR

A. YOVCHEV* A. LE-BAIL** A. KOLEVA* A. KRASTEVA*

Abstract: This paper presents a study on the influence of topinambur flour on bread crumb structure using an Image analysis. Selected amounts of topinambur flour (3% and 6% based on flour) and of dough hydration (55, 60 and 65 % based on flour) were added to the recipe. The addition of topinambur flour led to decrease of the mean cell area and does not influence significantly on cell area to total area ratio. No trend was observed about the influence of the topinambur flour on the cell distribution in the bread crumb. The obtained bread had higher specific volume, when topinambur flour was added to the recipe.

Keywords: image analysis, topinambur flour, bread crumb

1. Introduction

Bread, especially wheat bread, is an essential and popular element of the diet in a large part of the world, and it meets nutritional recommendations [5]. However, the use of refined flours during the last decades has led to a deficiency in dietary fibres.

Helianthus tuberosus L. (Asteraceae), a perennial plant commonly known as Jerusalem artichoke or Topinambur, contains a big amount of fructose polymers- inulin, around 80% d.b. [4]. Jerusalem artichoke tubers (with 14÷19% inulin) can be a valuable source of inulin [7]. Chemically, inulin is a linear polydisperse fructan (degree of polymerization, DP, 2÷60 or higher) consisting of fructose molecules linked by β (2-1) glycosidic bonds with, generally, a terminal glucose unit connected to the last fructose with α (1-2) bond. Fibers, and more particularly the soluble ones, like inulin and oligofructose, might help to prevent diseases like intestinal infections, colorectal cancers, obesity, cardiovascular diseases and type II diabetes [3]. Therefore, new formulae for bread enriched in fibers like inulin can be developed.

The addition of fibres is known to influence dough behaviour and bread quality [2].

The three-dimensional network formed by individual components determines the final appearance of the crumb. Image analysis is suitable to quantify crumb porosity and enables an objective assessment of the bread cut image texture [6].

The present study aimed at understanding whether the topinambur flour influences on bread crumb structure, as assessed by an Image analysis procedure.

2. Materials and methods

White flour with the following basic properties was used: 15% (wb) moisture content; 0.56 % ash content; 10.3% protein on dry matter; falling number 341 s.; alveograph parameters W= 250, Pm/L= 0.64.; farinograph water absorption 57.4%.

The topinambur flour, produced from the tubers, was supplied by "Tcharodeitsi- 07" Purvomai, Bulgaria. The basic parameters were: moisture content 6.3% on wet basis; sugars/invert 71.2%; total protein 4.32%; fat content 0.87%; energy value 305.6 kcal/ 100g. In appearance, it is pale beige-creamy colored powder, with specific sweet taste and odour.

Different recipes were observed as follows: 100g of flour; three different amounts of water were used- 55, 60 and 65g; topinambur flour- 0, 3 and 6 g; 2g of dry yeast (Pante- Puratos Group); 1.5 g of salt.

Ingredients were mixed in a SP10 spiral mixer (VMI, Montaigu, France) during 4 min at 100 rpm and 12 min at 200 rpm. The salt was added 5 minutes before the end of kneading. At the end of mixing, dough temperature was found to be around 26÷27°C. Dough was then rested for 10 min, and divided and moulded manually to obtain two dough pieces of 750g each. The dough pieces

* Dept. of Technology of Cereals, Fodder, Bread and Confectionary Products, University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria. Correspondent e- mail: yovchev.aleksandar@gmail.com

** Dept. of GEPEA, LUNAM University, Oniris, Nantes, France.

were installed in pans and were placed in a fermentation cabinet at 35°C and 90% RH (relative humidity). A dough expansion ratio of 3.5 to 4 times the initial volume was considered to terminate the end of fermentation. Baking was done in electrical oven (Sofinor) at 200°C. The end of baking was considered as the time for which the temperature reaches 95°C at the center of the bread core, followed by another fixed period of 15 min (over baking). This definition for end of baking was applied for the whole set of experiments. Temperatures in the bread core were logged with K type thermocouples (Omega, USA, 0.3mm diameter) connected to a SA 32 Data Logger (AOIP-France). After baking the breads were cooled for 1 hour at ambient temperature, before being analyzed.

Bread crumb was assessed using a procedure issued from mathematical morphology proposed to characterize visual texture in relation to particle size - Image Analysis [1]. Scanning was performed on colour flatbed scanner "HP Scanjet G4010". Scans of breads were analyzed by the image analysis software - Image J (Wright, Toronto, Canada) and then exported as a Microsoft Excel file. Breads were cut with electric slicer transversely in order to obtain slices about 10mm thickness. Three slices were used for analysis. Two experimental sets were done.

A computer-controlled bread volume measuring instrument (BVM-L500, TexVol Instruments-Sweden), which employs laser sensor, was used. At least two samples of each experimental set were measured. A calibration procedure was performed prior each test. The specific volume was calculated. Two experimental sets were done.

Statistica 6.0 (StatSoft) software was used. One-way analysis of variance was carried out followed by Tukey HSD test at $\alpha= 0.05$ confidence level.

All experiments are conducted at GEPEA, Oniris, Nantes, France.

3. Results and discussion

Image analysis parameters of bread crumb and the specific volume values of bread with different quantity of topinambur flour and of dough hydration are showed in table 1.

When the dough is kneaded with 55% water, the specific volume of the obtained bread with addition of topinambur flour (no matter 3 or 6%)

was higher than the control one. The highest value of the specific volume is for the bread with 3% topinambur flour. The crumb of bread with 6% topinambur flour had the lowest mean cell area value. The addition of topinambur flour led to decrease of the mean cell area within $0.18\div 0.22\text{ mm}^2$. The addition of topinambur flour does not influence significantly on cell area to total area ratio (CA/TA) values. This ratio expresses the proportion of cells in the measured area, i.e. relative porosity.

When the dough is kneaded with 60% water, again the highest value of the specific volume was observed for the bread with 3% topinambur flour. The results of the other two parameters are similar as previous case.

When the dough is kneaded with 65% water, the highest value of the specific volume was for the bread with 6% topinambur flour. The highest value of CA/TA ratio (0.36) was observed in the bread with 6% topinambur flour.

One can see that with increasing of the dough hydration the values of the three parameters are increasing for all samples. The bread obtained with addition of topinambur flour had higher value of the specific volume and crumb structure with cells having lower area values.

The results of the Image analysis regarding the cell distribution by area classes are shown in table 2. Around 60% of the cells in the bread crumb (with or without topinambur flour) have area lower than 1 mm^2 . The cells with area within $1.0\div 2.0\text{ mm}^2$ share about 15% of the crumb. The cells with area lower than 5.0 mm^2 are about and above 10%. No trend was observed about the influence of the topinambur flour on the cell distribution in the bread crumb.

4. Conclusion

Topinambur flour quantity does not affect the crumb relative porosity (cell area to total area ratio) significantly in any particular case of dough hydration. The mean cell area also is not affected significantly, except the case of 55% dough hydration. Topinambur flour led to increase the bread specific volume significantly for cases of 55% and 60% dough hydration, but not for 65%. Overall, the crumb structure with topinambur flour had lower values of the mean cell area and the bread had higher specific volume if compared to the control one. No negative influence of topinambur flour on the analyzed bread characteristics was observed.

Image analysis data of crumb and specific volume of bread with topinambur flour

Table 1

Indices	55% Water			60% Water			65% Water			
	SV	CA/TA	MCA	SV	CA/TA	MCA	SV	CA/TA	MCA	
	[ml/g]	-	[mm ²]	[ml/g]	-	[mm ²]	[ml/g]	-	[mm ²]	
Topinambur flour quantity	0%	3.47a	0.25a	1.62a	3.95a	0.28a	2.08a	3.99a	0.32a	2.90a
	3%	4.81b	0.25a	1.44b	5.07b	0.27a	1.73a	4.48a	0.25a	1.70a
	6%	4.03c	0.24a	1.40b	4.67b	0.28a	1.63a	5.04a	0.36a	2.10a

Within the same column, the values with different letters are significantly different (p< 0.05).

Cell distribution by area classes obtained by Image analysis of bread with topinambur flour

Table 2

Topinambur flour quantity	55% water			60% water			65% water		
	0%	3%	6%	0%	3%	6%	0%	3%	6%
Cell classes by area, [mm ²]	Cell distribution in bread crumb, [%]								
0<A<0.5	47.4	49.1	47.6	42.4	45.8	48.2	37.3	46.1	45.1
0.5≤A<1	17.5	19.3	18.5	15.4	17.3	17.1	15.9	18.2	17.0
1≤A<2	15.6	15.1	15.9	16.8	15.1	15.1	15.4	15.8	15.5
2≤A<5	13.3	11.6	12.3	15.4	14.2	12.8	16.1	13.6	13.5
5≤A<10	4.1	3.3	4.1	6.4	4.9	4.3	9.3	4.2	5.6
10≤A<20	1.4	1.3	1.3	2.7	2.0	1.8	3.6	1.7	2.4
20≤A	0.8	0.4	0.4	1.1	0.7	0.7	2.4	0.3	1.0

References

- Bertrand, D., Le Guerneve, C., Marion, D., Devaux, M., Robert, P.: *Description of the textural appearance of bread crumb by video image analysis*. Cereal Chem. 69:257-261, 1992.
- Cavella, S., Romano, A., Giancone, T., Masi, P.: *The influence of dietary fibres on bubble development during bread making*. In: Campbell, G.M., Scanlon, M.G., Pyle, D.L. (Eds.), Bubbles in Food 2- Novelty, Health and Luxury. Eagan Press, St Paul, USA, pp. 311-322, 2008.
- Franck, A.: *Prébiotiques*. In: Roberfroid, M. B., Coxam, V., Delzenne, N. (Eds.), Aliments fonctionnels. Tec & Doc, Paris, pp. 113-137, 2008.
- Kosaric, N., Wiczorek, A., Cosentino, G., Duvnjak, Z.: *Industrial processing and products from Jerusalem artichoke*. Book Series: Advances in Biochemical Engineering/ Biotechnology- Volume 32. Book Agricultural Feedstock and Waste Treatment and Engineering. Springer Berlin/Heidelber, ISBN 978-3-540-15490-7, 1-24, 1985.
- Mann, J., De Leeuw, I., Hermansen, K., Karamanos, B., Karlström, B., Katsilambros, N., Riccardi, G., Rivellese, A., Rizkalla, S., Slama, G., Toeller, M., Uusitupa, M., Vessby, B.: *Evidence-based nutritional approaches to the treatment and prevention of diabetes mellitus*. Nutrition metabolism and cardiovascular diseases 14, 373-394, 2004.
- Švec, I., Hruskova, M.: *Image data of crumb structure of bread from flour of Czech spring wheat cultivars*. Czech J. Food Sci., 22: 133-142, 2004.
- Vanloo, J., Coussement, P., Deleenheer, L., Hoebregs, H., Smits, G.: *On the presence of inulin and oligofructose as natural ingredients in the western diet*. Crit. Rev. Food Sci., Nutr. 35, 525-552, 1995.

CONTRIBUTIONS ON SEGMENTING CUSTOMERS WHO RENT CARS THROUGH ONLINE SYSTEMS AND ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF SERVICES RECEIVED

A. I. NECHITA D. M. DĂNILĂ

Abstract: *The papers presents the importance of tourism transportation services quality for different types of customers as well as an online monitoring system for assessing the quality of tourism transportation services.*

Key words: *car rental, quality, customers, online system.*

1. Introduction

Tourism has become a very competitive economic branch, led increasingly by science, information technology and innovation. Development processes in information and communications technology and the Internet, in particular, have revolutionized the industry of tourism, creating new business models, changing the structure of its distribution channels and changing all processes related to the industry and, not least, influencing suppliers of package holidays, destinations and stakeholders.

Information technology facilitates the speed and efficiency with which information is handled, the handling of information reduces costs, increases transfer speed and the extraction of information and transactions involving customers in control. Information transmitted in real time enables companies to anticipate the needs of their customers and global market developments, to face increased competition.

Exponential development of numerous technologies and software systems has generated opportunities for effective management of clients with online monitoring systems. Online monitoring systems consist of several modules including an office module, which allows editing customers' information, finalizing and confirming reservations and ultimately renting cars to customers.

2. Online customer features

The decision to purchase online or offline is not always a voluntary process, but it is often based on the consumer's previous history. Customers have certain predefined patterns of behavior when buying online and expect their online experience to be predictable, considering previous personal experience.

There are three types of potential clients or partners, depending on how they consume information on a site: fast users, selective users and conscientious users. *Fast users* scan quickly the site to see what is being sold. Generally they are very dismissive, determined and clearly know what they want before going on that site. *Selective users* spend more time than fast users on the site page. They quickly scan it, but if they come across something that attracts their attention, they stop to check the details. They are open-minded. *Conscientious users* read the entire page of the site from top to bottom. These people are usually undecided and need a lot of information and comparisons to make a decision. They are hard to persuade.

3. Assessment of car rental services, quality according to different categories of customers

A series of one-off factors resulting mainly from deep transformations generated by the phenomenon of globalization, have led in recent decades to a significant expansion of the service sector and in consequence, of the car rental service. A first important aspect of the car rental business is that, due to overall economic development, at the national and international level, this service is no longer mainly addressed only to a category of tourists, but it aims to meet the demands of all categories of customers.

In this paper we analyze the assessment of car rental quality by www.eurocars.ro customers. EuroCars is the leader in providing online car rental services in Romania, whose targeted customer segment consisted since the beginning of foreign tourists. They booked a car on EuroCars website, and their booking was then processed by an online system management.

This online system allows centralizing and analyzing customer data in order to improve service quality and increase consumer satisfaction.

Thanks to this online monitoring system, customer segmentation could be performed, considering geographic and demographic criteria, and assessing the level of quality of car rental services in Romania by tourists coming from different areas.

Looking on geographical segmentation, it can be seen from Figure 1 that most customers were from Europe.

Comparing the situation in 2010 with that of 2011, it can be seen that the number of European customers who rented a car in Romania slightly decreased in 2011 and the number of customers coming from America slightly increased.

Figure 1. Customer geographic location in percentages

In Europe, the number of customers who rented a car in Romania in 2011 decreased by 1% compared to the previous year. The main consumer countries were Romania (31%), Italy

(20%), Spain (10%), France (8%), England (7.5%) and Germany (5%).

Figure 2 shows customer preferences by types of rented car classes. A tendency for medium class cars, followed by economy cars, was observed.

Figure 2. Preference of rented car classes by European customers

The majority of people renting cars in 2011 in Romania belonged to the 31-40 years (38%) and the 21-30 years age groups (33%).

The youngest customers came from France, and the older ones from England.

An assessment of the quality of the rented cars is shown in Figure 3, with a majority of very good

and excellent assessments. Romanian customers assessed car rental quality as excellent in a majority of cases, while customers from other European countries were more balanced between the excellent and very good qualifiers.

Figure 3. Romanian car rental quality assessed by European customers

In America the number of clients coming from America in 2010 increased by 1% in 2011, for a rate of 15%. American customers came mainly from the U.S. (55%) and Canada (34%).

Their preference on rented car class is shown in Figure 4. As with European customers, American customers preferred medium class cars, followed by full size cars for US customers, and economy class by Canadian ones.

Figure 4. Tendency of rented car classes by American costumers

In terms of age, most American customers were over 40 year old.
 Assessment of the rented cars' quality

illustrated in Figure 5. As with European customers, American customers rated car quality as excellent and very good.

Figure 5. Romanian car rental quality by American customers

4. Conclusions

Consumers form their opinions about certain market offers, and their value and purchasing decisions are made according to these views. If the product does not meet performance expectations, the consumer will be dissatisfied. If this performance exceeds expectations, the customer will be very satisfied or thrilled.

Very satisfied customers are less willing to change brand. Delighted customers create an emotional affinity for a particular product or service, not just a rational preference, and this underlies customer loyalty.

To achieve customer loyalty, it is necessary to implement an online system for monitoring service quality and customer satisfaction. This system allows centralizing all customer data

obtained from the use of a service and their analysis in order to improve quality.

References

1. Dănilă D. M, Gaceu L., *Monitoring the tourism services using online instruments*, In Challenges in Higher Education and Research in 21 st Century June 2-5, 2009 Sozopol Bulgaria.p 374 – 378.
2. Dănilă D. M, Gaceu L ., *Online evaluation method for assessing the variation of the tourist number interested in car rental*, Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Braşov , • vol. 2 (51) – 2009.
3. Capatana A., Customer Relationship management, course support, *Dunarea de Jos Galati University*

COGNITIVE AND MANAGEMENT DIMENSIONS OF SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

V. GHERASIM*

Abstract: *Sustainable tourism is a strategic term to describe a specific approach to the development of tourism and aims to take all impacts, positive and negative, into account. All tourism has the potential to be more sustainable. The impact of practicing a sustainable tourism manifests itself by stimulating the keeping of a peace atmosphere, favorable to the travels in security conditions, both by developing the cultural traditions of the local community, and by favoring the creation of new jobs and the economic development of the respective area, etc. For experts and practitioners in tourism industry its very important to know the indicators and the criteria for a sustainable tourism.*

Keywords: *sustainable tourism, sustainability's tourism indicators, sustainable tourism criteria*

1. The concept of the sustainable tourism

According to United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), sustainable tourism can be defined as tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities. An agenda for more sustainable tourism needs to embrace the ability of tourism to continue as an activity in the future, ensuring that the conditions are right for this, on the one hand and the ability of society and the environment to absorb and benefit from the impacts of tourism in a sustainable way, on the other hand. This agenda can be articulated as a set of twelve aims that address economic, social and environmental impacts (UNEP, UNWTO, 2005):

- ❖ *Economic Viability* - to ensure the viability and competitiveness of tourism destinations and enterprises, so that they are able to continue to prosper and deliver benefits in the long term. Policy areas to address are: understanding the market; delivering visitor satisfaction; maintaining good trading conditions; maintaining and projecting an attractive destination; delivering business support.
- ❖ *Social Equity* - to seek a widespread and fair distribution of economic and social benefits from tourism throughout the recipient community, including improving opportunities, income and services available to the poor. Policy areas to address are:

- developing income earning opportunities for disadvantaged people; utilizing income from tourism to support social programmes.
- ❖ *Environmental Purity* - to minimize the pollution of air, water and land and the generation of waste by tourism enterprises and visitors. Policy areas to address are: promoting the use of more sustainable transport; reducing the use of environmentally damaging chemicals; avoiding the discharge of sewage to marine and river environments; minimizing waste and where necessary disposing of it with care; influencing the development of new tourism facilities.
- ❖ *Biological Diversity* - to support the conservation of natural areas, habitats and wildlife, and minimize damage to them. Policy areas to address are: working with national parks and other protected areas; promoting development and management of ecotourism; using tourism to encourage landholders to practice sustainable land management; working with private parks and reserves; minimizing damage to natural heritage from tourism; raising visitor awareness of biodiversity; raising support for conservation from visitors and enterprises.
- ❖ *Physical Integrity* - to maintain and enhance the quality of landscapes, both urban and rural, and avoid the physical and visual degradation of the environment. Policy areas to address are: ensuring that new tourism development is appropriate to local environmental conditions; minimizing the

* Faculty of Tourism Geography, Christian University "Dimitrie Cantemir", Romania, e-mail: virginiagherasim@yahoo.com

physical impact of tourist activity; maintaining high quality rural and urban landscapes as a tourism resource.

- ❖ *Local Prosperity* - to maximize the contribution of tourism to the economic prosperity of the host destination, including the proportion of visitor spending that is retained locally. Policy areas to address are: reducing leakages; strengthening links between businesses; influencing levels of visitor spending.
- ❖ *Employment Quality* - to strengthen the number and quality of local jobs created and supported by tourism, including the level of pay, conditions of service and availability to all without discrimination by gender, race, disability or in other ways. Policy areas to address are: increasing employment opportunities and the proportion of year round, full-time jobs; ensuring and enforcing labour regulations; encouraging enterprises to provide skills training programmes and career advancement; concern for the wellbeing of workers who lose their jobs.
- ❖ *Local Control* - to engage and empower local communities in planning and decision making about the management and future development of tourism in their area, in consultation with other stakeholders. Policy areas to address are: ensuring appropriate engagement and empowerment of local communities; improving the conditions for effective local decision making; addressing the specific position of indigenous and traditional communities with respect to local control.
- ❖ *Community Wellbeing* - to maintain and strengthen the quality of life in local communities, including social structures and access to resources, amenities and life support systems, avoiding any form of social degradation or exploitation. Policy areas to address are: getting the balance right in the volume, timing and location of visits; reducing congestion; careful planning and management of tourism enterprises and infrastructure; careful planning and management of tourism enterprises and infrastructure; influencing the behaviour of tourists towards local communities.
- ❖ *Visitor Fulfillment* - to provide a safe, satisfying and fulfilling experience for visitors, available to all without discrimination by gender, race, disability or in other ways. Policy areas to address are:

improving access for all; providing holiday opportunities for the economically and socially disadvantaged; maintaining a duty of care to visitors; monitoring and addressing visitor satisfaction and the quality of experience.

- ❖ *Cultural Richness* - to respect and enhance the historic heritage, authentic culture, traditions and distinctiveness of host communities. Policy areas to address are: ensuring effective management and conservation of cultural and historic heritage sites; working with communities on the sensitive presentation and promotion of culture and traditions.
- ❖ *Resource Efficiency* - to minimize the use of scarce and non-renewable resources in the development and operation of tourism facilities and services. Policy areas to address are: taking account of resource supply in the planning of tourism development and vice versa; minimizing water consumption by the tourism sector; ensuring the efficient use of land and raw materials in tourism development; promoting a reduce, reuse, recycle mentality.

Domestic tourism has intensified in most developed and newly industrialized countries and international tourist arrivals have also almost quadrupled over the past 30 years. The doubling of international tourist movements predicted for the next 15 to 20 years will bring considerable pressures. If serious harm to the very resources on which tourism depends is to be avoided, this growth must be well managed. This will require careful planning of the location and types of new development, improved environmental management practices and influencing consumption patterns. Between types of location particularly vulnerable to pressure, must be included those listed below (UNEP, UNWTO, 2005):

- ◆ Marine and coastal environments, where badly sited development, poor management of waste from resorts and cruise shipping, and general over-use by tourists leads to serious loss of amenity and natural habitats.
- ◆ Historic towns and cities and cultural heritage sites, where pressures and congestion from visitors and their traffic affect overall amenity and residents' quality of life.
- ◆ Fragile natural environments, where even quite low levels of visitation can threaten biodiversity.

2. Indicators of sustainability for tourism activities

In the context of sustainable tourism development, indicators are information sets which are formally selected for a regular use to measure changes in assets and issues that are key for the tourism development and management of a given destination.

UNWTO has been promoting the use of sustainable tourism indicators since the early 1990s, as essential instruments for policy-making planning and management processes at destinations. *The Guidebook on Indicators of*

Sustainable Development for Tourism Destinations, published in 2004, is the result of an extensive study on indicator initiatives worldwide, involving 62 experts from more than 20 countries. The publication describes over 40 major sustainability issues, ranging from the management of natural resources (waste, water, energy, etc.), to development control, satisfaction of tourists and host communities, preservation of cultural heritage, seasonality, economic leakages, or climate change, to mention just a few.

Baseline indicators considered most relevant and feasible to measure are suggested for each issue (Tabel 1).

Table 1

BASELINE ISSUE	SUGGESTED BASELINE INDICATOR(S)
1. Local Satisfaction with Tourism	◆ Local satisfaction level with tourism (questionnaire)
2. Effects of Tourism on Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Ratio of tourists to locals (average and peak period/days) ◆ % who believe that tourism has helped bring new services or infrastructure. (questionnaire-based) ◆ Number and capacity of social services available to the community (% attributable to tourism)
3. Sustaining Tourist Satisfaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Level of satisfaction by visitors (questionnaire-based) ◆ Perception of value for money (questionnaire-based) ◆ Percentage of return visitors
4. Tourism Seasonality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Tourist arrivals by month or quarter (distribution throughout the year) ◆ Occupancy rates for licensed (official) accommodation by month (peak periods relative to low season) and % of all occupancy in peak quarter or month ◆ % of business establishments open all year ◆ Number and % of tourist industry jobs which are permanent or full-year (compared to temporary jobs)
5. Economic Benefits of Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Number of local people (and ratio of men to women) employed in tourism (also ratio of tourism employment to total employment) ◆ Revenues generated by tourism as % of total revenues generated in the community
6. Energy Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Per capita consumption of energy from all sources (overall, and by tourist sector, per person day) ◆ Percentage of businesses participating in energy conservation programmes or applying energy saving policy and techniques ◆ % of energy consumption from renewable resources (at destinations, establishments)

7. Water Availability and Consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Water use: (total volume consumed and litres per tourist per day) ◆ Water saving (% reduced, recaptured or recycled)
BASELINE ISSUE	SUGGESTED BASELINE INDICATOR(S)
8. Drinking Water Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Percentage of tourism establishments with water treated to international potable standards. ◆ Frequency of water-borne diseases: number/percentage of visitors reporting water-borne illnesses during their stay
9. Sewage Treatment (Wastewater Management)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Percentage of sewage from site receiving treatment (to primary, secondary, tertiary levels) ◆ Percentage of tourism establishments (or accommodation) on treatment system(s)
10. Solid Waste Management (Garbage)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Waste volume produced by the destination (tonnes) (by month) ◆ Volume of waste recycled (m3) / Total volume of waste (m3) (specify by different types) ◆ Quantity of waste strewn in public areas (garbage counts)
11. Development Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Existence of a land use or development planning process, including tourism ◆ % of area subject to control (density, design, etc.)
12. Controlling Use Intensity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Total number of tourist arrivals (mean, monthly, peak periods) ◆ Number of tourists per square metre of the site (e.g. at beaches, attractions), per square kilometre of the destination, mean number/peak period average
<i>(Source: United Nations Environment Programme and World Tourism Organization, 2005)</i>	

3. The Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria

The criteria are part of the response of the tourism community to the global challenges of the United Nations' Millennium Development Goals. Poverty alleviation and environmental sustainability – including climate change – are the main cross-cutting issues that are addressed through the criteria.

Beginning in 2007, a coalition of 27 organizations – the *Partnership for Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria* – came together to develop the criteria. They have analyzed more than 4,500 criteria from more than 60 existing certification and other voluntary sets of criteria, and received comments from over 1500 individuals. The first version of the criteria was released in October 2008 and was publicly available for comment until April 2011. Again all comments were reviewed and addressed, to produce this version 2 of the Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria for hotels and tour operators. The next revision will take place in 2016

The Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria are administered by *The Global Sustainable Tourism Council*. As an effort to come to a common understanding of sustainable tourism, The Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria are the minimum that any tourism business should aspire to reach.

The Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria established by the *Global Sustainable Tourism Council* includes to two types of target: (a) *The Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria for Hotels and Tour Operators* – published in March 2012, after 3 years of review and public comment on version 1 (released in 2008); (b) *The Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria for Destinations* – it's the draft version available in for public consultation, for two months until June 2012 and has been designed to guide destination specialists, managers, communities, and businesses towards the steps that are needed to sustain the natural and cultural attractions that draw-in tourists, while economically benefitting the local community and businesses (Tabel 2).

Table 2

CRITERIA	SUBCRITERIA
I. Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria for Hotels and Tour Operators	
I. A. Demonstrate effective sustainable management	<p>I.A.1. The organization has implemented a long-term sustainability management system that is suitable to its reality and scope, and which addresses environmental, social, cultural, economic, quality, health and safety issues; I.A.2. The organization is in compliance with all applicable local to international legislation and regulations (including, among others, health, safety, labor and environmental aspects); I.A.3. All personnel receive periodic guidance and training regarding their roles and responsibilities with respect to environmental, social, cultural, economic, quality, health and safety issues; I.A.4. Customer satisfaction, including sustainability aspects, is measured and corrective action taken; I.A.5. Promotional materials are accurate and complete with regard to the organization and its products and services, including sustainability claims. They do not promise more than is being delivered; I.A.6. Planning, design, construction, renovation, operation and demolition of buildings and infrastructure - comply with zoning requirements and with laws related to protected areas and heritage consideration (I.A.6.1); respect the natural and cultural heritage surroundings in planning, siting, design and impact assessment (I.A.6.2); use locally appropriate sustainable practices and materials (A.6.3); provide access for persons with special needs, where appropriate (I.A.6.4); I.A.7. Land and water rights, and property acquisition are legal, comply with local communal and indigenous rights, including their free, prior and informed consent, and do not require involuntary resettlement; I.A.8. Information about and interpretation of the natural surroundings, local culture, and cultural heritage is provided to customers, as well as explaining appropriate behavior while visiting natural areas, living cultures, and cultural heritage sites.</p>
I. B. Maximize social and economic benefits to the local community and minimize negative impacts	<p>I.B.1. The organization actively supports initiatives for local infrastructure and social community development including, among others, education, training, health and sanitation; I.B.2. Local residents are given equal opportunity for employment including in management positions. All employees are equally offered regular training, experience and opportunities for advancement; I.B.3. Local services and goods are purchased and offered by the organization, following fair-trade principles; I.B.4. The organization offers the means for local small entrepreneurs to develop and sell sustainable products that are based on the area's nature, history and culture (including food and beverages, crafts, performance arts, agricultural products, etc.); I.B.5. A documented code of conduct for activities in indigenous and local communities has been developed and implemented with the collaboration and consent of the affected community; I.B.6. The organization has implemented a policy against commercial, sexual or any other form of exploitation and harassment, particularly of children, adolescents, women and minorities; I.B.7. The organization offers equal employment opportunities to women, local minorities and others, including in management positions, while restraining child labor; I.B.8. The international or national legal protection of employees is respected, and employees are paid at least a living wage; I.B.9. The activities of the organization do not jeopardize the provision of basic services, such as</p>

	<p>food, water, energy, healthcare or sanitation, to neighboring communities; I.B.10. Tourism activity does not adversely affect local access to livelihoods, including land and aquatic resource use, rights-of-way, transport and housing.</p>
<p>I. C. Maximize benefits to cultural heritage and minimize negative impacts</p>	<p>I.C.1. The organization follows established guidelines or a code of behavior for visits to culturally or historically sensitive sites, in order to minimize negative visitor impact and maximize enjoyment; I.C.2. Historical and archeological artifacts are not sold, traded or displayed, except as permitted by local to international law; I.C.3. The organization contributes to the protection and preservation of local historical, archeological, culturally and spiritually important properties and sites, and does not impede access to them by local residents; I.C.4. The organization incorporates elements of local art, architecture, or cultural heritage in its operations, design, decoration, food, or shops; while respecting the intellectual property rights of local communities</p>
<p>D. Maximize benefits to the environment and minimize negative impacts</p>	<p>I.D.1. Conserving resources - I.D.1.1. Purchasing policies favor locally appropriate and ecologically sustainable products, including building materials, capital goods, food, beverages and consumables; I.D.1.2. The purchase and use of disposable and consumable goods is measured and the organization actively seeks ways to reduce their use; I.D.1.3. Energy consumption is measured, sources are indicated, and measures are adopted to minimize overall consumption, and encourage the use of renewable energy; I.D.1.4. Water consumption is measured, sources are indicated, and measures are adopted to minimize overall consumption. Water sourcing is sustainable, and does not adversely affect environmental flows; I.D.2. Reducing pollution - I.D.2.1. Greenhouse gas emissions from all sources controlled by the organization are measured, procedures are implemented to minimize them, and offsetting remaining emissions is encouraged; I.D.2.2. The organization encourages its customers, staff and suppliers to reduce transportation-related greenhouse gas emissions; I.D.2.3. Wastewater, including gray water, is effectively treated and is only reused or released safely, with no adverse effects to the local population and the environment; I.D.2.4. Waste is measured, mechanisms are in place to reduce waste, and where reduction is not feasible, to re-use or recycle it. Any residual waste disposal has no adverse effect on the local population and the environment; I.D.2.5. The use of harmful substances, including pesticides, paints, swimming pool disinfectants, and cleaning materials, is minimized, and substituted when available, by innocuous products or processes. All storage, use, handling, and disposal of chemicals are properly managed; I.D.2.6. The organization implements practices to minimize pollution from noise, light, runoff, erosion, ozone-depleting compounds, and air, water and soil contaminants; I.D.3. Conserving biodiversity, ecosystems, and landscapes - I.D.3.1. Wildlife species are not harvested, consumed, displayed, sold, or traded, except as part of a regulated activity that ensures that their utilization is sustainable, and in compliance with local to international laws; I.D.3.2. No captive wildlife is held, except for properly regulated activities, in compliance with local to international law. Living specimens of protected and wildlife species are only kept by those authorized and suitably equipped to house and care for them humanely; I.D.3.3. The organization takes measures to avoid the introduction of invasive alien species. Native species are used for landscaping and restoration wherever feasible, particularly in natural landscapes; I.D.3.4. The organization supports and contributes to biodiversity conservation, including natural protected areas and areas of</p>

	high biodiversity value; I.D.3.5. Interactions with wildlife, taking into account cumulative impacts, do not produce adverse effects on the viability and behavior of populations in the wild. Any disturbance of natural ecosystems is minimized, rehabilitated, and there is a compensatory contribution to conservation management.
II. Global Sustainable Tourism Destinations Criteria	
II.A. Demonstrate sustainable destination management	II.A.1. Sustainable tourism strategy; II.A.2. Tourism management organization; II.A.3. Sustainable tourism monitoring; II.A.4. Tourism seasonality management; II.A.5. Climate change adaptation; II.A.6. Inventory of attraction sites; II.A.7. Design and Construction; II.A.8. Site accessibility; II.A.9. Local property rights; II.A.10. Tourist satisfaction monitoring; II.A.11. Private sector sustainability; II.A.12. Tourist safety and security; II.A.13. Crisis preparedness; II.A.14. Marketing for sustainable tourism; II.A.15. Promotional materials
II.B. Maximize social and economic benefits to the host community and minimize negative impacts	II.B.1. Economic Benefit; II.B.2. Local career opportunities; II.B.3. Public participation; II.B.4. Local satisfaction; II.B.5. Local access; II.B.6. Tourism awareness; II.B.7. Preventing exploitation; II.B.8. Local community support; II.B.9. Fair trade Principles; II.B.10. Tourism enterprise performance
II.C. Maximize benefits to communities, visitors and cultural heritage, and minimize negative impacts	II.C.1. Attraction protection; II.C.2. Visitor management plans; II.C.3. Visitor behavior and interpretation in sensitive sites; II.C.4. Cultural heritage protection; II.C.5. Site interpretation; II.C.6. Protection of community property and rights; II.C.7. Travelers Philanthropy
II.D. Maximize benefits to the environment and minimize negative impacts	II.D.1. Environmental Assessment; II.D.2. Ecosystem Protection II.D.3. Energy conservation; II.D.4. Greenhouse Gas Reduction; II.D.5. Water Conservation; II.D.6. Water Consumption; II.D.7. Surface and sea water quality; II.D.8. Waste management; II.D.9. Solid waste pollution reduction; II.D.10. Pollution reduction; II.D.11. Local transportation; II.D.12. Environmental management; II.D.13. Conserving biodiversity, ecosystems and landscapes
(Source: Processing after <i>Global Sustainable Tourism Council, 2012</i>)	

The expected uses of the *Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria* include the following: serve as basic guidelines for businesses of all sizes to become more sustainable, and help businesses choose sustainable tourism programs that fulfill these global criteria; serve as guidance for travel agencies in choosing suppliers and sustainable tourism programs; help consumers identify sound sustainable tourism programs and businesses; serve as a common denominator for information

media to recognize sustainable tourism providers; help certification and other voluntary programs ensure that their standards meet a broadly-accepted baseline; offer governmental, non-governmental, and private sector programs a starting point for developing sustainable tourism requirements; serve as basic guidelines for education and training bodies, such as hotel schools and universities.

4. The coordinates of the sustainable tourism in The Tourismogenus Sibiu-Făgăraș Passageway. Case study

The *Tourismogenus Sibiu - Făgăraș Passageway* are rich in their ecological and cultural diversity. The dimension and complexity of the urban and rural communities has an important contribution in the development of the touristic areas. The beauty of these places, the purity of the air, of the waters, of montane zones from the north of The Romanian Meridional

Carpathians, as well as plentiful cultural and the religious existing patrimony, has a rich touristic potential, which can be compared to another touristic famous zones from the country. In order to make this evaluation we used *The administratively map of The Tourismogenus Sibiu-Făgăraș Passageway* (Fig. 1) (Gherasim Virginia, 2008).

Fig. 1. Sustainability level in habitat's sectors of The Tourismogenus Sibiu-Fagaras Passageway (Source: Gherasim Virginia, 2008, p. 194)

The geographical conditions has created the environment in favour of south-transylvanian touristic habitat. On his border there are 119 settlements, grouped at present in 42 administrative formations, respectively 9 urban centre and 33 commune. From among these settlements, 52 are situated in Sibiu County and 68 in Brasov County. *The Tourismogenus Sibiu - Făgăraș Passageway* has an entire area of 1675 km². The biggest weight of the touristic potential has been remarked in the rural environment, with 51,35 % and succeed by the urban environment with 48,65 %. In *The Tourismogenus Sibiu - Făgăraș Passageway* there are the following sectors of sustainable tourism (Gherasim Virginia, 2008):

- ❖ 16 administrative formations with a percentage between 60 – 79 % tourist sustainability which are distribute 1 in the urban environment (Talmaciu) and 15 in the rural environment (e.g.: Sura Mica, Sura Mare, Selimbar, Harseni etc.);
- ❖ 17 administrative formations with a percentage between 80 – 95 % tourist sustainability which are distribute 4 in the urban environment (Sibiu, Ocna Sibiului, Cismădie, Avrig) and 13 in the rural environment (e.g.: Jina, Orlat, Cristian, Recea, Sercaia etc.);
- ❖ 6 administrative formations with a percentage over 95 % tourist sustainability which are distribute 2 in the urban

environment (Paltinis, Saliste) and 4 in the rural environment (Rasinari, Sadu, Rau Sadului, Cartisoara).

Implementing and promoting the concept of sustainable tourism are the most important actions of the experts and practitioners in tourism activities in present and in the future and it means the promoting of natural and traditional values that respect nature, as tourism attractions; the promoting this type of tourism concept and its principles at the local, regional and national level, for nature conservation; encouraging tour operators to use local services etc.

References

1. Gherasim, V., *Culoarul turismogen Sibiu-Făgăraș din perspectiva dezvoltării durabile. Concepte*, Revista Geo-Carpathica, Anul IV, Nr. 4, Editura Universității Lucian Blaga, Sibiu, 2004, p. 211 – 220.
2. Gherasim, V., *The coordinates of the sustainable tourism in the tourismogenus Sibiu – Fagaras Passageway*, in Proceeding of The First International Carpathians Tourism Conference „Sustainable Tourism Development in The Carpathians Mountains”, University of Bucharest, Faculty of Geografy & Tourism Studies and Forecast Research Center, Universitara Housing Press, 2008, p. 190 – 194.
3. * * * (2004), *Indicators of Sustainable Development for Tourism Destinations*, UNWTO (<http://sdt.unwto.org/>).
4. * * * (2005), *Making Tourism More Sustainable. A Guide for Policy Makers*, United Nations Environment Programme and World Tourism Organizatio (<http://www.unep.fr/shared/publications/>).
5. * * * (2012), *Global Sustainable Tourism Council* (<http://new.gstcouncil.org/>).

DESIGNING TIMBER HARVESTING SITE MAPS WITH LOW INVESTMENT TOOLS

STELIAN ALEXANDRU BORZ*

Abstract: A major problem in timber harvesting sites map designing is represented by high investments which sometimes are required in order to provide the tools for such design activities. Different data comes from different data sources, being more or less expensive. In this context, the present paper describes an alternative approach, by using different low cost data sources and software, combined with field surveys in order to obtain an actual state of a timber harvesting site.

Keywords: timber harvesting site, low cost, map designing, software.

1. Introduction

Designing an appropriate logging network, as well as organizing the harvesting site represent complex tasks, having as prerequisites a series of input data.

Most of the design software comes to high acquisition costs. The utilization of high accuracy data may involve supplementary acquisition costs, especially if updated data is necessary (remote-sensing imagery).

Also, most of the logging specialized economic agents from Romania are small-medium enterprises, which may not afford supplementary investments in software and data acquiring. As a consequence, the design activity is empirically realized or not realized at all. These problems may lead to higher costs regarding the applied technology, as well as decreased productivities, and wrong strategies regarding the environment protection.

There is heavy to establish the affordable limit for each logging company regarding the investments in survey and mapping software products. But, on the current market can be purchased low cost products which can be used in harvesting site mapping and organization activities.

In this context, the paper presents such tools, as well as main procedures to be applied in a current situation harvesting map realization in order to provide the base for ulterior design activities. Some of the necessary tools or data require investments, and other may be available for free use.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Mapping software

Currently, the market offers an ample range of GIS-CAD software, specialized for map design and analysis. The acquisition costs are correlated with functions and tools provided by different packages, varying from a few hundreds of dollars to several thousands. The software packages which provide complex functions and tools are usually available on prices greater than one thousand dollars.

There are also available quite complex software products, which are coming to reduced prices. For this paper purpose, there was used GlobalMapper software [1], due to its reduced acquisition cost (around 400 \$), and extended functionality. It provides the user with an ample range of functionalities such as:

- direct access to DigitalGlobe high resolution imagery for the entire world;
- easy access to WMS, OSM and TSM data sources, 3-arcsecond world SRTM terrain database, 1.5 arc-second ASTER GDEM terrain database, and color global Landsat imagery;
- supports true 3D viewing of loaded elevation and 3D vector data including datasets drapping on the 3D surfaces;
- crop, reproject, and merge/mosaic of any raster and elevation data;
- provides digitizing support for area line and point features. Also offers support for existing features editing;
- offers GPS support;

* Dept. of Forest Engineering, Forest Management and Terrestrial Measurements, Transilvania University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: stelian.borz@unitbv.ro

- provides accurate conversions between a large list of projection systems and datums;
- provides an export utility support for most currently used formats (Vector, Raster, Elevation Data);
- provides support for image rectification (geo-referencing);
- provides support for contour generation from any combination of elevation data;
- provides support for automatic triangulation and gridding of 3D point datasets;
- provides advanced drawing capabilities (area, line and points styles).

2.2. Data available from free or low cost sources

In order to realize a timber harvesting site map, a series of data and data sources may be used. Ground existing situation (terrain) can be obtained from different sources: available elevation datasets, contour maps, field surveys.

The available elevation datasets may be provided free of charge, but their resolution varies in accord with data source. By using GlobalMapper, some elevation data sources become available free of charge: SRTM terrain database 3-arcsecond accuracy [4-5] and ASTER GDEM [3] available at 1.5-arcsecond accuracy. For this paper purpose SRTM terrain database was used.

Contour maps are realized at scales of 1:5,000 – 1:10,000 for Romanian forest sector. Usually, their acquisition cost is around 10-12 Euros, and are provided in analogical format. These contour maps can be reverse engineered in order to extract vector contour layers. Some of the forest surface from Romania is already covered by using this technique.

Field surveys, especially in fragmented terrains can involve high investments in capital and time. For this paper purpose a field survey was realized in order to collect only planimetry data.

Stand and limits (boundaries) data can be provided by a wide range of data sources. If an accurate GIS is realized for certain studied area, elements regarding, compartments, as well as parcels, hydrographic and other themes can be acquired from this source. But field surveys are in order to more precise elucidate the current situation: seed zones, felling area compartments, etc.

If recent imagery is available (orthophotoplans, satellite imagery) it can be used in

delimiting necessary elements. If not, supplementary field surveys may be necessary.

For example, in this paper were used orthophotoplans provided by A.P.I.A. (Funding and Interventions in Agriculture Agency), realized in 2004-2005. The extraction of necessary elements could not be realized due the fact that supplementary interventions occurred between realization period and survey period. In order to elaborate an adequate map for current situation field surveys were realized in order to collect data for the following elements: existing logging infrastructure (tractor roads), small streams, timber harvesting site limits (boundaries), and regeneration (seed) zones location.

2.3. Field survey data collectors and download-transfer software

A wide variety of data collecting instruments is currently available on the market. High accuracy data collectors usually come to high acquisition costs, as well as the associate software. For timber harvesting site map realization, as well as for less important survey works in forest sector the high accuracy instruments are not mandatory. For this purpose, GPS receivers (navigator-mappers) may be used in conditions in which they provide an adequate accuracy.

For this paper purpose, field surveys were realized by using a Garmin GPSMap 60 CSx unit (figure 1), which was used for the above mentioned surveys [2].

Fig. 1. *Garmin GPSMap 60CSx unit*

This GPS unit has the following characteristics:

- Two dimension accuracies up to 1 meter;
- Elevation accuracies of -3...+3 m, by using a barometric altimeter;
- Easy to use-transfer the collected data;
- Reduced acquisition cost (around 400 Euros);

- Data correction possibilities by using free of charge software;
- Data transfer and analyzing software (included in package).

An important capability of this GPS unit is represented by the possibility of office designed data transferring in the unit, as well as its materialization in the field. Logging network development features, as well as any

compartments and design elements can be materialized in the field on adequate accuracies, especially by using both, on data acquisition as well as on data materializing a free of charge utility realized by Trimble – Trimble Planning Software. This application allows the definition of a station and provides the user with tools in order to estimate the better period for data acquisition and materializing.

Fig. 2. Planning the satellites visibility by using Trimble Planning Software

2.4. Methods and procedures for current situation map realization

For demonstrating the possibilities of low investments for a current situation map realization, a beech stand was chosen (figure 3), having the following characteristics:

- Silvicultural system: group shelter wood, second and final interventions;
- Composition: 100% Beech;
- Available data: orthophotoplans, SRTM 3-arcsecond elevation data, forest management map;

Additional data was collected by field surveys using GPSMap 60CSx receiver. For survey data analysis and map design facilitating, the survey data collected from field as points was coded according to elements presented in table 1.

Table 1

Surveyed element	Point code	Example
Point number	1...n	25
Property limit	LProp	6_LProp
Felling area limit	LP	2_LP
Parcel limit	LPar	
Compartment limit	LSub	5_Sub
Stream (hydrology)	Parau	21_Parau
Dry channel (hydrology)	PS	204_PS
Existent tractor road	DT	121_DT
Seed zone limit	S	220_S
Management point	B	81_B81
Intersections	INT	25_INT_DT

The realization of current situation map involved the following steps:

- Survey data transfer from GPS unit in computer. This task was realized by

- using the software provided by GPS unit manufacturer.
- Points file saving in an appropriate format;
- Points file importing into the mapping software. This task was realized by using the import tools and support of the GlobalMapper software (figure 4);

Fig. 3. 3D Perspective of the felling area by overlapping used imagery on a S.R.T.M. elevation data file with a three times vertical exaggeration index

Fig. 4. A preliminary map showing the field surveyed points

- Imagery import. An ortho-photoplan was imported by using the raster import capabilities for .ecw files;
- Elevation data import. A S.R.T.M. file was imported for the studied area;
- Map re-projection. Using the adequate tools, the coordinate system was converted from Geographic to Stereo (Romanian coordinate system);
- Necessary elements digitizing and styling (figure 5); for demonstration purposes there were used only line and point features. The area features can be utilized for specific elements, and by their creation, supplementary attributes are generated (area);
- Existing ground generation (contours generation); for the example map was chosen a contour interval (equidistance) of 5 meters (figure 6). The utilization of elevation data permits the generation of any contour interval;
- Existing conditions map finalizing (figure 7). In order to publish the existing ground situation map, several tasks are necessary, involving the map scaling as well as legend or north arrow generation. Usually the final (after design) map is published, reason for which this step was omitted.

Fig. 5. Map showing the digitized elements: 1 – Felling area limit; 2 – hydrographic network; 3 – existing logging network; - 4 – regeneration (seed) areas

3. Time and money investment

Designing an existing ground map for timber harvesting sites involves two main categories of investments: money for software and survey equipments acquiring, and time for field surveys

and office design. The total investment (money) in order to acquire the necessary equipments and software is about 900 U.S. \$ (mapping software and GPS unit including the accessory software).

Additionally investments may occur in case of accurate imagery and elevation data.

In such cases, some of the field survey operation may be omitted.

Time investment usually refers to field and office spent time. Depending on the complexity of field survey operations as well as on surveyed area and its characteristics, the spent time may vary from a couple of hours to one-two days.

Office time refers to data preparing, data downloading from survey equipment as well as design time. For the presented situation all office activities took approximately two hours, including the time spent in data acquiring.

Fig. 6. Map showing the all the elements, including contours

Fig. 7. Ready to plot map

4. Conclusions

Several conclusions may be formulated from the above presented ideas. One of them refers to the necessity of an adequate planning of the timber harvesting sites. If any of the figures 6 or 7 is analyzed, there can be observed that the existent logging network is chaotically developed. There are not respected the principles for logging network development, some portions being overcharged with tractor roads and others having no one. By taking a carefully field survey, there has been found that there are no reasons for this network development, especially in the eastern part of the felling area. Also, most of skidding operations were made uphill by taking in consideration of an existing tractor road in this area. This situation leads to supplementary operating costs, especially due the fact that the closest forest road is located at about one kilometer from the felling area.

One of the explications may reside in the fact that the logging companies (most of them) do not possess the necessary tools, equipment or training in developing best practices. Another explication may be the high acquisition costs for the necessary software tools and equipment. For the last one, a possible solution may be that presented in this paper.

References

1. ***GlobalMapper user's manual available on http://www.globalmapper.com/helpv13/Help_Main.html (accessed on 28th February 2012).
2. ***Garmin GPSMap 60 CSx mapping unit http://www.rqa.ro/products.php?id=75&subcat_id=30&cat_id=13 (accessed on 28th February, 2012).
3. ***Aster Gdem elevation data <http://www.gdem.aster.ersdac.or.jp> (accessed on 28th February 2012).
4. ***SRTM Topography http://dds.cr.usgs.gov/srtm/version2_1/Documentation/SRTM_Topo.pdf (accessed on 28th February 2012).
5. ***SRTM acquisition <http://srtm.usgs.gov/index.php> (accessed on 28th February 2012).

USAGE OF INTERNET SERVICES BY FARMERS IN HUNGARY

A. CSEH**

Abstract: *In the information society information became new factor of production in the economy. The efficiency of farming depends on whether we can possess the suitable information in the suitable time or can't. We can make better decision that what kind of product we should produce and when and where we have to buy the necessary materials. The agricultural producers are in a much weaker bargain position compared to the traders in addition the price of the products may change quickly within a few days. It is hard to decide that the product should be sold promptly after the harvest or later waiting for a favorable sales opportunity. It is important to select the suitable and authentic information channel, not only the information deficiency, but the excessive information dangerous, because this may cause indecisive situation. Nowadays we get information most quickly through the internet. This is true for the enterprises, who working in the agricultural sector. In my article I examine what main information sources are visited by farmers based on a questionnaire survey. I give a brief overview based on my study the what the farmers habit are in utilizing of internet services in foreign countries.*

Keywords: *information sources, internet usage, e-government, farming.*

1. Introduction

The aim of my research is recognition of agricultural producers' external information resources and analysing their adaptation. External information resources are vitally important for producers because farming's efficiency really depends on that adequate information are available on time. They are able to make better decision what they produce, when and whereof they purchase materials. Nowadays one of the fastest information channel is the Internet which is accessible in even more household (Várallyai & Herdon, 2010). Much of private farmers manage their farming from home so they use their already existing computer and internet in their household. Also the EU and the Hungarian government recognised that Internet may play an important role by agricultural organizations in rural areas (Herdon & Hausman, 2007), for instance, it can give a hand in connection with marketing of products or gaining new markets. These opportunities are the purposes of e-Agrarium which have already worked out in the Hungarian Information Society Strategy (IHM, 2003).

Several international publications pointed why farmers buy computers and other information technologies. The main mentioned causes were (Nuthall, 2004):

- realize higher income through the selection and consumption of much more cost effective input materials;
- spare time because of the faster and easier supplying of data to state and public administration organizations;
- easier leader tasks since faster decision, more effective planning, construction and audit processes are feasible;
- easier get in touch with market participants and governmental organizations;
- extended education curricula, more effective professional development;
- maintain competition with other farmers who have already used computers.

Because of the fact that Internet became one of the fastest and most important information channel recently, using questionnaire I show the main features of farmers' usage of Internet and frequency of farmers' attendance on state and administrative supplying of data web sites.

In this study I represent the main advance conclusion from my questionnaire. The online questionnaire was made by LimeSurvey programme. One of the main advantages of online questionnaire is that with selection of

** Faculty of Applied Economics and Rural Development, University of Debrecen e-mail: cseh@agr.unideb.hu

the adequate question type the filling is much more controlled and contains less logical contradiction so the rating of questionnaire is developed. In addition to this it is a more cost efficient solution. The questionnaire was filled by farmers or social intermediaries according to farmers' answer. The filling is based on free-will, the sample size is 279. 149 farmers responded from Hajdu Bihar county and I had got the other 130 completed questionnaires via the Internet from the other counties of Hungary.

2. Results and evaluation

2.1. Internal and external information in farming

I created a model which shows an average farmer's main information associations (Figure 1.). Usually decision is formed by several factors, working of a farm we have to allow for lot of internal information: what we can produce according to existing aptitude, where we can purchase the needful input, to whom sell our products and so on.

Figure 1. *Farmer's information relationship*

All data can be considered as external information resources which arose not in farms' internal processes, but describe enterprises' environment and have a meaning as regards decision making (Pető, 2004).

Changing of data among market participants is in connection with tender, order, delivery documentation, market survey, promotion. As regards government – because of their importance – we have to mention the law and subsidy rules, namely production won't be profitable without subsidy regarding the whole agricultural production. After submitting of different applications farmers can get their subsidy, besides from time to time different administrative notification is compulsory for government. Eventually the agricultural producer has a great number of data from their external environment which may complicate their job, so due to huge amount of data they may become indecisive.

I analysed farmers' situation – with regard to information circulation – just in connection with government because growers must be in contact with members of this sector.

A sort of information systems are at work by all members in the government sector; these systems common attribution are to collect, analyse, store, retrieve and forward information about economic participant so help the government in decision making (Heteyi, 2002). Several administrative studies have revealed that client associations are primary among areas which should be converted into electronic processes. The supplier character demands that office provides communication channel for clients in an easily practicable way.

Many experts claim, that in the operation of public administration the use of information technologies may cause fundamental change, because electronic administration may evolve. Nowadays the judgement of opportunities of e-democracy is not clear. On the one hand, one part

of people regards e-democracy as the solution of all problems on the other hand others look it as a future dream. The main argument of oppositions is that e-administration generates digital gap in the society due to its costly appliances (PC) and the relative high demand of knowledge (PC and internet use) (Buday & Tózsza, 2007).

In case of the electronic governmental services the communication pass via internet, so it is important to analyse how long private farmers have an own internet access. Figure 2. shows the measure of spread of own internet access by private farmers.

2.2. Internet usage and services

Figure 2. *Distribution of home Internet access by private farmers (n=279 year=2011)*

In the period 2004-2006 the number of own internet access increased to the full. Computer purchases within the confines of Sulinet program might have helped for this growth in the previous

period. I find it important to analyse what measure private farmers use different internet services.

Figure 3. *The measure of use of internet services by private farmers who have own Internet access (n=253 year=2011)*

Figure 3. shows that each private farmers, who has internet access, use web browser and more than 80% use e-mail during their farming as well.

Using of FTP may be lower because of the fact that by using email not just texts but files with small size can be transferred as well. The cause of low-level use of electronic mailing list may be

that farmers don't put down their name to the list, because they don't spend enough time in front of the computer in order to read each letter.

Figure 4. represents why farmers, who have own internet access, use internet browser. In the

course of browse almost everybody searches for information and at least half of them use it in reference to market research or services of e-government and bank.

Figure 4. The purpose of web browser by private farmers who have own Internet access (n=253 year=2011)

Figure 5. Attendance of web sites of government and public administration offices by Internet access (n=279 year=2011)

2.3. e-Government sources

With the help of my questionnaire, we can see (Figure 5.) what measure private farmers visit

web sites of government and public administration. Web sites of the Ministry of Rural Development, Agricultural and Rural Development Agency (ARDA) and Agricultural Administration Office (AAO) are visited because

of actual laws and regulations. On the web site of ARDA we can find training assistances related to electronically submission of the application form. On the governmental web pages located the client gate which helps for citizens to arrange their administrative, official proceedings and attain services related to them. After registration online users are able to use electronic governmental services with the help of client gate.

The cause of less attendance of Market Price Information System may be that respondents are mainly plant growers. But the system is much more important and useful those farmers who produce fresh, easily deteriorating foods (e.g. fruit, milk, egg, meat) so the measure of attendance is higher by them.

3. E-claiming of subsidies

In Hungary, one of the main important e-administration systems is the e-claiming system on subsidies for crop production. The system receives approximately 160 thousand farmers' application for financial support. From 2010 only electronic submission is possible, however, the electronic submission is difficult for the majority of farmers, because they do not have the necessary IT skills to use the system. The government provides them consultants who help in filling the application. 40% of the respondents for my survey in 2011 submitted their own grant application via the internet. The self-completion rate is growing, but the national average is below 40%, the rate can be about 10 to 15% or better. The better results of my survey might come from that fact the Internet questionnaire returned by the people who use computers routinely, so there is no problem to make their electronic application.

Figure 5. *Self-completion rate of the electronic submission % (n=279 year=2011)*

4. Client Gateway to access services

The Client Gateway is located to the government portal, which requires authentication, administrative affairs organize, and related services provide access to citizens. Now via on the Client Gateway hundreds of services are

available. It is useful that customer can access the relevance administrative documents and forms by unified method. This uniformity in the Internet Client Gateway implements a kind of one-stop shop. The portal provides the managed service 24-hour availability.

Figure 5. Using methods of Client Gateway by farmers (n=279 year=2011)

5. Conclusions

From the point of my view, e-services have great opportunities in agriculture, since the fast and effective serving of 200-300 thousand customers is attainable with the help of Internet. As regards e-services, a farm with some or with more thousand acre need the same IT infrastructure, just a computer with internet accessibility is needed. In short period the employ of experts, who could use these services instead of farmers but in favour of farmers, may help the spread of e-services. However, in long period farmers' information technology knowledge must be developed in order to increase the own use of e-services. Namely, if the farmer requires the help of external person he has to go to the office. It would be opposite to one purpose of electronic administration, because the main target of these services would be that services would available from home at any time.

References

1. Buday B. B., Tózsá I.: *E-government (E-közigazgatás)*. DE-AMTC AVK Debrecen, Hungary, 2007.
2. Herdon M., Houseman J.: ICT and Innovation in Rural Areas. *Agricultural Economics and Rural Development*, Agricultural Information Conference Proceedings. Debrecen, Hungary, 2007. pp. 1-11. ISBN:978-963-87118-7-8
3. Heteyi J.: *Information Systems of Financial institutions and Government Agencies in Hungary (Pénzüntézetek és állami Intézmények Információs Rendszerei Magyarországon)*. Computerbooks, Budapest, Hungary, 2002.
4. IHM (Informatikai és Hírközlési Minisztérium): *Hungarian Information Society Strategy: Program Guide e-Agriculture (Magyar Információs Társadalom Stratégia: eAgrárium programfüzet)*, Budapest, Hungary, 2003.
5. Nuthall P. L.: *Case studies of the interactions between farm profitability and the use of a farm computer*. Computers and Electronics in Agriculture, Volume 42, Issue 1, January 2004, Pages 19-30
6. Petó I.: *Development of external agricultural information systems (Mezőgazdasági külső információs rendszerek fejlesztése)*, 2004.
7. Várallyai L., Herdon MDigital Europe – Chance for Job in Hungary. *AGRIS on-line Papers in Economics and Informatics II:(1)*, 2010. pp. 49-56. Faculty of Economics and Management CULS Prague ISSN 1804-1930

ASPECT RELATED TO THE COLOUR ANALYSES OF VEGETABLE PRODUCTS DURING CONVECTIVE DRYING PROCESS

GACEU L.¹, TECUCEANU. E., BYELYAYEVA I.M., OPREA O. B.²

Abstract: *The paper presents the importance of convective drying of fruits and vegetables as part of the process of preserving, emphasizing the main aspects of quality changes. One important characteristic is related to the colour changes during drying. Experimental researches were done with apple, carrot and banana, and digital pictures were captured. The image analyses show the altering of the original colour of products and can be used for optimization of the drying conditions.*

Keywords: *colour analyses, convective drying, vegetables products*

1. Introduction

Drying is the oldest method of preserving foods. With the means of hot sunny weather and strong winds Arboriginals in Australia's 60 000 years old culture have already dried fruit-seed pastes for a later consumption (Russell-Smith 1997). Drying in slices form provide a better surface which improves the mass and heat transfer and makes the drying process faster. Also, the cutting and removing of the useless parts before drying saves the necessary energy for water removal so the drying process is made easier when the products are fresh. The drying process influences the textural changes and especially the loss of aroma and flavor, but also the optical and nutritional changes.

Incorrectly operated drying not only causes damage to food products, also a number of microorganisms can develop that can even create

toxic substances. The shelf-stability of dried products is determined by its moisture content and how easily it can collect water from the air. This is a typical characteristic for each type of food but can also vary with humid air. Therefore, not only drying but also appropriate packaging influences shelf-storage. During the drying process of fruits and vegetables is given a very big importance to the drying temperature and the moisture content of the final product. The temperature is main parameter which is harmful to the product quality, which is able to destroy the nutrient values and having a harmful effect on the enzymes. The final umidity indicates the storage on shelves of the product and therefore the products storage capacity. As numerous studies has to be taken in consideration in order to setup a drying temperature and a convenient time of the drying process.

Fig. 1. Apple, carrot and banana transversal sectioned and prepared for drying

¹ Transilvania University of Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism, gaceul@unitbv.ro

² Engineering and Management in Catering and Agritourism, Faculty of Food and Tourism, Transilvania University of Brasov, oana882003@yahoo.com

A lot of research has already been done in the food industry to indicate water activity for an estimation of the mold-free shelf storage ability (Chaplin 2011). The lower water activity, the better microbial, mold and yeast growth can be prohibited. Enzymatic reactions cause tissue damage after harvesting (J. 2011). A low water activity reduces the extent of the damage. Non-enzymatic browning takes place, because carbon hydrates and proteins are concentrated during drying and reactions with sugars are likely. This

causes food damage because some proteins are destroyed and substances are lost (Sturm 2010). Also browning is undesired for customer's acceptance of dried food. Browning can be prevented or slowed-down when water activity is very low. The analyses of browning need proper method for investigation for example white illumination and specific software for RGB content analyses.

Overview	Time
	0h0min0s
	2h0min0s
	4h0min0s

Fig. 2 Overview of the sliced products during the main moment of the drying process

2. Material and method

For experimental research a cabinet dryer of the size 2.20m x 1.12m x 2.30m [l x b x h] was used. The cabinet dryer consists of a chamber with a door and a movable wagon with trays. Fruits and vegetables slices were positioned on a tray of mesh fibers, in order to provide good heat transfer. The dryer has an air inlet and outlet. Fresh, cold, dry air from the outside is mixed with hot drying air inside the dryer. A ventilator conducts the airflow from outside to the electrical heat exchanger, where the air is heated up. After that, the hot, dry air is dispersed in the whole dryer. The pre-set drying temperature of 50°C was regulated with a PID regulation.

Also, as material for drying were used: apple (golden type), carrot and banana, sliced in transversal section, 2.4 mm thickness. Slices were arranged on a fiber mesh like in figure 1. Pictures were taken with a 5 MB pixels Panasonic digital camera, between 30 min during the drying process, saved on computer and analyzed after the end of process.

3. Results and discussion

After pictures were taken, they were post processed. First, they were cropped, including maximum surface from the fruit slice. Then, the pictures were analyzed in order to determine medium values for RGB contains and also 3D diagraphmes for a qualitative results of isolated area colour changing. For synthetic presentation, were selected 3 important moments: 1- the beginning of the

In fig. 2 it is shown the overviews of the slices in the main moments of the drying process.

Figure 3 shows the pictures of banana, surface 3 D plot, and the values of R, G, B, mean RGB value, and luminance= $0.299R+0.587G+0.114B$. All this data are shown for the main moments of the drying process (0h0min, 2h0min, 4h0min)

Use clear ideas, short sentences, and standard terminology. Special characters, symbols, and measure units must comply with the standards in use.

Fig. 3. Analyse of banana colour changes during drying process

Fig. 4. Analyse of apple colour changes during drying process

Fig. 5. Analyse of carrot colour changes during drying process

Similar, in figures 4 and 5 can be observed the pictures, surface 3D plot, and the specific results regarding RGB components for apple and carrot.

It can see from the surface 3D plot for banana that the uniformity of brown is increasing, but for apple the differences between max and min value of the surface became bigger. As can be observed in correspondent picture, the apple slice is browning in middle, and the center of carrot slice is turning to white. Regarding the mean values of R and G, the tendencies are to decrease, instead of B behavior, which is increasing toward the final drying stage.

4. Conclusions

The colour analyse of the sliced products is a useful method for evaluating the quality of the drying process. Using of capable software it is possible to determine the uniformity of colour, the mean, min and max RGB components. For the next research, it has to be taken in consideration: the area of product with specific colour and the distance between these area. Also, graphical representation of these parameters versus time should be useful for a proper analyze of the drying regime

References

1. Anne E Carpenter, Thouis R Jones, Michael R Lamprecht, Colin Clarke, In Han Kang, Ola Friman, David A Guertin, Joo Han Chang, Robert A Lindquist, Jason Moffat, Polina Golland, David M Sabatini: "CellProfiler: image analysis software for identifying and quantifying cell phenotypes", *Genome Biol*, pp. R100, 2006.
2. Christof Karmonik, Michele York, Robert Grossman, Ekta Kakkar, Krutina Patel, Hani Haykal, David King: "An image analysis pipeline for the semi-automated analysis of clinical fMRI images based on freely available software", *Computers in biology and medicine*, 2010.
3. Christopher A Myrick: "A low-cost system for capturing and analyzing the motion of aquatic organisms", *J N Am Benthol Soc*, pp. 101—109, 2009.
4. Clayton M Costa, Suann Yang: "Counting pollen grains using readily available, free image processing and analysis software", *Ann Bot*, pp. 1005—10, 2009.
5. Sturm B. et al. „Determination of quality changes during the production of dried food products using colorimetry.“ The 19th International Daaam Symposium, 22-25. 10 2008: 1-2.
6. Sturm, B. „Einfluss der Führung des Trocknungsprozesses auf den Trocknungsverlauf und die Produkteigenschaften empfindlicher biologischer Güter.“ Dissertation, Ger, Witzzenhausen, 2010.
7. 126. L. Gaceu – Preliminary studies regarding the infrared images uses in the drying process of agricultural products – Agricultural Informatics 2011 conference, Debrecen, 11-12 nov, pag. 53-58, ISBN: 978-615-5094-7
8. 124. Liviu GACEU, Daniel Ola, Walter W. Thierheimer, Daniel Danila – Mathematical Method of Analysis for the Quality Control of the Wheat Germs Drying using Infrared Images – Recent Research in Manufacturing Engineering, 3rd WSEAS International Conference on Manufacturing Engineering, Quality and Production System (MEQAPS '11), 11-13 april 2011, pag. 90-93, ISBN:978-960-474-294-3.
9. E. SCHUR, L. GACEU O. B. OPREA, PRELIMINARY STUDIES REGARDING THE USE OF INFRARED IMAGING IN THE DRYING PROCESS OF VEGETAL PRODUCTS, *Journal of EcoAgri Tourism*, Vol 7, no 2, 2011,pag. 114-118, Brasov, Romania

THE EFFECT OF THE USE OF DIFFERENT CATERING PRODUCTION SYSTEMS UPON THE CONTENT IN SOLUBLE VITAMINS OF FISH AND MEAT MEALS

G. PLOSCUTANU (LENCO) ^{*}, A. MAZAREL ^{}**

Abstract: *The diet is a vast source of important nutrients. These nutrients include several important classes of biomolecules such as: energy yielding components (i.e.: carbohydrates, lipids, and proteins), essential and nonessential amino acids, essential fatty acids, minerals, and vitamins. Vitamins are organic substances that must be provided by the diet either because they cannot be biosynthesized or the amount that is provided through biosynthesis is inadequate for maintaining normal metabolism. Food preparation could trigger vitamin losses, depending on the method of cooking. Operations such as refrigeration, freezing, heating and reheating (thermal regeneration) or hot holding have all been shown to lead to further loss of vitamins and other nutrients. Because each cooking system has specific advantages and disadvantages and each is most suited to a particular set of operational conditions, a careful selection of a food service system (cook-serve, cook-chill, and cook-freeze) is strategic initiative for preserving the nutritional qualities of foods. The present paper focused on the effect of different processing methods: cook-serve, cook-chill, cook-freeze on the content in soluble vitamins – thiamine, riboflavin and nicotinamide of two types of catering products: fish meal (which have the composition of salmon fillet, carp fillets and vegetables) and minced meat meal (which have the composition of pork and beef). The study revealed that processing systems involving conventional heating, freezing and multiple heating cycles influence the content in water soluble vitamins.*

Keywords: *thiamine, riboflavin, nicotinamide, catering products, cook-serve, cook-chill, cook-freeze.*

1. Introduction

Foods are a complex mixture of inorganic, organic, and biochemical compounds. Therefore, it is not surprising that heat, oxygen, and shifts in pH can affect the nutrient quality [1].

Generally three main parameters could influence the nutritional quality of food preparation: the choice of raw materials, the recipe and composition of a meal, and the preparation process. Also, meals produced on a large scale in foodservice units have to go through several preparation steps before they are served and the temperature and time history during preparation and distribution, i.e. systems like cook-chill, cook-freeze, or hot-holding, need particular attention with regard to some sensitive nutrients such as vitamins. If the main technological parameters and influencing factors (i.e.: time and temperature) are kept under control, it should not be difficult to produce, in catering units, foods with high nutritional quality.

In cook/chill/freeze food-services, substantial losses of sensitive vitamins could occur during each of the chilling, storage, and reheating cycles. Also, different reheating methods have similar effects on the amount of vitamin retention [2].

Vitamin losses can be induced by a number of factors: cooking time, temperature, and cooking method. Some vitamins are quite heat-stable, whereas others are heat-labile. Additionally, many other factors than heat can destroy some vitamins, such as: solubility in water, exposure to air (oxidation), exposure to light (UVs), storage losses etc [3].

Significance of losses depends on a given food's context in the overall diet. Of course, not all vitamin losses have detrimental consequences, since some vitamins are widely available (such as pantothenic acid). The vitamins in which some deficiencies are occasionally observed are: A, D,

^{*} Dept. of Food Science, Food Engineering and Applied Biotechnology, *Dunărea de Jos* University of Galați, Romania, e-mail: Gabriela.Lenco@ugal.ro

^{**} Dept. of Food and Tourism, *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Romania, e-mail: mazarel.adrian@unitbv.ro

E, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, folate, and B12. Of those, only thiamine, niacin, and folate would be destroyed significantly by excessive exposure to heat and/or water [4].

Recommendations to preserve vitamins include among others to avoid overly long cooking times. Therefore, choosing a cooking system, in the context of “simple” processing techniques, aim to protect the food components [4, 5].

Due to their multifunctional role, water-soluble vitamins thiamine, riboflavin and nicotiamide were chosen for this study. Particularly, thiamin’s heat lability has been well documented and it often has been used as an indicator nutrient even though the food in question may not be a significant source of the vitamin. The influence of conventional foodservice (the cook-serve system) and ready-prepared foodservice (the

cook-chill or cook-freeze methods) on the retention of the vitamins in fish and minced meat meals was determined.

2. Materials and methods

Samples preparation. Refrigerated meat and fish were purchased from a local store. The other materials were purchased from fresh market or local grocery.

After the preliminary cleaning procedures, meat and fish meals were portioned, assembled, packed, and processed according to the chosen cooking system. The fish meal portion had 267 grams and minced meat meal had 229 grams. In Table 1 are presented the structure of the meals and the specific consumption per portion.

Table 1
Meals composition and specific consumption per portion

Meals composition		Specific consumption (kg/kg)			
		„cook-serve” ^a	„cook-serve” ^b	„cook-chill”	„cook-freeze”
Fish meal	Salmon fresh file	0.7586	0,7333	0,8148	0,8800
	Carp fresh file	0.6897	0,6667	0,7407	0,8000
	Tomatoes	0.1379	0,1333	0,1481	0,1600
	Sweet cream	0.0345	0,0333	0,0370	0,0400
	Frozen carrot	0.0276	0,0267	0,0296	0,0320
	Sun flower oil	0.1034	0,1000	0,1111	0,1200
	Green parsley	0.0345	0,0333	0,0370	0,0400
	Garlic	0.0138	0,0133	0,0148	0,0160
	Black pepper	0.0007	0,0007	0,0007	0,0008
	Sweet paprika	0.0007	0,0007	0,0007	0,0008
	Salt	0.0172	0,0167	0,0185	0,0200
Minced meat meal	Deboned pork chops	0.6000	0,5802	0,6429	0,6923
	Fat pork meat	0.3333	0,3224	0,3571	0,3846
	Lean beef meat	0.2000	0,1934	0,2143	0,2308
	Red bell pepper	0.1000	0,0967	0,1071	0,1154
	Morcov congelat	0.0333	0,0322	0,0357	0,0385
	Onions	0.0667	0,0645	0,0714	0,0769
	Sun flower oil	0.1333	0,1289	0,1429	0,1538
	Green parsley	0.0133	0,0322	0,0357	0,0385
	Garlic	0.0133	0,0129	0,0143	0,0154
	Black pepper	0.0007	0,0006	0,0007	0,0008
	Sweet paprika	0.0007	0,0006	0,0007	0,0008
Salt	0.0167	0,0161	0,0179	0,0192	

a - Heat treatment performed into a convection oven

b - Heat treatment using microwaves

Before processing, products were divided in batches and coded according to: type of product, applied catering processing system, respectively the type of heating treatment (Table 2).

The specific operations for cook-serve, cook-chill, and cook-freeze systems and the working parameters are described in Table 3.

Table 2
Description of the product code and type of cooking system

Type of product	Description of products	Product code
Fish dish	Raw product	A0
	Cook-serve system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	A2
	Cook-serve system. Heat treatment using microwaves	A3
	Cook-chill system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	A4
	Cook-freeze system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	A5
Meat dish	Raw product	B0
	Cook-serve system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	B2
	Cook-serve system. Heat treatment using microwaves	B3
	Cook-chill system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	B4
	Cook-freeze system. Heat treatment performed into a convection oven	B5

Table 3
The specific operations and working parameters for cook-serve, cook-chill, and cook-freeze systems

Process operations and working parameters		Catering products									
		A0	A2	A3	A4	A5	B0	B2	B3	B4	B5
Preliminary operations	Working time/ 30 kg charge/operator (hours)	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	3
	Temperature (°C)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Thermic treatment (baking)	Temperature (°C)	-	170	-	170	170	-	220		220	220
	Time (minutes)	-	20	15	20	20	-	20	20	20	20
	Power (watts)	-	-	567	-	-	-	-	567	-	-
Cooling (from 63 to 20°C)	Time (minutes)	-	60	60	60	60	-	60	60	60	60
Cooling (from 20 to 4°C)	Time (minutes)	-	60	60	60	60	-	60	60	60	60
Freezing (from 4 to -18°C)	Time (minutes)	-	-	-	-	60	-	-	-	-	60
Storage	Time (days)	-	-	-	3	20	-	-	-	3	20
	Temperature (°C)	-	-	-	4	-18	-	-	-	4	-18
Thermal regeneration	Temperature (°C)	-	-	-	100	100	-	-	-	100	100
	Time (minutes)	-	-	-	5	10	-	-	-	5	10
	Power (watts)	-	-	-	-		-	-	-	-	-
Cooling (from 63 to 4°C)	Time (minutes)	-	-	-	60	60	-	-	-	60	60

Product analysis. All samples were analyzed from dry matter, riboflavin, thiamine, and nicotinamide content stand points. The dry matter content of the samples was determined according to the standard SR 9036/3-73 [3]. The samples, previously weighed, were dried into an oven, at $102 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, until their weight was constant. The dried matter content was expressed as grams per 100 grams of product.

Vitamins determination. Thiamine content was determined by using the fluorometric method described in AOAC (1995). Following the enzymatic hydrolyze of the samples, the resulted solution was oxidized under alkaline conditions. The dosage of the extracted tiochrome is determined by using fluorimetry [2].

The readings were made at $\lambda=365$ nm, using a UV-VIS spectro-photometer, against a blank sample (without thiamine). Also, a standard (pure oxidized thiamine), was used to determine thiamine standard spectrum. The final content in thiamine of the processed samples was expressed as mg per 100 grams dry matter [2].

The content in riboflavin was determined by using fluorometry as described in AOAC (1995). Riboflavin content was expressed as mg per 100 grams dry matter.

Nicotinamide content was determined by using the spectrophotometric AOAC method. The content in nicotinamide, calculated by using a standard curve, was expressed as mg per 100 grams dry matter [2].

Real and apparent retention coefficients. (respectively R_r and R_a) were calculated according to Berechet and Segal (2006).

3. Results and discussion

Thiamine. From the data presented in Fig. 1 it can be noticed that the thiamine content varies according to the processing system and type of meal. During processing in the cook-serve system, the reduction in thiamine content, when compared with the unprocessed products, consists in 0.68 mg/100g dry matter, for sample B2, and 0.55 mg/100g dry matter, for the sample B3. In the case of fish meals, thiamine reduction in A2 sample was 0.078 mg/100g dry matter, and 0.061 mg/100g dry matter in A3 sample (Fig. 1).

Cook-serve systems (microwaves heating and conventional oven) preserve a greater amount of thiamine; this could be observed from the high real retention coefficients, respectively 52.40 to 62.01% for fish meals and 39.14 to 49.39% for minced meat meals (Table 4).

Fig. 1. Thiamine content of cook-serve, cook-chill or cook-freeze processed meals

Table 4.
Real and apparent retention coefficients of thiamine, riboflavin and nicotinamide in fish and minced meat meals

Sample	Real and apparent retention of thiamine		Real and apparent retention of riboflavin		Real and apparent retention of nicotinamide	
	Ra (%)	Rr (%)	Ra (%)	Rr (%)	Ra (%)	Rr (%)
A0	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
A2	50.10	52.40	43.11	45.10	37.63	39.36
A3	60.45	62.01	30.58	31.37	39.68	40.70
A4	34.25	37.60	16.08	17.65	21.35	23.43
A5	29.78	32.97	12.40	13.73	19.22	21.28
B0	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
B2	37.43	39.14	38.44	40.19	49.71	51.97
B3	49.39	49.39	36.01	36.01	43.07	43.07
B4	31.06	34.54	24.58	27.33	32.73	36.40
B5	23.43	28.34	18.87	22.83	27.42	33.16

Within the cook-serve group, the existing differences in thiamine content are sole based on the type of heating. It could be observed that the microwaved group retains a higher percent of thiamine than the conventional heated group, respectively 62.01% and 49.39%, for A3 and B3 samples, and 52.40% and 39.14%, for A2 and B2 samples.

Cook-chill and cook-freeze systems are less advantageous for thiamine retention in both fish and minced meat meals.

A dramatically reduction in thiamine content corresponds to low real retention coefficients: 37.60 and 34.54% for the samples processed in cook-chill system, respectively 32.97 and 28.34% for the samples processed in cook-freeze system.

The extensive processing during cooking in these two systems such as: exposure to higher temperatures during cooking and thermal regeneration, freezing, and prolonged storage under freezing conditions seem to trigger the thiamine losses.

Riboflavin. Similar results were obtained for riboflavin (Fig. 2). A higher retention of riboflavin is associated with less extensive processing such as cook-serve system whereas cook-chill and cook-freeze systems lead to thiamine-deprived final products, as could be observed from the data presented in Table 4.

Riboflavin real retention was not favoured by microwaving, like in the case of thiamine. After conventional heating into an oven, the fish and minced meat meals were retaining a higher

percent of riboflavin than the microwaved meals. For the cook-serve system, with conventional heating, riboflavin retention was differentiated by the type of meal. Fish meals retained 45.10% of the riboflavin and minced meat meals retained only 40.19%.

Cook-chill and cook-freeze systems were depleting both fish and minced meat meals in riboflavin. A better retention of this vitamin was observed in minced meat meals when compared with the fish meals.

Based on riboflavin retention coefficients (Table 4), the efficiency of the cooking systems can be summarized as following: cook-serve > cook-chill > cook-freeze.

Nicotinamide. The content in nicotinamide is also influenced by the type of cooking system (Fig. 3).

Cook-serve system provided a better protection of nicotinamide when compared with the cook-chill and cook-freeze systems.

The differences between microwaved and conventional heated samples were not significant in terms of vitamin retention; a slightly increment in nicotinamide is observed for the meals heated by using the microwave oven.

When compared with the uncooked meals, the fish and minced meat meals retain only 30 to 50% of the initial nicotinamide content.

If for cook-serve system nicotinamide content was 6.41 to 6.76 mg/100g dry matter, for cook-chill and cook-freeze, nicotinamide content was 3.63, respectively 3.27 mg/100g dry matter.

By comparing the real retention coefficients of fish and minced meat meals presented in Table 4 it could be observed that the minced meat meals retain better the vitamin than the fish meals for all the types of cooking systems.

In the case of fish meals, cook-chill and cook-freeze versus cook-serve, determine another 50% loss in nicotinamide content.

Comparing the data presented in Tables 4 and Figures 1-3 it can be observed that the retention of vitamins depends on the processing system.

Fig. 2. Riboflavin content of cook-serve, cook-chill or cook-freeze processed meals

Figure 3. Nicotinamide content of cook-serve, cook-chill or cook-freeze processed meals

4. Conclusions

The cook-serve system proved to be superior to cook-chill and cook-freeze systems because it determines a higher percent of retained water-soluble vitamins.

Slight differences in vitamins retention were between microwaved and conventional heated samples. Thiamine and nicotinamide retention was favoured during microwaving whereas riboflavin was not protected.

In the case of cook-serve treatments, thiamine and riboflavin retention coefficients were higher

for fish meals, whereas nicotinamide retention was high for minced meat meals.

All the vitamins were highly affected by the extensive processing during cook-chill and cook-freeze. By applying the cook-chill and cook-freeze systems, the vitamins retention could be dramatically diminished. Thiamine retention in fish meals was lesser affected, with a 62.80% reduction in retention coefficient, whereas riboflavin retention coefficient was diminished with 86.27%, when compared with the uncooked meals.

References

1. Berechet, G., Segal, R.: *Influence of microwave heating on some B vitamins and minerals in traditional Romanian dishes*. In: Conference Newsletter DKMT Timișoara, Physiology (16), 2006, p. 21-25.
2. Clark, J.R.: *Improving catering productivity by using cook-chill technology*. Journals online www.emeraldinsight.com - School of Leisure and Food Management at Sheffield Hallam University, UK, 2009.
3. Kala, A., Prakash, J.: *Nutritional composition of microwave and conventionally cooked vegetables*. In: Foodservice Research International, 15(1): 1-12, 2004, www.blackwell-synergy.com/.
4. Mogos, V.T.: *Food in nutritional and metabolic diseases*. Didactic and Pedagogical Publishing House, București, 1997.
5. Zgherea, G.: *Devices and practical work of instrumental analysis*. Fourth Edition, Educational Publishing Foundation *Dunărea de Jos*, Galați, 2006.

A SURVEY ON IDENTIFICATION OF USER NEEDS REGARDING LINGUISTIC SUPPORT FOR ORGANIC.EDUNET PORTAL

M. UMIT UNAL,¹ ZEYNEL CEBECI,² M. ALI GOKCE³

Abstract: Interest in organically produced food is increasing throughout the world in response to concerns about intensive agricultural practices and their potential effect on human health as well as on the environment. However, organic agriculture in Turkey is still developing. The Organic.Edunet Web portal (www.organic-edunet.eu) is a network of learning repositories with content on organic agriculture and agroecology. In order to identify user needs for linguistic support and new features for Organic.Edunet a survey was conducted. The survey results showed that language was a barrier for the respondents when searching, discovery, retrieval, exploitation and extension of digital educational content related to organic agriculture and agroecology. New multilinguality features to be introduced to Organic.Edunet Web portal are expected to provide additional help to the users.

Key words: Organic agriculture, Digital educational resources, Organic.Edunet, Multilinguality

1. Introduction

Conventional agriculture production has been applied through heavy reliance on nonrenewable resources (mechanization, fertilizers, pesticides etc.) resulting in numerous agricultural burdens such as soil degradation, water run-off, pollution, reduced biodiversity and landscape image, escalating production costs. Public awareness of the irreversible damage done to the environment has led to calls for a more responsible attitude towards our natural heritage. Interest in organically produced food is increasing throughout the world in response to concerns about intensive agricultural practices and their potential effect on human health as well as on the environment (Roitner-Schobesberger et al, 2008)

Since the beginning of the 21st century, the development of organic farming worldwide has showed a strong growth. Almost 23 million hectares are managed organically worldwide in 2002. The total world retail sales of organic products reached US\$25 billion in 2002, which increased by 42.9% compared to 2000. Organic agriculture is practiced in almost all countries of the world, and its share of agricultural land and farms are growing. The market for organic products is growing, not only in the major markets like Europe, North America, and Japan, but also in many other countries, including developing countries (Shi-mingl and Sauerborn,

2006). However, organic agriculture in Turkey is still developing, which can be attributed to slow introduction of organic agriculture topics as a priority of academic and vocational educational systems of all levels that contribute to the education of agricultural professionals.

Large international organizations (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements), as well as non-profit associations such as the Soil Association in UK, drive their own awareness and education initiatives for the promotion of organic agriculture in countries around the world (Anon., 2012.).

2. Organic.Edunet Web portal and Its Enhancement

The Organic.Edunet Web portal (www.organic-edunet.eu) bridges together a network of learning repositories with content on organic agriculture and agroecology. The portal provides its users with a significant volume of relevant learning resources which are suitable for pupils, students, teachers and researchers, as well as general learners. The Organic.Edunet Web portal was developed in the context of the Organic.Edunet Project (<http://project.organic-edunet.eu>), in order to facilitate end-users'

¹Çukurova Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi, Gıda Mühendisliği Bölümü, Adana, Turkey, muunal@cu.edu.tr

² Çukurova Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi, Biyometri ve Genetik Anabilim Dalı, Adana, Turkey, cebcez@gmail.com

³Çukurova Üniversitesi Su ürünleri Fakültesi, Su Ürünleri Yet. Bölümü, Adana, Turkey magokce@cu.edu.tr.

search, retrieval, access and use of the content in the connected learning repositories. The Organic.Edunet Web portal acts as a multilingual front-end for accessing the available quality educational resources of the Organic.Edunet federation, since its user interface has already been translated in 17 languages and more translations are planned in the near future (Dimitropoulos et al, 2011).

Organic.Edunet offers some advantages to the users compared to traditional search engines:

- i) its focus on a specific area makes it easier for the user to find resources that are relevant to their topic of interest.
- ii) The resources are validated by experts in the field, assuring a standard quality.
- iii) A number of search mechanisms are set on the portal to facilitate retrieval of relevant resources. As a result, it provides access to high-quality, specialized content that is appropriate for educational and learning purposes and promotes its use and reuse (Dimitropoulos et al, 2011).

As of April 30th, 2011 the portal has received almost 41.000 visits from almost 30.500 unique users from 160 countries. In total, the various pages of the portal have been accessed almost 174.000 times. The resources available at the Organic.Edunet Web portal cover a wide range of topics, mainly on organic agriculture and agroecology. However, there are also resources on ecology, nature, green, biodiversity, environment, energy, food security and climate change. The resources exist in various file formats, such as documents, presentations, videos and lesson plans. (Dimitropoulos et al, 2011). There are now more than 4.000 registered portal users

As already mentioned the interface of the Organic.Edunet Web portal has already been translated into 17 languages and it has been designed in a way to facilitate usage and navigation. Furthermore it currently provides access to resources in ten (10) different languages. Since the initial content providers were members of the project's consortium, the languages of the resources were limited to the languages spoken by the members of the consortium. However, since the portal is constantly improved and new collections are networked with the existing ones, content in new languages is expected to be available through the

portal during the next months. (Dimitropoulos et al, 2011)

The portal facilitates four search mechanisms for resources (text-based search, browse through subjects, tag-based search and semantic search) as well as a search function for educational scenarios. Through these functions the diverse needs of users are being covered in the highest possible degree. Most of the resources available in the Organic.Edunet Web portal come from accomplished educational institutes, where they were used for either research or educational purposes.

Organic.Lingua (www.organic-lingua.eu) is an EU-funded project that aims to build automated multilingual services and tools that facilitate the discovery, retrieval, exploitation and extension of digital educational content related to organic agriculture and agroecology. The project will be built upon the Organic.Edunet Web portal. Although the portal is now available in 17 languages, it attracts visitors around the world. Organic.Lingua aims to capitalise on international demand for Organic.Edunet by transforming it into a truly multilingual service.

While the portal presently supports nine languages, the current process makes it translation error prone and time consuming, and misses opportunities to enhance the quality and efficiency of cross-language functions with available technology. The existing solution relies completely on human effort in translating and does not use existing linguistic resources and tools to help make resources and descriptions available in different languages or to enable cross-lingual search. Instead, the Organic.Edunet portal uses multiple languages supported by different kinds of knowledge organization schemes, namely, keywords (as expressed in metadata), ontology terms and tags provided openly by users. Resource retrieval is restricted as a consequence of the fragmentation of resource descriptions in several languages.

Applying automated language tools to translate descriptions will enable multi-lingual search for the largest part of the content base and fulfil the growing demand for a genuinely multilingual service that Organic.Edunet has identified. The Organic.Lingua project aims to achieve this end by extending the current Organic.Edunet portal to fill the abovementioned gaps in multilingual support and cross-language resource organization and search by significantly expanding its linguistic coverage. It particularly

aims at analyzing and re-engineering the service infrastructure and related facilities and business models in order to support multilingual access and use more widely and effectively. It should be noted that the linguistic limitations of Organic.Edunet are common to most current specialized information portals, and the techniques and methods devised and deployed in Organic.Lingua could be easily translated as a good practice to other similar systems.

Organic.Lingua will use the Organic.Edunet platform – and its existing transnational service and user community – to enhance the linguistic coverage of existing and planned Organic.Edunet services. In this way, it aims to cover public sector needs, by providing agricultural and environmental researchers and educators with a pan-European information, communication and collaboration platform that already involves users and operators from a wide range of countries as well as to create new business opportunities for the relevant private sector by demonstrating how a commercial system that serves a global education market can be deployed.

With regards to the Organic.Edunet Web portal, new multilinguality features are expected to provide additional help to the users who search for educational content, making it easier for them to access all resources relevant to their topic of interest. Fragmentation of knowledge as a result of language barriers is expected to be significantly reduced. To this end cross-lingual search will act as the key language technology developed. Also, the cost-effectiveness of the translation work will be increased by providing support in the process of labels, metadata and resource descriptions. Furthermore the generation of suggested descriptive metadata from text and translations is going to increase the completeness of metadata.

Through Organic.Lingua two new repositories will be connected to the portal offering access to a large set of new educational resources (i.e. French National Institute of Agricultural Research (INRA) repository (www.prodinra.inra.fr) and Cukurova University's TragLOR (<http://traglor.cu.edu.tr>)). Furthermore, existing resources will be annotated with multilingual metadata and thus they will be easily accessible from a larger number of users (i.e. Miksike's Estonian repository (www.miksike.ee) and UAH's Spanish repository (<http://oe.confolio.org>)). The VOA3R platform (Virtual Open Access Agriculture & Aquaculture

Repository - <http://www.voa3r.eu>) aims at re-using existing and mature metadata and semantics technology to deploy an advanced, community focused integrated service for the retrieval of relevant open content and data that includes explicit models of the scholarly methods and procedures used and of the practical tasks targeted by applied research (which represent a principal information need expression for practitioners).

Open access to scientific/scholarly content removes the access barriers related to copyright retention to the outcomes of research. The service will enable researchers to formulate their information needs in terms of elements of the scientific methods established in their field (variables, techniques, assessment methods, kinds of objects of interest, etc.) combined with topical descriptions as expressed in metadata. Through close cooperation with the VOA3R project, Organic.Edunet will provide access to a handful of quality open access resources, which will lead to a further upgrade of its role as a central point of access to learning resources for organic agriculture educators and learners. New content on organic agriculture will be provided by Aarhus Universitet, the Agricultural University of Athens and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Furthermore, relevant resources from Universitaet Duisburg-Essen, Universiteit Hasselt, Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet, Universidad de Alcala and the Association de Coordination Technique Agricole are also expected to be added to the portal's indexes resulting in thousands of new educational resources. (Dimitropoulos et al, 2011)

3. Methodology

In order to identify user needs for linguistic support and new features for Organic.Edunet, a survey was conducted at University of Cukurova, Adana, Turkey. A total of 33 participants took part in the survey, of which three were academics, five were postgraduate students and 25 were undergraduate students. All participants were involved in agriculture. Prior to the distribution of the questionnaire, participants were provided with functions and features of the portal and had a hands-on session so that they got familiarized with the portal.

4. Results and Discussion

The respondents use search engines for finding resources in repositories with learning content for research, study, general interest, homework, and field practice. Types of educational resources that respondents search for are texts, images, audio, presentations and lesson plans. 24% of the respondents use automatic translations services like Google translate. 78% of the respondents prefer using terms in native language when searching. 73% of the respondents try to guess English terms for text-based search. Frequency of using digital educational content in a foreign language among the subjects varied from 9% never/always to 38% rarely (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Frequency of Using Digital Educational Content in a Foreign Language

77% of the respondents prefer their native language when using Organic.Edunet. 70 % of the respondents have already tried automatic translation of the Organic.Edunet portal into native language. The preference of the respondents for translation is given in Figure 2. As can be seen from the figure, 49% of the respondents prefer using automatic translation and the translation done by Organic.Edunet.

Fig. 2. Preference for Translation

The respondents were asked questions regarding requirements and new functionalities for Organic.Edunet portal, such as automated multilingual services and tools that facilitate the discovery, retrieval, exploitation and extension of digital educational content related to organic agriculture and agroecology. They were asked to choose from the following answers: not important, slightly important, fairly important, quite important and very important. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Questions asked	Not important	Slightly important	Fairly important	Quite important	Very important
A feature that allows reporting on errors and suggestions for a translation	0	3	53	19	25
A feature for translating voluntarily educational material that you access	0	0	40	17	43
A feature to rate translated material you access and for others to rate your translations	0	6	39	42	13
A feature that would allow for automatic translation of your search terms to other languages (e.g. English)	3	3	19	28	47
A multilingual Organic Lexicon (with terminology translated to all languages and images)	3	6	19	16	56
Semantic search in your mother language	0	16	22	25	37
Translation of the tag cloud to your mother language	0	16	22	25	37
A feature to automatically translate the terms you enter in your native language	0	0	24	33	43
A feature that will allow automatic translation of actual resources e.g pdf	0	10	22	26	42
A feature that allows automatic translation of comments made by other users	0	16	34	12	38
A feature to rate the results of automatic translations	29	0	0	0	71
A procedure to suggest / request that a human translator provides a translation of specific content	26	0	0	0	74

A salient feature of the results in Table 1 is that automated multilingual services and tools that facilitate the discovery, retrieval, exploitation and extension of digital educational content

related to organic agriculture and agroecology were important for participants. Especially the following services and tools were considered to be important by participants

- ✓ A procedure to suggest / request that a human translator provides a translation of specific content
- ✓ A feature to rate the results of automatic translations
- ✓ A multilingual organic lexicon
- ✓ A feature that would allow for automatic translation of your search terms to other languages (e.g. English)

5. Conclusions

The survey results showed that language was a barrier for the respondents when searching, discovery, retrieval, exploitation and extension of digital educational content related to organic agriculture and agroecology. In this context new multilinguality features to be introduced to Organic.Edunet Web portal are expected to provide additional help to the users.

References

1. Anon.: <http://www.organic-mednet.eu/> 2012.
2. Dimitropoulos, A., Koutoumanos, A., Protonotarios, V., Stoitsis, J. and Kastrantas, K.: *Organic.Edunet: A growing network of organic and sustainable Educators*. Scientific Bulletin of ESCORENA. 2011, 3, p. 7-10.
3. Roitner-Schobesberger, B., Darnhofer, I., Somsook, S. and Vogl, C. R.: *Consumer perceptions of organic foods in Bangkok, Thailand*. Food Policy. 2008, 33, p. 112–121.
4. Shi-mingl, MA. and Joachim, J.: *Review of History and Recent Development of Organic Farming Worldwide*. Agricultural Sciences in China. 2006, 5(3), p. 169-178 .

THE PERCEPTIONS OF AGRICULTURAL GRADUATES ON THE CORRELATION OF THEIR LABOUR MARKET SITUATION AND QUALIFICATION IN HUNGARY

M. HERDON * Z. ZÖRÖG **

Abstract: *The examination of the ways how starters are provided with the opportunity of filling in a post tailored to their skills, abilities and qualification in the least complicated and smoothest way has already been a subject of several labour market studies in Europe. In Hungary finding a job has apparently become more difficult for the graduates since the 2000's. This fact has been stressed as it was actually in contrast with the expectations of the 1990's. Economic catching up was related to the expansion of higher education and it was supposed that it was easier for the graduates to find a job, which could reduce unemployment.*

The present paper examines this issue among the agricultural graduates. The respondents' evaluation of the work carried out in the higher education institution is considered together with how they could make use of their knowledge, to what extent their qualification correlates with their present job and also how fast they could find a job after taking the final exams.

Keywords: *labour market research, course start, graduate career tracking*

1. Introduction

Several researches stressed the fact at the turn of the millennium that obtaining a degree did not automatically mean an entry to the labour market. Nowadays a degree is not enough as the competencies developed must meet labour market expectations. The survey of the graduate supervision system provides an excellent opportunity to examine whether the students entering the labour market from higher education institutions meet these expectations.

According to FALUSNÉ (2001) a degree can reduce structural unemployment but can hardly reduce global unemployment. The hardship of finding a job for the graduates is a recent phenomenon in Hungary although it has been discernible in the developed countries for several decades. In the United States, for example, a degree gained at a renowned institution cannot guarantee a job immediately or a job tailored to the qualification.

STADLER (2003) considers that in the European Union a depreciation of degrees can be observed and consequently smaller salaries can be earned. On the basis of the research of FURLONG (2003) 60% of those aged between 16 and 29 feel underemployed.

Studies have been written on the stages and mechanism of the transition from higher education to labour market. For example, TEICHLER (1999) does not consider the transition from higher education to labour market to be an independent period. He concludes that there are several transitions in an individual's life that correlate with the entry to the labour market. When carrying out the thorough analysis, other turning points of the life of the people concerned and their other transitions such as leaving home must also be considered. Other researches do not examine transition within such broad framework. Instead, they concentrate on emphasising the improvement in the level of education and approaching the system of education to employers' expectations. It can be agreed as it is a logical expectation of the labour market players for the educational system.

According to SCHOMBURG-TEICHLER (2006) it must be considered that the short transitory period is not necessarily favourable for a starter. In the case of a short placement, i.e. the graduate is incorporated by the labour market too quickly; chances are that they are not convinced to have selected the most suitable job.

Not only in Hungary but also in Europe as a result of expansion and the accumulating number of undergraduates thus the increased labour

*Faculty of Applied Economics and Rural Development University of Debrecen e-mail:herdon@agr.unideb.hu

**Faculty of Applied Economics Károly Róbert College e-mail: zzorog@karolyrobert.hu

supply may lead to the fact that it takes fresh graduates considerably longer time to find employment. As a result of the decrease of the relative higher salary newcomers to the labour market receive lower payments than what used to be the norm, they also find suitable employment with greater difficulty, and the number of unemployed amongst graduates is on the increase (GALASI, 2002).

It must be noted though that the smooth entrance into the labour market does not depend solely on labour supply and demand, it also depends on the social trends of the transitional

period, also on the habits and practices that help or hinder solving situations. Therefore the structure of the transition and the structure of the labour market must also be taken into consideration when examining the length of the transition.

Another international career tracking examination (CHEERS) points out unambiguously that the employment tendencies of higher education graduates greatly vary (Schomburg, H.–Teichler, U. 2006). Table 1 shows the differences in the length of the transitory period by nations.

Table 1

The percentage of graduates finding a job within and over 3 months, by nations

Country	within 3 months (%)	over 3 months (%)
Italian	48	52
Spanish	44	56
French	55	45
Austrian	67	33
Danish	64	36
Dutch	72	28
English	73	27
Finnish	77	23
Swedish	80	20
Norwegian	81	19
Czech	84	16
Japanese	37	63
Hungarian	71	29

According to the table the Czech and the Norwegian graduates were able to find employment quickly in the greatest percentage. The examination revealed that Spanish undergraduates needed almost a whole year to find a job but the table also supports the fact that compared to the graduates of other nations less Spanish graduates were able to find employment quickly – that is within 3 months.

As indicated by the research the favourable Norwegian and Czech results were facilitated by the fact that higher than the average number of graduates started looking for employment prior to graduation. The commencement of job search showed a varied picture in different countries, which naturally indicates the wide-ranging length of the transition period. In some countries the early start of job search is acceptable. For instance in Japan those who cannot get hold of a decent job offer during the last semester are thought to be “losers”. They therefore start looking for employment even six months prior to graduation. This trend does not characterise

European students as only one third of British undergraduates start looking for a job three

months before graduation. In France more than half of the undergraduates in their last year, while in Spain and Italy about fifty percent of undergraduates wait until they have earned their degree and only after that do they make the first steps to secure a job for themselves.

Similarly to Czech and Norwegian students Hungarian undergraduates also find a job relatively quickly. This speed might prove important not only from the point of view of a decreasing unemployment rate but according to YORKE (2006) it may also function as the indicator of the usefulness of the gained knowledge.

2. The target group and method of the research

In our research secondary data collection took place within the framework of which the 2010 database of the National Graduate Research was analysed. In the national survey the examined

population included the students who graduated from the bachelor and master courses as well as supplementary courses of accredited higher education institutions in 2007 in all programmes and financing forms.

The method of sampling was simple and accidental. The sample consists of institutional subsamples for which the list of graduates was made available by the institutions that are

involved in the research. The sample includes almost the entire range of institutions of the programmes concerned. As nearly the entire list of graduates was provided, the accidental sample represents the national breakdown of graduates of a certain programme. Table 2 illustrates the size of the population and the number of questionnaires of the sample.

Table 2

The size of the population and sample per scientific branch

Programme	Number of graduates	Size of the sample
Agriculture	3879	383
Human sciences	7592	536
Economics	11504	733
Informatics	3293	278
Law and administration	3714	308
Technical	6016	569
Medical and health care	3195	355
Pedagogy	3732	581
Social sciences	4499	516
Sciences	1958	249
Total	49382	4508

The examination comprises ten areas of education (programmes) as the four smallest areas (sports science, defence and army, arts and applied arts) were not regarded due to their lowest number of graduate population. Data was recorded by the interviewer network of Median Public Opinion and Market Research Institute and GFK Hungária Market Research Institute in May-June 2010.

3. Agricultural graduates on the labour market

According to the survey of CHEERS it is advisable to pay enough attention to finding a job even during the academic years as well as to aim at obtaining professional experience and practice. On the basis of Figure 1 we can conclude the presence or the lack of this thoughtful way of thinking.

Figure 1 The proportion of those with a job during their academic years

On the basis of the first column of the figure we could be assured when concluding that more than half of the undergraduate students have a job regarding all programmes and the same holds true for 40% of agricultural students. However, the last column shows that most undergraduates did not respond so the situation is not that optimistic. If we take all the respondents of the questionnaire of the programmes (undergraduate and not undergraduate) into consideration, we can see that only every tenth undergraduate has a

job. In addition, it is also important to note that students with a job are primarily not motivated by proactive, forward looking behaviour rather by their dire financial situation and the strive to cover their tuition fees. It is also supported by the fact that a great number of those without a job does not even look for a job during their academic years.

Afterwards we examine how long it took to find a job after graduating (Figure 2).

Figure 2 The average length of job search after graduation for students of agriculture

The examination of the time passed between graduation and finding a job depicts a more unfavourable picture of the placement of agricultural graduates. In addition to looking for a job for almost one month longer than the average, agricultural starters spend the longest time on finding a job in this area. Moreover, the spread of the number of months spent on

searching a job is more unfavourable in the case of agricultural graduates as starters.

On the basis of the above mentioned facts we considered it interesting to examine whether three years after graduation they worked in an area of their qualification (Figure 3).

Figure 3 The perception of graduates' correlations of their jobs and qualifications

Less than half of the graduates who are employed in agriculture stated that their job mostly correlated with their qualifications. Although the loose correlation makes the situation a bit more different, it can be concluded that this field undermines the qualification-job correlation proportion of the population to a great extent as 64% great and 17.4% slight correlation comprises more than three quarters of all the respondents. Every tenth agricultural graduates can be regarded to leave their careers as their jobs

are not in connection with their qualifications. However, it is important to stress that one quarter (24.9%) of those who have agricultural qualifications but do not work in agriculture did not give up the hopes of being employed in a job they are qualified in the future. Seventy percent of the agricultural graduates are employed after three years of their graduation and 7% are entrepreneurs (Figure 4).

Figure 4 The employment status of graduates

The latter one is regarded to be exceptionally high as of the total sample. It can be due to the

great number of sole proprietors and self employed statuses that are typical of agriculture. Figure 5 also supports the data above.

Figure 5 Employees in vertical job sharing

In the case of agricultural graduates 59% are employees, 7.2% are self employed while 33.8%

are senior managers. It is also discernible that on almost all managerial levels agricultural

graduates represent a higher proportion than in the other programmes except those with technical qualification who try to catch up: that is why their proportion is higher on the level of junior management.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

To sum it up we can conclude that the graduates of agriculture **can relatively find a job quickly after their final examinations** although it takes them longer time than the average. In some exceptional cases rather long time is necessary to find the first job. The job of the graduates who took part in the survey **correlated with their qualification only in 50% of the cases** but in the case of agricultural graduates the situation is more unfavourable, unfortunately. **More than 80% of the respondents feel that their job and qualification correlates at least to a slight extent but unfortunately, regarding agricultural undergraduates this proportion is smaller.** However, the fact that 24.9% of the agricultural graduates who did not perform agricultural activity at the time of the survey declared to keep on searching a job that correlates with their qualification is remarkable.

An important result of our research is that we could conclude that **agricultural graduates could make a career more quickly** than the employees with other qualifications. In our opinion this attractive factor should also be considered when recruiting students for institutions.

References

1. Falusné Szikra K. (2001): Munkanélküliség és diplomás túltermelés, Közgazdasági szemle, November
2. Furlong, A. (2003): Sebezhetőség és ifjúsági munkaerőpiac. In: Furlong, A., Stadler, B.&Azzopardi, A: Sebezhető ifjúság: Sebezhetőség az oktatásban, a munkaidőben és a szabadidőben Európában: Perspektívák, Szeged
3. Galasi, P. (2002): Fiatal diplomások életpálya-vizsgálata, In: Társadalmi riport (2002), TÁRKI, Budapest, pp. 245-255
4. Schomburg, H.–Teichler, U. (2006): Higher education and graduate employment in Europe. Higher Education Dynamics, Volume 15. Springer
5. Stadler, B (2003): Sebezhetőség és oktatás. In: Furlong, A., Stadler, B.&Azzopardi, A: Sebezhető ifjúság: Sebezhetőség az oktatásban, a munkaidőben és a szabadidőben Európában: Perspektívák, Szeged
6. Teichler U. (1999): Higher education policy and the world of work: Changing Conditions and Challenges, Higher Education Policy 12.
7. Yorke, M. (2006): Employability in higher education: what it is – what it is not. Heslington: The Higher Education Academy.

5th International Conference on Sustainable Tourism Conference

13th to 15th June 2012

A Coruna, Galicia, Spain

Website: www.wessex.ac.uk/12-conferences/sustourism-2012.html

Contact person: Alice Jones

Sustainable Tourism 2012 aims to find ways to protect the natural and cultural landscape through the development of new solutions which minimise the adverse effects of tourism.

Organized by: Wessex Institute of Technology, UK & Complutense University of Madrid, Spain

2nd Advances in Hospitality and Tourism Marketing and Management Conference

31st May to 3rd June 2012

Greotel Corfu Imperial Hotel, Corfu Island, Greece

Website: <http://www.ahtmmc2012.gr>

Contact person: Dr Chryssoula Chatzigeorgiou

Corfu Island has golden beaches, rich gastronomy, vibrant night-life. Conference includes: refereed papers, special issues in 20 journals, PhD workshop, keynote speakers, social activities. New deadline for abstracts: 20 November 2011.

Organized by: Alexander Technological Institute of Thessaloniki, Democritus University of Thrace, Washington State University, Greek Research Institute for Tourism

Innovation for Sustainability Conference

27th to 28th September 2012

Porto, Portugal

Website: <http://www.ulusiada.pt/is2012/>

Contact person: Paula Rodrigues

Bearing in mind the importance of the contribution of innovation towards sustainability, the Universities Lusfada promote the first conference on this subject, which is going to be held on Oporto.

Organized by: Lusfada University
